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EDUCATION, SOCIAL
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Contents

Sl. No.	Title and Authors	Page No.
1.	INFORMATION ASSURANCE? FROM MEANING TO FOUNDATION P. K. Paul P. S. Aithal	1
2.	A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE ON OFFLINE RETAIL BUSINESS Vivek T. S. Divya U	8
3.	A STUDY ON THE PORTRAYAL OF TRANSGENDERS: A CASE STUDY ON “NAANU AVANALLA.... AVALU” MOVIE Clifford Chetan Ambler, Dr. Shubha. H. S, Dr. Laveena D’Mello	14
4.	FACTORS WHICH INFLUENCE ON-LINE BUYING BEHAVIOR DURING FESTIVE SEASON V. T. Shailashri, Dr.P.S.Aithal, Dr. Surekha Shenoy	20
5.	FIPPS & INFORMATION ASSURANCE: THE ROOT AND FOUNDATION P. K. Paul P. S. Aithal A. Bhuimali Kalishankar Tiwary, R. Rajesh	27
6.	A STUDY ON SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN MANGALURU CITY- CUSTOMER BENEFITS Devika Bhavya G	35
7.	A CASE STUDY ANALYSIS ON INDIAN TRANSPORTATION INDUSTRY Sharada V. H. Sagar Srinivas	49
8.	CLOUD BASED SMART DUSTBIN SYSTEM FOR METRO STATION Chandana Sagar Pooja Sanil	59
9.	A NEW ATTITUDE-BEHAVIOUR (AB) THEORY FOR ACCEPTABLE LEADERS IN WINNING ORGANIZATIONS P. S. Aithal Shubhrajyotsna Aithal	67
10.	STUDY OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES Rekha M Lewlyn L R. Rodrigues	79

11.	DEMONITISATION AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIAN ECONOMY Mr. B. Sudheer Kumar	81
12.	DIGITALIZATION IN EDUCATION - A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN GOVERNMENT SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS IN MANGALURU CITY. MS. Renita Joyce Fernandes Ms. Kavya	88
13.	HOW TO MEASURE THE PERFORMANCE LEVEL IN COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM – SOME SUGGESTIONS P. S. Aithal Mike Dillon Suresh Kumar P. M.	93
14.	EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM INITIATES TO MANAGE THE PERFORMANCE OF THE ORGANIZATION Ravisha B Chethan Divya	103
15.	PROBLEMS OF FARMERS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UDUPI DISTRICT Fathima Jabina K Swathi Shet Jableen	110
16.	UPGRADING B.TECH. CURRICULUM AS B.TECH. (HONS) BY INTEGRATING STEAM, ESEP & IPR FEATURES P. S. Aithal Shubhrajyotsna Aithal	123
17.	FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG WORKING WOMEN - A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MANGALORE CITY Ms Bharathi R Ms Helma Preethi Rodrigues	137
18.	A STUDY ON PROBLEMS FACING BY THE GOVERNMENT COLLEGE STUDENTS IN RURAL AREAS - SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KUNDAPUR TALUK, UDUPI DIST. Vaishnavi H. Ramya Rao Kavyashree	142
19.	A CSR ORIENTED EQUILIBRIUM CAMPUS PLACEMENT APPROACH Varun Shenoy P. S. Aithal**	151
20.	A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON REGULAR AND DISTANCE EDUCATION Vidyalaxmi M.N Prajna Kumari	156

21.	EFFECTS OF MUSIC ON COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF TEENAGERS Mrs. Krupamani Divya Rani M Seema. S	164
22.	SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN HAZARDOUS EMPLOYMENTS Pradeep M. D.	169
23.	A SURVEY ON VARIOUS MULTICAST ROUTING PROTOCOLS WITH AND WITHOUT CROSS LAYER TECHNIQUES IN MANET Adithya Aithal Akshay D Bhat Mrs.Shifana Begum	172
24.	MICRO HEALTH INSURANCE FOR THE POOR- A CASE STUDY OF SAMPOORNA SURAKSHA SCHEME IN MANGALURU CITY Ms Shobha Dr Udayachandra P N	178
25.	STUDENTS SATISFACTION LEVEL IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTES-A STUDY OF PUBLIC INSTITUTES IN MANGALORE CITY. Ms. Sulfathu Nafila M. K. Ms. Shreeraksha	189
26.	ACCOUNTING STANDARDS AND FINANCIAL STATEMENTS OF MANGALORE CHEMICALS AND FERTILIZERS LTD AND KARNATAKA BANK LTD Ms Sandhya Rani Caroleena Janefer	199
27.	HOW DOES THE TRANSFORMATION OF AN AVATAR FACE GIVING A FAVORABLE IMPRESSION AFFECT HUMAN RECOGNITION OF THE FACE? Reshma Balakrishnan Thrupthi P J	204
28.	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND SENSORS BASED ASSISTIVE SYSTEM FOR THE VISUALLY IMPAIRED PEOPLE Nikita Nakte Soumya	210
29.	LEARNING AND CAPABILITY ACQUISITION: A CASE STUDY OF THE INDIAN AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY Nithesh Shetty Mohammed Ridwan	219
30.	ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYMENT GENERATION- A CASE STUDY OF RUDSET INSTITUTE IN KERALA Dr. V. Shaharban	229
31.	SMART ENERGY METERING BASED ON IOT AND POCKET PICKING USING ARDUINO AND GSM Nisha Nikita V. Nakte	242

32.	INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR OF WOMEN INVESTORS IN THE STOCK MARKET: A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MANGALURU Ms. Helma Preethi Rodrigues Mrs. Bharathi R.	250
33.	A STUDY ON E-BANKING SERVICES IN MANGALURU CITY- CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND AWARENESS Sowmya K. P. Ashwini Pavanaskar	257
34.	ACHIEVEMENTS AND OUTCOMES OF INNOVATIONS: A CASE STUDY OF THE FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY Mohammed Ridhwan Nithesh Shetty	271
35.	A STUDY ON RURAL INFRASTRUCTURE FUNDING – A CASE STUDY ON PAVOOR GRAM PANCHAYAT Mr Shakin Raj Mr Arjun Prakash	281
36.	STUDY OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES Rekha M Lewlyn L R. Rodrigues	287
37.	CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS E-BANKING SERVICES, A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS IN UJIRE Vignesh Pai B. H. Padmini Y. S. Vijetha Pai B. H.	296
38.	NECESSITY OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS Vinutha Vranda	317
39.	WATER LEVEL MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT OF DAMS USING IOT Akhila Mekhala R.	322
40.	THE STUDY OF SOLAR CHARGE CONTROLLER USING PWM TECHNIQUE AND A MODEL TO IMPROVE ITS PERFORMANCE P. Sridhar Acharya P. S. Aithal	330
41.	CHANGES IN BASEL NORMS AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIAN BANKS Mr. Amith Donald Menezes	336
42.	A CRITICAL STUDY ON APPLICATIONS OF MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN BUSINESS ANALYTICS Krishna Prasad K.	346

Paper 1**INFORMATION ASSURANCE? *FROM MEANING TO FOUNDATION*****P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal²**¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India**Corresponding Author:** pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com**Abstract**

Information Assurance is one of the important area of Information Science and Technology in recent past. This is the advanced area of Information Security as well. Security is the prime focus for most of us today. The organizations and Institutions to Individuals everyone are interested and concern about this security and privacy related affairs. Information Assurance is the broader version of Security related affairs. It is mainly deals with assurance related to technological products and manual systems related to information and content. Initially within the security spectrum Cryptography treated as most valuable and important but gradually other areas have been developed viz. Computer Security, then Network Security, Web Security, Database Security etc. Gradually as a whole, these are treated as Information Technology Security; it is also important to note that many universities and researchers worked and thoughts about manual content's security related affairs and a new concept has been developed called Information Security. The field and nomenclature, IA i.e. Information Assurance is the latest of this security edition and this is talks about the manual and technological information security related affairs leading to design, development and formulation, framework of security related affairs for the organizations, institutions and individuals. This paper described the basics of Information Assurance with reference to its root and historical foundations, basics meaning and features. Paper also talks about the function of Information Assurance as a brief with special reference to the process of Information Assurance.

Keywords

Information Assurance, IT Security, Web Security, Network Security, Information Privacy, Information Security, Information Science, IT

1. Introduction

Information Assurance is about the application and integration of IT and Computing in the Security and Privacy domain. Importantly, Information Assurance professionals do both the technological part and affairs as well as manual information security and privacy related affairs leading to designing, development of planning and policies on different aspects viz.—

- Planning, designing, development of Information Management principles of the organizations, institutions and individuals [1].

- Designing, development and framing of Information Privacy and Security by manual tools and framework for the same.
- Policy formulation related to the Information and IT Security including Software Security, Database Security, Network Security, Web Security etc.

Information Assurance is thus as a whole responsible for the availability, integrity, authentication as well as confidentiality of the information systems. The Information Assurance is about tools, techniques, technologies, rules, policies, methods etc in respect of security, privacy etc [2], [5].

2. Objective and Agenda

The present work is a conceptual and theoretical work and thus it deals with following objectives and agenda, in brief—

- To know about the basics of Information Assurance with its basic components.
- To learn about the basic of Information Security and Assurance with special reference to the boarder and smaller areas.
- To learn about the features and function of Information Assurance in brief but in simple manner.
- To know about the advanced areas of Information Assurance with reference to the nature, characteristics of this field.
- To dig out the Information Protection Policy in brief and its requirement in Information Privacy, Security and complete Assurance.
- To learn about the Process of the Information Assurance in brief with special reference to the future potentials.

3. Information Assurance: *From the Root to Features*

As we know information assurance is a process of information privacy and security management with the help of manual and computation technology so it has different kind of process. The core of Information Assurance is supported by different kind of processes as Information Assurance deals with right information to the right people at right time so Information Assurance has the process of information risk management, trust management, appropriate architecture and so one [3], [4], [6]. Using this policy and process the information may be authentic. As information assurance is related with information security, so technological process also need to maintain for better result. Information Assurance is also associated with management principle so such management principle needs to follow up for better results. Information Assurance is talks about defending malicious hackers so practitioners in this fields is talks about and deals with following-

- Corporate Governance
- Issus related to regulation and standard of Information Assurance
- Auditing of Information Security
- Disaster recovery related to information system

4. Information Assurance: Smaller and Broader Zone

In respect of IT and Computing, the area and concept Information Assurance is a valuable name. Various kind of security related affairs viz. Information security, IT security, Network security, Database Security, Web Security etc are basically fall under the Information Assurance. Practically, Information Assurance is responsible for the managing as well as assuring of various kind of contents viz. information, data, and knowledge etc in different form. The Information Assurance is deals both the technological and policy solution to information and similar contents. The areas such as information privacy and security are an important area of IA [7], [9]. Information security is the smaller area of Information Assurance and various affairs leading to data and information uses, processing, storage, and transformation etc also fall under the IA. Most of the western countries use the term Information Assurance as an alternative of IT Security and Cyber Security also. There are two methods of Assurance of the Information viz.–

- **Computational Systems/ Technological systems.**
- **Traditional Systems/ Manual Systems.**

As far as technological systems following areas (i.e. all the areas of IT Security or Cyber Security) are fall under this—

- Database Security
- Network Security
- Web Security [8], [11].

We know that Information Assurance is broader field than IT security and Information security. And Information Security and Assurance professionals normally have the knowledge of following—

- Business and accounting
- User study and experience
- Fraud management
- Forensic science
- Management science
- System and security engineering etc.

Hence Information Assurance is a broader, interdisciplinary, and multi skill requirement based subject (Refer Fig: 1). Many government organizations, bodies and even govt. use the term Information Assurance for example govt. of United Kingdom, United States etc. The body and agency which are associated with Information assurance normally deals with affairs of system engineering, forensic investigation thread analysis, accounting and criminology.

Fig: 1-From smaller to broader areas of Security related affairs related to Information and Contents

In UK HMG Information Assurance standard 1 and 2 has been changed over HMG Information Security standard 2. This standard has been discussed about the principle and requirement of Information Assurance, Risk Management etc. Hence Information Assurance is about physical, technical and administrative control. Here data can be protected in different format (both in physical and electronic).

5. Function of Information Assurance

The area Information Assurance is deals with different purposes but among these few important are include (but not limited to)—

- With the help of Information assurance it is easily possible to make available information to all and right time.
- Information Assurance basically helps in Data and Information Privacy as well as protection from unauthorized means also illegal access.
- It is a fact that technological security lies on information, thus both information security and IT security can depend on Information Assurance.
- The virtue of homeland security such as terrorism, cyber terrorism, cyber war etc can be done scientifically with the help of Information Assurance.
- Information Assurance helps in mobile security and related means with technological and manual way.
- Different kind of security viz. network's privacy, security, database and its security, Network and its security may get wider success with Information Assurance[06], [10], [11].
- Design, implementation, development, modernization of secure database and information management system become possible with better and healthy Information Assurance practice.

- Cloud security, infrastructure management, and trust management of different components of IT may get the benefits of Information Assurance practice; both technically and manually.
- Various kind of strategies related to the risk management of information and technologies become possible with Information Assurance.
- Malicious attack prevention and hacking related affairs become easily managed with the help of Information Assurance practice.
- Fraud management systems it depends on IT Security and more dependable system creation, and here Information Assurance play a lead role.
- Information transparency, Governance of the contents and public right on information and IT become possible with better and healthy Information Assurance practice.
- Holistic development of manual and computational information system regarding security and privacy the core jurisdiction of Information Assurance, in different context.
- Designing, Developing and implementing Information (general and technological), Cyber and IT related policy and its framework are the basic component of Information Assurance practice.

6. Process Vs. Information Assurance

Information Assurance and Security requires various steps and process and among these few important are include—

- Information Assurance typically deals with few process normally they are treated as enumeration and classification of information assets to be protected.
- Information Assurance expert deals with the risk assessment and vulnerabilities of information dealing product.
- Information Assurance is also talks about threat management and here assessment is very important. Here assessment considers both probability and threat of avoiding vulnerabilities.
- Cost benefits analysis is also impotent point to be noted. The Information Assurance practitioner normally design and develop risk management.
- As per as risk management plan is concern it has different steps and point to be noted. Mainly; mitigating, eliminating, accepting, transferring, preventing, detecting, responding threats. For this different standard and guidelines may be follow up Information Assurance practitioners.
- Counter measurement is also important in Information Assurance process that includes policy and procedures related to firewall management, antivirus management, regular backup, configuration management etc.
- In Information Assurance process training and development is also a important name and here security related awareness program, training program on emerging technology should be initiated.
- In context of Human Resource Management a dedicated computer emergency response team to be established.

- Testing and evaluation of security is also very important and here proper steps should be initiated.

Hence Information Assurance is an iterative process and here risk assessment plan are very important. So, proper and routine basis evaluation and revision should be undertaken.

7. Information Protection Policy

Information protection policy is a kind of guidelines responsible for the processing, storage as well as transmission of sensitive information in different means. Information Protection Policy is an important component of Information Protection Policy which is responsible for ensuring as well as protection from different modification as well as disclosure. As far as Information Protection Policy is concerned following are important to noted—

- Should define who can have access to sensitive information.
- Should define how sensitive information is to be stored and transmitted (encrypted, archive files, unencoded, etc.).
- Should define on which systems sensitive information can be stored.
- Should discuss what levels of sensitive information can be printed on physically insecure printers.
- Should define how sensitive information is removed from systems and storage devices.
- Should discuss any default file and directory permissions defined in system-wide configuration files [6], [11].

Information Protection Policy is a broad area and thus following things are covered under this field and expert should follow these (viz.)—

- Network security and including Network security policy
- Computer security and including Computer security policy
- Information security and including Information security policies
- User account policy in different means
- Remote access policy for the information
- Internet and intranet security
- Industrial espionage
- Fair Information Practices and principles etc.

8. Conclusion

Cyber Security is a valuable concern these days for managing information and also risk management. Organizations and institutes of different kind are facing challenges on security as a result adequate and qualified man power required in this field of cyber and information security. Various aspects viz. Cloud Computing Security, Mobile Security, Risk Management etc are the major concern of current age. In today's Digital Age security is not only an issue but also a challenge. Various other organizations viz. Government body and Ministries, organizations, and individuals getting knowledge from the cyber world and as a result every organizations are

moving towards not only computational security related management but also manual information security and privacy. Hence Information Assurance concept is increasing rapidly. Apart from emerging computational security concerns viz. Data Security, Web Security etc for different alternative solutions.

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Paper 2

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE ON OFFLINE RETAIL BUSINESS

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Shankaraghatta.

Abstract:

E-commerce is one of the greatest inventions in this decade, it took the physical market into the virtual world with the help of the internet by offering more convenience logistics, easy return and variety of stocks, in the last five years Indian e-commerce industry has seen significant growth with the emergence of many online retailers, in the same period many offline retailers have suffered much loss on this background this study has been undertaken to know which type of offline retailers has suffered much impact among electronic shop, clothing shop, pharmacy, book shop, and provision store, electronics and clothing shop had much impact so far and all retailers feel the need of adopting e-commerce to their business.

Keywords: E-commerce, Retail business, offline, customer attraction.

1. Introduction

The concept of e-commerce started 40 years ago with electronic data interchange and teleshopping as a tool to do business, in last 15 years' development in technology helped e-commerce to include a number of features, today it is one of the effective ways of doing business. E-commerce is described as a commercial transaction which is conducted through the internet, like marketing, promotion, communication, order processing, bills payment, queries, it can be adapted to all models of business like B2B, B2C, C2B etc., Some companies adopted this invention and took the physical market into the virtual world by offering more convenience, logistics, easy return, varieties of stocks and a better shopping experience and made a traditional way of doing business outdated, this led to closure of many offline retail businesses when they couldn't adapt to a new trend. This article mainly discusses two things, they are about the impact of e-commerce on offline retail business and strategies that retailers have to adopt in order to compete with a new trend.

2. Recent Trends in E-commerce Industry

- The Indian e-commerce market has reached \$50 billion in 2018 from \$39 billion in 2017 and it is expected to grow as the world's second largest e-commerce market by 2034.
- Internet users in India are expected to reach 829 million in 2021 from 429.23 million in 2017, raising internet users is expected to boost the growth of e-commerce.
- In the online retail market electronics is currently the largest segment with 47% market share, followed by clothing 31%, home and furnishing 8%, books 7%, personal care 2%, baby products 2% and others 3%.
- Offline retailers share in the total retail market is expected to go down to 95% in 2020 from 97.5% in 2016, in the same period online retail is expected to grow from 2.5% to 5%.

- The Indian government has allowed the online sale of drugs by forming the e-pharmacy draft on 28th August 2018.
- The government has banned online retailers from making big and exclusive offers from 1st February 2019 in order to balance competition between offline retailers.

3. Impact of E-commerce on Offline Retail Business.

The emergence of e-commerce can be considered as a boon to traditional retail business when they know how to adapt and make use of it when they don't know how to adopt it and cope up with the new trend it will become difficult for them to succeed in this generation. It helps business in operating efficiently as well as effectively in reaching customers located thousands of miles away within minutes, most of the business process can be performed effortlessly through it, launching new products all over the world with low cost at same time is possible through it, so far it has helped many traditional retailers to expand their business, at the same time it also had negative impact others offline retailers.

4. Review of Literature

Menal (2017) "Study on E-commerce and its impact on retailers in India" studies types of markets and impact of e-commerce on retailers in India, Major advantages that e-commerce has over retailers are promotion of products, customer service, brand image, advertisement, customization, order-making process, customer values, all these factors affected retailers in decreased turnover, profit margin and increased customer demands like discounts, returns, home delivery etc., and there is a need for making more advertisement and offers by retailers, which are difficult to fulfill by them.

Amithshah (2015) "A study on the impact of online shopping upon retail trade business" Majority of retailers agree that there is a decrease in average turnover and profit margin in the last 3 years and many tried to regain customer attraction by giving offers, discounts, and after-sales service, and they didn't keep more variety of stocks rather kept the best stock to affect more sales, retailers have to provide better quality products with fair price and good consumer satisfaction in order to regain profits.

Kiran (2017) "Impact of e-commerce on global business and opportunities- a conceptual study" easy access to internet supports e-commerce growth, e-commerce will show tremendous support in the promotion of global business, it has both positive and negative impact on employment where it creates new type of jobs like web designing, computer engineering, system analyst and also employs creative people, artists, designers for making web content more attractive, automation in e-commerce in self-service facilities will reduce traditional employment opportunities like administration and back-office functions.

5. Research Gap

Earlier many studies were conducted regarding the impact of e-commerce on whole employment and retail business, and some suggested that e-commerce will have a negative impact on whole offline retail business and some said it will not have a negative impact on the whole traditional retail market, to clear these confusions this study was conducted. This study aims at knowing which kind of traditional retail business is more affected and which are less affected.

6. The problem of the Offline Retailers

- Some big online retail companies are giving very tough competition to offline retailers.

- In the last three years' easy access to the internet gave a boost to online retailer's growth.
- Big discounts and low price products offered by online retailers is a threat to the offline retailer's growth.
- Many traditional retailers don't have adequate skills and resources needed to adopt e-commerce.
- Many kinds of traditional retailers already have disappeared like record shops etc.

7. Objectives of the Study

1. To evaluate the impact of e-commerce on offline retail business.
2. To offer suggestions to develop the retail business in order to meet a new kind of customer needs.

8. Research Methodology

For this study, Shimoga district in the Karnataka state of India is selected as an area of study, primary data are collected from the respondents using structured questionnaire, ten respondents were selected each from the five types of retail business namely electronic appliances shop, cloth shop, pharmacy, books shop, and provision store. Further data required are collected from articles, journals, and reports. All the data's collected were analyzed using statistical tools and techniques and chi-square test.

9. Limitations of the Study

- 1) Only five types of offline retail shops were compared to know the impact of e-commerce on offline retail business.
- 2) A sample size of each type of shop is just 10 respondents.

10. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Impact of Online Retailers and E-commerce on Offline Retail Business

Particulars	Electronic gadgets shop		Clothing shop		Pharmacy		Books shop		Provision store	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Is there a decrease in average number of customers in last 3 years.	8	2	7	3	4	6	5	5	3	7
Is there a decrease in average profit margin in last 3 years.	5	5	6	4	3	7	3	7	4	6
Do you think big online retailers has caused loss to your business in the last 3 years?	9	1	8	2	4	6	6	4	3	7
Can you offer big discounts like online retailers.	2	8	5	5	4	6	3	7	4	6
Have you tried any strategies to compete with online retails.	4	6	6	4	3	7	2	8	1	9
Do you think online retailers are a big threat to your business in the future?	9	1	7	3	8	2	8	2	4	6

Do you feel the need of adopting e-commerce to your business.	8	2	9	1	6	4	7	3	5	5
Are you aware of the online market place offered by Flipkart, Amazon, and others?	8	2	7	3	7	3	6	4	4	6
Do you have the adequate skills needed to adopt e-commerce to your business?	7	3	3	7	3	7	4	6	2	8
Do you think adopting e-commerce will help the growth of your business.	7	3	8	2	5	5	8	2	6	4

Source: Field survey.

Data analysis of the respondents indicate that, electronic and cloth shops has witnessed much decrease in average profit margin and customers in the last 3 years, and they both mainly considers online retailers are reason for their cause, all type of shops feel the need of adopting e-commerce to their business but many of them are unaware of online market place offered by online retail brokers, except electronic shop owners majority of shop owners lack adequate skills and knowledge needed to adopt e-commerce, and many agree that adopting e-commerce will help in the growth of their business.

Table 2: Need for adopting E-commerce to the traditional Retail Business

Ho: There is no need to adopt e-commerce to the retail business.

H1: There is a need for adopting e-commerce to the retail business.

Particulars	Observed (O)	Expected (E)	O-E	(O-E) ²
Yes	35	27	8	64
No	15	23	-8	64
n = 2	50	50		128
				$\sum(O-E)^2$

Source: Field Survey.

$$E = \sum x/n = 50/2 = 25$$

$$\text{Degree of Freedom} = n-1 (2-1) = 1$$

$$X^2 = \sum(O-E)^2/E$$

$$X^2 = 128/25 = 5.12$$

Significance level= 5%

Table Value of chi square = 3.841

The primary data from the respondents were collected and analyzed and a hypothesis has been framed to test whether there is a need for adopting e-commerce among traditional retailers by using chi-square test, and the computed value of chi-square is 5.12 and the critical value is 3.84 by taking a degree of freedom 1 (n-1 i.e. 2-1) at 5% significance level. As the computed value 5.12 is greater than table value 3.84, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted which shows that there is a need for adopting e-commerce among traditional retailers.

11. Major Findings of the Study

- The emergence of e-commerce helped the growth of logistics and other related business and affected some business like print publication and others.

- All type of offline retail shops is not affected, electronic shop and clothing shops are more affected and others are less affected.
- Provision stores and other shops which sell daily household goods and perishable goods are not affected by e-commerce because people are not preferring e-commerce to buy everything.
- Traditional offline retail shops are unable to compete with online retailers in terms of pricing, offers, discounts, return and exchange offers.
- Majority of offline retail shops feel the need of adopting e-commerce to their business.
- Awareness level and skills needed to adopt e-commerce to the business among the traditional retailers is low.
- Pharmacies didn't have much impact in the past but they think government allowing e-pharmacy will have a negative impact on them in the future.

Suggestions

- Offline retailers have to adopt e-commerce in their business in order to grow in the present generation.
- **Adopting online and offline customer experience:** Many small offline retailers are not equipped with enough resource and skills to adopt e-commerce, so they can start adopting basics e-commerce features like
 - Adopting credit, debit card and mobile payment options.
 - Adopting teleshopping, it is a very easy way of reaching more customer by letting the customer order through phone and personally delivering those products to their home.
 - Storing customers purchase data and providing recommendations and discounts when they visit again.
 - Sending offers and information about the arrival of new products through SMS.
 - Analyzing new trends and strategies used by online retailers and trying to adopt it.
- **Partnering with online retail brokers:** There are a number of online retail brokers websites available nowadays which allow anyone to sell products online without setting up of their own store or website, terms and conditions of online market place vary between one to another, offline retailers can join multiple online market place and sell their products to wider areas, benefits of joining online market place are as follows.
 - Access, advertising and promoting products to a wider area is possible with very less cost.
 - Can sell directly to customers through online or sell in bulk quantity to the retail brokers.
 - The separate platform is available to launch new products and handmade goods.
 - Easy access to convenient logistics support.
 - Some online retail brokers provide storage and credit facility.

12. Conclusion

The way of doing business has been changed by the emergence of e-commerce, it has seen tremendous growth in the last few years in the same period some traditional retailers suffered slowdown in their business because they were unable to keep up with new trend, they should not be left out rather they should be brought up by making them aware of e-commerce and helping them in joining online market place where they can easily expand their business to the online world.

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Paper 3

A STUDY ON THE PORTRAYAL OF TRANSGENDERS: A CASE STUDY ON “NAANU AVANALLA... AVALU” MOVIE

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Abstract:

Transgenders are the individuals whose gender identity differs from their biological sex. For several decades, the transgenders have been victimized to harassment, stigma, physical assault, sexual violence and are being deprived of employment and education. The current study is aimed to look into the discrimination faced by transgender character(s) in the film “Naanu Avanalla... Avalu” directed by B. S. Lingadevaru. In this study we look into the protagonist, a character named Madesha (Vidhya) who faces discrimination at various levels for being a transgender person. On the contrary, there has been significant increase in the portrayal of transgender characters in Television shows, Stand up comedies, web series and movies. Specially in a country like India, where we have a conservative society that has been treating transgenders as outcasts. Hence, we have mostly seen the negative portrayal of transgenders where we have seen them as characters who are not well adapted to the society. Only recently we have seen transgenders playing major roles in television shows and movies. The current study will also observe transgenders playing lead characters in the film “Naanu Avanalla... Avalu”.

Keywords: Transgenders, Harassment, Stigma, Physical assault, Sexual violence, Homophobia, Individual rights

I. INTRODUCTION

- *Transgenders*

According to Dietert and Dentice, “Transgender” is a broad term to describe individuals whose gender expression differs from that of the societal norms of gender that is assigned at the time of birth. The manners by which transgender individuals self-recognize and express their sexual identity fluctuate depending upon the person. Some transgender individuals display some level of manliness and/or as feminine attributes relying upon their “*gender self-identification*” (Dietert & Dentice, 2009).

- *Transgenders in India*

For centuries, transgenders have been in Indian society and several historical texts have confirmed their existence. The terms “*napumsaka*” and “*tritiyaprakriti*” have been mentioned in early Vedic literatures and Hindu mythology. In fact, Jain scriptures makes a mention of the idea of “psychological sex” that accentuated the individual’s psychological make-up that is different from their sexual character (Michelraj, 2015). A *hijra* is a person who have the attributes of both masculine and feminine genders. Ones who are born as male, went through castration (a procedure involving removal of testicles and penis), vaginoplasty, or breast implants in order to trans into a feminine identity. They are also seen wearing a feminine attire. Any individual who recognizes oneself as person of the opposite sex from their biological sex identifies oneself as a *Hijra* (Chettiar, 2015).

- *Portrayal, Negative/Positive portrayal in films*

Homophobia still being prevalent in a country like India, scholarly discussions on topics such as homosexuality is considered as a taboo by both the society and the government. However, in the recent years, discussions and depictions of homosexuality has been surfacing in the Indian cinemas and the Indian television news medium as well. Stringent rules by the Indian censor board prohibited such portrayals. Even then, some film makers used transgender portrayals in humorous manner that would sometimes end up making a mockery of the LGBTQ group by hurting their sentiments. Such portrayals are now seen shifting. Gay themed films have been surfacing and surprisingly some of them have been winning awards (Sabharwal & Sen, 2012).

- *Naanu avanalla ... avalu.. about the film, awards*

“*Naanu Avanalla..Avalu*” is a movie based on an autobiography “I am Vidya”, the real life struggles of a transgender named Living Smile Vidya. The screenplay of the movie is written by the director B S Lingadevaru (Hooli, 2016). The movie received national award for Best Actor in 62nd National Film awards (Mehta, 2015). The film also received Karnataka State award for Best actor (Male) and Best Story.

- *Why this study?*

Gender scholars have only made few mentions of the transgender portrayal in cinemas and novels. However, there must be wider focus, attention and debates on the portrayal of transgender, gender and sexuality in Indian Cinemas. Hence, this study is aimed to look into discrimination faced by transgender Character(s) in the film “*Naanu avanalla... avalu*”.

II. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

- *Qualitative analysis*

Qualitative analysis of a content emphasizes a coordinated perspective of texts and the context on which it was written. Such study goes further than merely checking words or separating objective content from writings to analyze their meanings, themes, and examples that may be evident or hidden in a specific content. This study enables researchers to comprehend social reality in subjective way but in a scientific manner (Wildemuth, 2017).

- ***Homophobia***

According to McDermott, Roen and Scourfield, 'Homophobia' is a punishment the individual gets from the society for defying the norms of a heterosexual society. This punishment can occur at various levels such as, physical, verbal abuse, rejection and isolation that eventually leads to psychological distress (McDermott, Roen, & Scourfield, 2008).

- ***Harassment***

Harassment can be defined as causing annoyance, trouble, disturbing, bothering, pestering, irritating, picking on, or molesting an individual (Elliott, 2009).

- ***Stigma***

The *hijra* (Transgenders) tends to live a double life as feminine males who have masculine appearance but have a complete feminine mental alleviation when with peers. Wearing of garments that are usually linked with females were not accepted at homes. Display of such attitudes is also not encouraged by the relatives. Exhibiting such attitudes would decrease the chances of the siblings from getting married. Some trans individuals receive familial pressure to get married and have a 'normal life' (Khan, et al., 2009).

- ***Physical assault***

Physical assault can be defined as a "law threatening act" that involves physical harm/injury to a person. This involves beating, abusing, attacking or mugging (Elliott, 2009).

- ***Sexual violence***

An act is considered as Sexual violence when it is committed on an individual who is not in a position to consent or to refuse. This could be because of a disability, abuse of authority, age or violent threats (Rutherford, Zwi, Grove, & Butchart, 2007).

- ***Education***

The trans individuals confront several challenges in pursuit of gaining proper education. These barriers include uniforms, academic records, sports and other facilities that accommodates transgendered individuals. Hence, a lot of trans individuals become victims of violence, bullying and exclusion from schools. The attitudes of the teachers and students become indicators of weather the institution is inclusive of transgenders (Byrne, 2013).

- ***Employment***

Not all organizations are inclusive of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and transgender employees. Certain individuals often do not disclose their gender identities at their workplaces. They often allow people to believe they are heterosexual. It gets difficult for transgenders, bisexuals and lesbians when the organization tolerates the homophobic attitudes of its employees. Creating inclusive workspaces and atmosphere by removing homophobic attitudes must be implemented in all work setups (Buccigrossi & Frost, 2003). The *hijras* (Transgenders) are unable to get mainstream jobs because they are less educated and the tend to exhibit a lifestyle that is unacceptable at workplaces. Which is why they are denied from getting proper jobs (Khan, et al., 2009).

- ***Individual rights/ legal protection***

Colonial era laws that criminalized the same sex behavior and gender expressions curbs down the individual rights of the individuals belonging to the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgenders (LGBT). However, recent discussions on the matter have resulted in revision of the constitutional framework to emphasis on the rights of LGBT individuals (Narain, 2018).

III. 'NAANU AVANALLA... AVALU': ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Homophobia

We can find few instances of Homophobia towards Madesha. We can observe it when Madesha is often spotted with only one friend in school. He also expresses this towards Govinda, his close friend. Madesha faces rejection from most of his classmates. Later, we also see Govinda avoiding Madesha as he comes to a realization that Madesha is falling in love with him in a way that the society does not accept. Madesha's attitude towards Govinda disturbs him and makes him uncomfortable.

Homophobia is also shown through people's reaction on seeing Vidya. At one scene we see a passenger in the train walking away after seeing Vidya approaching him.

Harassment

There are several instances in the movie where we see Madesha being harassed by the society for the way he behaved. In school, Madesha is often ridiculed by his classmates for his girlish behavior. After school, his classmates chase him in the streets making fun of him.

After Madesha grows up and continues to show feminine characteristics, his father asks him to leave the house. When Madesha moves to his sister's place, his brother in law tries to educate Madesha to behave like men. He forces him to fix his posture and body language. At one instance, Radha his sister gets annoyed while she spots Madesha watching Transgender related television program and turns off the Television by giving him a warning.

After Madesha trances into Vidya, she encounters harassment in other way. Once, a stranger at a tea stall eve teases Vidya. Though she feels uncomfortable, she tends to ignore the man. The movie also shows an instance where Vidya, Selvi and Naani are being questioned by the ticket collector in the train even after they had the reservation tickets. Vidya is also seen being mocked by passengers in train, to which Vidya responds strongly.

When Madesha returns home as Vidya, she faces rejection from father and brother in law. The brother in law rebukes Vidya for choosing a transgender lifestyle. He and Radha forces Vidya to wear a shirt and appear before her father.

Vidya also faces harassment from interviewers while she was seeking for jobs.

Stigma

Being in a Heteronormative society, Madesha is challenged psychologically. His feminine behavior attracts ridicule from his classmates. When he feels like playing Kho kho, the Physical education teacher sends him away suggesting him to play the games those linked with boys, such as Volley ball. When Madesha's father receives remarks from his friends regarding his feminine character, he gets offended by it and asks Madesha to leave the house. The Brother in law constantly asks Madesha to behave like a man. After Madesha returns home as Vidya, the father refuses to accept him as his daughter. As he worries what the society would say to Madesha's transformation. Hence, Vidya decides to leave her family.

Physical Assault

Madesha gets flogged by father for getting caught wearing his sister's clothes. Another instance of physical assault was seen after Madesha transes to Vidya where a man slaps Vidya for asking money. The same person trashes Vidya badly when she tries to protest. The film also shows the brutality of the person where he is seen repeatedly kicking Vidya. He later throws her out of the train mercilessly.

Sexual Violence

Sexual Violence in this is shown through the character Selvi who was forced into prostitution.

Education

Though Madesha had no difficulty in getting proper education, being constantly ridiculed by his classmates made him hesitant to attend classes. At one scene we could see Govinda literally dragging Madesha to college.

Employment

A couple in the train mocks at Vidya for begging. To which Vidya responds in a bold manner that she would work with dignity if she had gotten a job. There were two scenes that showed Vidya attending interviews and the interviewers rejected her the moment they got to know about her sexual identity.

Individual Rights

We see Vidya running into identity issues after going through a gender change. Her birth name Madesha becomes a hinderance in getting her a job. She tries to seek help from a lawyer to have her name changed. However, since there is no such provision for transgenders, the lawyer refused to offer her help.

IV. CONCLUSION

The movie 'Naanu Avanalla...Avalu' has both positive and negative portrayal of transgenders. However, the negative portrayal in this film was used deliberately to show the grim realities of a transgender's lifestyle. It is important to notice the lead characters of this film playing transgender roles. The movie has achieved its goal in creating awareness on including the transgenders in mainstream society and breaking the stereotype.

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Paper 4**FACTORS WHICH INFLUENCE ON-LINE BUYING BEHAVIOR DURING FESTIVE SEASON****V. T. Shailashri, Dr.P.S.Aithal, Dr. Surekha Shenoy**Professor, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore 575001.India
shailashrivt@gmail.com**Abstract**

Rising incomes in the hands of a young population, a growing economy, expansion in the availability of products and services and easy availability of credit all has given rise to new consumer segments and a rising acceptability of debt, whether it is mobile phones, credit cards, apparel or organized retail, people clearly seem to be spending more, particularly on discretionary items. The credit facility from business houses has been increasing at a rapid rate. This shows the terrific cut-throat competition in the ever changing market. Consumers in large metros are opting for online retail and e-commerce for most of their purchases, the trend is slowly penetrating in non-metro cities as well.

Festival Sales are a latest fad in India contributing tremendously to the growth of the online sales. All marketing retailers use the festival time to promote their products – either new or stock clearance products at heavy discounts or other offers (freebies, cash backs, buy 1 get 1 etc), The major shopping festival in India comes around the period of the period of October-November when Diwali is celebrated and most of the online e commerce sites provide big ticket offers during this period having created unique names for such shopping events – for example – Big billion days by Flipkart, Great Indian Shopping Festival by Amazon to name some. This study is an attempt to understand consumer buying behavior in India during the festive season.

Keywords: Consumer Buying Behavior, Online Marketing, Festive season, Digitization**1. INTRODUCTION**

Festival Sales are a latest fad in India contributing tremendously to the growth of the online sales. All marketing retailers use the festival time to promote their products – either new or stock clearance products at heavy discounts or other offers (freebies, cash backs, buy 1 get 1 etc), The major shopping festival in India comes around the period of the period of October-November when Diwali is celebrated and most of the online e commerce sites provide big ticket offers during this period having created unique names for such shopping events – for example – Big billion days by Flipkart, Great Indian Shopping Festival by Amazon to name some.[1,2]

2. OBJECTIVES

The study is being carried out to understand the following key parameters apart from other parameters as part of the survey:

1. Various Factors that contribute highly towards festival spends which determine the consumer buying behaviour.
2. Relationship between Income and Spends during festival sales.
3. Relationship between Spends and payment mode.
4. Relationship between day of sale and the expenditure.
5. Frequency of problems faced by consumers during festival sales shopping.
6. Other patterns observed based on the data captured/generated.
 - Advertisement Channels Influence
 - Items Shopped
 - Websites accessed
 - Eagerness of festival sale

3. CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

Consumer behaviour deals with the study of buying behaviour of consumers. Consumer behaviour helps us understand why and why not an individual purchases goods and services from the market.[3] The study of consumer behaviour explains as to:

- Why and why not a consumer buys a product?
- When a consumer buys a product?
- How a consumer buys a product?

Consumer Behaviour is a branch which deals with the various stages a consumer goes through before purchasing products or services for his end use.[4]

Why do you think an individual buys a product?

- Need
- Social Status
- Gifting Purpose

Why do you think an individual does not buy a product?

- No requirement
- Income/Budget/Financial constraints
- Taste

When do you think consumers purchase products?

- Festive season
- Birthday
- Anniversary
- Marriage or other special occasions

There are in fact several factors which influence buying decision of a consumer ranging from psychological, social, and economic and so on.

The four type of consumer buying behavior are:

- Routine Response/Programmed Behavior □ buying low involvement frequently purchased low cost items; need very little search and decision effort; purchased almost automatically. Examples include soft drinks, snack foods, milk etc.[5]
- Limited Decision Making □ buying product occasionally. When you need to obtain information about unfamiliar brand in a familiar product category, perhaps. Requires a moderate amount of time for information gathering. Examples include Clothes-- know product class but not the brand.[6]
- Extensive Decision Making □ Complex high involvement, unfamiliar, expensive and/or infrequently bought products. High degree of economic/performance/psychological risk. Examples include cars, homes, computers, education. Spend a lot of time seeking information and deciding. Information from the companies MM; friends and relatives, store personnel etc. Go through all six stages of the buying process.[7]
- Impulse buying □ no conscious planning.[8,9]

We can briefly understand from the above that consumer buying is not an easy process to understand and devise marketing strategies. The purpose of this study is to understand the consumers buying behaviour during online festive sales.

4. METHODOLOGY

Primary Data collection with a small sample of 30 respondents. An Online Google form questionnaire has been devised for the same that enlists questions evoking different responses from the consumers. The responses were coded and entered in SPSS to generate different levels of output analysis in the form of tables and charts.

5 Analysis and Interpretation

Factor Analysis

The following 8 factors as shown below in the figure are analysed using factor analysis to understand as to which of the factors have a higher degree of influence on the consumer buying behaviour during festival shopping.

Which of the below factors influences your decision to purchase during a festival sales? *

(Please Tick Only one Rating for each row)

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Heavy discounts i...	<input type="radio"/>				
Additional freebie...	<input type="radio"/>				
Combo discount ...	<input type="radio"/>				
Free Delivery.	<input type="radio"/>				
Free additional W...	<input type="radio"/>				
Exchange Offers.	<input type="radio"/>				
No-Cost-EMI (Inte...	<input type="radio"/>				
Bank Tie-Ups (10...	<input type="radio"/>				

		Heavy Discounts	Freebies	Combo Discount	Free Delivery	Free Addtl Warranty	Exchnng Offers	No Cost EMI	Bank Tie Ups
Correlation	HeavyDiscount s	1.000	-.104	-.033	-.082	-.041	.049	.015	.123
	Freebies	-.104	1.000	.414	.107	.293	.192	.383	.420
	ComboDiscount	-.033	.414	1.000	.330	.660	.308	.187	.258
	FreeDelivery	-.082	.107	.330	1.000	.159	.300	-.040	-.180
	FreeAddtnlWarranty	-.041	.293	.660	.159	1.000	.505	.373	.470
	ExchnngOffers	.049	.192	.308	.300	.505	1.000	.408	.410
	NoCostEMI	.015	.383	.187	-.040	.373	.408	1.000	.636

BankTieUps	.123	.420	.258	-.180	.470	.410	.636	1.000
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Interpretation

- A correlation matrix is simple a rectangular array of numbers which gives the correlation coefficients between a single variable and every other variables in the investigation.
- With respect to Correlation Matrix if any pair of variables has a value less than 0.5, consider dropping one of them from the analysis (by repeating the factor analysis test in SPSS by removing variables whose value is less than 0.5).
- The off-diagonal elements (The values on the left and right side of diagonal in the table below) should all be very small (close to zero) in a good model. The values in the above table conform to the condition as stated.

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
HeavyDiscounts	1.000	.799
Freebies	1.000	.564
ComboDiscount	1.000	.666
FreeDelivery	1.000	.721
FreeAddtnlWarranty	1.000	.673
ExchngOffers	1.000	.597
NoCostEMI	1.000	.671
BankTieUps	1.000	.815

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Interpretation

- The next item from the output is a table of communalities which shows how much of the variance (i.e. the communality value which should be more than 0.5 to be considered for further analysis. Else these variables are to be removed from further steps factor analysis) in the variables has been accounted for by the extracted factors.
- BankTieUps , HeavyDiscounts and FreeDelivery have the highest variance
- All these are good extraction values since they are more than 0.5 in value

SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSION

A sample study of 30 respondents geographically scattered in different cities mostly in South India and with 53% respondents in the 20 to 30 Years age bracket, a detailed SPSS analysis revealed that Festival sales is indeed very beneficial for the marketers. Marketers will need to take holistic approach in preparing marketing campaigns for their products to be promoted during a festival sale on the different ecommerce sites. Flipkart and Amazon are their best bets

in deriving profits. No separate marketing strategy is required to target men and women separately as the proportions of the gender shopping during festival sale are the same.

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Paper 5

FIPPS & INFORMATION ASSURANCE: THE ROOT AND FOUNDATION**P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal², A. Bhumali³, Kalishankar Tiwary⁴, R. Rajesh⁵**¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India³Vice Chancellor, Raiganj University, West Bengal, India⁴Dean (Science & Management), Raiganj University, West Bengal, India⁵Principal, Rohini College of Engineering and Technology, TN, India**Corresponding Author:** pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Within Information Science there are various concepts and among these Information Privacy and Security is important one. Within this security among the important topics the Fair Information Practice is important one. Fair Information Practice in short is called as FIPPs. It is the result of commission's enquiry into the web in which online entities collect various personal information and also assure that practice in information is fair enough. The Fair Information Practice is a core for healthy information privacy protection. It is important to note that FTC has been engaged regarding the online privacy from 1995. The Fair Information Practice basically was proposed in the year 1973 in the report called US Secretaries Advisory Committee on Automated Personal Data System. It was proposed to talk about records, computers and Rights of the Citizen. The fundamental contribution of this committee was to design and development of codes for fair information practice for the betterment of Automated Personal Data System. It is important to note that this commission might also have played a big role in development of Fair Information Practice Principle (FIIPs) in 1977 as mentioned in their report called Personal Privacy in an Information Society. The Information assurance is about the design, development, management of information related policies. It talks about the assurance of the content and information having manual and technological attributes. Information Assurance is the broader area of Security related areas. The FIIP is an important affair of Information Assurance. As Information Assurance is about the policy and framework designing hence in this paper several affairs leading to FIPPs, its role and importance, its characteristics, features and functions have been described in brief manner.

Keywords: Information Assurance, Fair Information Practice Principle, FIPPs, Information Security, IT Laws, Information Policies

1. Introduction

Information Assurance is a topic of the Information Science and Technology. This is the latest addition in Security and Privacy segment. Information Assurance deals with the both manual and computational security related affairs leading to database, websites and networks etc. Information Assurance is broad domain which is also closely associated with different

legal and managerial affairs leading to security policies; which include design, development, management etc. Cyber law, IT Act, Policies on information, Data and Information Privacy etc including their protections are also under the jurisdiction of Information Assurance [1], [5]. This field is concerned about the technologies as well [2], [3], [7]. Many of the academicians, organizations and institutions are using Information Assurance as synonym with other field viz. IT Security, Information Security and Cyber Security; however there are differences. Information Assurance deals with manual information privacy/ security related affairs and also legal affairs such as designing and formulation of security related concerns viz. Information Policy, Information Privacy, Information Security etc [6], [18]. Information Assurance and its development normally depend on various kind of objective, methods and procedure and among these Fair Information Practice Principles are important. FIPPs are core for suitable and sophisticated information development.

2. Objective and Agenda

This paper is conceptual as well as theoretical in nature and deals with various aims and objectives and among these, few important are included—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance in brief with reference to the characteristics and features.
- To know about the core functions and objectives of Information Assurance with reference to the current trends.
- To dig out the latest on Information Assurance with special focus on information protection policies.
- To learn about the Fair Information Practice Principles including its meaning, characteristics and features.
- To know about the steps and process of good information practice and with reference to the Fair Information Practice Principles.

3. Information Assurance: Overview

Information assurance (IA) is the safeguard mechanism for the security, privacy and integrity of data which are used by the individuals as well as organizations. Here it deals with the occupations related with the managing the risks and also its uses [4], [9]. The IA also deals with the processing, storing, as well as transferring of data. As a complex task, Information assurance applies in different places regarding data management in both digital and physical means. It is worthy to note that, Information assurance is concerned about the affairs in electronic device privacy and security [8], [18], [21]. The reputed and renowned organization viz. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) explain that *any measures that protect and defend information and information systems by ensuring their availability, integrity, authentication, confidentiality, and non-repudiation. These measures include providing for restoration of information systems by incorporating protection, detection, and reaction capabilities*—As Information assurance.

Fig: 1-The smaller and brooders knowledge and practice field of Security related areas

4. Information Assurance: Characteristics with Function

Information Assurance is a broad area for information privacy management and technological solutions; and there are many features and functions in this field viz.

- Information Assurance may be considered for the manual as well as technological areas. In manual areas it is the aspects related to design, development of information privacy policies and framework etc [10], [20], [27].
- Information assurance is for making information available to every entities to the concerned one and in a right place.
- The data privacy, Information Privacy, protection become easy with the Information Assurance from different unauthorized and illegal access of information.
- Technological security is the core of Information Assurance and these are lies on information security and also IT security.
- Information Assurance promotes and helps in reading homeland security viz. terrorism, cyber terrorism, cyber war.
- To ensure and managing mobile security, network privacy, security and assurance, database etc Information Assurance is highly recommended.
- Designs, development, security of database and information system become easy with Information Assurance practice.
- Various areas viz. cloud security, infrastructure management, and trust management are the core of Information Assurance.

- Strategies on information management, risk management of information including technological means are the important factor for better Information Assurance practice.

5. Information Protection Policy

Information protection employs security solutions, encryption, and other technologies, as well as policies and processes, to secure information. Information protection can be thought of as a sub-discipline or component of information assurance. While both share a goal of maintaining the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of information, information protection is specifically focused on achieving this through information security, whereas information assurance focuses on ensuring the quality, reliability, and retrievability of information in addition to keeping it protected [11], [18], [23].

FIPPs?

Information Assurance is a broad field within Information Science and within this field there are various concepts. Among these, Fair Information Practice is important one which is called as FIPPs. The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) is a core for healthy information privacy protection designing, development and management. The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) has been engaged as an online privacy from 1995. The commission of The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) here consider following principle as a core:

- Notice or awareness
- Choice or consent
- Problem with choice or consent
- Access or participation
- Integrity or security

In the year 1973, The Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) was proposed in the report (*named as US Secretaries Advisory Committee on Automated Personal Data System*). The affairs leading to record, computers and Right of the Citizen basically covered under the Fair Information Practice (FIPPs) [12], [22], [28]. The concerned committee developed the Fair Information Practice Principles (FIPPs) due to design and development of codes for healthy information practice for Automated Personal Data System. It is worthy that; this commission played a big role in development of Fair Information Practice Principle in their report called Personal Privacy in an Information Society [14], [18], [26].

It is a fact that different countries have initiated privacy law. So, FIIPs also developed rapidly with a focus on International implications of privacy regulation. The Council of Europe in the year 1980 has adopted convention for the protection of individuals with regard to automated processing of personal data.

At the same time, OECD guidelines have been proposed by the organization for economic co-operation and development (OECD). Hence, it is important to note that Council of Europe Convention, OECD guidelines, European Union Data Protection Directives play a vital role for the formation of FIPPs principles. Moreover, these organizations have revised and extended the original US statement of FIPPs [14], [19], [25].

FIPPs & Core Principles

A Healthy Fair Information Practice Principles basically depends on various types of process and methods. The core principles of Fair Information Practice Principles include the following (also refer fig:2 for more clarification)—

1. **Notice:** It is important to note that every consumer should get information on different kind of information regarding best information practice. Ultimately regarding notice or awareness following should be taken into consideration:
 - Identification of the entity collecting the data.
 - A suitable place for the user and uses to which data will be used or put.
 - The nature of the data collected and the way of collection.
 - Steps taken for ensuring confidentiality, integrity and quality of data [16], [19], [24].
2. **Choice or content:** Choice or content is an important part of fair information practice. It is actually the giving consumer option regarding the content. More importantly choice is related with the secondary use of information apart from urgent requirement information collector. The following two are typical model for choice viz.-

i) **OPT-ON**

ii) **OPT-OUT**

In first method consumer basically give permission for their information to be used for other purposes. Without this permission this information handling are not possible. Whereas the second option OPT-OUT requires users to decline permission for other uses. Basically both of the system is designed for better information transparency.

Fig: 2 The core principle of Fair Information Practice Principles

3. **Access or participation:** It is an important part within fair information practice principle. Here all the data and information should be collected and verified with proper accuracy. It is worthy to note that access of information should be inexpensive and timely otherwise it is very difficult to use information for the consumer [17], [20].
4. **Integrity and security:** Within fair information practice principle integrity talks about this security of the information. Here all the information should be secured, if all the information are kept in a place with good interactive policy. However it is important to note that proper cross referencing and reputable database should be provided. Information collectors basically can keep their data in a particular or linked database. It is worthy to note that internal and external security threats should be kept in mind. Data encryption as well as different kind of based system may be used for avoiding threat from the outside.
5. **Enforcement:** Enforcement may be treated as the redress. It is important to note that fair information practice is only possible with good, sophisticated and dynamic enforcement system. There are following three types of enforcement systems viz.-
 - i) **Self regulation** (Here information collector or similar body perform the self regulation)
 - ii) **Private remedies** (Here civil causes of action for the individual: those information are misused)
 - iii) **Government enforcement** (It includes civil and criminal penalties by the government bodies or ministry) [18], [21].

6. Issues and FIPPs

There are various concern about the Fair Information Practice Principles and among these few important are included in the collection of data of any human being should be in legal way and by appropriate and authentic means. The personal data should be appropriate, complete and up-to-date in nature. The purpose of the data collection should be specified and personal data should be disclosed. As far as Fair Information Practice Principles is concerned it is worthy to note that the security safeguard principles should be modeled and followed as much as possible. Moreover, a general policy regarding the openness about developments, practices as well as policies with respect to personal data may also be undertaken [13], [20].

7. Conclusion

The Fair Information Practice Principles and its importance are important and valuable in different context. The Information development is the root for the development of any kind of Organizations, Institutions and government bodies those are doing well in terms of better information practice. Information Practice is included in the affairs of information leading to collection, selection, organization, processing, management and dissemination. As far as Fair Information Practice Principles is concerned, the role of information governance is treated as vital one. Previously only developed countries have focused on better and healthy Information Practice and thus different nations have developed various policies and framework on this. As far as Fair Information Practice Principles is concerned it may be called as Personal Data Protection or Simply Data Protection. For the successful information practice we need to follow-up all the steps and procedure as much as possible.

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A STUDY ON SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN MANGALURU CITY-CUSTOMER BENEFITS

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Abstract:

Social media is playing a vital role especially in developing countries. It is an emerging source for all companies to create awareness for their products or services in customer minds now a day the majority of the customer in modern days using internet. Social media is one of the ways to give short and eminent information to their target customers and to improve the company sale with the help of Social media companies are share message via the internet through websites, social networks. Social media now a day is among the 'best possibilities available' to an item to get in touch with potential customers. Community social networking websites are the method to interact socially. These new media win the believe in of customers by linking with them at a deeper level. Social media is most important for social networking content sharing and online accessing did to its reliability. Social media opens a wide place for business such as online marketing .marketing which occurs via social media marketing. Social media marketing is a powerful way for businesses of all sizes to reach prospects and customers. Your customers are already interacting with brands through social media, and if you're not speaking directly to your audience through social platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram,

Keywords: social media, growth of internet user. Forms of social media, role of social media techniques of marketing management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media marketing is the use of social media platforms and websites to promote a product or service. Although the terms e-marketing and digital marketing are still dominant in academia, social media marketing is becoming more popular for both practitioners and researchers. Most social media platforms have built-in data analytics tools, which enable companies to track the progress, success, and engagement of ad campaigns. Companies address a range of stakeholders through social media marketing, including current and potential customers, current and potential employees, journalists, bloggers, and the general public. On a strategic level, social media marketing includes the management of a marketing campaign, governance, setting the scope (e.g. more active or passive use) and the establishment of a firm's desired social media "culture" and "tone."

When using social media marketing, firms can allow customers and Internet users to post user-generated content (e.g., online comments, product reviews, etc.), also known as "earned media," rather than use marketer-prepared advertising copy. A Social media

networking allow individuals, businesses and other organizations to interact with one another and build relationships and communities online. When companies join these social channels, consumers can interact with them directly. That interaction can be more personal to users than traditional methods of outbound marketing and advertising. Social networking sites act as word of mouth or more precisely, e-word of mouth. The Internet's ability to reach billions across the globe has given online word of mouth a powerful voice and far reach. The ability to rapidly change buying patterns and product or service acquisition and activity to a growing number of consumer's .In 2014, over 80% of business executives identified social media as an integral part of their business and also it is a business strategy. Business retailers have seen 133% increases in their revenues from social media marketing.

2. OBJECTIVE

- To study the benefits to consumer from social media marketing
- To identify what type of strategies are suitable for the company to satisfy the customer.
- To identify the most usable social media in marketing.

3. METHODOLOGY

- Our research study was conducted to know the benefits of customers from the social media marketing reference of Mangalore city. This was done through collection of 50 respondents.
- The research instrument used in collecting data was a questionnaire and survey was conducted through the means of Google form.
- For secondary data other sources like PDF files and internet has been used.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Table1: Gender wise distribution of sample

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
female	36	71.4
male	14	28.6
total	50	100

As per the above table, 71.4% respondents are female and rest of them 28.6% respondents are male.

Table 2: Age wise distribution of sample

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
	26	52
25-30	19	38
30-35	4	8
35-40	1	2
total	50	100

As per this table, majority of the 52% of the respondents are from 18-25 years of age group, 28% of the respondents are from 25-30 years of age group, 8% of the respondent from 30-35 years of age group, 2% of the respondents are from 35-40 years of age group.

Table 3: qualification wise distribution of sample

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
SSLC	3	6
PUC	5	10
UG	26	52
PG	16	32
total	50	100

As per the above table 50% of respondents are PG qualification, 32% of the respondents are UG qualification, 10% of the respondents are the PUC qualification, 6% of the respondents SSLC qualification.

Table 4: How many time's you use social media?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
once in a week	9	18
Twice in a week	16	32
monthly	21	42
Twice in a month	4	8
total	50	100

As per the above table, 42% of the respondents are monthly using social media, 32% of the respondents are twice in a week using social media, 18% of the respondents are once in a week using the social media, and 8% of the respondents are twice in a month using social media.

Table 5: Which type of social media are you use?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
twitter	6	12
Facebook	14	28
Amazon	10	20
YouTube	14	28
Flipkart	6	12
total	50	100

As per the above table, 12% of the respondents are use Twitter, 28% of the respondents are use Facebook, 20% of the respondents are used Amazon, 28% of respondents are used YouTube, 12% of respondents are used Flipkart.

Table 6: What type of benefit you may get in social media marketing?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
access new information	17	34
less cost	12	24
Time consuming	11	22
quick delivery	10	20
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 34% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit for access new information, 24% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit for less cost , 22% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit for time consuming, 20% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit forquick delivery.

Table 7:Which type of social media you benefited more in marketing?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
amazon	17	34
Flipkart	17	34
Twitter	16	32
total	50	100

As per the above table, 34% of respondents are benefited more in Amazon marketing, 34% of respondents are benefited in Flipkart marketing, and 32% of respondents are benefited in Twitter Marketing.

Tables 8: Are you agree "social media is backborn of marketing in present scenario"

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Agree	16	32
Strongly agree	30	60
disagree	4	8
Strongly disagree	0	0
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority of 60% of respondents are strongly agree the above statement, 32% of respondents are agree the above statement and rest of the 8% of respondents are disagree the above statement.

Table 9: From which platform do you mostly access your social media accounts for marketing purpose?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Phone	25	50
Laptop	16	32
computer	6	12
tablet	3	6
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 50% of respondents access phone social media accounts for marketing purpose, 32% of respondents access laptop social media accounts for marketing purpose, 12% of respondents access computer social media accounts for marketing purpose remaining, 6% of respondents access tablet social media accounts for marketing purpose.

Table 10: Social media is highly beneficial for marketing purpose?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Yes	42	84
No	8	16
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 84% of respondents are says that yes social media is highly beneficial for marketing purpose and remaining 16% of respondents says that No.

Table 11: Social media helps to improve the business activities?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Yes	40	80
No	10	20
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 80% of exponents are says that social media helps to improve the business activities and rest of the 20% of respondents says that No.

Table 12:Do you think social media marketing is the most effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Yes	27	54
No	7	14
Maybe	16	32
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 54% of of respondents says that social media marketing is the most effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer but 32% of responses says that maybe and 14% of responses that No.

Table 13:How much do you agree with this statement " social media marketing helps consumer growth"

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
agree	29	58
Strongly agree	19	38
disagree	2	4
Strongly disagree	0	0
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 58% of respondents are agree the above statement, 38% of respondents strongly agree with the above statement and 4% of respondents disagree the above statement.

LIMITATION

- The study was restricted only to the Mangalore city.
- There can be chances of bias in the response given by the respondents.
- The sample size limited to 50 respondents only.

FINDINGS

- The most of the respondent are benefited from the Social media marketing.
- The 80% of respondents are agreed that Social media helps to improve the business activities.
- Most of the respondent says that it is effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer.
- Some of the respondent not agree that social media marketing helps consumer growth.

SUGGESTIONS

- Since social media has become part of everyone's life instead of spending so much money on advertisements, social media is the best platform to promote products.
- Government should encourage social media marketing and must frame rules and regulations.
- Social media is the best source for marketing because a large number of people are using social media.

5. CONCLUSION

This study discussing about benefits to consumers from social media marketing are conducted today in terms of technological, economical, political and cultural exchanges brought about by these forms of modern communication. As we know this modern communication platform giving benefits to customers today. Social media providing big opportunity to organizations to build better relations with clients and providing real one-to-one communication. Customers are now becoming more particular about with whom and from where they are buying products or services. One of the main reasons why businesses must use social media is because their competitors are using this platform daily as a marketing strategy. Customers and future customers also use that. Any products related to social media also help boost the world economy. Products like laptops, iPads, iPhones, headphones, headsets and so on which are used by customers to access social media received very high demand. Social media contains a lot of tools and applications which let the users express their opinion, publish articles, share videos and so on easily. Customers are now becoming more particular about with whom and from where they are buying products or services. They are willing to make an online search before making any purchase decision especially for expensive items. Since the internet is now more conveniently searchable through smartphones, customers can make a search in just a few minutes. That's why companies must have a social media presence and put some attention to manage customers. There is no better advertising than "word of mouth". Satisfied customers surely will share to their friends in their social network about their experiences with a particular company.

6. QUESTIONNAIRE:

“A study on Social Media Marketing in Mangaluru City-Customer benefits”

Name:

Gender: a) Male b) Female

Age:

- 18-25
- 25-30
- 30-35
- 35-40

Educational qualification:

- SSLC
- PUC
- UG
- PG

1. How many times do you use social media?

- Once in a week
 - Twice in a week
 - Monthly
 - Twice in a month
2. Which type of social media you are use?
- Twitter
 - Face book
 - Amazon
 - Flip Kart
3. What type of benefit you may get?
- Quick delivery
 - Time consuming
 - Less cost
 - access new information
4. Which type of social media you benefited more in marketing?
- Amazon
 - Flip kart
 - Twitter
 - Other
5. Are you agree social media is backbone marketing in present scenario?
- Agree
 - Strongly agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
6. From which platform do you mostly access your social media accounts for marketing purpose?
- Laptop
 - Phone
 - Tablet
 - Computer
7. Social media is highly beneficial for marketing purpose?
- Yes
 - No
8. Social media helps to improve the business activities?
- Yes
 - No
9. Do you think social media marketing is the most effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer?
- Yes
 - No
 - Maybe
10. How much do you agree with this statement?
“Social media marketing helps consumer growth”

- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

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Paper 8

LOUD BASED SMART DUSTBIN SYSTEM FOR METRO STATION

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Abstract:

RFID based Smart Dustbin System is a prototype model of next generation dustbin which would be highly equipped with sensors. This model mainly focuses on the security aspects. Some of bomb blasts during 2008 serial blasts in Delhi were placed in dustbins. After the blasts dustbins were removed from all the metro stations in Delhi. This is because dustbins are an easy way to put the explosives. In this paper we present a viable solution for dustbins at metro stations. We have built this prototype model of this smart dustbin system using RFID tags, RFID reader, Ultrasonic sensors, Geared motors, Servo motors, Arduino UNO, Raspberry-pi and solar panel for power supply. The system uses cloud based monitoring system for garbage monitoring. With the use of cloud based system there is no need of routine checking of dustbins. To make the system ecofriendly and preserve carbon neutral footprint of metro we are using miniature solar panel for power supply.

Keywords: RFID, Smart Dust Bin, Ultrasonic sensor, PIR Motion sensor, Solar Panel.

1. Introduction

With an average daily ridership of 2.7 million passengers, Delhi metro simply don't house the facility as basic as dustbins premises. Till 2008 Delhi metro stations were having dustbins, but after 13 September 2008 serial bomb^[1] blasts, dustbins were removed from all the metro station citing security threads. But removal of dustbin is not a good solution. One more problem with dustbins on public places is that they needed to be checked frequently so that they don't overflow. Routine checks for cleaning the waste are not efficient has dustbin may get filled early and vice versa. So with the use of Ultrasonic sensors we ensure that dustbin is emptied only when it is close to filling. Delhi metro already uses RFID based tickets and smart cards for ticketing purpose. So there is no need to create new RFID tags for the purpose of using bins. The users with their metro smart cards could easily access these bins. To get the access of these bins customer could have to have register through their Aadhar card at the Registration Desk for the verification of their identity. Once they are verified, the authorities would have a full data base of each customer who is using the bin. So, even if by chance something happens the officials could have all the data of each and every user for that particular interval which could include users address, fingerprints, photograph, retina scan etc. This could help the authorities to find the culprits very easily.

Fig 1: System Architecture

2. POWER SUPPLY

To provide the power supply to our automated system we are using two Solar Panels^[2] of 5v output each. The cumulative output of both these panels would be used to charge the rechargeable lithium ion battery of 9v. This battery would be used to provide minimal power supply to our Arduino Development Board, Raspberry pi Development Board, RFID EM-18 Module and the motors.

We are using solar power as it is a renewable source of energy. This power source would also make our system efficient even in the remote areas where there is no source of power supply nearby. And since our power source is renewable source of energy, so it would be cost efficient too. We would be only requiring one-time setup investment which is also not very expensive to operate the system lifelong.

3. ARDUINO DEVELOPMENT BOARD

Arduino^[3] is a very cheap development board, which was developed in Italy for the first time. It has an ATmega328 microcontroller. It also has a 32 KB Electrically Erasable Programmable Read Only Memory whose function is to store the set of instruction in the form of code written in Embedded C Language on the Arduino IDE, Integrated Development Environment^[4]. It has 6 analog pins to take analog data as input. It has 6 PWM pins to provide us with analog output. It has 14 digital pins which help us take output as well as input data digitally. Except from the input/output pins it also has a bunch of power pins which include 3 ground pins, one 5v output pin, one 3.3v output pin and a V_{in} pin. The development

board is capable of taking of input power supply in 3 different ways which are:

- Through USB Serial Port.
- Through Vin pin present on the development board.
- Through DC input jack.

The best part about this development board is that it can easily interface with almost all the sensors present in the market. This quality of this board makes it most susceptible for prototype development.

Fig 2: Arduino development board

4. EM-18 RFID READER MODULE

RFID stands for Radio Frequency Identification. EM-18^[5] is a RFID reader that is basically used to read RFID tags and extra data from that particular RFID tag. This module basically functions on the concept of electromagnetic induction. Both, the reader as well as tag consists of a coil. The basic difference between these two coils is that the reader has an active coil, i.e. it is provided with an initial power supply while the tag has a passive coil. When the tag coil comes inside the electromagnetic field of the reader coil it starts conducting. When it starts conducting current starts following through the passive coil. This passive coil at one end is connected to an IC which has a unique identification number in Hexa-decimal format. When the tag comes in the range of the reader it sends this number to the reader which further forwards this data to the micro controller. The main objective of the micro controller is to check whether the person using the bin is authentic or not from the database at the cloud server. If the user authentic it grants the permission to the microcontroller to open the bin.

5. ULTRASONIC SENSOR

Ultrasonic^[6] sensor is a device that is used to measure the distance between a particular object from the sensor. It has a transmitter which transmits sound wave and a receiver that receives the same signal. The concept of calculation of distance behind this sensor is very simple. It basically calculates the time taken by the signal to come back after reflection from the object, multiplies it with speed of sound and then divides it with 2 as travelling double distance i.e. going towards the object and coming back from that object. Here we are using this sensor to find the distance between the garbage and the lid of the bin. So, as the bin starts filling the distance between the garbage and the lid would start to decrease, and when it will cross a certain level the microcontroller would send the data regarding clearing the garbage from the bin to the cloud server which can be easily forecasted on the frontend with the help of an app or a webpage.

6. GEARED MOTOR AND SERVO MOTOR

Geared motors^[7] are simple motors that have number of gears attached to it control the speed and power of the motor. Here in this model we are using this motor to open and close the lid of the dustbin with the help of L293D^[8] motor driver IC. We require a motor driver IC in this case because our motor requires (9-12) V power supply which our development board Arduino UNO cannot afford as it works on 5V power supply. So, our microcontroller basically sends a control signal which further is responsible for turning motor ON or OFF with the help of L293D motor driver IC.

Servo Motors^[9] are simple motors which are connected to a sensor that provides it with a position feedback system. As a result of this feedback system this type of motor is able to control its angular and linear displacement as well as acceleration and velocity. We are using this motor to open and close the lock system of the dustbin's lid. When there would be an authorized User ID tag swiped in front of the dustbin, the microcontroller would instruct the servo motor to open the lid. If the User ID is not authorized, simply the controller will open the lid lock hence, the lid of the bin will not open.

7. PIR MOTION SENSOR

PIR Motion sensor^[10] is nothing but Passive Infrared Motion Sensor. As its name suggests that its basic function is to sense motion in the surrounding. Here we are using this sensor to check whether there is any kind of movement inside the bin after opening the lid or not. If we would be throwing anything inside the dustbin it would result in producing motion inside the bin. Due to this movement our PIR Sensor would simply generate a HIGH digital signal which would be sent to the microcontroller. As a result of this microcontroller would mark that particular user has thrown something inside the bin and send this data to the cloud server which would be a maintained record for the authorities to easily find the culprit if anything goes wrong. Apart from this our PIR also has two 10K potentiometer on it. Both of them have their specified tasks designated to it. The task of the first potentiometer is control the range of the sensor. This simply means that, this potentiometer would specify the area which the sensor would specify the area which the sensor would cover to sense the motion. So, with the help of this potentiometer, our sensor will not sense any motion outside the bin. The task of second potentiometer is to set delay which simply means, for how long the sensor will provide the same response at the output terminal. Both of these potentiometers are very

important for the proper functioning of the sensor so, we have to set their values very precisely to get the correct output at the output terminal of the sensor.

8. RASPBERRY-PI AND RASPBIAN

Raspberry-pi^[11] is low cost, credit card sized, small single board computer developed in United Kingdom. The development board has a 1.2GHz 64/32bit quad core ARM Cortex processor. It also has an inbuilt RAM of 1 GB. We in install an Operating System on this board with the help of 0 a micro-SD card or a pen drive. It has 4 USB ports, 1 HDMI Port, an Ethernet jack, a micro USB port for power supply, 40 GPIO (General Purpose Input Output) pins to connect sensors through it. It is very compatible and helps to build IOT Projects very easily. Here we are using Raspbian operating system on this board which is nothing but a LINUX operating system specially made for this board. With the help of Raspberry-pi we would be handling the cloud server for this particular project. The main objective of this board would be to connect our hardware interface with the cloud server and this board would be connect our hardware interface with the cloud server and this board would only be responsible for the back-end part of the project.

9. AWS IOT CLOUD

AWS (Amazon Web Services) IOT Cloud^[12] provides secure, bidirectional communication between IOT devices and cloud. This enables us to collect telemetry data from multiple devices, and we can store and analyze the data. We can take benefit of the huge processing power at our disposal to take care of large no of requests coming from IOT devices.

10. DJANGO AND PYTHON

Django^[13] is a web development and CMS platform built using python. Server-side programming for the system is done in Django.

11. ADHAR API AND AUTHENTICATION OF SMART CARD

Role of Aadhar API^[14] will be pivotal in the identification and registration of metro card holders authorized to use dustbins. Computers will be required to connect and authenticate their Aadhar card with the help of fingerprint reader. Those persons which connect and authorize their Aadhar number with metro card will be allowed to use dustbins by simply swiping their card on the card reader present on the dustbin. Authentication of smart card will be done via cloud. But there will be fail-safe mechanism so that when the internet connection is not working the cards can be checked against the local copy of list of smart cards. Processing power of the raspberry pi device is limited so the data is sent over the cloud for authentication. But as a fail- safe mechanism we are having local authentication also if the internet connection is not working.

12. REGISTRATION DESK

A registration panel is there for Aadhar card authentication. It is made using Django at backend and makes use of Aadhar API's eKYC (Known Your Customer) feature for registration of users. The RFID tag User ID will be regularly uploaded on cloud on a central database. Raspberry pi will be regularly updated with RFID tag User ID's. This is in place as a fail-safe mechanism so if the internet is not working the tag id can be authenticated locally.

Fig 3: Aadhar API and authentication of smart card

13. ANALYTICS PANEL

There will be analytics panel on every metro station so as to monitor the garbage levels in the bins, so that there is no need of routine checking. Marketing use of individual ultrasonic sensor data it will represent the garbage level in a dustbin.

14. CONCLUSION

In the upcoming years India is going to get densely populated and more number of smart cities would overhead in the upcoming years. Due to large population density in those cities metro trains would be a major requirement for the means of transportation. So, these systems will help us to keep our environment clean near the metro station as well as inside the city with keeping all security aspects in mind. These systems will also help us in waste management. The authorities would also help us in waste management. The authorities would also have a track of each and every user which would help them to monitor the cleanliness in the city.

15. FLOW CHART OF THE PROJECT

Fig 4: Project flowchart

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Paper 8

A NEW ATTITUDE-BEHAVIOUR (AB) THEORY FOR ACCEPTABLE LEADERS IN WINNING ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

The organizational fate depends on a committed effective decision maker who can predict the future business situations based on various affecting parameters on the organizational business. The right decisions taken at right time can elevate an organization as winning organization and the decision maker can transform himself as an acceptable leader. Such decisions can also decide the fate of the organization along with the livelihood of its employees. A winning leader is an asset of an organization and the employees are directly and indirectly get the benefits of such leader. If the leader fails in predicting the future of a profit oriented organization or not for profit organizations, the employees are directly going to be the victims of such wrong decisions. Leaders should able to make correct judgement while taking decisions based on effective predictions by using predictive analysis framework. The attitude of the leader plays an important role while making decisions on solving organizational/individual problems. In Simon's model of decision making, the attitude of the leader decides his ability of identifying a problem, finding alternative solutions, analysing these alternatives to find optimum alternative, and finally to implement the best alternative to practically solve the problem. Attitude is the mental status of a human being which represents the emotions based on his/her feelings at a given time and controls his/her instantaneous behaviour. In this paper, we have developed a theory on winning leaders actions based on their behaviour in organizations. It is argued that the behaviour of a leader depends on his/her attitude which may be positive or negative depends on the four factors identified as feelings, emotions, belief, and environment. Thus a supportive, effective, good environment creates positive attitude and hence winning leaders. The bad environment supports negative attitude due to wrong belief, negative emotions, and frustratiive feelings which are again depends on the present and past environment of the decision maker.

Keywords : ABCD Theory of Leadership, Attitude, behaviour, Choice, and Decision

1. INTRODUCTION :

An effective leader is the strength of an organization and his ability of making decisions related to the problems on short term and long term objectives of the organization decides the fate of the organization and hence the fate of the stakeholders. A committed leader in business organizations is an effective decision maker who can predict the future business situations based on various affecting parameters on the organizational business. Making right

decisions at right time on organizational challenges can elevate an organization as winning organization and transform the decision maker into an acceptable leader. Making right decision in organizational and business environment depends on three factors (1) leaders personality and behaviour, (2) quality of the information related to the problem/challenge, and (3) the ability of the leader on predicting the future. Since the decisions taken by the leader decides the fate of the organization along with the livelihood of its employees and their dependent family members, the role of the leader is very challenging and risk taking. It is argued in many scholarly analysis that a winning leader is an asset of an organization and the employees are directly and indirectly get the benefits of such leader. If the leader fails in predicting the future of a profit oriented organization or not for profit organizations, the employees are directly going to be the victims of such wrong decisions. Thus an understanding leader who can be role model for every employee is important in every organization for sustainability for long time.

Leaders should able to make correct judgement while taking decisions based on his personal traits (personality), his attitude, and ability to make effective predictions by using predictive analysis framework. The attitude of the leader plays an important role while making decisions on solving organizational/individual problems. It is argued that the personality of a leader cannot be changed easily [1]. In Simon's model of decision making, the attitude of the leader decides his ability of identifying a problem, finding alternative solutions, analysing these alternatives to find optimum alternative, and finally to implement the best alternative to practically solve the problem. Thus identifying a problem is the behaviour of a leader and is important initial instinct and is depends on the attitude of a leader.

According to ABC model of attitude suggested by Eagly & Chaiken 1993 & Van den Berg et al. 2006 [2-3], human attitude as an object has three components identified as Affect (A), Behaviour (B) and Cognition (C). Affect component represents the individual's feelings about the object Attitude, Behavior component represents the individual's intention towards the object Attitude, and Cognitive component represents the beliefs of an individual towards the object attitude.

But based on the observation and review of related works, we have developed an improved model on successful leadership for winning organizations which is based on Attitude and Behaviour of a leader called Attitude-Behaviour framework of Leadership. This model holds good for individual leadership and organizational leadership and describes how the past and present environment of a leader effects the present decisions on future performances of the organization for sustainability.

2. RELATED WORKS :

2.1 Leadership Theories

Many leadership theories are evolved during last 100 years. These theories are tried to explain the successful leadership qualities individually, working in teams, working in organizations and even working as leader in society. The important theories developed during last century with generality in their model include Great-man theory, Trait theory, Contingency or situational theory, Style and Behavior theory, Process Leadership theory, Transactional leadership theory, etc. Table 1 contains some of general leadership theories developed during last century. These theories are framed based on certain characteristics of a leader while making decisions and certain nature of the leader towards the problems he faces

in his life/organization/society. These theories focus on attitude of a leader and his behaviour towards making decisions.

Table 1 : Review of General leadership Theories and their focus

S. No.	Leadership Theory	Focus	Reference
1	Great-man Theory	Leader is born not made	Thomas Carlyle (1847) [4]
2	Trait Theory	Based on (i) emergent traits (those which are heavily dependent upon heredity) as height, intelligence, attractiveness, and self-confidence and (ii) effectiveness traits (based on experience or learning), including charisma	Ekvall & Arvonen, 1991 [5]
3	Contingency Theories (Situational)	There is no single right leadership because the internal and external dimensions of the environment require the leader to adapt to that particular situation	Greenleaf, 1977 [6]
4	Style and Behavior Theory	Leaders of three categories as democratic leaders, autocratic leaders, and laissez-faire leaders	Yukl (1989) [7]
5	Process Leadership Theory	Process theory focus on servant leadership, principal centered leadership and charismatic leadership	Greenleaf, (1996) [8]
6	Transactional leadership Theory	Type of contingent-reward leadership that had active and positive exchange between leaders and followers	Bass and Avolio (1994) [9]
7	Transformational leadership Theory	A transformational leader attempts to induce followers to reorder their needs by transcending self-interests and strive for higher order needs. Such leaders empowers the followers	House & Shamir, (1993) [10]

Further specific leadership theories developed and tested during last 50 years are also listed in table 2 which also include some of the general leadership theories. The focus or the constructs of the theories are listed along with scholarly published references. These theories are build or developed based on the leaders attitude of seeing and understanding the problems or situations to make decisions and his behaviour towards individual or organizational or social problems. All leadership theories deal with the decision making abilities of a leader in internal or external environmental uncertainties. Thus the published work deals with mainly on the behaviour of a leader in a given environment.

Table 2 : Specific Leadership theories developed during last 50 years

S. No.	Type of leadership Theories	Focus/ Constructs	Reference
1	Implicit leadership Theories	Individuals create cognitive representations of the world, and use these preconceived notions to interpret their surroundings and control their behaviours.	Offermann, L. R., (1994) [11]
2	Managerial leadership Theories	Leader who engages in an influence process for the purpose of helping others understand what needs to be done, or that helps other individuals or groups accomplish shared objectives	Yukl, G. (1989). [12]
3	Transactional and transformational leadership theories	Transactional leaders focus on organization, supervision, and group performance, where as transformational leaders focus on change within the organization.	Wofford, J. C., (1994) [13]
4	Contingency leadership Theory	It claims that there is no best way to organize a corporation, to lead a company, or to make decisions. Instead, the optimal course of action is contingent (dependent) upon the internal and external situation.	Yukl, G. (2011). [14]
5	Strategic Leadership Theories	It is the ability to influence others to voluntarily make decisions that enhance the prospects for the organisation's long-term success while maintaining short-term financial stability.	Tone Hosmer, L. (1982). [15]
6	Situational leadership Theories	It refers to when the leader or manager of an organization must adjust his style to fit the development level of the followers he is trying to influence.	Hersey, P., (1997) [16]
7	Personality and charismatic leadership	Articulating a vision and mission, and creating and maintaining a positive image in the mind of followers	House, R. J., (1992) [17]
8	Distributed leadership Theories	It equates with shared, collective and extended leadership practice that builds the capacity for change and improvement.	Barry, D. (1991) [18]
9	Shared leadership Theories	It broadly distributes leadership responsibility, such that people within a team and organization lead each other.	Pearce, C. L., (2000) [19]
10	Servant leadership	It is a philosophy and set of practices that enriches the lives of individuals, builds better organizations and ultimately creates a more just and caring	Van Dierendonck, D. (2011). [20]

		world.	
11	Clinical leadership	The concept of clinical healthcare staff undertaking the roles of leadership: setting, inspiring and promoting values and vision, and using their clinical experience and skills to ensure the needs of the patient	Stanley, D. J. (2012). [21]
12	Spiritual leadership	It is a holistic approach to leadership in which the leader strives to encourage a sense of significance and interconnectedness among employees.	Fry, L. W. (2003). [22]

2.2 Attitude–Behaviour Models :

Attitude-behaviour relations model is initially systematically studied in social psychology by Ajzen I et al during 1977 [23]. According to this model, the attitudinal and behavioral entities consisting of four different elements: (1) the action, (2) the target at which the action is directed, (3) the context in which the action is performed, and (4) the time at which the action is performed. The model predicts that behaviour is a monotonic function of attitudes and external conditions and that the strength of the attitude-behaviour relationship is a function of the strength of the external environment [24].

Ellis et. al [2] developed another ABC Model on human behaviour where – A stands for Antecedent (situation), B stands for Beliefs (thoughts of the situation/ interpretation of an event), and C stands for Consequences (outcome).

3. OBJECTIVES :

The paper is conceptual in nature and follows a research model of review based prediction and postulates based analysis to identify the suitable model in the form of a Theory to answer a question on what factors decides an acceptable leader in Winning Organizations. This also include :

- (1) To identify a suitable reason for success of a leader in winning organizations
- (2) To develop a suitable theory on Leaders’ action called behaviour.
- (3) To determine the underlying constructs of behaviour which decides the decision making characteristics of a leader in business organizations which a have a long term objectives.
- (4) To suggest some recommendations to redefine the objectives of both winning organizations and losing organizations.

4. FACTORS AFFECTING THE ATTITUDE :

The attitude of a person is determined by psychological factors like ideas, values, beliefs, perception, etc. All these have a complex role in determining a person's attitude. Aman Sharma, (2016) [25] identified eight factors responsible for the development of attitudes. These eight factors are (1) family, (2) peers, (3) conditioning, (4) social adjustment functions, (5) direct instruction, (6) modelling, (7) satisfaction of wants, and (8) prejudices. Another study [26] on factors influencing the attitude lists nine factors which are considered as (1) Social Factors, (2) Direct Instruction, (3) Family, (4) Prejudices, (5) Personal

Experience, (6) Media, (7) Educational and Religious Institutions, (8) Physical Factors, and (9) Economic Status and Occupations.

5. FACTORS AFFECTING THE BEHAVIOUR :

Behaviour is the outcome of the attitude of a person. The behaviour of a leader in a given situation depends on the attitude of him. This is well known and the outcome of many psychological studies [27]. According to one school of thought, the four main factors that influence behaviour and performance are: Biographical and demographical characteristics, Intellectual and physical abilities, Self-concept and self-esteem, and Personality. As per another school of thought, the behaviour of a person depends on six factors : (1) Willpower, (2) Knowledge and skills, (3) Social motivation, (4) Social ability, (5) Structural motivation, and (6) Structural ability. The third school of thought includes three factors as (1) Personal factors, (2) Environmental factors, and (3) Organizational factors affect individual behaviour. Finally, it is also argued that the following five factors affect the behaviour of a leader which include : (1) Personality, (2) Situation, (3) Needs, (4) Leadership style, and (5) Operating environment.

6. ATTITUDE-BEHAVIOUR MODEL OF LEADERSHIP :

Attitude is the mental status of a human being which represents the emotions at a given time and controls his/her instantaneous behaviour. Such behaviour reflects in instantaneous decision making of a leader.

6.1 Postulates of Attitude-Behaviour Model :

It can be argued that the behaviour of a human being depends on his/her attitude and the attitude depends on his or her feelings at that time which in turn depends on the emotions of the person. It can be argued that the emotions of a person depend on his/her beliefs on the situation. It is also known that the belief of a person is strongly depending on the environment around him during his present and past life. Accordingly, we propose the following postulates :

- (1) Personality cannot be changed so easily, but behaviour of a person can be changed.
- (2) The behaviour of a leader depends on his attitude.
- (3) The attitude of the leader depends on his feelings.
- (4) The feelings of a leader depend on his emotions.
- (5) The emotions of a leader mostly depend on his beliefs.
- (6) The belief of a leader depends on his present and past environment.

(Behaviour) => (Attitude) => (Feelings) => (Emotions) => (Beliefs) => (Environment)

Fig, 1 : Block diagram representing depending factors of Attitude and behaviour of a leader

6.2 Leadership and decision making :

A winning leader will make winning decisions by rightly analysing the situations to predict the future state of affairs. According to our theory of leadership, the behaviour (action) of a leader to solve an identified problem depends on his attitude. Hence the theory is called attitude-behaviour theory, which states that the behaviour of a leader depends on his attitude towards solving a problem or making a decision which further depends on his feelings, emotions, beliefs, and hence his present and past environment. The constructs of Attitude-Behaviour (AB) model are :

(1) Attitude :

Attitude is a tendency to act in a certain way, either favourably or unfavourably concerning objects, people, or events. Attitude of a person depends on how a person feels about a situation or an issue. It expresses an individual's positive or negative feeling about an object or a situation. Attitude of a person towards a given situation can be measured by measuring and understanding his feelings, and thoughts by asking questions to a person one can measure his feelings and thoughts. In general, if a person has a positive attitude about his work responsibilities, it will be reflected by good work performance, less absenteeism, less turnover, obedience towards rule or authority, etc. If a person has got a negative attitude towards his work responsibilities, he will act in exactly the opposite way. The negative attitude can be changed by simple persuasion or by training and coaching. Attitude is an abstract learned reaction and as per our postulate, it heavily depends on the feeling of a leader towards an object or an issue.

(2) Behaviour :

As mentioned earlier, behaviour is the outcome of the attitude of a person. The behaviour of a leader on a given situation depends on the attitude of him. This is well known and the outcome of many psychological studies. Behaviour can be measured by understanding the attitude of a person either by observing the actions or simply by asking questions to him about how he would behave in a particular situation. Behaviour is the action performed by a

person based on his attitude towards an object or an issue. As per our postulate behaviour of a leader depends on his attitude. Hence by improving the attitude, the behaviour can be improved.

(3) Feelings :

In psychology, the word is usually reserved for the conscious subjective experience of emotion. Feelings are also known as a state of consciousness, such as that resulting from emotions, sentiments or desires. Feeling is an internal state of affair of a human being. As per our postulate, feelings of a leader depend on his emotions.

(4) Emotions :

Emotion is considered as the feedback of feeling. Emotion is the external state of affair of a human being. Emotions are mental states of readiness that arise from appraisals of events or one's own thoughts. It is argued that emotions are event-driven, while feelings are learned behaviours that are usually in hibernation until triggered by an external event. Unlike feeling, an emotion involves little cognitive awareness. As per our postulate emotion of a leader depends on his beliefs about that event or issue or object.

(5) Beliefs :

Belief of a person depends on what he follows with or without any reason. Beliefs of a leader are distinguished into three types as : (1) behavioural beliefs, which are assumed to influence attitudes toward the behaviour, (2) normative beliefs, which constitute the underlying determinants of subjective norms, and (3) control beliefs, which influence perceived behavioural control. As per the postulate of our attitude-behaviour theory, belief of a leader depends on his present and past environment.

(6) Environment (Past & Present) :

The operating environment around a leader supports for risk taking and is motivating and encouraging creativity and allowing appropriate flexibility, rather than with rigidity and inflexibility. The environment which affects the attitude of a leader through his beliefs has various components (figure 3). The important components which decide the attitude of a leader are (1) Individual maturity of generous thinking which may have positive or negative effects as a positive thinker or negative thinker respectively. (2) Living place and the country situation which may have positive impact or negative impact. (3) Family culture and tradition has mainly positive impact. (4) Organizational atmosphere which may have positive or negative impact. (5) Competing situations internally or externally in the organization which is against organizational objectives or individual objectives of a leader.

Fig. 2 : Components of environment which effects the leaders' attitude

The important environmental components which affects the belief and hence the attitude of a leader and hence affects his behaviour are discussed below :

(1) Impact of Individual Maturity for effective Leader :

Leadership maturity is a leader's ability to engage consistently with others who are the stakeholders of the organization. Individual maturity demands the ability to make wise and appropriate judgments about different problems. Usually, the leadership maturity is decided based on certain parameters like (1) relevance to time, place and person, (2) productive in terms of contributions made, and (3) uplifting in such way that interactions are positive, fulfilling, and enriching. Acquiring leadership maturity is a lifelong process and involves various stages. In each stage of developing maturity, leaders will develop a corresponding identity. Based on how a leader process life events and experiences, he may spiral upwards to higher maturity or downwards to lower maturity. Sometimes, they may also get stuck at one level for the rest of their life.

(2) Impact of Living place & Country on effective Leader:

The environment in living place and the people in the surroundings also play an important role in developing the characteristics of a leader. Positive and encouraging atmosphere in home and surroundings will cultivate positive, generous feeling within a leader. Family stress may affect the decision making ability of a leader and such cases may create a catastrophic outcome in organizational performance. Similarly, the political and economical environment of the country and its impact on organizational performance or on society also affects the decision making ability of the leader.

(3) Impact of Family culture & tradition on effective Leader:

Culture plays a primary role on the person's perception of the world. Many studies have shown that people from different cultures perceive things differently. Perception is the process by which we become aware of our environment. Culture and perception are closely related because it is through their own culture that people view and perceive themselves and others in the environment. The application of a leadership style cannot be an imposition but needs to consider the diversity of cultures in order to be effective. Although we live in a

globalized economy in which everything is standardized, it is unlikely to find a generalization of the way culture influences leadership perception and execution.

(4) Impact of Organizational atmosphere on effective Leader:

Organizational business, opportunities, and culture also effect and makes an impact on a leader's ability and quality. It also improves the confidence of a leader for further innovation. A positive organizational atmosphere supports the leader for taking winning decisions. Stakeholders view on the organization or society in that country enhances or suppresses the confidence and risk taking ability of a leader.

(5) Impact of competing situations on effective Leader:

Both internal and external competition affects the strategic thinking ability of a leader. Competition may have either positive or negative effect on leaders decision making ability based on his personality, which depends on his attitude and hence his feelings, emotions, and belief. Positive leaders turn difficult situations into engaging learning moments whereas negative leaders convert challenges into unsolved problems.

7. CONCLUSIONS :

Based on reviewing related research, it is concluded that the attitude is the central characteristics of a leader and decides his behaviour in a given situation in an organization. Based on our postulates, the behaviour of a leader while reacting or responding to a situation depends on his attitude towards the problem, which in turn, depends on the feelings, emotions, and beliefs. It is also argued that the belief and hence feelings of a leader mainly depends on his present and past environment where he has grown and learned the life skills. Based on these aspects, we have developed a theory on winning leaders actions and their behaviour in organizations. It is argued that the behaviour of a leader depends on his/her attitude which may be positive or negative depends on the four factors identified as feelings, emotions, belief, and environment. Thus a supportive, effective, good environment creates positive attitude and hence winning leaders. The bad environment supports negative attitude due to wrong belief, negative emotions, and frustratiive feelings which are again depend on the present and past environment of the leader.

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Paper 10

STUDY OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES

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Abstract:

Background of the Study:

Knowledge Management (KM) is defined as those processes, tools and infrastructures by which an organization continuously improves, maintains and exploits all those elements of its knowledge base which the organization believes are relevant to achieving its goals.

Knowledge Management helps to improve the overall organizational performance. Active and dynamic implementation and management of knowledge are the two critical ways of enabling organizational performance enhancements, problem solving and decision making (Liebowitz, 1999).

Knowledge is often defined as a “justified personal belief.” There are much taxonomy that specify various kinds of knowledge. The most fundamental distinction is between “tacit” and “explicit” knowledge. (King, 2009)

Objective – This research attempts to study the importance of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in software industries.

Design/methodology/approach –The questionnaire on the two dimensions namely Knowledge Management policies and knowledge sharing of knowledge management (having 7 and 9 questions respectively) was prepared and distributed in Google Forms to the employees of different software companies. 141 employees from different software industries were responded to the questionnaire. The questionnaire had 13 a priori items on a Likert 5-point scale (5-strongly agree and 1-Strongly disagree).

This study tests only one main hypothesis (the role of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in effectiveness of knowledge management).

Total responses for each category is tabulated, analyzed and graph was prepared to show the importance of each of the factors in the knowledge management

Results and Discussions: Total of 141 responses were collected from different employees by distribution of questionnaire..

Out of 141 responses 77% of the employees have accepted that they have Knowledge Management policies in their organizations and 74% accepted that they have knowledge sharing methods in their organizations.

Conclusions:

The knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing methods are proved to be two important dimensions of knowledge management adopted in software industries.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Knowledge Management policies and knowledge sharing

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Paper 11**DEMONITISATION AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIAN ECONOMY****Mr. B. Sudheer Kumar**

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-Mail Id: - bskmba06@gmail.com**Abstract:**

On 8th November 2016, the Government of India announced the demonetization of all Rs.500 and Rs.1000 banknotes of the Mahatma Gandhi series. The government claimed that the action would curtail the shadow economy and crack down on the use of illicit and counterfeit cash to fund illegal activity and terrorism. The demonetization that happened will not only have economic impact but also social and political ramifications, both from immediate and long-term perspectives. This paper attempts to study impact of demonetization with reference to Common man. Through this article an attempt had been made to understand both its merits and demerits of demonetizations on Indian economy.

Keywords: Demonetization, Indian economy, Common man, Black Money, Corruption**1. INTRODUCTION:**

Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. It occurs whenever there is a change of national currency. The current form or forms of money is pulled from circulation and retired often to be replaced with new notes or coins. Such a step, for example, was taken when the European Monetary Union nations decided to adopt Euro as a currency. Zimbabwe, Fiji, Singapore and Philippines were other countries to have opted for currency demonetization. The demonetization of 500 and 1000 was a policy enacted by the Government of India on 8th November 2016. All 500 and 1000 banknotes of the Mahatma Gandhi series ceased to be legal tender in India from 9th November 2016. After the announcement that 500 and 1,000 rupee notes were no longer legal tender; people were given 50 days to deposit them in bank accounts or exchange them for new notes at banks and post offices, when only half of Indian adults have bank accounts. By withdrawing 86 percent of circulating currency when 70 to 80 percent of transactions are cash-based, the Indian government has burned down its economic house in order to eradicate the pest of corruption. According to The Reserve Bank of India, the most important reason for the demonetization of 500 and 1000 rupees note was the rise of fake currencies of the same notes, and also the higher occurrence of black money in the economy. "The fake notes are being used for illegal activities by anti-nationalists like terrorists and India being a nation of a cash-based economy, the circulation of fake currency continues to be a threat. But it has been taken care by Government that the public that a person who changed his higher value cash will get exactly the equal amount in lower denominations. Though people had time until the end of the year to deposit the notes in bank accounts, doing so in large quantities could expose them to high taxes and fines. So they rushed to gas pumps, banks, foreign-exchange counters, ATMs, to jewelry shops, and to creditors to repay loans.

2. HISTORY OF DEMONETISATION IN INDIA

The first demonetization was when Rs.1000, Rs.5000 and Rs.10,000 notes were taken out of circulation in January 1946 a year and a half before the country won independence from the British. The Rs.10,000 notes were the largest currency denomination ever printed by the Reserve Bank of India, introduced for the first time in 1938. All three notes were introduced in 1954. In the early 1970, the Wanchoo Committee, direct tax inquiry committee set up by the Government, suggested demonetization as a measure to unearth and counter the spread of Black Money. The move was called a „death blow“ to black marketers. The repercussions were similar to present demonetization with people dying of shock, exceptionally long lines at the banks and the middle classes being hit. Then in 1977, the Janta Party coalition government came into power. A year into the government’s term, party leader Morarji Desai was more bullish about cracking down on counterfeits and black money. The High Denomination Bank Notes (Demonetization) Act, instated by the ruling party on January 16th 1978, deemed the Rs.1,000, Rs. 5,000 and Rs.10,000 notes illegal for the second time. It was termed as “an Act to provide in the public interest for the demonetization of certain high denomination bank notes and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto”.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is based on Desk Research through collection of Secondary Data hence it is theoretical in nature with emphasis on Indian Economy. Following are the objectives of the study:

- ✓ To study the impact of demonetisation on common man.
- ✓ To study the impact of demonetisation on Indian Economy.
- ✓ To understand the impact of demonitisation on different industrial sectors.

Need for Demonetization

Demonetization is one of the Government’s bold steps towards transformation of Indian Economy. It is probably one of the biggest big-bang reforms undertaken by Government after a long time. In spite of many reasons quoted by Government, RBI in its FAQ on “Withdrawal of legal tender character of existing bank notes in the denomination of Rs. 500 and Rs. 1000” mentions reasons why this scheme is introduced. It reads as follows: “The incidence of fake Indian currency notes in higher denomination has increased. For ordinary persons, the fake notes look similar to genuine notes, even though no security feature has been copied. The fake notes are used for antinational and illegal activities. High denomination notes have been misused by terrorists and for hoarding black money. India remains a cash based economy hence the circulation of Fake Indian Currency Notes continues to be a menace. In order to contain the rising incidence of fake notes and black money, the scheme to withdraw has been introduced”.

Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi quoted the following reasons for demonetisation during a television address to the nation on 08.11.2016: “In a historical move that will add record strength in the fight against corruption, black money, money laundering, terrorism and financing of terrorists as well as counterfeit notes, the Government of India has decided that the five hundred and one thousand rupee notes will no longer be legal tender from midnight, 8th November 2016. The Government has accepted the recommendations of the RBI to issue Two thousand rupee notes and new notes of Five hundred rupees will also be placed in circulation.” One more reason for demonetization is to minimize Fiscal Deficit. It has subsidiary benefits as it will take out the counterfeit notes from circulation and the

unaccounted money, if does not come out, will be of no use. It will stop Hawala trade too. Some of the facts and figures to describe the existing parallel economy can be viewed and analysed as follows: First of all, if you look at our currency system, India is a cash-based society. 70% of values of transactions are in cash and even our gross domestic product (GDP), 45% of our GDP comes from informal sector. Informal sector accounts for 80% of our population.

4. IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON INDIAN ECONOMY

The demonetization is very important to everyone. Everyone got affected by this he/she might be a business man, salaried, housewife, students, working professionals, politicians etc.

5. POSITIVE IMPACTS

- For quite some time at least, people who are involved in counterfeit currency and terrorism will not be able to continue it further. The smuggling of arms and dealing with the terrorist will not sustain further as all the money will be on record now.
- It will drastically affect the corrupt practices. People who are holding black money in cash will not be able to exchange much as they would be in a fear of getting penalized by authorities.
- It will certainly flush out a good chunk of black money hoarded in currency notes of such denominations (Rs.500 and Rs.1000).
- Decline in inflationary pressure as demand along with household inflation expectations are likely to go down. This would make RBI more comfortable on managing inflation in future increasing the possibility of rate cuts.
- Government revenue will boost up as more earnings will be declared
- Collection of higher taxes will help in nation building like development of roads, infrastructure, transportation and many others.
- People who have opened Jan Dhan accounts under the Prime Minister Jan Dhan Yojna, can now deposit their cash under this scheme and this money can be used for implementation of national developmental projects which will demand more labor and other skilled manpower which will give rise to employment opportunities.
- Cash in system will boost educational loans and business loans thus bringing more opportunities.
- Substantial increase in the demand of digital transactions, E-Wallets, usage of plastic money, online transactions using E-banking etc.

6. NEGATIVE IMPACTS :

- Commodity and general cash market transactions felt an immediate impact. There is a disruption in current liquidity situation, as households are likely to get affected by the note exchange and currency withdrawals terms laid by the government.
- Economy has already borne short-term costs such as the time people wasted in long ques, liquidity crisis in the informal economy, the worker layoffs and many tragic deaths.
- Certain sections of the society namely agriculture sector, small traders, households, daily wage earners etc faced short-term disruptions due to absence of liquid cash.

- GDP formation will be affected with the reduction in consumption demand and negative impact on disposable income.
- Land parcels are usually paid in cash. With restrictions on cash transactions, land prices would fall. As smaller/unorganized players get affected, demand for real estate may decline.
- There would be negative impact on NBFC"s that make disbursements in cash and do most of their collections in cash. These include gold financing companies, micro finance institutions etc.
- There will be added replacement costs of currency. Increased cost of operating ATM"s need to be refilled more often and also it will be a huge burden on banks. Moreover disruption of old currency units and printing of new currency will involve costs, which has to be borne by government and if costs are higher than the benefits then there is no use of demonetization.
- Demonetization itself will not fight black income. The most important policy should be tax administration where the tax authorities can monitor expenditure and matching it with income of the respective individuals.
- Professor Arun Kumar, Jawaharlal Nehru University, is of the view that demonetization is no silver bullet against fake currency. Fresh printing and import of counterfeit currency will not stop with demonetization.
- Though Digitization may be a positive effect of demonetization, India to become cash less economy will take time. Bloomberg data shows the share of cash in the volume of consumer transactions is 98% and much of the cash transactions are in rural India. PwC Report showed that India's unbanked population still stood at 233 million, suggesting that much remains to be done before people can be on boarded on to the digital bandwagon.

Indirect Effect of the Demonetization:

1. Assets in the form of Cash or Gold and Silver seized during demonetization period i.e. November and December through raids.
2. Action on "Benami Property" under the "Benami Transactions (Prohibition) Amendment Act, 2016" is expected to take place which will be the toughest attack on black money and corruption in India.
3. Rising Digital payments are due to demonetization. During the period of November and December 2016, people faced cash-crunch and they found the digital payment problem solving.
4. After 08th November 16, the RBI, Income Tax department and other Central Government departments have announced different rules and restrictions on cash transaction. This has positively affected the mindset of people in India against accumulation of Black money through corruption and other unfair means. This can be termed as "Psychological effect of demonetization on Black Money".

5. **IMPACT OF DEMONITISATION ON DIFFERENT SECTORS::**
 Demonetization created effect on different sectors in different manners resulting into boom for some sectors like E-Wallet businesses and somewhere resulting into temporary slowdown like micro businesses like vegetable vendors or some small

seasonal businesses, where most of the transactions are on cash basis. Some of the sectors having major effect of demonitisation are covered for the study

Domestic/Household Sector: The logic behind this demonetization is to curb the use of these high value notes in the black money market. Now almost everyone has Rs1000/500 notes so now it would become difficult for the common people to do their business/ household works easily.

Reduce Government Liability It will reduce the risk and cost of cash handling as soft money is safer than hard money. It will also reduce government liability. Since every note is a liability for the government, the old currency will become worthless for those people, who choose not to disclose their income. Thus, this will extinguish government's liability to that extent.

Health care sector:

The impact on the health care sector was huge with most of the hospitals refused to accept the old currency. The issue was faced by the Union Minister Mr. Sidharamaiah in Bengaluru when the hospital administration refused to accept the old currency to retrieve his brother's dead body. The common man faced severe issues transacting in the hospitals with old currencies and several cases of death have been registered for not attending the patients due to demonetization.

Farming and fishing industry Farmers generally deal in cash . The poor people through middlemen are getting their currencies exchanged for Rs.300 or Rs.400. Farmers have difficulty buying seeds and fertilizer and selling crops and perishable products. The demonetisation led to unavailability of cash to pay for food products. The reduction in demand that arose in turn led to a crash in the prices of crops. Farmers were unable to recover even the costs of transportation from their fields to the market from the low prices offered. This forced the farmers across the country to dump their products in desperation. Some farmers resorted to burying unsold vegetables. Agricultural products such as vegetables, food grains, sugarcane, milk and eggs were dumped on roads. The fishing industry which depends on cash sales of freshly caught fish was close to collapse.

Impact on Common man: The demonetization has a positive impact on the common people that now they the use of digital currencies got increased. So the people no need to carry physical currencies to any places which also reduced the crime rate. The price of some of the important commodities got decreased.

E-Business

E-commerce companies saw up to a 30% decline in cash on delivery (COD) orders. Several e-commerce companies hailed the demonetization decision as an impetus to an increase in digital payments. They believe that it would lead to a decline in COD returns which is expected to cut down their costs. The demand for point of sales (POS) or card swipe machines has increased. The goods and services tax (GST), whose objective is to replace all taxes levied by the federal government and the states with one central tax.

Jewelry and Real Estate Business The liquidity squeeze caused by demonetisation will be negative across sectors with high level of cash transactions. Real estate, jewellery, retailing, restaurants, logistics, consumer durables and luxury brands, cement and some segments in retail/SME lending space will be facing short term instability. Those companies with high level of debt will face more pressure and can face loan defaults.

E-wallet firms could gain good business

A digital wallet is an electronic device which allows an individual to make electronic commerce transactions like payment of bills or online bookings etc. An individual's bank

account can also be linked to the digital wallet. The examples of wallet in India are- Paytm, PayU India, MobiKwik, and Free charge and so on. Such E-wallets are expected to be the biggest beneficiaries of the decision of demonetization taken by central government.

Impact on IT Industry

This step can bring grey market commodities / illegal money lending / money laundering etc., under control which is otherwise unmanageable. The IT industries prefer purchase and sales through banking system only. It won't curb grey channel market but will surely have an adverse effect on the products which are promoted by grey channel. This move will help brands to grow and helps in curbing the fake, grey market, and Chinese import cash sales. New-age payments like PayTM, Instamojo Payment Gateway, PayUMoney and Mobikwik, online banking and e-commerce platforms will see an increased demand in the near future as people will show willingness to move away from cash. This particularly will benefit IT startups and Fintech domains that work on online payments that enable technology processes for such companies. This also could create key requirements for technology processes for tracing financial information, eKYC form Income Tax departments. Government initiatives such as Aadhar, Jandhan will nudge a lot of Fintech companies to enable financial institutions and banks to adopt these facilities.

On the other hand sales at all major electronic and computer hardware retailers have hit rock bottom. Unable to compete with the massive discounts and low taxation offered by online giants, like Flipkart, Snapdeal and Amazon, computer retailers are forced to decrease their margins and offer freebies to walk-in customers. Currently, retailers profit from a 3%-5% margin on laptops, desktop computers and accessories. The adoption of cashless transactions through debit cards or credit cards eats into this margin as the retailer has to pay 1.8%-2% bank commission on each transaction. This has already resulted in significant slowdown of demand across PC, tablet PC and Mobile devices.

6. Conclusion:

The action of the Indian government to eradicate the four social problems- black money, corruption, counterfeiting and terrorist funding was a very bold move but it definitely affected the many parts of the economy. Due to demonetization, the first thing that happened in India was it curbed the purchasing power of most of the people. So this in turn decreased the overall trade in the country. It can be said that demonetization will create cash crunch and liquidity crisis causing inconvenience to the general public in short-term, but it will prove to be beneficial to the economy in long run on aspects like government revenue, increase in deposits, low interest rates on loans, and decline in inflationary pressure etc. Government can now easily track unreported income resulting in reducing of corrupt practices and money laundering. But it is also to be noted that the ultimate objective of demonetization to flush out black money from the economy may not be achieved, until the actual people behind black money are targeted. Moreover, people have invested their black money in assets like real estate and gold; therefore it becomes difficult on government's part to track black money. The success of demonetization depends upon the formalization by the government which will hopefully change the mindset of people to refrain from illegal activities and black money. Demonetization technically is a liquidity shock; a sudden stop in terms of currency availability. The intensity of demonetization effects clearly depends upon the duration of the liquidity shocks.

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Paper 12

DIGITALIZATION IN EDUCATION - A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN GOVERNMENT SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS IN MANGALURU CITY.

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Abstract :

Information technology has reformed each sector it has grasped and it is currently in the promising phases of altering academia. In the coming decades if information technology has its approach, education will be far changed, more immersive and hopefully more constructive to the people than it is today. Digitization in education industry has totally changed the learning and also the teaching process to a very great extent. Technology has made imparting education stress-free for both students and educators. The true revolution in education can only be achieved via digitization of education so that students can learn at their own speed both within and outside the classroom. Their learning upgrades while they carry on to advantage from fostering, mentorship and direction of their teachers. Various teachers are ready to accept the wave of digitization but more effort still need to be exercised when it comes to teacher training. Most educators are at the stage of figuring out how to use technology meaningfully for teaching. And these teachers are right to be concerned, since depending on how it is used, technology can either help or hinder the education process. So, this paper highlights the gap between the usage of digital technologies in teaching between the private school teachers and government school teachers and to know their perception regarding digitalization.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Teachers, Students, digital techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, so many of our old assumptions and ideas have turned around. It is clearly a different place in which the kids are growing up. More than 75% of the Indian population has a cell phone. A new online world has emerged and has become the focus of many of today's kid's attention. In such environment, that change would finally come to our young people's education as well, and it has.

Today's students do not have short attention spans or the inability to concentrate that they are often accused of having, many of the same students who do not concentrate in schools will sit focused on movies or video games. More and more young people are now deeply technology enhanced, connected to their peers and the world in ways no generation has ever been before.

Streams of information come at the 24*7. More and more of what they want and need is available in their pocket on demand.

All teachers today know that digital technology is becoming an important part of student's education. But just how to use it in schools is not yet completely clear, and most educators are at the stage of figuring out how to use technology meaningfully for teaching. And these teachers are right to be concerned, since depending on how it is use, technology can either help or hinder the educations process. So this paper highlights the gap between the usage of digital technologies in teaching between the private school teachers and government school teachers and to know their perception regarding digitalization.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To know the perception of teachers towards digitalisation in education.
- To know the adoptability of teachers towards digital education.
- To compare the perception and adoptability.

3. METHODOLOGY

For data collection, structured questions were framed and 16 questionnaires were filled through Google forms and 34 questionnaires were filled through personal interview method. The sample size was 50. The samples were the primary government school and private school teachers working in Mangaluru city. Quota sampling method is used to collect the primary data. Based on the requirements of the study data are also collected from various secondary sources such as internet, PDF files etc.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The survey results are organized as follows. In the first section, the demographic profile of the respondents is presented. Where this section has been classified into categories and 25 respondents each from government schools and private schools is taken into consideration.

PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS: The selected 50 respondents include the primary government school and private school teachers working in Mangaluru city. A profile of respondents based on gender, age, sector, educational qualification and work experience are presented below.

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of sample

Gender	Government respondents	Percentage	Private respondents	Percentage
Male	-	-	-	-
Female	25	100	25	100
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary data

Table 2: Age wise distribution of the sample

Age	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
18-30years	-	-	5	20
31-40years	4	16	10	40
41-50years	6	24	5	20
51 and above	15	60	5	20
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

Table 3: Educational Qualification wise distribution of sample

Education qualification	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
PUC	3	12	-	-
Graduate	5	20	09	36
Post Graduate	5	20	12	48
D.Ed	12	48	04	16
TOTAL	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

Table 4: Teaching experience of respondents

Experience	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Less than 5 years	1	4	07	28
5 – 15 years	1	4	08	32
15 – 25 years	13	52	06	24
25 & above	10	40	04	16
TOTAL	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

Above tables reveals the demographic profile of the respondents. On the basis of demographic profile following analysis and interpretations are made.

Table no 5: Response towards usage of modern methods in teaching

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	14	56	23	92
No	11	44	02	08
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals the usage of modern methods in teaching. In the government school's majority 56% of them make use of modern techniques and only 44% of the respondents do not use modern techniques while teaching. In the private school's majority 92% of the teachers are inclined towards the modern teaching methods and only 08% of the respondent's do not use modern techniques. As compared to the government school's usage level is higher in the private schools.

Testing of hypothesis I

Response of government school and private school teachers towards usage of digital technology

Table 5. 11

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	14	23	37
No	11	2	13
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

H0: No difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology

H1: There is difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology

Chi square test:

Row total for the row of that cell X Column total for the Column of that cell

$$\text{Expected frequency of any cell} = \frac{\text{Row total} \times \text{Column total}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

Table 5.12 Expected frequencies or Expected values

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	18.5	18.5	37
No	6.5	6.5	13
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

Table 5.13: Calculation of Chi square

Observed frequency	Expected frequency	(O-E) ² /E
14	18.5	1.095
11	6.5	3.115
23	18.5	1.095
02	6.5	3.115
		8.42

Primary Data

$$X^2 = \sum [(O-E)^2/E] = 8.42$$

$$V = (r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(2-1) = 1$$

For V = 1: Table value of Chi square at 5% level of significance = 3.841

Since the calculated value of Chi square is more than the Table value of Chi square, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. **We therefore conclude that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology.**

Table no 5.21: Response towards techniques of modern teaching

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Smart class	3	20	18	50
PPT	2	13.33	11	30.5
WhatsApp learning	-	-	-	-
Others	10	66.67	7	19.5
Total	15	100	36	100

*Multiple responses

Primary Data

The above table reveals the response towards modern techniques. In government schools 66.67% respondents make use of tabs, mobile phones, laptops while teaching and the least preferred method is ppt that is 13.33%. In private school's majority 50% of the teachers make use of smart classes as compared to the other techniques.

Table no 5.22: Response towards span of usage

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Less than 1 year	5	35.71	4	17.39
2-4 years	8	57.14	9	39.13
4-6 years	1	7.14	5	21.74
6 years and above	-	-	5	21.74
Total	14	100	23	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals the span of using digital technology. In the government schools Majority 57.14% of the teachers use the digital teaching methods for more than 2 years and less than 4 years. Similarly, in private school's also majority 39.13% of the respondents use the digital technology for more than 2 years. When compared to government schools, private schools have an experience of using digital methods for a longer period.

Table no 5.23: Response towards impact of digitalization on workload

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	2	14.29	11	47.83
No	12	85.71	12	52.17
Total	14	100	23	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in the government school's majority 85.71% of the respondents feel that there is no impact on their work due to digitalization and for the remaining 14.29% it has impacted their work. Similarly, in the private schools Majority 52.17% of the respondents have no impact on their work due to implementation of digital education.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	6	42.86	16	69.57
No	8	57.14	7	30.43
Total	14	100	23	100

Table no 5.24: Response towards compulsion in using digitalization

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in 57.14% of the government schools it is not mandatory to use digital techniques whereas 69.57% of the private schools make digitalization mandatory. This shows that private schools give more importance to e-learning.

Table no 5.31: Response towards reasons for not adopting digitalization

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Lack of knowledge	4	21.05	-	-
Lack of infrastructure	4	21.05	-	-
Lack of time	-	-	1	33.33
Not mandatory	11	57.9	2	66.67
Total	19	100	3	100

***Multiple responses**

Primary Data

The above table reveals that, in government school's majority 57.9% of the teachers do not use digitalization as it is not mandatory and 21.05% of the respondents do not make use of digitalization due to lack of knowledge and infrastructure respectively. Similarly, out of 3 private school responses majority 66.67% of them have restricted to traditional methods of teaching and 33.33% of the respondent do not make use of digitalization due to lack of time.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	2	8	22	88
No	23	92	3	12
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 6: Response towards training to teachers in using digital techniques

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in government school's majority 92% of teachers have not got any training to use the digital techniques and in contrast majority 88% of the private school teachers have got the training for using digital techniques. As in government school's no much importance is given for the training of the teachers because there is no compulsion in using digital techniques.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	11	44	25	100
No	14	56	-	-
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 7: Responses towards computer education as a part of curriculum

Primary Data

The above table reveals that 56% of government schools respondents do not have computer classes and only 44% of the respondent's schools provide computer education. where as 100% of private school's respondents have computer classes as a part of curriculum. As basic computer knowledge is necessary for today's competitive world and all private schools knowing its importance have implemented it their curriculum as compared to government schools.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	22	88	24	96
No	3	12	1	4
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 8: Responses towards updating parents on student's status

Primary Data

The above table reveals the Response towards updating parents on student's status. In government school's majority 88% of the teachers update on student's status and only 12% of them do not update on student's status. In private schools' majority 96% of the teachers update parents on student's status whereas only 4% teachers do not update on student's status.

Table no 8.1: Response towards the techniques of updating the parents on student's status

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
WhatsApp Group	1	4.17	3	8.34
Personal contact	22	91.67	12	33.33
SMS	-	-	11	30.55
Customised App	-	-	4	11.11
Others	1	4.16	6	16.67
Total	24	100	36	100

***Multiple responses**

Primary Data

The above table reveals that in government school's majority 91.67% of the respondents update the parents through personal contact and only 4.16 % of the teachers update the parents through writing a dairy. In private school's majority 33.33% of the respondents update the parents through personal contact and only 8.34% of the respondents update the parents through WhatsApp group.

In both the school's parents are updated mostly through the personal contact but when compared, digital techniques are used more in private schools as to government schools for updating the parents.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	18	72	21	84
No	1	4	-	-
Neutral	6	24	4	16
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 9: Response towards digitalization results in better learning

Primary Data

The above table reveals, majority 72% of the government school respondents feels that digitalisation will result in better learning. Similarly, majority 84% of the private school respondents have a similar view as that of the government teachers.

Table no 9.1: reasons towards digitalization leading to better learning

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Easy learning	15	60	8	25.81
Time saving	-	-	4	12.90
Interesting	10	40	19	61.29
Total	25	100	31	100

***Multiple responses**

Primary Data

The above table reveals, majority 60% of the government respondents feel that digitalization leads to easy learning and remaining 40% feel that it is an interesting way of learning. Whereas, Majority 61.29% of the respondents of private schools have perceived that it is an interesting mode of learning and only 12.90% of them feel that it saves their time.

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	21	84	25	100
No	4	16	-	-
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 10: Response towards necessity of digitalization in today's competitive world

Primary Data

The above table reveals that majority 84% of the government respondents perceive that digitalization is necessary in today's competitive world. Similarly, cent percent of the private respondents have a similar opinion.

Hypothesis testing -2

Response of government school and private school teachers towards the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.

Table 10.1

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	21	25	46
No	4	-	4
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

H0: No difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.

H1: There is difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.

Chi square test:

Row total for the row of that cell X Column total for the Column of that cell

$$\text{Expected frequency of any cell} = \frac{\text{-----}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

Table 10.2 Expected frequencies or Expected values

Perception	Govt teachers	Private teachers	Total
Yes	23	23	46
No	2	2	4
Total	25	25	50

Primary Data

Table 10.3: Calculation of Chi square

Observed frequency	Expected frequency	(O-E) ² /E
21	23	0.174
4	2	2
25	23	0.174
0	2	2
		4.348

Primary Data

$$X^2 = \sum[(O-E)^2/E] = 4.348$$

$$V = (r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(2-1) = 1$$

For V = 1: Table value of Chi square at 5% level of significance = 3.841

Since the calculated value of Chi square is more than the Table value of Chi square, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. **We therefore conclude that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.**

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Yes	15	60	14	56
No	6	24	10	40
Neutral	4	16	1	4
Total	25	100	25	100

Table no 11: Response towards popularity of schools based on usage digital methods

Primary Data

The above table reveals, majority 60% of the government school teachers have an opinion that schools using digital classes are popular than the once not using it and majority 56% of the private school respondents have a similar opinion. This shows that the government school teachers have a strong opinion on the above statement when compared to that of private teachers.

Table no 12: Response towards the statement "Technology never replace great teachers but technology in the hands of the great teachers is transformational."

Particulars	Govt respondents	Percentage	Pvt respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	12	48	8	32
Agree	12	48	16	64
Neutral	1	4	-	-
Disagree	-	-	1	4
Strongly disagree	-	-	-	-
Total	25	100	25	100

Primary Data

The above table reveals that majority of 48% of government school teachers strongly agree and agree the above statement respectively. Where as the majority 64% of the private teachers agree with the above statement.

5. FINDINGS

- In the government school's majority (56%) of them use the modern techniques in teaching and in the private school's majority (92%) of the teachers are inclined towards the modern teaching methods. The hypothesis testing concluded that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers in using digital technology.
- In government school's out of the respondents who do not use digitalisation majority (57.9%) do not use as it is not mandatory. Similarly, out of the 3 private school responses majority (66.67%) of them have restricted to traditional methods of teaching.
- In the government school's majority (91.67%) of the teachers are not trained in using digital techniques and in contrast majority (88%) of the private school teachers are trained for using the same.
- In government school's majority (91.67%) of the respondents update the parents through personal contact. In private school's majority (33.33%) of the respondents

update the parents through personal contact and only (8.34%) of the respondents update the parents through WhatsApp group. Digital methods are you used in a higher rate in private schools as compared to that of government schools on updating the parents on the student's status.

- Majority 72% of the government school respondents feels that digitalisation will result in better learning. Similarly, majority 84% of the private school respondents have a similar view as that of the government teachers.
- Majority (84%) of the government respondents perceive that digitalization is necessary in today's competitive world. Similarly, cent percent of the private respondents have a similar opinion. The hypothesis testing concluded that there is significance difference between the government and private school teachers about the perception that digitalisation is necessary in today's competitive world.
- Majority 60% of the government school teachers have an opinion that schools using digital classes are popular than the once not using it and majority 56% of the private school respondents have a similar opinion
- Majority (48%) of government school teachers strongly agree and agree the statement "Technology never replace great teachers but technology in the hands of the great teachers is transformational." respectively. Whereas the majority (64%) of the private teachers agree with the above statement

6. SUGGESTIONS

- Lack of infrastructure in the government schools is discouraging the parents to admits their children to the government schools. So, the government should provide proper infrastructure facilities in order to attract the parents to admit their children.
- Digital education must be made mandatory in all the schools from the primary level because it is necessary for fostering the student's life and make them ready to face the competitive world.
- Along with making digital education compulsory all the facilities required to implement the digitalization should be given.
- In government schools there should one teacher for every class so that teachers can properly concentrate on each student and this will ease them in implementing digital techniques.
- Training must be provided on a continuous basis as the technology gets outdated rapidly. So, the teachers must have the knowledge of all recent digital technologies.

7. CONCLUSION

"The only constant thing is change so you have to learn to embrace it". Digital age is the truth of today lives which is unavoidable to live, learn and move ahead in today's world. Digitalization in education is a potentially liberating process helping the teachers and students in acquisition of information and enabling them to focus more on the creative processes of making connections and creating new paths. It offers great opportunities in education sector, especially to our schools as it provides information and learning. Existing traditional practices necessarily be changed by the use of technology in the future. Teachers must direct the students towards the right direction whereas students should be provided with the freedom to explore, discover and inquire. teachers must be provided with adequate training

and should be educated digitally. But all this will require support from our education system as well as the readiness to change and learn from everyone including the students.

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Paper 13

HOW TO MEASURE THE PERFORMANCE LEVEL IN COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM – SOME SUGGESTIONS

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Abstract

Competence means ability or capability and performance is the proof of competence. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. As opposed to this, is the credit based system where the grades directly speak what a student has earned through education ?. But the question is how to measure competency among the graduates who pass out. Various indicators are available in Competency Based Education System (CBES). One is employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job with little of support. However, this is something that is decided by the employer and difficult to set a benchmark. Our competency measurement model suggests that apart from knowledge, specific skills, and experience on a job, other supporting skills like Communication, proficiency in writing, generation of new ideas, preserving a vision in life, desire for learning, and improvement in life, attitude towards life, respect for fellow-beings, and such other qualities could be hugely a measure of competency acquired from education. It may be difficult to quantify, yet it is essential to be considered through a properly developed measuring scale to be given as competency level. In this discussion, an attempt has been made to identify such factors which contributes to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome using a newly suggested model based on different ranking scales.

Keywords : CBES, Competency based education, Outcome based education, Performance level, Competency Measurement model, Competency Measurement Scales.

1. INTRODUCTION :

The objective of higher education is to develop systematic thinking ability of the students by means of enhancing knowledge, skills, and experience which in turn expected to increase the confidence of the solving problems of self and society [1]. In the process of imparting higher education, two models are considered to be relevant in the current century which are (1) Conventional classroom based education model [2-4] and (2) Technology supported online ubiquitous education model [5, 6, 7]. The two higher education systems which are expected to be attractive to the learners are Choice Based Credit system (CBCS) and Competency based Education system (CBES) [8].

Presently Indian higher education system follows choice based credit system of assessment and evaluation. A credit system is a systematic way of describing an educational programme by attaching credits to its components. The credits in higher education systems may be based on different parameters, such as student workload, learning outcomes and contact hours. University Grants Commission has come up with the Choice Based Credit System (CBCS), a programme in which the students while choosing the prescribed course, which is the core, can opt for any elective or minor or soft skill courses and the entire assessment is graded, based on a credit system. The CBCS provides choice for students to select the elective components in any other institution as well.

Competency-Based Credit System (CBES) is a significant improvement in CBCS model. It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment. Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution. A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content [6, 8]. This model allows students to work and learn anywhere and as per the curriculum of the University/Higher education institution where they enrolled for their courses have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is most challenging and there is no hard and fast method as well as the rating scale accepted by universally exists today. Competency based education system is not a new concept and is under discussion since 1970 [10-17]. Due to the limitations involved in the evaluation and distribution of scores/ rating of outcomes, CBES model in higher education could not become popular and not adopted in most of the universities.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER :

This conceptual paper based on explorative research has the following objectives :

- (1) To analyse the objectives of competency based education system (CBES).
- (2) To analyse the distinctive features of CBES.
- (3) To study the factors which contribute to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome.
- (4) Suggestions to effective implementation of CBES based on critical analysis.

3. COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM –OBJECTIVES :

Competence means ability or capability and performance is the proof of competence. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. As opposed to this, is the credit based system where the grades directly speak what a student has earned through education?. But the question is how to measure competency among the graduates who want to pass out. However, this is something that is decided by the employer and difficult to set a

benchmark at university level during evaluation for offering graduation certificate. In this paper, we have proposed two grading methods based on a modified 1-10 rating scale and the other is a modified Likert scale model to measure and express competency of a graduate in a given subject/area. In its final form, the Likert Scale is a five or seven-point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on the Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged.

4. FEATURES OF CBES :

CBES involves educating a student in order to improve the competency of performance in one or more fields of specializations. This includes enhancing his knowledge, skills, and experience along with ethical aspects of doing things systematically to the expectations of the industry. The evaluation of competency should focus on developing the progress report of the candidate periodically to report the speed of learning and achieving the different levels of competency. Such an evaluation process and outcome is called competency rating and reporting. The distinctive features of CBES are :

- (1) Competency based education system focus on building and measuring some pre-defined competency in performing a specified task efficiently and effectively.
- (2) It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment.
- (3) Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit.
- (4) It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills, and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution.
- (5) A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content.
- (6) The system allows a student to choose any number of areas where he/she is interested to enhance the skills required to do a particular job with learned required competency.

5. PERFORMANCE LEVEL MEASUREMENT IN CBES :

Competency based education system focus on developing working skills on a particular set of jobs during a time frame. These working skills called competency comprises of working knowledge, expertise, and smartness to complete the job/jobs. Various teaching-learning methods including classroom teaching, laboratory based learning, experiential learning, experimental learning, online learning, internship based projects, fieldwork practicum etc. are considered as effective methods to be adopted in competency based education system. There are various factors contributes to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome. Our competency measurement model suggests that apart from knowledge, specific skills, and experience on a job, other supporting skills like Communication, proficiency in writing, generation of new ideas, preserving a vision in life,

desire for learning and improvement in life, attitude towards life, respect for fellow-beings, self-control and such other qualities could be hugely a measure of competency acquired from education. Table 1 lists such factors which contribute to the competency and their expected performance outcome.

Table 1 : Factors which contributes to competency and their expected performance outcome.

S. No.	Factors contributing to the Competency in CBES	Expected Performance Outcome
1	Communication	Rapid Action
2	Proficiency in writing	Quick response with accuracy
3	Generation of new ideas	Innovation & Efficiency
4	Preserving a vision in life,	Adaptability & Value addition
5	Desire for learning and improvement in life	Pro-activeness
6	Attitude towards life	Positive view
7	Respect for fellow-beings	Increased co-operation
8	Self-control	Courage in action

Various rating scales have been used in the past to measure intangible quantities like attitude, feelings, qualities, perception, love, affection, happiness, pain, satisfaction, status, talent, knowledge, etc. Two popular rating scales used to give an opinion about a product, service, taste, and even competency of a person to do a given task are Likert scale and 1-10 rating scales (sometimes 0-10 scale). The Choice Based Credit System has modified 1-10 rating scale for allotting grade points with grade levels between Outstanding to Fail as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Allotment grades in modified 1-10 rating scale in Choice Based Credit system

S. No.	Letter Grade	Grade Level	Grade Point
1	O	Outstanding	10
2	A+	Excellent	9
3	A	Very good	8
4	B+	Good	7
5	B	Above Average	6
6	C	Average	5
7	P	Pass	4
8	F	Fail	0
9	Ab	Absent	0

The proposed Competency Based Grading system is a Measurement system to grade the level of competency and its equivalent points instead of offering credits. The evaluation system and grading pattern may contain any model of allocating grading levels and grade points based on student competency shown at the time of evaluation. Here, we propose two models of competency grading.

5.1 Models for Competency Grading System :

Model 1 for Competency Reporting:

This model is based in 1-10 rating scale. This is an extension of choice based credit system grading. Here, the competency level of a student under evaluation is graded using grade points anywhere between one to ten. Absent to evaluation process by the respective student is graded as zero. Depending on evaluator's assessment on a candidate, grading level and corresponding grading point should be determined. Table 3 lists various competency levels and the corresponding grade points.

Table 3 : Competency rating model in a given skill based on 1-10 rating scale

S. No.	Competency Grading Level	Grade Point
1	Outstanding	10
2	Excellent	9
3	Very good	8
4	Good	7
5	Above Average	6
6	Average	5
7	Below Average	4
8	Weak	3
9	Very Weak	2
10	Extremely Weak	1
11	Absent	0

Model 2 for Competency Reporting:

Even if competency is an intangible property, it can be measurable to some extent through various traits. To measure the competency of a graduate in any area/field, we propose another model which is a modified Likert scale model [18]. This scale or metric supports to measure and express the competency of a graduate in a given subject/area to a greater extent in a systematic way. In its final form, this scale is a seven point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on this modified Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged. This model is based on 7 point Likert Scale. Here, seven grades are allotted based on a student's competency on a given skill or subject. The evaluator, through demonstration, shall decide the competency level and fix it to any deserved level and the grade points should be allotted accordingly. In this model, the competency reporting system may follow either optimistic assessment by using positive scale, a most likely assessment scale called neutral scale, or a pessimistic assessment model by using negative scale.

(1) Positive Scale :

This is an optimistic /positive assessment scale used to measure and report the strength of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(2) Neutral Scale :

This is a neutral most-likely assessment scale used to measure and report the abilities of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(3) Negative Scale :

This is a negative assessment scale used to measure and report the weakness of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

Table 4 : Competency rating model based on positive modified Likert Scale rating for a given skill

S. No.	Competency Level	Grading	Grade Point
1	Outstanding		7
2	Excellent		6
3	Very good		5
4	Good		4
5	Above Average		3
6	Average		2
7	Below Average		1

Table 5 : Competency rating model based on neutral modified Likert Scale rating for a given skill

S. No.	Competency Level	Grading	Grade Point
1	Very good		3
2	Good		2
3	Above Average		1
4	Average		0
5	Below Average		-1
6	Weak		-2
7	Very Weak		-3
8	Absent		-

Table 6 : Competency rating model based on negative modified Likert Scale rating

S. No.	Competency Level	Grading	Grade Point
1	Average		-1
2	Below Average		-2
3	Low		-3
4	Weak		-4
5	Very Weak		-5
6	Extremely Weak		-6
7	Not qualified		-7
8	Qualified		0

5.2 Complete Performance Measurement Model based on above Scales :

The competency based performance measurement format consists of listing of various skills required to perform a job satisfactorily and the competency grading level of a candidate along with corresponding grade point. This also includes the time taken by the candidate to reach the required competent level as shown in Competency Report format given in table 7.

Table 7 : Competency Report format for a Job _____

S.No.	Skills Required for the Job	Competency Grading level	Grade Point	Time taken to reach the level
1	Knowledge			
2	Working skills			
3	Expertise level			
4	Communication			
5	Proficiency in writing			
6	Generation of new ideas			
7	Preserving a vision in life			
8	Desire for learning and improvement in life			
9	Attitude towards life			
10	Respect for fellow-beings			
11	Self-control			

Table 8 : Example of competency report based on positive scale for Accounting job

Name : Ashok B.		Roll No. : 2019K29		DOB:04/04'1999
S.No.	Skills Required for the Job	Competency Grading level	Grade Point	Time taken to reach the level
1	Knowledge	Very good	5	12 months
2	Working skills	Good	4	18 months
3	Expertise level	Excellent	6	12 months
4	Communication	Average	2	08 months
5	Proficiency in writing	Very good	5	18 months
6	Generation of new ideas	Excellent	6	18 months
7	Preserving a vision in life	Average	2	24 months
8	Desire for learning and improvement in life	Excellent	6	12 months
9	Attitude towards life	Average	2	18 months
10	Respect for fellow-beings	Below Average	1	18 months
11	Self-control	Good	4	12 months

6. CONCLUSION :

CBES involves developing various employability skills of a student in order to improve the competency of performance in one or more fields of specializations. In this system, apart from enhancing the knowledge, skills, and experience along with ethical aspects, of doing things systematically to the expectations of the industry. CBES in higher education provides a

proper direction of required skills to be developed by a student while choosing the subjects, and the assessment. Competency-based education programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. In this system, students have to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience. CBES is a continuous improvement program for individuals and as per the demands of the industry. Since a student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses, but to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content. Hence the model allows students to work and learn anywhere and have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is discussed in this paper and an appropriate solution of grading model based on developed competency is proposed.

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Paper 14**EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM INITIATES
TO MANAGE THE PERFORMANCE OF THE
ORGANIZATION****Ravisha B*, Chethan**, Divya****

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Abstract:

In the recent days because of globalization there is a rapid change in the developmental concepts of the industry. Industries want to establish new sophisticated Employee development technologies to improve the quality and to produce the standards products in the market. Improving and giving modernized Employee development touch to the machines are not only important concept in the corporate world. But more than that majority of the companies want to develop their employees to achieve the desired Employee development result. Employees are the real asset for the company; it is the duty of the every HR department has to make a good plan for employee development. HR department has to execute many employee development projects based Employee development on the employee developments of the employees in the organization. Proper research oriented Employee development activities will help the companies to find out the areas where employees are require Employee development to develop their skill. Development of employees is ongoing process in the every company by looking at the future prospective. Development will increase the ability, skill and competitive positions of the employees. This will lead to increase the productivity of the employees and increase the production ability of the company. Employee development projects are the investment on employees for the future to get good returns from them. Developing a good work team will always turns as a real asset for the company. This paper designed Employee development with a purpose that to identify the areas where employees are want to be develop themselves and take necessary step to meet the requirements of the employees. Research tools are developed Employee development to analyze the data collected Employee development to interpret the result in the meaningful way. Theoretical part is developed on the basis of statistical analysis to know the importance of the employee development.

Key words: corporate, projects, skill and ability.

1. Introduction

Employee is a key element of the organization. The success or failure of the organization depends on employee performance. Therefore, organizations are investing huge amount of money on employee development programmes. Implementation of employee development programme and managing employee performance every day is the key to an effective

performance management system. Setting goals, making sure your expectations are clear, and providing frequent Employee development feedback help people perform most effectively. Managing the performance of the employee with the help of employee development programmes plays a very vital role in each and every organisation. The objectives of the organisations will be more effective when employees actively participate in employee developmental programmes and gives good performance to achieve organisational objectives. For this both employee and employer plays important role. There is direct relationship between employee performance and organizational effectiveness. Managing performance of employee with Employee development programmes is not just the responsibility of the employee. In today's diverse workforce, business practices have evolved Employee development to reflect economic competitiveness in developing and retaining talented Employee development employees. Organizations are continually seeking new solutions to assess, understand, and strategize employee development. One of the greatest challenges faced Employee development by managers is the strategic personal development of their employees in order to ensure effective use of their talent. To properly manage this vital resource, they must identify their challenges and then implement employee development and training for improvement.

2. Objectives of the study

1. To know the importance of employee development programmes in an organisation.
2. To establish relationship between performance of the organisation with employee development programme.
3. To find the role of employee and employer or manager on managing performance of the organization.
4. To identify is there any affect of employee development to employee performance.
5. To know the importance of employee development programme to achieve organisational objectives.

3. Employee development for the present study

1. To suggest organizations that overall goals of the organisations can be achieved Employee development when there is active participation by employee and employer.
2. To remove the perception as employee development as a cost in financial terms rather than an investment in the assets of organisation.
3. Recommending that performance of employee can be increased Employee development by providing effective employee development programme.
4. To ensure that employee development is essential to the employees within the organisation.
5. To ensure that environmental changes will require employee development programmes.

4. Methodology applied

The research is developed through primary and secondary source of data. Primary data obtained through issue of questionnaires. The sample size taken for this research is 50 respondents randomly selected from Mangalore and Puttur taluk of Dakshina Kannada district. Theoretical information collected through referring secondary source such as books, journals and magazines.

5. Principal goals of performance management through employee development programme.

1. Improve employee performance:

Employers expect good performance by employees to attain a goal of organisation. Most employers adopt performance management processes primarily to help employees perform more effectively in their current positions and to be more successful in accomplishing organizational goals and also provides different training and developmental programmes to achieve organizational goals.

2. Develop people for promotional opportunities:

When the organisation provides good developmental programmes and manage the performance of the organisation properly this will provide more promotional opportunities to the employee. By providing training and developmental programmes to the employees it will help to develop people for the future new assignments. Employee developmental programmes can serve to help develop people for new assignments and promotional opportunities.

3. Meet Employees' employee development for feedback:

Majority of the employees want to know how they are doing on the job. When there is proper management of performance of the employee by providing employee development programmes this will help the employees to know about their performance standard and they would like to get positive feedback from their employer about their accomplishments and suggestions on how they can improve.

4. Ensure that employees are working toward organisational goals;

This is another important principal goal of managing performance through employee development. When the employer provide employee development programme to employees, obviously employer expect some efforts from employee to achieve organisational goals.

6. Role of Employee Development in the present scenario

The development of people is essential. Employee development is not just training. It has a much broader range of components that have a deeper impact on an individual that training alone does because it is not only the individual who is impacted upon but the organisation and the wider environment within which the organisation works.

The term human resources refer to the knowledge, skill, creative abilities, talents, aptitude, values and beliefs of an organisation's workforce. Effective performance of an organisation depends not just on the availability of resources, but its quality and competence as required by the organisation from time to time. The efficiency of production process and various areas of management depend to a greater extent on the level of employee development.

1. Changes in Economic Policies

Almost all the governments across the globe have changed their economic policies from communistic/socialistic pattern to capitalistic pattern. Even the government of India liberalized its economic policies in 1991. Liberalization, privatisation and globalisation posed threat to the weak firms and created opportunities to the large firms. These firms started developing their human resources in order to exploit the opportunities.

2. Changing job requirements

Organisational dynamism brings changes in organisational design and job design. The changes in job design bring changes in job description and job specifications. These changes demand for employee development programmes.

3. Employee development for multi skilled employees

The changing trends in industrialization, structuring jobs and organisations demand the employee to take up multiple activities. The customer centered approach led to flexible organisations and flexible work. All these changes demand the employees with multiple skills. Employee developmental activities provide the opportunity to the employee to acquire and develop multiple skills.

4. Organisational viability and transformation process

Organisational viability is continuously influenced by the environmental threats. If the organisation does not adapt itself to the changing environmental factors, it will lose its market share. If the organisation desires to adopt these changes then it has to develop employees through developmental programme.

5. Technological advances

Organisation in order to survive and develop should adopt the latest technology. Adaptation of the latest technology will not be complete until they developed their employees.

7. Some stages to finding success in employee development

There is no one way to finding success in employee development. The continually changing nature of the business environment means that unique demands are constantly being placed on people because they must acquire new skills and resources in order to cope with those demands. Therefore employee development plays a very important role.

1. Full participation

All employees need to participate fully in the identification of their own developmental employee developments.

2. Individual responsibility

There has been a growth in individual's taking responsibility for planning their own continuous development, that is, work based and longer term career based training and development.

3. Reward system

The recognition and reward system is important when individuals take responsibility for their own continuous development. Monetary or non monetary rewards must be provided to employees those who will actively participate in employee developmental programmes.

4. Flexible workforce

A more flexible workforce comes about with more breadth and depth in individual development.

5. Record Keeping

With the increased use of electronic data system, it is now easier to store records of achievement for all employees. These systems keep track of the skills and knowledge accrued Employee development by employees.

6. Diverse workforce

There has been an increase in opportunity for utilizing flexible temporary labour, for example outsourcing, job sharing, part time working and sub-contracting. Such practices allow organizations to maintain a highly skilled and specialized workforce with the competitive strengths required to meet the employee developments of the stakeholders. A diverse and decentralized workforce is essential.

Performance of the employees will depends upon the employee development program of the organization

SL No	Statements	Gender	SA	A	N	DA	SD	X ²	Accept/Reject
1	Employees are find it necessary to improve their skill and achieve objective.	M	8	11	6	0	0	.76	Accept
		F	11	13	1	0	0		
2	Organization taking major part to fulfill the requirement of the employees.	M	3	6	2	8	6	6.02	Accept
		F	4	3	9	4	5		
3	Health, Safety and Welfare facilities are one of the important concepts to improve the performance.	M	9	13	3	0	0	.32	Accept
		F	11	13	1	0	0		
4	Coaching, Counseling and mentoring will help to meet the requirement of the employees.	M	7	14	2	1	1	.09	Accept
		F	8	11	3	2	1		

5	Reward management will work as a motive to improve the performance.	M	11	14	0	0	0	.08	Accept
		F	10	13	2	0	0		
6	Create good atmosphere to work better in the organization.	M	9	12	4	0	0	1.60	Accept
		F	13	12	0	0	0		
7	It helps to improve their career and to reach high in the organization.	M	10	13	2	0	0	.08	Accept
		F	9	14	2	0	0		

Source: Primary Data

Note: Degrees of Freedom: 4. Value = 9.488 at 5% of level of significance.

From the above result it clear that all the statements are falls under acceptance region in the chi square test. This will make us that employee development programmes will helps to improve the performance of the employee.

Findings

1. Employees feel that skill development program will helps them to adjust with a changing situation.
2. Employee development programmes are essential in organization to achieve its objective.
3. It helps to improve the performance of the employees over a period of time.
4. It makes the employees to take higher level of job without any fear in the mind..
5. It builds good work environment in the work place to achieve the results.

Suggestions

1. Organization has to understand the requirement of the employees before designing the employee development plans.
2. Active participation of employees is required in all employee development programmes.
3. Develop a good reward management system to improve the performance of the employees
4. Take care of the family members of the employees who are working in the organization.

8. Conclusion

Employees are the real asset for the organization to achieve its vision and to be a supporting hand in every successful project executed by the company. Achievement of the organization is directly related to the effort and dedication of the employees who are really working for that industry. In the present scenario to make employee competent to this changing world we have to update our skill and knowledge as per the demand of the industry. If company invests on the employee develop project it will enjoy the fruits of success for a long period of time. It will strengthen our capability to compete in the global world with its developed employee force.

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Paper 15

**PROBLEMS OF FARMERS WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO UDUPI DISTRICT****Fathima Jabina*, K Swathi Shet*, Jableen****

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Abstract

Agriculture is one of the most important pillars of the Indian economy. The science and practice of farming including cultivation of the soil for the growing of crops and the rearing of animals provide food, wool and other products. Rural farmers account for the greater part of the population of any developing country such as India. The history of Indian agriculture dates back to 10000 years. Indian agriculture began during 9000 BC as a result of early cultivation of plants and domestication of crops and animals. The middle ages in India saw irrigation channels that reached a new level of sophistication. Land and water management systems were developed with objective of providing uniform growth. The agricultural sector employed 8.2 per cent of the total workforce in India, and despite a steady decline of its share in the GDP, it still remains the largest economic sector. Agricultural development is one of the most talked about issues as a major portion of our population is still engaged with the agricultural industry. The widespread modernization of agriculture, development of many modern techniques and improvement in farm productivity all are the basic characteristics of agricultural development. Since the beginning years of economic development, it has been one of the main drivers of growth of the economy as it supplies was a major source of raw materials to most of the manufacturers. To examine the different innovative measures adopted by different social groups for agricultural development in the district at block level. Agricultural extension services can and should play an important role in addressing many of these challenges.

Key words: Agricultural production, Growth, Technology, changes, Farm, Crops.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Agriculture plays a pivotal role in the Indian economy. Although its contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) is now around on sixth, it provides employment to 8.2 per cent of the Indian workforce.

Due to this reason most of the strategies of development even with its focus on different domains often emphasize upon rapid agriculture development in general and its modernisation in particular. Is a person engaged in agriculture, raising living organisms for food or raw materials The term usually applies to people who do some combination of raising field crops, orchards, vineyards, poultry, or other livestock. A farmer might own the farmed land or might work as a labourer on land owned by others, but in advanced economies, a farmer is usually a farm owner, while employees of the farm are known as farm workers, or farmhands. However, in the not so distant past, a farmer was a person who promotes or

improves the growth of (a plant, crop, etc.) by labour and attention, land or crops or raises animals.

Rural farmers or farmers are those who live in rural areas and fully depend on agriculture and its allied activities for their survival. But the problems of rural farmer are a major barrier in economic development. Therefore governments of developing countries have a major responsibility of ensuring that there is adequate rural development in their various communities and local governments which would lead to effective and efficient.

Poverty refers to a situation when people are deprived of basic necessities of life. It is often characterized by inadequacy of food, shelter and clothes. In other words, poverty refers to a state of privation where there is a lack of essential needs for subsistence.

Agricultural system not only supply food and animal protein but also fosters the utilization of natural resources in a sustainable manner (CGIAR, 1995). When the rural farmer lack access to knowledge and information that would help them achieve maximum agricultural yield, they are not only grope in dark but are driven to the urban centres in search of formal employment, as the only option for survival (Munyua, 2000; Blait, 1996) pointed out that the least expensive input for improved rural agricultural development is adequate access to knowledge and information in areas of new agricultural technology, early warning systems(drought, pests, diseases etc), improved seedlings, fertilizer, credit market prices etc. There have been short-comings of traditional print and library methods (Van and Fortier, 2000) of providing such agricultural information to rural farmers who are generally illiterate and relatively remote from sources of information.

In Assam around 8.2% of the state's population relies on agriculture as farmers or as agricultural labour. But almost all the farmers faces many problems like poverty, lack of knowledge about modern technology, illiteracy etc. In my study area Lowphulabori village under the Raha Block Development Area of Nagaon District of Assam, agricultural labours are pertaining to 3/4 of the total labour force. Agricultural labour and farmers in this area still remain serfdom or slavery system. Their income, standard of living, social status is very low. Increase the number of rural farmer in this study area due to increasing the size population, decline of cottage and village industries, evictions of small farmers, uneconomic holdings, growing indebtedness, deforestation, growth of capitalist farming etc. As a result the farmer of this area faces many problems such as poverty, lack of knowledge, about modern technology, lack of knowledge about market demandable agricultural.

BENEFITS OF AGRICULTURE

1. Land :

Conservation agriculture improves soil structure the soil against erosion and nutrient losses by maintaining a permanent soil cover and minimizing soil disturbance. Furthermore, CA practices enhance soil organic matter (SOM) levels and nutrient availability by utilizing the previous crop residues.

2. Labour:

Because land under no-till is not cleared before planting and involves less weeding and pest problems following the establishment of permanent soil cover /crop rotations, farmers in Ghana reported a 22% saving in labour associated with maize production.

3. Water:

Conservation agriculture requires significantly less water use due to increased infiltration and enhanced water holding capacity from crop residues left on the soil surface.

4. Nutrients:

Soil nutrient supplies and cycling are enhanced by the biochemical decomposition of organic crop residues at the soil surface that are also vital for feeding the soil microbes.

5. Soil biota:

Insect pests and other disease causing organisms are held in check by an abundant and diverse community of beneficial soil organisms, including predatory wasps, spiders, nematodes, springtails, mites and beneficial bacteria and fungi, among other species.

6. Economic benefits:

Farmers using CA technologies typically report higher yields (up to 45-48% higher) with fewer water, fertilizer and labour inputs, thereby resulting in higher overall farm profits.

7. Environmental benefits:

Conservation agriculture represents an environmentally-friendly set of technologies. Because it uses resources more efficiently than conventional agriculture, these resources become available for other uses, including conserving them for future generation.

8. Equity considerations:

Conservation agriculture also has the benefit of being accessible to many small-scale farmers who need to obtain the highest possible yields with limited land area and inputs.

9. Active role for farmers:

As with any new agricultural technology, CA methods are most effective when used with skilful management and careful consideration of the many agroecological factors affecting production on any given farm or field.

10. NEED FOR THE STUDY:

- To know the how many people's are doing agriculture in Udupi and North Canara District
- To know the knowledge regarding new agricultural technologies.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To know the income and productivity of the farmers.
2. To create awareness among farmers about credit facilities for agriculture in the nearby financial institution.
3. To examine the different innovation measures adopted by different social groups from agricultural development in the district at the block level.

IMPORTANCES OF AGRICULTURE:

Agriculture has its own importance. They are discussed in under:

1. Source of Livelihood

The main source livelihood of many people is agriculture. Approximately 70% of the people directly rely on agriculture as a mean of living. This percentage in agriculture

is as a result of none development of non-agricultural activities to absorb the fast – growing population.

2. Contribution to National revenue

Agriculture is the main source of national income for most developing countries. However, for the developed countries, agriculture contributes a smaller percentage to their national income.

3. Supply of Food as well as Fodder

Agricultural sector provides fodder for domestic animals, Cow provides people with milk which is a form of protective food. Moreover, livestock also meets people's food requirements.

4. Significance to the International Trade

Agricultural products like sugar, tea, rice, spices, tobacco, coffee etc. Constitute the major items of exports of countries that rely on agriculture. If there is smooth development practice of agriculture, imports are reduced while export increases considerably.

5. Marketable surplus

The growth of agricultural sector contributes to marketable surplus. Many people engage in manufacturing, mining as well as other non-agricultural sector as the nation develops. All these individuals rely on food production that they might meet from the nation's marketable surplus.

6. Source of Raw Material

The main source of raw materials to major industries such as cotton and jute fabric, sugar, tobacco, edible as well as non-edible oils is agriculture. Moreover, many other industries such as processing of fruits as well as vegetables and rice husking get their raw material mainly from agriculture.

7. Significance in Transport

Bulks of agricultural products are transported by railways and roadways from to factories. Mostly, internal trade is in agricultural product.

8. Foreign Exchange Resources

The nation's export trade depends largely on agricultural sector. This demonstrates that agriculture products also continue to be important source of earning a country foreign exchange.

9. Great Employment Opportunities

Construction of irrigation schemes, drainage system as well as other such activities in the agricultural sectors is important as it provides large employment opportunities.

10. Economic Development

Since agriculture employs many people it contributes to economic development. As a result, the national income level as well as people's standard of living is improved.

11. Source of saving

Development in agriculture may also increase savings. The rich farmers we see today started saving particularly after green revolution. This surplus quantity may be invested further in the agriculture sector to develop the sector.

12. Food security

A stable agricultural sector ensures a nation of food security. The main requirement of any country is food security.

SOURCES OF DATA:

The present study is mainly based on the available primary data collected from the A Study on Problems of farmers with special reference to Udupi district. The period of April 2019 were considered for the study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research paper is based on both primary and secondary data. In this research paper, the primary data was collected through face to face interaction of the farmers. In this research paper, recommendations and conclusions are based on primary data. The paper is based on investigation for the present research. The main role of investigation is based on the new creative ideas.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

1. PURPOSE OF FARMING

	SUBSISTANCE	COMMERCIAL	TOTAL
FORMERS	26	24	50

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table, out of 50 farmers, 26 farmers are growing products for subsistence purses remaining 24 farmers are growing the products for commercial purses.

2. TYPES OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

	PADDY	ARKNET	CASHEW	COCONUT	RUBBER	TOTAL
FARMERS	36	4	0	10	0	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers 36 are growing paddy, 4 farmers are growing ark nut, and 10 farmers are growing coconut.

3 REVENUE FROM AGREICULTURAL ACTIVITIES?

	BELOW 50000	50000-100000	100000-200000	200000-300000	TOTAL
FOREMERS	38	11	1	0	50

INTERPRITATION:

From the above chart the majority of the agriculturist yields below 50000 of revenue for a year (38).

4. AGRICULTURAL CREDIT FACILITY

	BORROW FROM FINANCIAL INSTITUTION	BORROW FROM MONEY LENDER	BORROW FROM OTHER	TOTAL
FARMERS	22	15	13	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above, table financial institutions are the major fund supplier for the farmers.

5. DO YOU HAVE MARKETING FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	25	25	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table only half of the farmers have marketing facility, remaining half farmers are not get sufficient marketing facility to market their product.

6. DO YOU HAVE STOREAGE FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	20	30	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table out of 50 respondents, only 20 are having storage facility, remaining 30 farmers are not have storage facility.

7. DO YOU HAVE GOOD TRANSPOTATION FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	19	31	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 19 farmers are getting a good transportation facility, remaining 31 farmers are not get sufficient transportation facility.

8. ARE YOU GETTING FINACIAL SUPPORT OF GOVERNMENT?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	11	39	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, only 11 formers are getting financial support to the Government, remaining 39 farmers are not got any financial support to the government.

9. HAVE YOU GOT FAIR PRICE FOR PRODUCT?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	10	40	50

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 10 farmers are get a fair price for their product, remaining 40 farmers are not get a fair price for their product.

10. DO YOU HAVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY BASED MARKETING FACILITIES?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	8	42	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 8 farmers are get a information to technology based marketing facility, remaining 42 farmers are not get a information to technology based marketing facility.

11. DO YOU HAVE LACK OF IRRIGATION FACILITY?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	16	34	50

INTERPRITATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 16 farmers are get a good irrigation for their agriculture, remaining 34 farmers are not get a sufficient irrigation for their agriculture.

12. DO YOU GET ADEQUATE PROFIT?

	YES	NO	TOTAL
FARMERS	11	39	50

INTERPRETATION:

Frome the above table, out of 50 farmers only 11 farmers are get a adequate profit fore their agricultural product, but remaining 39 farmers are not get a adequate profit for their agricultural product .

SUGGESTIONS:

Based on the survey findings,

- Department of Agriculture must give a relevant information about new technology, transportation facility etc.
- Department o Agriculture must to promote the farmers to sale their product.
- Also Government take nasusury mashers to overcome the problem of money lender in the rural aria by extending the banking facilities and expansion of bank branches.

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of the above study we can say that the chronic poverty, illiteracy, lack of mechanisation, scarcity of HYU inputs, lack of capital formation, flood and drought, poor agricultural marketing facilities, lack of knowledge about demandable crops or more appropriately the absence of commercialization of agriculture sector are the main problems of

the rural farmers. Small farmers are an important component in society. Now it is time to focus on social economical problem of these farmers & try to find the solution to the problem. In above study farmers strongly demanding pension scheme only for food security not for luxurious life.

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Paper 16

UPGRADING B.TECH. CURRICULUM AS B.TECH. (HONS) BY INTEGRATING STEAM, ESEP & IPR FEATURES

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Abstract:

Innovation in course curriculum is a continuous process in the higher education system (HES). As the amount of published information growing with time at geometric progression, it is necessary to increase the depth and breadth of the HES curriculum of every course with time. Engineering education is one of the prominent areas in science & technology education, finding many opportunities and facing many challenges in the 21st century due to the accelerated advancement of technologies in many areas. Keeping students in pace with such developments and adopting such newly emerging areas of technology in the current curriculum is an essential requirement of the education industry's progress. In this paper, we have proposed improvement in engineering education in India at the undergraduate level by means of six innovations to improve the depth, breadth, and vigorousness of the B.Tech. programme by suggesting a Student integrated development Framework in engineering based on STEAM-Employability Model with a focus on experimental learning. The six innovations proposed in this model upgrades the B.Tech. (Pass) programme into B.Tech. (Honours). The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages from students, institutions, and job offering industries point of view are analysed. Finally, some recommendations are submitted based on the analysis to make this model of B.Tech. (Honours) more effective in its objective of enhancing competency and employability of graduates to secure better employment.

Keywords : B.Tech. degree, B.Tech. (Hons), Engineering curriculum, STEM, STEAM, Employability skill enhancement program (ESEP), Experimental learning, STEAM-Employability Model.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Higher education system (HES) has an objective of improving the knowledge, skills, experience, & ethics of students towards increasing their confidence to identifying and solving problems of the society through effective and contemporary education using a suitable teaching-learning model [1]. Innovation in course curriculum is a continuous feature in the higher education system. As the amount of published information growing with time at geometric progression, it is necessary to increase the depth and breadth of the HES curriculum of every course with time. This also involves in removing obsolete part of the curriculum without hesitation to give room for new and emerging issues in the course subjects. Upgrading HE curriculum by adding area based specific focus models like STEM

(Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), and STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts & design, and Mathematics) are the current trend in both secondary and college education system. It is believed that such an education model can prepare students all-rounder to face any challenges in their life and make them innovative in their working place. Apart from area-based specific focus during higher education which enhances knowledge and subject-specific skills, additional supporting skills like communication, proficiency in writing, generation of new ideas, enhancing competitiveness, preserving a vision in life, desire for learning and improvement in life, attitude towards life, respect for fellow-beings, self-control and such other qualities inculcate confidence and enhances leadership behaviour among the students to become winner in competitive society. These factors also enhance the employability of the students in industry specific areas where general skills and competency are essential for survival [2].

Engineering education is one of the prominent areas in science & technology education, finding many opportunities and facing many challenges in the 21st century due to the accelerated advancement of technologies in many areas of society [3-5]. Technology is considered as lifeblood of all developments and solutions to all problems related to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human being in the society. Keeping engineering students in pace with such developments and adopting such newly emerging areas of technology in the current curriculum is an essential requirement of the education industry's progress. In this paper, we have proposed a new improved model on engineering education system of India which includes basically STEAM model with employment skills enhancement program (ESEP) subjects in every semester and earning IPR by every student as top-ups. This model proposes six innovations at the undergraduate engineering level to improve the depth, breadth, and vigorousness of the B.Tech. programme by suggesting a Student focussed integrated development (SFID) Framework. This integrated development framework in engineering education is based on STEAM-Employability Model with a focus on experimental learning. The six innovations proposed in this model with increased credits in every semester upgrades the conventional B.Tech. (Pass) programme into B.Tech. (Honours). The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages from students, institutions, and job offering industries point of view are analysed. Many recommendations are submitted based on the analysis to make this model of B.Tech. (Honours) more effective in its objective of enhancing competency, confidence, and employability of graduates to secure better job.

2. RELATED SCHOLARLY WORKS :

2.1 STEM Model as First School of Innovative Thought :

STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) as integrated single subject in school education is becoming popular in many countries and now spreading its roots to higher education system. Apart from school education, if college level curriculum is planned with STEM subjects, the scientific thinking and innovative ability of students can be improved to make them smart graduates who can adopt technology in decision making and problem solving. In STEM curriculum model at college level, a student has to study science, technology, engineering, and mathematics subjects in each year (preferable in semester) to be competitive in order to get further opportunities. Identifying such subjects in a systematic combination to make effective STEM interconnected model is the challenge for educators. Table 1 contains some of research papers published during the 21st century related to college education.

Table 1 : Published papers related to STEM education

S. No.	STEM Curriculum	Focus	Reference
1	21st century STEM education concepts & priorities	A tactical model for long-range success	Ostler, E. (2012). [6]
2	STEM subjects for College education	College student pathways to the STEM disciplines	Engberg, M., (2013) [7]
3	Facilitating change in undergraduate STEM education	STEM for Change in knowledge & skills	Beach, A. L., (2012) [8]
4	Innovation processes in university STEM education	System model	Porter, A. L., (2016) [9]
5	Integrated STEM education	Benefits and procedure of integration	Roehrig, G. H., (2015) [10]
6	How an integrative STEM curriculum	For students of engineering design practices	Fan, S. C., (2017) [11]
7	From STEM to STEAM Strategies for enhancing engineering & technology education	Importance of Arts & Design education for enhancing creative abilities	Connor, A., et al. (2015) [12]
8	The potential of technology education	STEM education	Wells, J. G. (2008) [13]
9	STEM and technology education	International state-of-the-art education	Ritz, J. M., (2015) [14]
10	Developing effective STEM professional development programs	Design of STEM programs	Avery, Z. K., (2013) [15]
11	Reformation of engineering education.	Transitioning from STEM to STEAM	Watson, A. D., (2013) [16]
12	Rethinking STEM education	An interdisciplinary STEAM curriculum	Madden, M. E., [17]

2.2 STEAM Model as Second School of Innovative Thought :

An improvement in STEM is argued by many researchers in education to make students as all-rounders. As per this argument, apart from learning for knowledge, skills, and experience which are specific for a given industry, student should also enhance their creative thinking and design abilities by involving in art and design related trainings. Hence a new model which integrates STEM with Arts & Design subjects is proposed. Based on studies it is realized that such a transdisciplinary STEAM model is the current requirement to enhance the creative thinking abilities among engineering graduates. Table 2 reviews some of the papers published related to STEAM education model.

Table 2 : Published papers related to STEAM education

S. No.	STEAM Curriculum	Focus	Reference
1	STEAM education	Development of a theoretical model	Kim, Sung-Won, et al. (2012) [18]
2	Development and application of STEAM teaching model	Based on the Rube Goldberg's invention	Kim, Y., (2012) [19 2]
3	A study of teaching-learning methods for the IT-based STEAM education model	With regards to developing people of interdisciplinary abilities	Kim, J. A., (2011) [20]
4	Rethinking STEM education	An interdisciplinary STEAM curriculum	Madden, M. E., (2013) [21]
5	Transitioning STEM to STEAM	Reformation of engineering education	Watson, A. D., (2013) [22]
6	From STEM to STEAM	Toward a human-centred education	Boy, G. A. (2013) [23]
7	An analysis on STEAM education teaching and learning program	On technology and engineering areas	Ahn, J., (2013) [24]
8	STEAM teaching practices	Developing a conceptual model	Quigley, C. F. (2017) [25]
9	From interdisciplinary to transdisciplinary	An arts-integrated approach to STEAM education	Liao, C. (2016). [26]
10	STEAM Education	Study on the current status	Park, H., (2016) [27]
11	STEAM as social practice	Cultivating creativity in transdisciplinary spaces	Guyotte, K. W., (2014) [28]
12	STEAM Education through Case Studies	Examination of the Practical Model	KIM, J. W. (2015) [29]
13	From STEM to STEAM	Students' beliefs about the use of their creativity	Oner, A. T., (2016) [30]

2.3 Improving Competency through Employability Skills Enhancement Model :

Competency means ability or capability to do things effectively and performance is the proof of competency. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. But based on many studies, it is evident that a major portion of engineering graduates have lack of competency to be employed. This problem can be resolved by means of offering special training on employability skills enhancement during the engineering course by adopting such training in the college curriculum. Many research papers published on such industry oriented employability skills to be inculcated with the students to transfer them as employable graduates. A review on some of the papers on employability skills enhancement based education is given in Table 3.

Table 3 : Published papers related to Employability skills enhancement based education

S. No.	ESEP Curriculum	Focus	Reference
1	Career management skills	Enhancing graduate employability	Bridgstock, R. (2009). [31]
2	Employability skills in higher education	Various methods in order to promote employability skills in HE	Asonitou, S. (2015). [32]
3	A European study	Graduate employability, 'soft skills' versus 'hard' business knowledge	Andrews, J., (2008) [33]
4	Engineering employability skills required by employers	In Asian countries	Zaharim, A., (2009) [34]
5	Recognizing the enhancement of graduate attributes and employability	Through part-time work while at university	Muldoon, R. (2009). [35]
6	Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation	In Higher Educational Institutions	Aithal, P. S., (2015). [36]
7	Bridging the gap between degree programme curricula and employability	Through implementation of work-related learning	Hills, J. M., (2003) [37]
8	Defining and measuring employability	Measurement ideas	Harvey, L. (2001). [38]

3. OBJECTIVES :

This paper is a conceptual suggestion based proposal to convert B.Tech. (Pass) course into B.Tech. (Honours) with the following objectives :

- (1) To study emerging models in undergraduate engineering programmes and emerging technologies in the 21st century to be incorporated in the curriculum of undergraduate engineering programmes.
- (2) To propose employability and research oriented curriculum in engineering education based on emerging technologies.
- (3) To suggest an innovative curriculum scheme based on STEAM and employability skill enhancement Program (ESEP) papers along with a focus on research in the improved model.
- (4) To analyse such improved Honours degree in engineering by identifying its advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages from students, institutions, and job offering industries point of view.
- (5) To provide recommendations based on the analysis to make this model of B.Tech. (Honours) more effective in its objective of enhancing competency and employability of graduates to secure better employment.

4. EMERGING MODELS IN UNDERGRADUATE ENGINEERING EDUCATION :

4.1 New Models in Engineering Education :

Autonomy for higher education institutions supported many innovations in course identification, course design, course pedagogy, student services, examination, and evaluation systems. Engineering education, being a prominent field in higher education, became witness in such innovations. Many student centric models are offered in engineering education during last few years mostly by autonomous and private universities. Some of such successful models which attracted many students are as follows :

(1) Industry Integrated B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

These courses are designed to train students for specific industries. The curriculum of such courses is designed by involving experts from such industries along with academicians. Such courses will have more practical components in the form of industry specific projects and industry based internships.

(2) Super speciality B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

These courses are designed to train the students in emerging engineering and technology areas to full fill the requirements in future industries. These emerging areas usually falls under General purpose technologies which offers huge job opportunities in future days in many industries.

(3) Skill focussed B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

These courses focus on developing some specific skills along with the general requirements of engineering knowledge, skills, and experience. Usually, these courses have components which are taught by a specific set of professionals or consultants who have proprietary knowledge in that area.

(4) B.E./B.Tech. Programs with Multi-continent exposure :

In this model, students are exposed to different educational environment by taking them to three to four continent. The students get multi-cultural, multi-teaching- learning atmosphere, along with multi-country industry exposure. Student will study foreign language, and the attitude of other country people due to their immersion in different country environment. The social and technological scenarios will modify the critical and creative thinking abilities to contribute differently to their future organizations.

(5) Integrated Dual degree during B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

In this model, a student registers for two university degrees simultaneously either at the same institution or at different institutions of same university or some times of different universities. This model allows a student to study two degrees in different subject areas simultaneously so that the precious time resource can be utilized effectively. Such studies may be of two different undergraduate programmes as parallel programmes in different disciplines or two sequential programmes as undergraduate and postgraduate programmes in a single discipline.

(6) Research focussed B.E./B.Tech. Programs :

Undergraduate degree programmes in engineering can be made innovative and more intensive by integrating research components in one or more semesters so that along with

conceptual and practical studies, students are compulsorily involved in research and publications along with the faculty members so that students are exposed to systematic innovative thinking and analysis.

4.2 Emerging Technologies to be Incorporated in Engineering Education :

The future education is mostly driven by technology and hence customizable. In this century, education sector, being a part of the service industry is also going to witness the fourth industrial revolution (IR 4.0) with the features of mass customization, personalization, and student centric approach. The technology based disruptive model of education is going to be a driving force of future education at both school and college levels. The engineering education also be accessed via following nine trends [x] which include (1) ubiquitous education model, (2) personalized learning model, (3) choice based pedagogy model, (4) project & experimental based learning model, (5) field based learning through internship, (6) data interpretation skills, (7) competency based evaluation model, (8) teachers as facilitators & guides during learning process, and (9) student-self designed curriculum model. These trends of education 4.0 can be realized using various emerging technologies under the umbrella of ICCT (Information communication and computation Technology) and nanotechnology.

The various emerging technologies which have an impact on teaching – learning and various industrial applications [39-42] are :

(1) Artificial Intelligence : Artificial intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science which focuses on the creation of intelligent machines which can mimic the decisions of human beings. The primary objective of AI technology is to develop machines which can think and do things better than human beings. The main functions of artificial intelligence machines are to recognize the environment such as speech recognition, Learning, Planning, Problem solving, and hence decision making. Artificial intelligence machine mimics cognitive functions of human beings associated with other human minds, such as learning & memorising and decision making for problem solving. ICCT has created a platform for AI to be introduced and developed for adding intelligent thinking components in electronic systems used in any industrial sectors. Artificial intelligence has its applications in almost all industries in the primary sectors, secondary sectors, tertiary sectors, and quaternary sector.

(2) Machine learning : Machine Learning is the learning in which machine can learn by its own without being explicitly programmed. It is an application of artificial intelligence that provides the system with the ability to automatically learn and improve from experience. Machine learning is based on the idea that we can build machines to process data and learn on their own, without our constant supervision.

(3) Robotics : Robotics technology deals with the study of design, construction, operation, and application of computerized robots and their control, sensory feedback, and information processing abilities. Robotics technologies are useful in developing machines that can replicate and substitute human actions.

(4) Internet of things : It is a network of various electronic, computing, and optical devices/objects including human beings connected virtually by means of internet or intranet for enabling them to send and receive data and information. These objects are provided with unique identifiers (UIDs) and are capable to transfer data and information over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction by using IoT technology. Such a connection of physical things/objects through the Internet allows to

access remote sensor data and to control the physical devices connected to it from a distance. The data captured from such sources, can create new synergistic services which will be superior to such services provided by an isolated embedded system. Internet-of-Things (IoT) is not in any new disruptive technology but is the pervasive deployment and innovation of ICCT.

(5) Autonomous vehicles : An autonomous vehicle can guide itself without human control. This kind of vehicle has become a concrete reality and may pave the way for future systems where computers take over the art of driving. An autonomous car is also known as a driverless car, robot car, self-driving car or autonomous vehicle. An autonomous vehicle is an application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in automobile engineering.

(6) Bio and nanotechnology : Bionanotechnology is a branch of **nanotechnology** which uses biological starting materials, utilises biological design or fabrication principles or is applied in medicine or biotechnology. For example, nanoparticles can serve as probes, sensors or vehicles for biomolecule delivery in cellular systems.

(7) 3-D printing : 3D printing is an ICCT application where various materials are joined or solidified using various processes under the control of the computer to create a three-dimensional object. In 3D printing, an object is created by laying down successive layers of material until the object is created. 3D printing can be divided into metal, fabrics, bio and a whole host of other industries with many applications in many industries worldwide. 3D printing is a variant of ICCT general purpose technology and has wide scope in various industrial automation and home automation processes. 3D printing technology is expected to revolutionise the material fabrication processes. 3D printing comprises of many other technologies along with ICCT. Some of the 3D printers make use of nanomaterials and nanocomposites for anything, anywhere manufacturing.

(8) Material science for energy Storage : Sustainable materials are the key requirement of many advanced energy technologies including solar cells, batteries, fuel cells, and catalysis. There is a large demand for cost-efficient methods for energy storage and conversion in the society and hence it has become imperative to accelerate the rate at which energy-related materials are developed. Material scientists are developing various materials which show improved properties like smart materials, superconductors, nanomaterials, polymers, etc.

(9) Quantum computing : High speed computers based on optical signal switching and optical signal processing are expected to breakthrough with their full potentials and capabilities using optical logic gates and flip-flops fabricated by nanocomposites are expected to breakthrough in this century. High speed computation and data storage using nanotechnology based optical/quantum computers are going to revolutionize the entire computer industry. Optical computation is joining both general purpose technologies of Nanotechnology and ICCT through the processes of design & production as well as operation & applications respectively. Various optical principles like photo-refraction, optical spatial solitons, and optical logic gates are under considerations for building all-optical computers.

(10) Business Analytics : The emerging subfield of ICCT named big data and business analytics focus on handling huge amount of data continuously generated in any business or data capturing process and analyses it using various quantitative analytical techniques and mathematical models to study the pattern and descriptive information, predictive information, and prescriptive information for supporting the decision makers to take optimum decisions to the problems related to future aspects of the business. Predictive analytics in various functional areas like Marketing analytics, Retail Analytics (Customer Analytics/ Supply

Chain Analytics), Pricing Analytics, Financial analytics, Social media analytics, sports analytics, and Healthcare analytics are finding importance in the business environment for effective decision making. Further Prescriptive Analytics for optimizing the decisions with multiple objectives/ portfolio analytics, optimizing complex decisions/ sales force analytics, and Retail Analytics etc are also have futuristic impact on effective business decisions.

(11) Cloud Computing : Cloud computing is one of the advances in computer technology and is uses information communication technology as well. Due to the ubiquity of cloud computing facility with flexibility in scaling it has become an important topic of research and provides the value for computing processes in the business. The cloud computing model also provides a most important application called Business Intelligence (BI) for effective decision making in business processes via the Internet. Cloud computing model provides its clients with both hardware as well as software to process the data and information online as a rental service. Cloud computing model has three variations as Software as a Service (SaaS), Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) and Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) to provide ubiquitous computing service solutions to the business. The cloud computing solution used by any business will allow companies to reduce their investment cost, maintenance cost, and hence business cost without compromising to have access to BI solution which will give the business an edge on their competition.

(12) Blockchain Technology : Blockchain is basically a growing list of records containing data or information, called blocks, which are linked using a secured technique called cryptography. Every such block contains a cryptographic hash code of the previous block, a timestamp, and transaction data. By design, a blockchain is resistant to modification of the data. Blockchain gives the history of currency transaction and hence its spending pattern. Blockchain technology is widely used by cryptocurrency transactions. The discovery of the blockchain technology for bitcoin made it the first digital currency to solve the double-spending problems without the need of a trusted authority. Blockchain technology has potential applications in digital currency technology and secured transactions.

(13) Online education technology : Online educational technology supports learning from distance so that a person can earn educational credentials and improve his performance by creating, using and managing appropriate technological processes and resources using internet and multimedia technologies. Online educational technology is the use of both physical hardware and educational theoretic along with wireless systems and internet. This technology has huge amount of applications in many kinds of services in almost all industry sectors for training and development.

(14) Virtual & Augmented Reality : Virtual reality is an artificial environment that is created with the help of computer-based software and presented to the user in such a way that the user suspends belief and accepts it as a real environment. On a computer, virtual reality is primarily experienced through two of the five senses: sight and sound. Currently, the virtual reality is mainly developed and used in simulated training and education as well as the simulated game environment. But it may further find its applications in many other areas including business as augmented reality and may enter the group of general purpose technology.

These emerging technologies have many applications in engineering industries. Having knowledge and learning such technologies is essential for undergraduates during their studies so that such exposure

5. EMPLOYABILITY & RESEARCH ORIENTED CURRICULUM BASED ON EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES :

Engineering graduates are expected to have certain minimum knowledge, skills, and experience as their graduate attributes to identify problems, design solutions, and develop processes and products with new innovative features in industries. Creativity, design thinking, problem solving, self-motivation, positive attitude towards professional challenges, working culture, team work and leadership qualities are essential traits to be successful in getting good job and further promotions. Engineering colleges should focus on planning and implementing such education model which can offer essential employability skills to their students. Some of major employability skills for engineering graduates are in table 4 along with their description and method of acquiring.

Table 4: Major Employability skills required for Engineering graduates

S. No.	Employability skills	Description	Method of gathering
1	Effective Communication skills	Communication of information in understandable manner and in right time	Training
2	Team work skills	To increase the performance of the team	Target based group projects
3	Problem solving skills	Use a combination of intuition and logic to come up with right solutions at right time	Experimental learning based laboratory courses
4	Data interpretation & Numerical competency	To measure an individual's ability to interpret and manipulate data, which is required in most industry roles	Skill labs
5	Leadership skills	How to analyze, how to synthesize, and evaluate situations to make sound decisions	Training
6	Technology skills	Technology awareness	Technology adoption
7	Self-awareness & Competency in specific engineering discipline	Re-defining the goal & SWOC analysis	Competitions
8	Attitude & responsibility towards work	Accountability in overall performance	Workshops & Field works
9	Innovative & creative thinking	Research based new knowledge creation	IPR
10	Design thinking	Product and Design & simulation	Self designed courses

6. B.TECH. (HONOURS) MODEL WITH STEAM & EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS FOCUS :

Based on focus group analysis, we have gather ideas and concepts to improve engineering curriculum with above requirements of new knowledge, new skills, new experience through hard and dedicated learning model which is based on STEAM, Employability enhancement features, creating intellectual properties and industry oriented internship for the 21st century education Industry 4.0 version. The findings are postulated as follows :

- (1) Semesters with increased subjects & Credits (from 6 to 9 subjects & from 20 Credits to 25 Credits).
- (2) Redesigning the Subjects in each Semester as per STEM/STEAM model wherever possible with emerging technologies.
- (3) Increasing Experimental/lab based learning (EL) part in each semester so that equal importance is given to theory and practicals.
- (4) Introducing employability skills enhancement papers (ESEP) in each semester from Industry Experts.
- (5) Focussing on IPR awareness and Patent analysis in every student’s specialized area.
- (6) Compulsory IP generation through Copyright/Patenting/International Journal Publication of the internship based project.

The above postulates are identified as integrated student development framework in engineering based on STEAM-Employability Model with a focus on experimental learning and IPR generation. The model is also represented in the form of a block diagram as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1 : Integrated Student development Framework for effective engineering education

The ideas and concepts to improving engineering curriculum with above requirements of new knowledge, new skills, new experience through hard and dedicated learning model which is based on STEAM (Science, technology, Engineering, Arts & Design, and Mathematics), Employability skills enhancement program (ESEP) features, creating intellectual properties, and industry oriented internship.

7. CONCLUSION :

An innovative, effective, efficient new model in engineering education is proposed. This Integrated student development model based on STEAM, ESEP & IPR features enhances the weightage of conventional B.Tech. (pass) course and elevate it to highly employable based on enhanced competency in concerned engineering subjects called as B.Tech. (Hons). It is predicted that B.Tech. (Hons) graduates have better capability to work and solve problems in the industry due to their enhanced knowledge, skills, experience, and confidence. Such innovations in existing higher education courses are essential to ensure that the graduates studied in such courses are useful for society to contribute to their specialized fields.

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Paper 17

FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG WORKING WOMEN - A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MANGALORE CITY

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Abstract :

Financial literacy is closely connected to an individual's emotional, personal, social, economic, and employment success. An individual needs to understand the basics of money management, and use financial resources appropriately to function well in society at a personal, professional, business and community level. Financial literacy enables the people to access, effectively use and derive maximum benefit from financial services. This is a continuing process by which individuals improve their understanding of financial products, concepts and risks develop skills and confidence to be more aware of financial risks and opportunities to make informed choices. There is a vast segment of population in India who suffer from lack of financial literacy in terms of utilizing their own money and also safe and secure place to avail savings, credit, insurance and remittances .Financial literacy enables people to know, understand and also to estimate the future risk and return associated with the financial products and make responsible decisions. Financial literacy is needed for maintaining the financial stability of the country.

Keywords: financial literacy, investment avenues, government.

1. Introduction:

Financial literacy is the skill, knowledge and information which an individual acquires in order to make effective judgement to manage financial resources and financial well-being of his future. Globalization resulted in introduction of many new financial products which are unique, profitable and also risk oriented. To make a qualitative decision regarding these financial products an individual must be financially literate. Women are a vital part of the Indian Economy, both at the national and the household levels. They make one-third of the national labour force. Indian women contribute a much larger share of their earnings to basic family maintenance with the result that women's earnings positively and immediately affect the incidence and the security of poverty. Availability of credit is made very simple and easy for individuals but if individuals fail to understand the terms and conditions on which credit is made available, and then they may end up entering into debt trap. Therefore understanding the concepts of financial literacy has become the need of an hour. Financially literate individuals are able to improve their quality of life that is they will be in a better position to sail through toughest financial times by having diversified investments, insurance cover, and savings. Financial literacy enables people to know, understand and also to estimate the future risk and return associated with the financial products and make responsible decisions.

Definitions:

¹NFER defines Financial Literacy as, 'the ability to make informed judgements and to make effective decisions regarding the use and management of money'.

²PACFL defines the term Financial Literacy as 'the ability to use knowledge and skills to manage financial resources effectively for a lifetime of financial well-being.

2. Review of literature:

Hussein A. Hassan³³ (2009) in his study states that financial literacy of UAE investors is below the needed level. The study analyses the relationship between the financial literacy and the influence of the factors that affect the investment decisions. The study found that a significant difference in the level of financial literacy was found between the respondents according to their gender. Women were found to have lower level of financial literacy than men.

Lusardi et.al; (2010) in their study made an attempt to understand the factors that contribute for acquisition of financial knowledge. Influence of parents on youngsters in gaining financial knowledge is also highlighted. Study was conducted with an objective to know level of financial literacy youngsters have and the main factors contributing to acquisition of financial knowledge. The study revealed that parent's education especially mothers education directly contributes for gaining financial literacy. Study suggested that parents should educate their children on financial concepts and products so that in future they can gain complete knowledge of financial products which will help in their saving and investment.

Saritha (2012) made an attempt to study the level of advanced financial literacy which working women of Punjab possessed and observed that the younger women have already developed the plan for investment. Working women invest their money in insurance plans as they are not willing to take risk to earn profit and want to have a safe future. Overall level of financial literacy among women of Punjab is average.

Jiyane and Zawada (2013) made an attempt to determine money management behaviour and utilisation of financial products of informal sector women entrepreneurs in South Africa. The study revealed that eradicating poverty through financial literacy will result in economic development of a country. The level of financial literacy among the selected sample members was very poor than estimated.

Nurul and Saleh (2013) conducted an exploratory study in Malaysia to examine how financial literacy influences individual savings in modern market. The main objective was to examine the dependency of financial literacy on individuals saving behavior. Results of demographic profile of respondents show that financial literacy of aged people is higher than because of long term investments than younger people. The study observes that the respondents have very good knowledge on basic financial literacy concepts and knowledge on advanced financial literacy concepts was low. Majority of the respondents are aware about risk diversification. Study suggests conducting more programs on financial education.

Javed Iqbal Bhabha (2014) made an attempt to assess the financial literacy and its impact on saving-investment behaviour of working women in Pakistan. The working women though possess better understanding about basic financial concepts but they lack knowledge about advanced financial concepts. From the study it is examined that working-women in Pakistan are financially illiterate. One of the biggest problems, with working women in developing

¹ National Foundation for Educational Research

² President's Advisory Council on Financial Literacy, 2008 – Annual report (executive summary)

countries like Pakistan, is that they do not treat Personal Finance as something that's important for them. For ages, they have not participated in Personal finance, regarding it as the man's area. Study suggests that saving-investment behavior depends on their financial literacy.

Abdul Haque and Zulfiqar (2016) studied the impact of financial literacy, financial attitude and financial wellbeing on economic empowerment of working women. The main objective of the study was, to measure the level of financial literacy and awareness of financial products among 300 working women of Pakistan. It was observed from the study that working women even after having good knowledge of financial products and good source of income, showed very low interest towards investment. Study suggested for improving and building positive financial attitude for working women on investment and savings. Financial wellbeing was the most influencing factor among all other selected factors.

Nishitha and Neerja (2016) conducted a descriptive and analytical study taking a sample of 200 respondents. The study makes an attempt to find out the saving and investing behavior of newly employed youth. Major findings are level of financial literacy among the respondents are same but they differ in selection of investment avenues. Female respondents give more importance to budget and they find investing in stock market difficult and usually prefer to save in commercial bank or post office products. Respondents have good theoretical knowledge financial products and returns but practically they fail in application of their knowledge.

Anshika and Anju Singh (2017) opined that the level of financial literacy in India is very poor. The level of financial literacy prevailing in India will not result in further economic growth. The study suggested conducting seminars, workshops, other awareness programmes to target groups in order to give them practical knowledge of financial aspects and also to collect feedback on such activities conducted.

Chetna and Raj (2017) conducted a study on, 'Financial literacy among women – Indian scenario with an objective to understand and evaluate the level of financial literacy among women in developing country like India. Women are financial experts, they are good in budgeting and managing cash but when it comes to taking big financial decisions they turn back and leave it to their spouses or other male members. Women lack confidence to take financial decisions and are always dependent on Men. Education, financial problems, socio-cultural barriers and physical barriers are some of the reasons for low level of literacy among women. Study also highlighted the efforts taken up by RBI with other financial institutions to improve financial literacy among individuals in India.

3. Objectives of the study:

- To study the degree of financial literacy among the working women.
- To study the obstacles faced by women in gaining financial knowledge.
- To suggest measures to improve the financial literacy of working women.

4. Significance of the Study:

Financial literacy is the basic requirement to promote financial inclusion. In India, the need for financial education is even greater considering the low level of literacy and the large section of the population, which is still out of the formal financial set-up. The Reserve Bank of India has undertaken a project titled "Project Financial Literacy" with an objective to disseminate information regarding the central bank and general banking concepts. Commercial Banks have come up with a link on its web site for the common person to give

the ease of access to information. A few banks have taken initiatives to start some centers in rural/ semi urban areas, which offer financial education and credit counselling services. It will also benefit the financially-included by helping them make informed choices about the products and services available in the market to their best advantage.

5. **Research Methodology:**

The study was conducted through descriptive survey methods using both primary and secondary data. Questionnaire was distributed randomly to 100 working women. Secondary data were collected from various books, journals, websites, and newspapers.

6. **Results and discussions:**

- Majority (46%) of respondents belong to age group of 30-40 years and 90% are working for a private company.
- 60% of respondent's monthly salary ranges from 20000-40000 and 80% of respondents are married.
- 64% of respondents have completed their graduation and 20% post-graduation. Respondent's education qualification is good which shows that they have knowledge about basic financial products.
- 42% of respondent's have savings up to Rs.8000 per month and their source of information to save is bank officials and friends.
- 21% of respondents have De-mat account. This may be because most of the women are comparatively not ready to face any kind of risk. They usually think about safer investment.
- Majority (40%) of respondents prefer to invest in jewellery, 16% in recurring deposit, 16% in mutual funds, 4% in real estate, 14% post office products and 10% in fixed deposit. This result proves that women are aware about modern financial products but because the risk factor is more they go for traditional investments.
- 34% of respondents are aware and have child life policy and 32% have opted for term policy.
- Majority (72%) of respondents are ready to face low risk in relation to their investment.

7. **Suggestions**

Women earn income and also save a major share of income but they opt only for risk free or less risky investment. Overall financial literacy among women is moderate. They are aware of all modern financial products but lack confidence to practically use those avenues. Therefore women should be given proper training to make use of modern financial products by conducting workshops, seminars, guest talks.

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Paper 18**A STUDY ON PROBLEMS FACING BY THE
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE STUDENTS IN RURAL
AREAS - SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KUNDAPUR
TALUK, UDUPI DIST.****Vaishnavi H., Ramya Rao, Kavyashree**1st year M.COM students

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Abstract:

Education to all is a global slogan of Government. Education is one of the most significant factors for development of the economy. It provides an opportunity to reflect on the social, cultural, economy and moral values in the society and also provides brightness to human life it is regarded as potential investment in future for individuals , government also takes initiatives to the development of higher education system of India. Students all over world face a number of problems which dishearten them.

The purpose of the study is examine to understand the distinctive problems and challenges faced by rural government college students in Udupi district , the objective of the study to know how government college are helping rural students in education. To find the problems and challenges of government college students and also identify the satisfactory level of students. The study is mainly based on primary data and collected through questionnaire form. The researcher collected the data from four government colleges in Udupi district.

Keywords: Challenges, Government colleges, satisfactory level, educational facility, rural community.

1. Introduction:

Education plays the most important role in societal development. Rural education implies both the economic betterment of people as well as greater social transformation. Education is a dynamic process that starts from birth. The barrier that the students from rural government to consider that some families don't have the ability to support their child through education process, which means rural student cannot obtain higher education in rural areas. Majority of the population in India still lives in villages and so the topic of rural education in India is of utmost importance.

The foundation to turn India into a strong nation has to be laid down at primary and rural levels and so the quality of education right from the beginning should be excellent. There are plenty of problems which the students face in the rural areas. Only government colleges are there but when you compare the quality of the education in a private and semi government colleges, the difference seems to be higher. The facility of using computers and

internet in the colleges of rural areas can help them a lot to improve the level of the study. Through internet the students will be able to acquire more knowledge and at the same time they will be able to know the outer world in the better way. It is true that the education system of rural areas has been improved a lot in the last 10 years. The government has taken many necessary steps. People have become aware of the necessity of the study. However, still the scope of improving is wide open and both government and common people should try to do that to improve the condition of colleges in rural areas. Rural education is important not only for the enhancement of life quality of the rural community, but also for the overall progress and development of the country.

2. Review of literature:

According to sidoti(2000) access to education in rural and remote areas is a human rights issue.

According to pennington Williams and karvonen,(2006) community colleges located in rural geographical regions also attempts to preserve their local rural culture.

According to a research study conducted by Susan Elkin in (2014), many rural students are academically, socially and culturally under prepared to initially handle college life at urban universities. Rural students often have limited resources including insufficient high school level courses. Rural students’ families may have had little time or resources for academic, socio-cultural challenges compared to urban students when moving into urban universities.

3. Objectives:

1. To understand the problems of rural government college students in kundapura taluk.
2. To understand the educational and basic facilities of the college.
3. To know the effective utilisation of scholarship by the government college students.

4. Research Methodology:

This paper is based on 50 students belongs to rural government degree colleges in kundapura taluk, udupi district. This study purely consists of primary data; it includes government colleges like koteswara SKVMS Govt. First Grade College, Byndoor Govt. First Grade College, Barkur Govt. First Grade College. The questionnaire collected from each college is approximately 13. The analysis done for the study is simple average method and their respective charts.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table No.1

Completion of PUC- education

	Out of 100%
Government	63
Private	37

Chart no.2:
Pie chart showing completion of PUC education

Interpretation:

From the above table shows 63% of the students finished their PUC in government colleges and remaining 37% of the students are from private colleges. From this analysis, majority of the students are from government colleges.

Table no.2:
Basis of selection of degree college by the students

	Out of 100%
Nearby home	20
More facility	40
Referred_by friends	35
None of the above	5

Chart no.2:
Pie chart showing selection of degree college by the students.

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 40% of students selected this college because they get more facilities, 35% of the students are referred by friends and 20% of the students selected this college because it is nearer to their home and only 5% students selected this college for no reason.

Table 3:

Distance from home to college

	Out of 100%
Below 1 km	12
1-5 km	15
5-10 km	28
More than 10 km	45

Chart no.3:

Pie chart showing distance from home to college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 45% of the students come from more than 10km, 28% of the students are coming from 5-10km, 15% from 1-5km and 12% of the students come from below 1km. In this we can interpret that majority of the students come to college from far away places.

Table no.4:

Educational facilities from the college

	Out of 100%
Library	58

Computer lab	27
Internet facility	15
None of the above	00

Chart no.4:

Column chart showing educational facilities from the college

Interpretation:

From the above chart shows, 58% of the college has library facilities, 27 % college has internet facilities, and 15% of the college has computer facilities. This analysis shows that in Government College most of the students are more benefited from the library.

Table no.5:

Basic facilities from the college

	Out of 100%
Rest room	50
Canteen	17
Clean toilets	20
Purified drinking water	13

Chart no.5:

chart showing basic facilities from the college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 50% of the college has rest room facilities for students and 20% of the college has clean toilets, 17% has canteen facilities and remaining 13% of the college has purified drinking water.

Table no.6:

Utilization of scholarship amount

	Out of 100%
Purchasing books	45
Household expenses	25
Payment of fees	20
Personal use	10

Chart no.6:

Pie chart shows the utilisation of scholarship by the students

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 45% of the students utilize their scholarship amount for purchasing book, 25% students use it for personal use, 10% uses their scholarship amount for household expenses and 20% of the student utilizes their amount forpayment of fees.

Table no.7

Types of teaching method used in college

	Out of 100%
Talk and chalk	40
PPT	25
Seminar/assignments	25
Dictating notes	10

Chart no.7:

Bar chart showing types of teaching method used in college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, 40% of the college uses talk & chalk method, 10% of the colleges dictating the notes and remaining 25% of the college uses PPT and seminar or assignments.

Table no.8:

Satisfaction level of the students about their college

	Out of 100%
Yes	100
No	0

Chart no.8:

Column chart showing satisfaction level of the students about their college

Interpretation:

From the above table shows, all the 100% students are satisfied about their college. None of the students are unsatisfied.

Findings :

This study respondents are completed their PUC in government colleges and the respondents are selected in government colleges, if they get more facilities from government colleges.

Most of the government college students are coming from very far places (more than 10km) this is the main problem by the government college students because there is no transportation facilities from home to college.

Library plays an important role for government college students other than computer lab, internet. According to basic facilities provided by the college to the students is 50% students are satisfied with rest rooms other than canteen, toilets, drinking water facilities.

Monetary benefits are also given by the college students by the way of scholarships. From the analysis we understood that 65% of students (purchasing of books and payment of fees) so, 65% of students are utilizing their scholarship in an effective purpose. 35% of students are not utilizing for the purpose of education they are utilizing for household expenses and personal use. The government should create awareness to the students for proper utilization of scholarships.

In the government colleges most of the teaching aids are chalk and talk method (40%) 25% of teaching aid is using PPT and 10% only says dictating the notes.

Suggestion :

There are many prominent crises that are holding back rural education to match up with the education system in urban educational centres. The right reformation can definitely bring about a positive change towards the development of rural education.

Indian education system has to improve a lot through creating awareness among students about importance of education and their social responsibility. Government has to take measures to develop the education system like quality teaching, research and development,

technological development and solving the problems of rural students by providing basic facilities.

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Paper 19

**A CSR ORIENTED EQUILIBRIUM CAMPUS
PLACEMENT APPROACH****Varun Shenoy* & P. S. Aithal****

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Abstract

It is a common phenomenon in placements, that a recruiter cannot visit all the institutions in the country or area simultaneously at once for their hiring requirements. Therefore, recruiters agree in a pooling agreement with a host college in the locality for mobilizing the candidates. However, such an arrangement still deems to open up the probability of certain students not reaching the host venue college owing to academic commitments or even personal issues or any other unknown arisable external / internal factors. Considering few recruiters also choosing only one Premium College for hiring owing to their own defined institutional benchmarks and also other unknown relationship criteria again opens up the probability of deprivation of job opportunity for other college students of the nation or a locality for the job positions. Therefore, to create parity in the unequal occurrence of generation of placement opportunity among various educational institutions of the country, in this paper, we recommend a possible equilibrium strategy through researching applications of technology as a cure to this predicament.

Keywords : Universal Campus Placements, Ubiquitous Campus Recruitments, Uniform Placement Opportunity, General Placement Event.

1. Introduction :

This paper primarily focused on Industries is an investigative study as to what solution can be offered to the HEI (Higher Education Institution) students of India when it comes to equal employment placements at their college campuses. There is already fee discrimination in various Government, Aided, Affiliate, Constituent and Private colleges and HEI's across India. Also, in the case of placement process of any of above HEI's, the recruiters or employers are the ultimate main decision makers no matter irrespective how much invitation communication that particular HEI's Placement cell extends to the recruiting companies. However, with an intention to create at-least equality in placement opportunities after all for all students irrespective of colleges and institutions, the job creating and offering recruiter's whole hearted support is sought here to see if the proposed model of placement equilibrium here in this study can be embraced and implemented to be a part of ethics and social responsibility of all involved stakeholders. Therefore, in this study we have offered to propose here a new CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) oriented Equilibrium Placement Opportunity Model. A CSR Programme can be an aid to recruitment and retention, particularly within the competitive graduate student market. Experience reveals most of the organizations take up recruitment and manpower placement as a commercial activity rather

than a social development affair. Therefore, the equal employment placement model proposed here in seeks to align CSR into the placement and recruitment process offered by recruiters of this country to infuse equality into the same.

2. Objectives of the Study :

The broad objectives of this research can be classified as below :

- (a) To create equal placement opportunity for the students of all eligible campuses in the country.
- (b) To develop a sustainable model of provision of equal employment opportunity for all job seeking students of all eligible campuses.
- (c) To facilitate increased healthy Industry-Academia Engagement.

3. Research Methodology :

Based on observations and direct interviews of few focus group of job seeking students, literature review, and secondary data gathering, the research problem i.e. plights of students not getting equal placement opportunities at different Indian HEI (Higher Educational Institutions) was determined. Therefore, the solution model is proposed through a schematic modular representation of ideas and elucidation. An Opinionnaire was also formulated to seek and understand the views from the recruiter sample of a random industry population regarding the model and interpret the results.

4. Proposed new CSR oriented Equilibrium Placement Opportunity Approach :

The Figure 1 below depicts the proposed framework as to how recruiters can offer placement opportunity in their organizations to placement seeking students in HEI's (Higher Educational Institutions) equally. The Funnel down approach proposed here begins from following processes :

- (a) With the help of technology, organize an online application and registration process for all colleges Nationally/State/Region/Area wise depending on company's Manpower requirement location and HEI's surrounding the same.
- (b) The Screening of CV could be done through AI or Bot and issue online interview call letter via mail/test sms or whatsapp to qualified students.
- (c) Organize an Online Proctored employment test for Students which can be taken anywhere so that it saves their travelling time and anxiety.
- (d) Deploy Online Video Conferencing for a Panel GD or even Personal Interviews
- (e) Finally, any other interactions can be done in company facility for shortlisted students.

Figure 1 : CSR Oriented Equilibrium Placement Opportunity Flow

The Primary Significance of the above model is to bridge the time old Industry-Academia gap where both the stakeholders here are in union with their intention of Nation's Human Resource Development contribution through social service approach. Currently, the divide exists when Academia tries to place their students in the industry through a social contribution approach, the absorbing industry in return is intending to recruit students for commercial or business requirements.

5. Industry Opinion regarding the above Proposed Approach :

The quantified data from Opinionnaire regarding the new model yielded below results from Industry :

Figure 2 : Chart Portraying the Opinoinnaire Results about the Framework

From the above figure, it is found that 47% of recruiters gave favourable approval, 44% of recruiters gave unfavourable approval, 7% of recruiters were neutral on the model, 2% did not solicit any response.

Further Direct Interviews with the sample population revealed that the recruiters who opined unfavourable and neutral conceded that the recruitment process has to be viewed as a commercial activity. Business Pressure as to new unit, expansion or filling vacant positions, client demands make them fill up candidates to meet timely targets overlooking about whether they have time to source the freshers from all colleges. They also opined Government to bring policies on campus recruitment in HEI's. The favourable recruiters however opined they welcome the initiative but needs considerable time to align CSR activities to the domain of HR Recruiting.

6. Conclusion :

The deep divide of Industry – Academia gap here could be widely witnessed projecting its dark effects on career opportunities of less fortunate students of Indian HEI campus left out of placement process due to recruiter's requirements. Therefore, we believe that model proposed in this research could do some justice to the students provided the recruiters embrace it. The Model is proposed keeping all stakeholders involved in mind and also intended to socially satisfy the young HR population of our country through seeking cooperation and support from recruiters.

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Paper 20

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON REGULAR AND DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Education is an integral part of human era. It helps in gaining knowledge and it changes the perspective of a person. We think logically and practically and then take decisions, as a result of which, we humans, are considered to be the most intelligent species on the planet. Education not only provides knowledge, but also contributes to the economic growth of a country and increases its stability. Since we all belong to different strata of the society, people go with a type of education which is suitable for them. According to the convenience of people, we have both regular and distance mode of education. In this paper, the Regular and Distance mode of education are compared based on their ability to provide quality and innovative post graduates in terms of quality, latest innovative curriculum, study materials, specialisations, programme duration, interactive sessions, flexibility, convenience, mentality of pupil and examination system and employability. Comparison is done by considering some of public and private universities who provide regular and distance post graduate education and their ability to add value to the programme with reference to quality, employability and convenience of pupil. Finally, merits and demerits of both regular and distance mode of education are identified and are listed under organisational, students, societal issues using focus group method.

Keywords: Regular education, Distance education, correspondence education, comparative study, education, interaction

1. INTRODUCTION:

Education is fundamental to human progress. It plays a major role in a development of an individual, a country, overall, a world. Every human needs to be educated. It makes him disciplined and social well being. Education system of India is similar to that of the Other South Asian countries. The components of our education system includes - regular program, correspondence program or distance program. Regular program consists of environment where students attend the class regularly and is being taught 6 to 7 hours a day, and then periodic exams are conducted by the college or university authority. The correspondence and distance education program means the same except for the fact that they differ in the methodology of teaching. A student pursuing correspondence program will be provided with the adequate study material and will be we asked to write the exams periodically. Here, no regular classes will be taken by any tutor to the students. Where as in the case of distance education 8 to 10 classes would be taken by the tutor online and the periodic examinations are conducted. Again, the classes here are not so regular like the regular education program. People pursuing correspondence or distance education program have an opportunity to work and learn simultaneously, that is they get paid and they need to pay.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Avani Trivedi , & Kalpana Gupte (2010) The article “**Quality Issues for Counselling in Open and Distance Learning in India**” is mainly intended to identify various aspects concerned with improving the quality of Counselling in Open and Distance Learning . The characteristics of distance education , the distance learner , the various mechanisms of learner support , the important role of the academic counselor in maintaining quality in distance learning are discussed and some measures are suggested based on TQM for maintaining the quality of counseling in distance learning with particular reference to IGNOU.[1]

Arun M. Sherry (2010) The author highlighted various benefits of distance mode of education and elaborates on how in a globalised society like that of India, the need for quality based higher education through distance learning mode is on constant rise. The author also examines various factors that are contributing to the growth of Management education through distance learning.[2]

Ashok Gaba and Shinja Koo (2007) The first part of the paper “**Research & Development of Distance Education in Asia: A Comparative Study between Korea National Open University, South Korea and Indira Gandhi National Open University, India**” compares the growth of distance education through analysis of the admission policies, enrolment trend, students support services and instructional system of both these institutions. The second part of the paper highlights the status, review and areas of research and research policies of these institutions. The findings of the paper are based on primary and secondary source of information.[3]

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the rate of regular and correspondence education obtained by the students in India.
- To evaluate the reasons of the rejection of correspondence education in India.
- To find the appropriate measures on how to equalize correspondence education with regular education.
-

4. METHODOLOGY:

The study on the above said objectives are based on secondary data. The conclusions drawn include details from authentic sources. This project consists of graphical representations and tables obtained from secondary data. Apart from this, expert in the area were consulted to arrive at a conclusion.

5. ANALYSIS:

According to the survey conducted during the year 2016 - 17 , by All India survey for higher education AISHE, 2,02,71,304 students have enrolled themselves under the regular education program, out of which approximately 23 lakhs students are pursuing post graduation program and 1,23,712 students pursuing PhD program. About 35,81,562 students have enrolled under distance education out of which 11,74,913 students have enrolled themselves in post graduation studies. In this analysis, the comparative study is done only for the post graduate programs of both regular and correspondence programs.

Table 01 – Enrolment of PG and UG in Regular mode of Education from 2012-2017.

ENROLMENT OF PG AND UG IN REGULAR MODE OF EDUCATION						
PROGRAMME		2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
UG	BA	7898579	9099473	9860520	9651891	9527060
	BSC	2947052	3579526	4299538	4618172	4978564
	BCOM	2810308	3117265	3381111	3422312	3484301
PG	MA	662839	674447	767027	878677	865410
	MBA	392587	392937	409432	416365	416490
	M.COM	179813	193373	222709	271266	275695
	M.SC	414316	431723	481330	519159	562896
	M.TECH	209720	260370	289311	257361	160888

Table 02 - Enrolment of PG and UG in Distance mode of Education from 2012- 2017

ENROLMENT OF PG AND UG IN DISTANCE MODE OF EDUCATION						
PROGRAMME		2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
UG	BA	1360044	1435302	1380114	1672872	1709590
	BSC	172442	272898	283185	201265	243606
	BCOM	372801	408957	460644	453274	507441
PG	MA	597170	729028	700338	652216	708599
	MBA	178742	165260	148895	132929	127275
	M.COM	86467	148419	147253	149447	171101
	M.SC	118150	125970	108962	96367	113938
	M.TECH	-	-	-	-	-

Fig. 01 – Comparison of Regular and Distance education for the year 2016 -17

From the above data it is clear that highest number of students prefer Regular education over Distance mode of education.

According to the present scenario, **A student with PG degree under any Open Universities are not preferred over the one with the same PG degree under regular University for**

teaching programs in both Government and private sector. So it is obvious that a student with the degree under Open University cannot become a teacher. Why is it so?

There are multiple reasons for this out of which some are being mentioned. These reasons are purely based on secondary data collected.

- It is assumed that students who have pursued their education under the correspondence program are introvert, they are thought to be less interactive as there are no interactive classes taken for them, which, makes them unable to teach.
- It is also presumed that these students lack practical knowledge when compared to other students who do their degree and the regular program.
- Most of them feel that students under correspondence program study only during exams and nearly attend any classes unlike the regular batch students who attend the class everyday and write their exams.

Validating the above said reasons, each one could be justified. As it is said, that a book cannot be judged by its cover, similarly, a person cannot be judged by his certificate. Just because a person has acquired education under correspondence program, it doesn't mean that he is an introvert. It is not always true that they lack practical knowledge and they are unable to teach. It depends from one person to another. And yes, every individual has a different capacity of gaining knowledge. It is not necessary that all the students under correspondence education need to study a day before and write the exams. This could be done by a student who has the capacity to cover the entire syllabus at a stretch irrespective of him or her studying in regular or correspondence program.

6. DISCUSSION:

Basically there are three types of education systems in India - regular education, distance education and correspondence education. All the three systems have similar materials for a student to study on a particular course but they differ in the methodology involved in learning.

Fig 02 –Different types Education systems.

In India, there are 903 regular universities, out of which, 15 Open Universities are established so far. The following table represent detailed distribution of the universities across India.

Table 03- Types and number of universities during 2017-18

Types of Universities	Number of universities in 2017 -18
Central Open University	1
Central University	45
Deemed Government University	33
Institution under state legislature act	5
Institution of National Importance	101
Deemed private University	80
State Private University	262
State Open University	14
State Public University	351
State Private Open University	1
Deemed University Government Aided	10
TOTAL	903

- ❖ **Central Open University:** Central universities or union universities in India is a public distance learning university established by an Act of Parliament. They are under the purview of the Department of Higher Education in the Union Human Resource Development Ministry.
- ❖ **Central University:** Central universities or union universities in India is a public learning university (distance / & regular) established by an Act of Parliament. They are under the purview of the Department of Higher Education in the Union Human Resource Development Ministry.
- ❖ **Deemed Government University :** As explained by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), "An Institution of Higher Education, other than universities, working at a very high standard in specific area of study, can be declared by the Central Government on the advice of the University Grants Commission (UGC), as an Institution 'Deemed-to-be-university'.[4]
- ❖ **Institution under state legislature act:** these contain institutions that are developed and run under state legislature act.
- ❖ **Institution of national importance:** it is a Public Higher Education institution which receives recognition and funding from the Government of India.
- ❖ **Deemed private University:** these universities are run under university grant commission and are approved as Deemed to be university.
- ❖ **State private University:** it is a private University which is run under the state government.
- ❖ **State Open University:** it is a University that runs distance education and the state government.
- ❖ **State public University:** it is the university e which is run by the state government and is of the public which is usually funded by national or sub-national government. In India, Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) , stands to be the largest University to provide distance education in the world, which is a state public University.

- ❖ **State private Open University:** it is a private University that provides distance education and is run by the state government.
- ❖ **Deemed university government aided:** it is a deemed university that is funded or aided by government.

As it is known every coin has two sides, our education programmes has both pros and cons.

Merits of regular education program include:

- ❖ Interaction - a classroom environment provides a better platform for one to share his opinion and to gain knowledge. A Regular programs makes one express his opinion and usually creates extroverts. Activities like seminars presentations discussions helps one to build his personality and makes them both physically and mentally strong and stable. It adds on to one's social behaviour.
- ❖ Clarification - it is easier for a pupil to clarify and clear his doubts then and there II in the classroom.
- ❖ Notes - on the regular basis of Pupil make sure that is notes is up to date.
- ❖ Schools for disabled - it is a great convenience for the special abled people. Disabled people require assistance which is provided by the regular schooling system.
- ❖ Social interaction. - Regular schooling helps one to gain many friends hence improving ones social interaction.

Demerits of regular education include-

- ❖ Providing education has become am your business. Our education system creates a lot of Machines but not what the creators. Students only depend on textbook and tutors for knowledge and do not approach themselves to study anything extra. This brings them a title of a perfect "bookworms".
- ❖ The selection process - the system of reservation has created quite a blunder in the regular education system. Reserved candidates have very low cut off, very low fee a great priorities because of which The talented individuals are left out.
- ❖ Syllabus - the regular education system consists of was syllabus which needs to be covered at a certain period of time. Hence, the teachers always in to cover the syllabus and rarely share things which are of great general knowledge.
- ❖ Homework: every Pupil in the regular education system is supposed to complete the homework which creates the burden in a pupil. These homework consists of writing pages and pages and nearly gaining knowledge. The result of this Bean we stop time burden to Pupil both physically and mentally and hatred towards this education system.
- ❖ Product of the education- it is said that India produces mostly service based students and not product based as we have lots of Service Company where as low levels of product based companies. We always lack in producing innovative products.
- ❖ Mentality of pupil towards the education system - students under regular education program nowadays have a mentality of just passing the University exams. The aim of this generation is to score good in the exams irrespective of whether he or she against the knowledge or not. Scores do not tell whether a person is knowledgeable or not.

Merits of Distance Education are:

- ❖ Saves time and money: Due to absence of regular class, time of the pupil is saved. Also, the fee for distance education is quite less as when compared to regular education.
- ❖ Preference of time for study: a student can easily fit into his time and study accordingly.

- ❖ Study from anywhere: A student can study from any place, according to his comfort zone.
- ❖ Flexible: Distance education offers flexibility than any other education system.

Demerits of Distance education includes:

- ❖ Feeling Isolated: Since distance education doesn't involve classroom environment, the pupil is readily to feel isolated.
- ❖ Lack of Oral communication Skills: absence of classroom environment and discussions has lead to a decrease in the oral communication skill.
- ❖ Need to have access to technology: To stay updated, a student needs to have a continuous access to internet and other technology.
- ❖ Doubts are not cleared immediately: Due to lack of interaction based classes, doubts of a pupil remain for a longer time.

7. SUGGESTIONS:

Evaluating all of the above gives rise to a question,- what could be done about to solve this? What could be the measures taken so as to equate regular program to correspondence program? Here are some of them. Again, these measures are truly based on the secondary data collected.

- In a country like India, nothing works without implementing the law. So, a suitable law must be implemented that equal opportunity must be given to the people who pursue their studies under the correspondence program. Only formulating law is not enough, it should be implemented effectively
- Both the mode of education must be given equal weightage by the universities and other organizations.
- Candidates must be selected for the particular designation based on his/her skills and knowledge rather than the mode of education.

8. CONCLUSION:

So far, we have seen how each education system has brought a great impact on us. Either way, both have their own merits and demerits. According to their convenience and needs, each prefers one of the systems. As witnessed through various studies, institution providing distance education programme also has comparable number of students pursuing their studies. Each mode of education has its own effectiveness which depends on mentality of the people and how they perceive it. Awareness about the qualities of each mode of education must be conducted so that society will give equal chance to both by analysing it.

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Paper 21

EFFECTS OF MUSIC ON COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF TEENAGERS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we describe the effects of music on cognitive development of teenagers. **Music is a form of art; an expression of emotions through harmonic frequencies.** Most music includes people singing with their voices or playing musical instruments, such as the piano, guitar, drums or violin. Music can be found in every culture all around the world. Music has become such a big part of our lives, that researchers can't help but want to study how music affects people, especially teenagers. Music affects various aspects of **cognitive development such as perception, memory, language skills, information processing, intelligence, reasoning and memory** etc. The purpose of this conceptual paper is to music involvement in teenagers lives to help develop memory, perception, language, vocabulary, spoken skills and reading skills. Music can helpful tool to enrich teenager's cognitive development. The effects of music on cognitive development of teenagers is elaborated with its aim, underlying principles and concepts, particular contextual features or challenging issues that have had to be addressed in detail.

Keywords : Music, Cognitive, Development, Teenagers, Skills.

1. Introduction

Music is a form of art; an expression of emotions through harmonic frequencies. Most music includes people singing with their voices or playing musical instruments, such as the piano, guitar, drums or violin. Music can be found in every culture all around the world. Music has become such a big part of our lives, that researchers can't help but want to study how music affects people, especially teenagers. Some researchers are interested in documenting effects that listening to music may have on teenager's cognitive development.

Our investigation of the literature on the effects of music in a teenagers life, inspired us to create a resource for families who wish to promote and support their adolescence interest in the arts, specifically music. The form of this resource was a print booklet that parents could use as a guide to local music options. We also gathered information through word of mouth, asking for information from the music department, and looking on the internet for other existing musical programs. We compiled all of the information and put them into five

categories: opportunities to observe music, ways to learn about music, informal ways to actively participate in music, ways to actively participate in a group setting, and places to get instruction. We provided a list of programs to get involved with, as well as a list of private instructors at the very end of the music guide. It emphasizes the importance of music involvement in teenager's lives to help develop memory, perception, language, vocabulary, spoken skills, and reading skills. We sought to educate and inform parents of the many ways that music can be a helpful tool to enrich teenager's cognitive development.

There is a need to study and test teenager's interest in music and its influences on the outcomes of teenager's academic performance. It would be intriguing if there could be an online network that would be setup for musicians and music organizations to collaborate and put themselves out there for the community, and to expand the music guide, adding to its resources. Although our guide does have some limitations, it is our hope that we educate parents and the community on the importance of music in teenager's lives.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Many parents, teachers, scholars, and businesses are interested in learning more about the influence of music on the cognitive development of teenager's. Teenagers could potentially be influenced by music in several ways. Some researchers investigate whether and how teenager's benefit from listening to music. Others focus on how formal music training impacts various aspects of cognitive development such as perception, memory, and language skills. Examination of the findings from each of these avenues of research can support teenager's learning.

Some researchers are interested in documenting effects that listening to music may have on teenager's cognitive development. One line of work in this area focuses on what teenager's learn about music itself by listening to music. Another line of work investigates how listening to particular forms of music may impact cognitive development outside of the musical domain. Explorations of the influence of experience on teenager's ability to match auditory and visual stimuli within the domain of music are an example of the first research direction.

While instrument identification does not have any implications outside of a musical domain, it leads to question whether listening to music has an effect on other areas of cognitive development outside of music. **Rauscher and Shaw (1993)** which found that **college students** who listened to Mozart's sonata in D major prior to taking a standard test of abstract spatial reasoning scored higher on tests of spatial intelligence than college students who listened to either some relaxing music or no music at all.

In contrast to the disputed nature of the **Mozart Effect**, research clearly reveals that music training has an influence on a variety of aspects of cognitive development in adolescence. There are many different types of musical skills a person learns when he/she is involved in musical training. For example, a musician needs to know how to physically play and work his/her instrument, or how to make vocal sounds the correct way. A musician also needs to know how to read music. In order to read music, a musician needs to know how to read different intervals between different notes on a staff and translate them to his/her instrument. The faster a person can read and interpret notes on a staff, the faster he/she can play his/her

instrument. Sight-reading is a skill that has to be practiced repeatedly in order to do it successfully.

The **cognitive processes of reading music also manufactures rhythm and structure**. In order to read music successfully, a musician needs to read the correct rhythms if the music is to be performed correctly. A musician also needs to pay attention to the meter, the tempo, the bar lines, and the phrases, which points to the overall structure of the music. Developing expertise in each of these areas enables a musician to put together a performance that is pleasing to not only the musician, but also to an audience. Music instruction is critical in helping musicians to develop these skills. An interesting question in the psychological literature is whether and how this type of training also impacts development more generally, such as within the areas of brain development perception, language, and memory.

Anvari et al. (2002) found that music skills were correlated with phonological awareness and early reading skills. The basic auditory skills for music perception were similar to early reading skills which shared some of the same auditory mechanisms that predicted reading ability.

Enhanced listening skills help develop linguistic organization. In a study **Milovanov, Tervaniemi, and Gustafsson (2004, as cited in Milovanov, Tervaniemi, Takio, & Hämäläinen, 2007)** suggest that there is a connection between music and language skill (Milovanov, Tervaniemi, Takio, & Hämäläinen, 2007). This led Milovanov, Tervaniemi, Takio, & Hämäläinen (2007) to believe that musical expertise might possibly affect the dominance of one side of the brain in controlling the musical and linguistic processing in the brain.

Southgate and Roscigno (2009) examined the relationship between music training and academic achievement among adolescents 13-17 years old. In order to measure this, they looked at music participation in three separate contexts: in school, outside of school, and parent involvement in the form of concert attendance. Looking at nationally representative data resources, the researchers found that music involvement had a positive association with grades and math and reading scores. What was concluded was that music is meaningful not as predictor of achievement but as a medium to support teenager's achievement.

3. Statement Of Problem

The aim of the study was to the Effects Of Music On Cognitive Development Of Teenagers.

Objectives

To assess the Effects Of Music On Cognitive Development Of Teenagers.

Operational definition

Music is a form of art; an expression of emotions through harmonic frequencies.

Cognitive development is a complex thinking of adolescence and they have ability to deal with formal logical operations such as perception, memory, language skills, information processing, intelligence, reasoning and memory , abstract thinking and aware of thought process etc.

4. Scope of the study

- **The relationship between music and the frontal lobes found that in general,** music increased activity within the left frontal lobes, which is associated with

happiness . This may in turn explain why music creates an environment with less tension. "Music in the classroom reduces stress, increases productivity, regulates energy, and creates a relaxed, supportive learning environment" (Davies, 2000, pg. 150). Along with this, 'there is clear evidence that music affects brain waves and physiological states," says Yoon. The influence of music on the stress levels of adult hospital patients. One group of anesthetized surgery patients listened to music on headphones while another group did not. The 'music' group had lower stress levels in the blood" (2000, pg. 24). This research may transfer to children and prove that children with anxiety may lower their stress levels when music is included daily in the learning process.

➤ **A connection between music and math** was also found during a **neurological research** study. It was documented that " higher brain functions of abstract reasoning as well as spatial and temporal conceptualization are enhanced by music activities. Activities with music can generate the neural connections necessary for using important math skills" (Church, 2000/2001 , p.50). Church also points out that "music is considered a right-brain activity. while math is a left-brain activity. When combined, the whole adolescent is engaged not only in the realm of thinking. but in all the other domains of social-emotional, creative and physical development" (2000/2001 , p.50).

➤ **Cognitive Growth Of Teenagers**

- a) Each Teenager's moves ahead at their own rate in their ability to think in more complex ways.
- b) Each Teenager's develops their own view of the world.
- c) Some Teenager's may be able to use logical operations in schoolwork long before they can use them for personal problems.
- d) When emotional issues come up, they can cause problems with a Teenager's ability to think in complex ways.
- e) The ability to consider possibilities and facts may affect decision-making. This can happen in either positive or negative ways.

➤ Using **music in the classroom for various reasons**, such as; decoding skills (because music and reading use sounds and symbols), listening skills (they both require imagination), rhythm skills, communication skills (verbal and written responses), vocabulary development (new words and meanings often encountered), expressive ability, memorization, and motor development through playing instruments and creative movement . Students can " rewrite the lyrics to familiar songs. Younger grades can work on phonological awareness by substituting individual rhyming words".

5. Limitations

The limitations of the study is as society and networking continues to progress, it would be interesting to see how this guide can further expand its' reach to other spheres like the Internet. It would be fascinating if there could be an online network that would be setup for musicians and music organizations to collaborate and put themselves out there for the community, and to expand the music guide, adding to its resources.

6. Conclusion

Music aptitude is associated with linguistic abilities, including phonological processing, facility with acquiring a second language, and in some instances, reading, whereas the notion of a special link between natural musical and mathematical abilities has virtually no empirical support. Moreover, many of the positive findings may be attributable to a more general association between music aptitude and cognitive functioning.

Music aptitude is associated with linguistic abilities, including phonological processing, facility with acquiring a second language, and in some instances, reading, whereas the notion of a special link between natural musical and mathematical abilities has virtually no empirical support. Moreover, many of the positive findings may be attributable to a more general association between music aptitude and cognitive functioning.

The research emphasizes the importance of music involvement in teenager's lives to help develop memory, perception, language, vocabulary, spoken skills, and reading skills. We sought to educate teenager's of the many ways that music can be a helpful tool to enrich their cognitive development. In addition, we created a resource for parents to help them easily find local musical opportunities with which to get their teenager's involved. These resources gives teenager's an opportunity to observe music, ways to learn about music, informal ways to actively participate in music, ways to actively participate in a group setting, and places to get instruction.

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Paper 22

**SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN HAZARDOUS
EMPLOYMENTS****Pradeep M. D.¹**¹Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University,
Mangaluru, Karnataka, India**Abstract**

Organization should provide safe and healthy environment to its employees. The Health and Safety Policies aims to create healthy work place by reducing hazards affecting the performance of employees. Hazardous working conditions will increase the health risks leading to high rate of absenteeism and attrition. Frequent exposure of the worker to the unhealthy working conditions slowly develops occupational diseases. Occupational hazards are the potential conditions both internal and external transforming into a series of events causing loss. Death, injuries and illness can arise out of safety violations or negligence. Safety is the protection against uncertain risks caused by the hazards of electricity, machinery, slip or trip, explosion causing injury, death or damage to people and property. This study aims to describe the fundamentals of industrial safety management for hazardous industries in India.

Keywords: Safety, Hazards, Occupation, Accident, Diseases, Negligence, damage.

1. Introduction:

Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing but not merely the absence of disease or infirmity according to the World Health Organisation. Industrial safety ensures protection against accidents and diseases occurring in the industrial establishment [1]. The basic elements of safety management covers the aspects risk, dangerous occurrences, accident, injury, disablement, Reportable Injury, Health, medical examination, occupational hazards covering chemical, biological, environmental and psychological, occupational diseases [2] prescribed under the Factories Act, 1948 vide Sections 89 and 90 [3].

2. Scope for Industrial Safety:

Accident is an unplanned and uncontrolled event resulting in an action or reaction resulting in the personal injury [4]. Disability caused by accident may be partial or total, fatal or non-fatal. Apart from mechanical failures, unsafe working conditions, ignorance and negligence of employee there could be multiple inter related causes contributing to the industrial accident [5]. The Industrial advancements are posting new dangers into the lives of workforce. The Factories act, The Indian Electricity Act, The Pesticides Act, The Boiler Act, The Environment Protection Act etc regulates the aspects of industrial safety. It is reported that in every twenty seconds of every working minute someone dies as a result of industrial accident [6]. Industrial activity exposes the employees into the threats caused by man, material and machines demands safety training to protect themselves from disabling injuries. Few causes for accident includes taking shortcuts, over confidence, incomplete instructions, poor housekeeping, ignorance, mental distraction, unplanned activities etc. Safety

programmes ensures zero physical hazards [7]. Accident Prevention is a Process to correct the unsafe working conditions in the industrial enterprises to prevent human suffering. The Bureau of Indian Standards is prescribing guidelines for recording any type of accidents [8].

3. Safety Analysis, Safety Audit & Safety Survey:

Job safety analysis is a technique to scrutinize the job tasks to identify various hazards to determine the relationship between the employee, assigned tasks, the machinery involved and the working environment to derive the possible risks. The identified uncontrolled hazards will be synthesized by reducing them to the acceptable risk level. Risk assessment is a legal requirement under regulation 3 of the Management of Health and Safety at Work, 1999 [9]. Job safety analysis is conducted for the job having highest injury rates, having high potential for severe injuries, possibility for human error is high which leads to severe accident, new processes and complex work profiles. Safety analysis conducts an observation on the each and every steps involved in the completion of assigned job to an experienced worker of the industry. The Potential hazards and unsafe acts are identified and communicated to such worker for further correction. A safety audit is a study of operations to determine actions required to render the potential hazards harmless. A safety audit is an inventory or checklists planned pertaining to an area on regular intervals to scrutinize the aspect of safety to correct the discrepancies [10]. The audit is conducted after conducting Preliminary visits to study the factory and identify audit elements, questionnaire is prepared, data is collected after discussion with the management, executives, workers etc., cross verification is performed at the site, perusal of records regarding previous accidents etc. are done, final report is prepared along with proper findings and suggestions. Safety Survey are made to have detailed observations of all types of unsafe physical and environmental conditions as well as unsafe practices committed throughout the industries. It can be done by statutory authorities, third parties or by internal personnel. Safety and health surveys in factories are conducted by CIF (Chief Inspector of Factories), DGFASILI (Director General of Factory Advisory Service and Labour Institute), Director of Health Services of Government of India or by anyone authorized by the above authorities

4. Safety Management:

Comprehensive Safety Approach should focus on revision of engineering, employee proneness, training, persuasion, appeal, discipline, design, construction, maintenance and operational procedures. As Prevention is better than cure, following measures can be taken to protect employee against occupational health hazards. It is recommended to conduct Pre-employment Medical examination, Periodic Post-employment Medical examination, Removal of hazardous conditions to the possible extent, Surveillance over special classes of workers including women and children, Emergency treatment in case of accidents, education of workers, first aid Training, Proper factory layout and illumination, effluent treatment plants, redesigning the job to eliminate monotony and fatigue and rescheduling of work etc. The accident prevention is possible through management efforts, safety measures, safety education, on the job training, publicity, safety inspections, safety audit, spot checking, inspection, enforcement, safety policy, safety committee, government support, feedback mechanisms etc.

5. Conclusion:

Industries are mostly concerned about cutting costs on all fronts to remain competitive instead of protecting the lives of workers. The ever increasing Mechanization, Electrification, Chemicalisation and sophistication have made industrial jobs more and more complex and intricate. This has led to increased dangers to human life in industries through accidents and injuries. An accident does not only result in the stoppage of work of a particular unit but disturbs the entire environment. It causes disturbance in the work pattern and tempo which is far more than the actual time loss or direct cost of an accident. Sometimes there is an erroneous notion that safety precautions are not compatible with higher productivity but, where managements have taken pain to reduce accidents which will increase the productivity and build industrial relations. In the twenty first century employee safety and health at work has grabbed the attention of psychologists who are concerned with controlling accidents through proper training and education of the workforce. It also focuses towards controlling the social and psychological factors that influence the workers behavior which lead for negligence at work place. Industrial stress caused by various Stressors such as task and role demands, organizational leadership, lack of group cohesion, intergroup and interpersonal conflicts, life and career changes, etc., lead to emotional disturbances which, in turn, lead to fatigue and exhaustion. All these affect health of employees. Safety responsibility is upon the shoulders of Plant Manager, production Manager, Chief Engineer, Personnel Manager, and Safety officer. In the twenty first century employee safety and health at work has grabbed the attention of psychologists who are concerned with controlling accidents through proper training and education of the workforce. It also focuses towards controlling the social and psychological factors that influence the workers behavior which lead for negligence at work place. It is difficult for Management to change the human nature, therefore, instead of trying to persuade employees not to make mistake try to remove opportunities for errors by changing the work situation, plant or equipment design and the method of working.

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Paper 24

A SURVEY ON VARIOUS MULTICAST ROUTING PROTOCOLS WITH AND WITHOUT CROSS LAYER TECHNIQUES IN MANET

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Abstract:

MANET is the wireless, infrastructure-less, continuously self-configuring network which plays an important role in the point-to-point communication and multipoint communication. Since unicast routing suffers from certain drawbacks, the Multicast Routing is introduced for the efficient and secured communication but it does not guarantee QoS. The Cross-Layer Multicast Routing is later introduced to increase the Quality of Services and for the effective communication. By using the CLMR Protocols, we can elicit the information from multiple layers and these can also be used to increase the performance of overall network. The CLMR uses several protocols which will increase QoS and increase the signal strength when compared to the nCLMR. This paper presents the survey based on various multicast routing protocols with cross layer and without cross layer techniques in MANET.

Keywords: MANET, communication, multicast, QoS, Cross- Layer

1 Introduction

Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET) is a collection of wireless mobile nodes that form a network dynamically without any support of central administration. It is self-organized network as it does not depend upon any infrastructure. Each device connected must forward traffic unrelated to its own use, and therefore be a router. If the network topology is changed, then their routing tables will also change. The mobile nodes can directly communicate with each other. And also some intermediate nodes are used to route the packets. The mobile ad-hoc networks are fully distributed and robust. Wireless applications, where sharing of information is mandatory, like Personal area networking, Military environments, Civilian environments and Emergency operations require rapid deployable and quick adoptable routing protocols, due to these reasons there are needs for mobile ad hoc network. MANETs are very flexible and can be established quickly and easily using low cost equipments.

MANET nodes are free to move in bidirectional and they move with the unpredictable time. In general two types of communications can be considered in classical MANETs, broadcast communications and multi-hop communications via routing protocols. Mobile Ad Hoc Networks are further

classified into three types. Vehicular Ad hoc Network (VANET), a subclass of mobile *Ad Hoc* network is a technology that uses moving cars as nodes in a network to create a mobile network. VANET enables effective communication with another vehicle or roadside equipments and responsible for smooth and secure vehicle behaviour across the roads. SPANs which stands for Smartphone Based Mobile Ad-Hoc Network which is the type MANET used across mobile phone devices by creating peer-to-peer network through the help of Wi-Fi and Bluetooth Technology.

2 Literature Review

Alaa Azmi Allahham and Muamer N. Mohammed, their study based on “Multipath Routing Protocol Based on Cross-Layer Approach for MANET”. Their work shows that the results show that the enhanced algorithm gives results better than the standard algorithm in terms of the routing traffic, delay. The constant motion of the nodes is one of the key challenges faced by MANET networks. The negative effects of not dealing with this challenge, such as: High consumption of bandwidth, overhead, delay and latency.

Qilin Wu, Xianzhong Zhou, Fangzhen Ge their study based on “A cross-layer protocol for exploiting cooperative diversity in multi-hop wireless ad hoc networks”. Their work shows that the Medium access control (MAC) and routing enabled cross-layer cooperative transmission (MACR-CCT) scheme uses the MAC and routing layer data for interference management. On the basis of intermediate distance and gain, relays are selected to forward the packets to multiple receivers. As compared to IEEE-802.11, CoopMAC, Reco-MAC, it supports delayed transmission with less error over a given range.

Deepika Vodnala, Dr. S. Phani Kumar, Srinivas Aluvala, their study based on “Analysis study on various Multicast Routing Protocols in MANET”. Their work shows that all multicast routing protocol tries to solve some problems, all of these routing protocols has their own advantage and disadvantages too. There is no any protocol founded yet that can be solving all ad-hoc network problems. Therefore, there are many issues in multicast routing protocol that can be discussed to develop the protocols to perform better multicasting in the future.

Lin Zhang, Zhao Wang, Ming Xiao, Gang Wu Shaoqian Li, their study based on “Centralized caching in two-layer networks: Algorithms and limits”. Their work shows that Cross-layer caching is a hybrid method which offers variable storage buffer for multiple receivers. The joint coaching method is used to determine the cache data over multiple layers. Acceptable level of cache gain rate is maintained for multiple users.

3. Review on Existing Protocol

3.1 PIM

Protocol Independent Multicast (PIM) distributes the multicast data using routes gathered by other protocols. PIM, which is a multicast routing protocol can use two information bases that are underlying unicast routing information base or a separate multicast-capable routing information base. It builds unidirectional shared trees rooted at a Rendezvous Point (RP) per group, and it will optionally creates shortest path trees per source. A PIM implementation is free to hold whatever internal state it requires and will still be conformant with this specification so long as it results in the same externally visible protocol behavior as an

abstract router. PIM has two tasks: To ensure that traffic from sources outside the PIM domain reaches receivers inside the domain. To ensure that traffic from sources inside the PIM domain reaches receivers outside the domain.

3.2 AMRIS

AMRIS is an on-demand protocol. To support multiple senders and receivers within a multicast session AMRIS construct a shared delivery tree. AMRIS is different compared to other protocols because each participant in the multicast session has a session-specific multicast session member id. AMRIS maintains a Neighbour-Status table which stores the list of existing neighbours and their multicast session member ids. Each node sends a periodic beacon to signal their presence to neighbouring nodes. AMRIS is designed to operate independently of underlying unicast protocols. AMRIS does not depends on the unicast routing protocol to provide routing information to other nodes.

3.3 ODMRP

On- Demand Multicast routing protocol (ODMRP) is a mesh based source-initiated protocol. It uses forwarding group concept and multiple paths exist between sender and receiver. It applies on-demand procedures to build route and maintain multicast group membership dynamically. By maintaining a mesh, instead of a tree, the drawbacks of multicast trees in ad hoc networks like frequent tree reconfiguration and non-shortest path in a shared tree are avoided. In ODMRP, group membership and multicast routes are established by the source on-demand. When a multicast source has packets to send but no route to the multicast group, it broadcasts a Join-Query control packet to the entire network. This control packet is periodically broadcast to refresh the membership information and updates routes.

3.4 PUMA

Puma is a receiver initiated routing protocol in which receivers join a multicast group using special address. The flooding of data or control packets is reduced using special address by all sources. Distributed algorithm is used to elect core among receivers of a multicast group. Multicast announcement acts as a single control message to perform all tasks in PUMA. In PUMA, core is responsible for creation and maintenance of mesh and forwarding the data packets. If the core node fails, core election takes place among the receivers. During the core election, energy of the receiver node is not considered.

3.5 MAODV

Multicast Ad-hoc On-Demand Distance Vector protocol is the extension to the Ad -hoc On-Demand Distance vector protocol. It has the capability of unicasting and as well as broadcasting. It can route the information using multicast routing. When a node wishes to join a multicast group then it originates a route request (RREQ) message and also if the node has some data to send to the group but it does not have a route to that group then also it does the same thing. Only the members of the multicast group respond to join RREQ.

Comparison of Existing Protocol:

PROTOCOL	MULTICAST TOPOLOGY	LOOP FREE	DEPENDENCE OF UNICAST	QoS	PERIODIC MESSAGE
MAODV	Tree	Y	Yes	No	Yes
PIM	Tree	Y	No	No	Yes
AMRIS	Tree	Y	No	No	Yes
ODMRP	Tree	Y	No	No	Yes
PUMA	Mesh	Y	Yes	No	Yes

4. Cross Layer

The Cross Layer is the technique where information sharing takes place between nonadjacent layers to optimize the overall performance of the network. By using the cross-layer interaction between layers many QoS parameters like energy, security, tree management cost and various control overhead can be optimized for improved performance. Cross-layer can be used to optimize the power for wireless links in such a way that maximum transmission range can be ensured.

Multicasting can reduce the communication cost. Cost of Tree-based routing operations is more expensive as compared to mesh-based operations due to complex multicast tree management iterations which consume multiple resources at the same time. Cross-layer multicast which can support the optimal tree operations w.r.t network resources as well as performance to meet QoS. The Cross Layer design is used to improve the QoS by reducing tree management cost and optimizing tree operations.

4.1 Cross-layer Multicast aware Routing (CLMR)

Cross-layer Multicast Link aware Routing (CLMR) exploits the information from PHY layer, Application, and Routing layer, to form a multicast group with the consideration of the following parameters:

a) Signal strength: If a non-member node wants to join the group, then it should have a better quality of signal strength which can be derived as:

$S_s = (S_t * G) / d_n * P_l$, Where S_s : Signal Strength, S_t : Packet transmitted with t signal strength, d_n : Distance between receiver node and the sender node.

b) Path loss: Path loss (PL) in wireless communication is a reduction in the power of a link. It is derived as:

$$PL = 20\text{Log}_{10}(d) + 20\text{Log}_{10}(f) + 32.44 -$$

$G(\text{Tx},\text{Rx})$, Where G: Gain, d : Distance from the transmitter, f: Signal Frequency, Tx: Gain by transmitter antenna, Rx: Gain by receiver antenna.

c) Link Life Time: It is defined as the maximum lifetime of the wireless link until a link breaks for a particular node.

Link Stability Factor (LSF) can be defined as: $LSF = \sum \text{Link - failure} / \sum T_i$, Where T_i is time interval.

d) Tree Link cost (TLC): Tree Link cost (TLC) is the cost which is required to maintain a tree link and it can be derived as,

$TLC = (rB + r_q B) / LC$, Where rB : the amount of bandwidth currently in use by existing connections, $r_q B$: the amount of bandwidth requested by the newly arriving group of participants, Link Capacity (LC): total bandwidth of the link.

e) Tree Update Ratio (Tur): It can be defined as the number of tree updates over a specific interval due to the Tree management Operations. It is derived as

$\sum Tur = \sum N_{tu} / \sum T_i$, Where Tur: tree updates ratio, N_{tu} : no. of tree updates, T_i : time interval

Comparison of Non-Cross Layer with Cross Layer:

PROPERTIES	nCLMR	CLMR
Throughput analysis	Less Efficient	More Efficient
Packet Delivery Ratio	Very Less	More
Routing Load	More	Less
End-To-End Delay	High	Low
Energy Consumption	High	Low
Tree Management Cost	More	Less
Mean Data Delay	High	Low

6. Conclusion

In this paper we can see that MAODV performed well using CLMR scheme which can be extended for other multicast routing protocols. CLMR builds the group using member nodes which have higher signal strength and energy level. MAODV without CLMR is less efficient in terms of throughput and Packet Delivery Ratio while with CLMR scheme its throughput and has increased up to a significant level. The Mean Data Delay, Energy Consumption, Tree Update Ratio, End To End Delay of MAODV, in case of nCLMR, it is higher as compared to CLMR. Without using CLMR, MAODV could not perform well and it has a less throughput and PDR due to extra control overhead. CLMR reduces the extra control overhead as well as the tree management cost thus results in improved QoS. Finally, it can be concluded that MAODV performed well using CLMR scheme which can be extended for other multicast routing protocols.

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Paper 25

MICRO HEALTH INSURANCE FOR THE POOR- A CASE STUDY OF SAMPOORNA SURAKSHA SCHEME IN MANGALURU CITY

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Abstract:

The greatest hurdle for poor families trying to be independent is the sudden incidence of serious illness requiring hospitalization. Today hospitalization expenses are so high which will drain the savings and push the poor to the vicious cycle of debt. Apart from medical expenses, other non medical expenses like, births and deaths also put them under severe financial crisis. Health is a right of everyone. The private companies offer different kinds of health insurance schemes with a premium which can't be afford by the poor sections of the society. Therefore micro insurance is one such scheme which will be exclusively helpful for the under privileged people in the country. The present case study focuses on the usage of the micro health insurance by the holders of the scheme. Study throws some light on the problems faced by the facilitators of micro insurance scheme. Data has been analysed by taking the beneficiaries of micro health insurance scheme sampoorna suraksha in Mangaluru city, of DK district. The findings of the study reveal that there is a maximum use of insurance scheme by the holders of the same. Micro Insurance schemes are functional mainly because of the NGOs. There is a need to support these NGOs to run these schemes in the long run in the most successful way. This can be made possible by providing them with financial assistance and help. But there can be some changes or developments done by government facilitate the continuity of the scheme.

Keywords : Sampoorna Suraksha, NGO, Health Insurance, Rural Poor, Women.

1. Introduction:

In India people in the below poverty line face a major financial crisis associated with health. Every serious illness, every accident and every natural disaster threatens the very existence of poor people and usually leads to deeper poverty in the rural India. The poor and rural population in India is still in worse economic conditions as compared to the urban population. They are exposed to various risks and their insurance requirements are not fulfilled easily as such. The development of a nation must consider and include all sections of the population of the nation.

As the major population of our country resides in villages and deprived of many facilities to grow and prosper, it is very necessary to take actions through various plans and policies to uplift them.

Poverty is not just a state of deprivation it is also backed by latent vulnerability. Micro insurance therefore, provides greater economic and psychological security to the poor as it

reduces exposure to multiple risks and cushions the impact of a disaster. There is an overwhelming demand for social protection among the poor. Micro insurance in conjunction with micro

Savings and micro credit could, therefore, go a long way in keeping this segment away from the poverty trap and would truly be an integral component of financial inclusion²

2. Micro Insurance in India:

Micro insurance business is usually done through intermediaries like non-government organizations, self-help groups or through microfinance institutions. The Government of India has taken initiatives through the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) under the IRDA Micro-Insurance Regulations, 2015. Traditional insurance companies do not like to approach this segment of society because of many reasons. Thus, Micro insurance is the solution for such people. The first and foremost priority of any Government is to eradicate the poverty of its population. In fact, in this move to reduce the poverty apart from the Government even the NGOs, Society and the corporate world are also expected to contribute in this move. In one-way poverty can be the best indicator showing the progress of any nation.

3. Sampoorna Suraksha as a Micro Health Insurance

Sampoorna Suraksha Group Health Insurance Programme is a unique and a great initiative of SKDRDP a large sized NGO based out of Dharmasthala, the abode of Lord Manjunatha Swamy and managed by Dr. D. Veerendra Heggade. “Sampoorna Suraksha” (total security) is a welfare scheme to give financial assistance to the poor people in their days of severe health problems necessitating hospitalization. In this programme members contribute to bring security to their insecure life during severe ailment/accident. The entire programme is designed on the basis of mutual help. Interested members of SKDRDP participate in this programme by contributing an annual subscription.

SKDRDP has tied up with the insurance companies for providing coverage of hospitalization expenses for the poor called Sampoorna Suraksha. This program collects pre-designated premium to provide hospitalization coverage, meet maternity expenses, death compensation, calamity compensation, domiciliary treatment and accidental coverage. Annual subscription is based on the premium quoted by insurance company for providing health cover.

In order to give opportunities to the housewives and unemployed young women in rural areas who have time and inclination to do social work, SKDRDP has developed a new cadre called the Sevaprathinidhi, who work in their spare time and support the SHG movement in the village. Most sevaprathinidhis are women and this has positively influenced women men ratio in the organisation.

Sampoorna Suraksha is a section 25 company and a subsidiary of SKDRDP. Apart from building the future for poor people, it's necessary to keep the present in good strength. Health Insurance is one such thing which builds strong foundation for the present state of affairs. In order to build a strong foundation Sampoorna Suraksha was established to give excellent medical facilities to poor people.

4. Literature review:

Pejawar, A. (2013)¹ explains that there is a synergy between banking industry and insurance industry. Using this synergy rural population can be provided with financial solutions. Its

possible with one stop shopping only. In rural areas the PSU banks and RRBs are the successful vehicles for the distribution of micro insurance.

Priyanka, P. (2013)² has explained the factors which hinders the performance of micro insurance in India. She feels under utilisation of distribution channels and mismatch of needs and the standard products also sometimes become the main problemes of micro insurance. For the inclusive growth its important for the insurance companies to reduce the costs which may be both managerial and financial. There is a lack of training among the agents of insurance companies. Insurance companies must invest in the training and development of these experts.

Pranav Prashad, J. L. (2014)³ explains the benefits of using mobile phones in the rural market for the promotion of micro insurance. It should increase the efficiency of transactions across the entire value chain, improving processes such as enrolment, premium collection, and claims settlement. Author presents several challenges that insurers and mobile network operators are likely to face as they venture into this space. The lack of distribution infrastructure, such as roads and payment platforms, has been a major barrier to the spread of micro insurance, with a significant amount of time, effort, and money required to collect and transfer information and administer products manually.

P K Rath, G. E. (2014)⁴ has given some suggestions to the financial institutions and insurers to approach the informal market. He feels it can be done by following any of these two ways they are either informalize the institutional set ups or tie up with another institution which is informal.

A relook at micro insurance, in essence, would call for a relook at insurance itself – which is about putting the power of mutuality to work, empowering people and communities towards managing lives and risks. Commercial insurers have a role to play as technical support providers and in building capacity and spread through reinsurance. Government may need to play a role in supplementing the community's pool and serving as an insurer of last resort in the event of ruin.

(Balakrishnan, 2015)⁵ has undertaken a study in Nagapattinam district of Tamil Nadu with the aim of evaluating micro insurance delivery mechanism. He has taken Dhan foundation and Avvai two institutions providing the scheme. It found out that the institutions increase the sale of policies and emphasizing renewals. The reasons are the institutions are facing the problems of either declining ratio of renewals to the number of potential renewals or decrease in the sale of policies. But organizations are successfully settling the claims. Challenges are educating the customers by creating the awareness of micro insurance.

Bhattacharya, A. (2016)⁶ feels that Micro insurance is the most underdeveloped part of microfinance. The drawback for the spread of micro insurance are low enthusiasm towards low income, lack of promotions, less benefits, conditions like exclusions for pre existing diseases.

The author feels that the root of success of these MIs is the insurance company's ability to accept the small payments of the beneficiaries. Sustainability of micro insurance schemes can be possible with good design and quality.

(Neelamegam, 2018)⁷ opines that the outreach of micro insurance product is severely hampered by the uncertain and low income of the poor. This paper brings to light the preference of low income customers for micro insurance policies in Kollam district, Kerala. Micro insurance company/ agent is required to know the preferences of prospective buyers of the policy. The analysis has brought to light that the preference for holding micro insurance

policy varies significantly in respect of area of residence, age, gender, educational level and annual income of policyholders.

5. Conceptual framework of Micro Insurance

There is no unanimously accepted definition of micro insurance inspite of vast usage across the stakeholders. The concept of micro insurance has also contributed by the concept of micro finance. There are different models of micro insurance given by different authors in their studies. Partner- agent *model* is one such model where insurer takes the help of MFIs for the distribution of micro insurance schemes. *Full service model* makes the scheme itself is in charge of design and delivery of products. There is advantage of full control. But there is higher risk on the provider of the same. The earlier Yeshaswini scheme is the example for this scheme.

Provider Driven Model is a model the healthcare provider is the micro insurance scheme, and similar to the full-service model, is responsible for all operations, delivery, design, and service.

Manipal health card is the example.

6. Meaning as per IRDA act 2015;

“Micro insurance policy means an insurance policy sold under a plan which has been specifically approved by the authority as micro insurance product Sec2(g)IRDA act.”

2(h) of the act defines Micro Insurance product as “any general micro insurance product or life insurance product or health insurance product , proposal form and all marketing materials in respect thereof.”

The below table shows the maximum coverage available for the micro non life insurance scheme

Type of Cover	Maximum Amount of Cover	Term of Cover Min.	Term of Cover Max.	Minimum Age at entry	Maximum age at entry
Dwelling and contents, or livestock or tools or implements or other names assets or crop insurance—against all perils	Rs.1,00,000 Per Asset/ Cover	1 year	1 year	N.A	N.A
Health Insurance Contract (Individual)	Rs. 1,00,000	1 year	1 year	Product specific	Product specific
Health Insurance Contract (Family/Group)	Rs 2,50,000	1 year	1 year	Product specific	Product specific
Personal Accident (Individual/Family/Group)	Rs. 1,00,000	1 year	1 year	Product specific	Product specific

7. Research Design:

The study is done by taking both primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from the beneficiaries of Sampoorna Suraksha in the past 3 years. Again data has been collected from the NGO by conducting an interview with the director of Sampoorna Suraksha. Secondary data has been collected from the research articles taken from the journals.

8. Sample size:

The Sample size of beneficiaries in Mangaluru is based on the number of members who claimed cashless benefits in the past 3 years. The total members who claimed cashless benefits in the last three years is 5153. So sample is taken at 1% of the 5153, which is 51.53 approximately 50 respondents.

9. Objectives of the study

1. To understand some economic status of beneficiaries of the scheme.
2. To find out the usage of the sampoorana suraksha scheme by the members in Mangaluru over the period of 3 years.
3. To understand the challenges faced by the NGO and the strategies to overcome the same

10. Analysis and Interpretation of data:

Tables showing the socio economic conditions of the beneficiaries of Micro health Insurance scheme.

1. Age and Poverty line of the users.

Age	Frequency	%	Poverty line	frequency	%
25 - 40	23	46	APL	9	18
41- 55	19	38	BPL	41	82
56 and above	8	16	Total	50	100
Total	50	100			

(primary data)

Interpretation; The above table shows that most of the the respondents are of 40yrs age group. There are 19 respondents coming within 41 to 55 age group which is 38%. There are a few respondents who are 56 and above, which is 16%. The above table also shows the standard of living of respondents through poverty line. 82% of the respondents come under below poverty line category. Only 18% of the respondents are coming under APL category.

2. Table showing employment status and annual income of the respondents.

Employment status	Frequency	Percentage
House Wife	17	34.0
Beedi Rolling	15	30.0
Coolie	4	8.0
Tailoring	1	2.0
Agriculture	1	2.0
Private Company	2	4.0
Others household work	3	6.0
Panchayath member	1	2.0
Cashew factory	6	12.0
Total	50	100.0

(primary data)

Interpretation: A 30% of members depend on beedi rolling. At the same time an equal percentage of respondents do not work. Next higher number of respondents work for cashew

factory, which is 12%. A small number of respondents depend on other jobs like coolie, working as maids, tailoring, agriculture.

3. Table showing the annual income of the family of respondents

Annual Income of the family	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 25000	2	4.0
25000-50000	17	34.0
50001-75000	9	18.0
75001-100000	5	10.0
more than 100000	17	34.0
Total	50	100.0

(primary data)

Interpretation: The above table shows that 34% of the respondents have got a family income which is ranging from 25000 to 50000. An equal number of respondents have family income which exceeds 1,00,000 rupees a year. A small number of respondents that's 4% have a family income less than rupees 25,000.

4. Table showing the source of income to pay the premium

Source Of Income	frequency	Percentage
own income	20	40.0
husbands income	19	38.0
Children's income	7	14.0
family income	4	8.0
Total	50	100.0

(primary data)

Interpretation: 40 percent of the respondents pay premium out of their own income. But an almost equal number of respondents depend on their husbands income to pay their premium, which is 38%. A very few respondents depend on their children and family to pay the premium.

5. Table showing the number of times the benefits has been received by the members in the last three years.

Time	Frequency	Percent
once	21	75
twice	6	21
four times	1	4
Total	28	100.0

(primary data)

Interpretation: the above table shows the total number of members who received the claim for themselves. Which is 28 members out of 50. Out of which 75% of members have received the claim only once. 21% of the respondents have received the claim twice and only 4% of the members have received the claim for four times in the last three years.

6. Table showing different types of diseases the insurance is used for by the respondent for their own purposes.

Disease Family	Frequency	Percentage
Medical conditions (primary+secondary+ Acute)	15	54
Accidental injury	1	4
Surgeries minor	6	21
Major surgeries	4	14
ENT	-	-
Maternity	2	7
	28	100

(primary data)

Interpretation: The above table indicates that 54% of the respondents have utilised the scheme for treatment of medical conditions. Which includes primary, secondary, acute and chronic. 21% of them have utilised for minor surgeries. 14% of them have utilised the scheme for some major surgeries. Only 7% of them have taken the benefit for delivery. 4% of them have utilised the scheme under accidental surgeries.

8. Table Showing out of pocket expense incurred by beneficiaries.

Out of pocket	Frequency	Percent
nil	9	32
less than 5000	10	36
5001-10000	5	18
10001-15000	2	7
15001-20000	2	7
Total	28	100

(primary data)

Interpretation: The above table indicates that out of the total number of respondents who utilised the services for self only 9 of them got the full amount claimed which is 32%. There are 10 respondents who incurred expense less than 5000 which is 36%. 18% of them incurred expenses within 10000. Only 7% of the respondents have incurred OOP between the range of 10000 and 20000.

9. Table showing the usage of insurance scheme for different diseases by the family members of the respondents

Disease Family	Frequency	Percentage
Medical conditions (primary+secondary+ Acute)	18	53
Accidental injury	2	6
Surgeries minor	7	21
Major surgeries	2	6
ENT	2	6
Maternity	3	8
	34	100.0%

(primary data)

Interpretation:

The above table indicates 34 respondents used the scheme for their family. Out of which 53% of respondents who have used the insurance scheme for the purposes of medical conditions such as primary, secondary, acute sickness which requires only a medical treatment. 21% of the respondents have taken the benefits of insurance scheme for the purpose of minor surgeries. 6% of them have used the scheme for major surgeries, accidental treatments and ENT. 8% of the respondents have used the scheme for the purpose of maternity of their family members.

10. Table showing bill amount exceeding the claim amount in case of family use.

Amount in excess of the claim	Frequency	Percent
nil	19	56
less than 5000	7	20
5001-10000	3	9
10001-15000	1	3
15001-20000	1	3
25001-30000	2	6
more than 50000	1	3
Total	34	100

(primary data)

Interpretation:

The above table indicates that 56% of the respondents said that they did not pay any additional in excess of the claim. 20% of the respondents have paid the extra charges which is less than 5000 rupees. 9% of the respondents incurred the amount between 5000 and 10000. There is 6% of the respondents who paid the amount which is within 25000 and 30000. 3% of them have paid between the range 10000 to 20000. 6% And again 3% of them paid more than 50000.

Problems faced by the NGO :

1. To give awareness among the rural poor. As these types of schemes are offered to the poor section of the society who are generally less educated and from rural background. Giving them awareness about the scheme itself is a tedious job for the NGOs. This requires additional effort on the part of NGOs to appoint additional staff to go to the field and render services to the rural people at their doorsteps.
2. To make sure that the scheme sustains in the long run. As the premiums are increasing because of increase in the cost of health expenses, it's difficult to survive in the long run. This is because the beneficiaries are in low income category.
3. There is no additional income from micro insurance schemes. Rather there is an additional cost of overhead on the NGOs. It's social service offered by the NGO, SKDRDP which no other institution must have done. Because this institution is one of the largest and oldest of some other NGOs in Karnataka, it's possible for the institution to run the scheme successfully for many years.

4. There is no additional funding by the government to run this scheme in the long run. NGOs do not get any monetary assistance from the central or state government to pay for their additional cost of overheads.
5. Difficulty in settling grievances. Some times the NGO finds it very difficult to convince and console the members who come with some complaints. Its because the rural illeterates are not able to understand the technicalities of insurance.

Findings of the study

1. The study reveals that most of the respondents fall within the age group of 40 ears and many of them come under BPL category.
2. Most of the respondents are financially self dependent. We can see that out of 50 respondents only 17 members, which is 34% of them do not go for any kind of job. Remaining 33 respondents or 66% of them are into something or the other. But mostly coolie work.
3. Most of the members annual income comes within the range of 25000 to 50000, which is 34%. There is another 34% of them are having a family annual income which is more than rupees one lakh. It's a very good sign that a very few respondents have an annual income of less than 25000, which is 4%.
4. There is a highest percentage of respondents, which is 40% paying the insurance premium by themselves. They do not depend on others income to pay for the premium. There is a good number of respondents depend on their husbands income to pay the premium of the insurance which is at 38%. Then the samll number of respondents depend on either their children's oncome or on the income of any other family member.
5. In last three years 75% of the respondents have availed the benefits of insurance only once in the last three years. Means others might have used the scheme for family members. 21% of them have utilized the scheme twice and only one respondent has used the scheme for four times.
6. The study reveals that, most of the respondents have used insurance claim for the medical treatment, which is at 54%. This means the respondents have used the services either for primary or secondary or acute or chronic health condition which required only a medical treatment. These sicknesses include cold, fever, asthma, pneumonia and some other ailments which requires only a treatment and not the surgery. 21% of them have used the benefits for minor surgeries and 14% of them have used the benefits for major surgeries. 7% of them have used the services for maternity purposes.
7. The study reveals that out of total number of 28 respondents who utilised the services for self there 32% percentage of respondents who did not get to pay any amount extra out of pocket. 36% of them incurred OOPE, which is very small amount of less than 5000. 18% of them incurred the additional expenses within the range of 5000 and 10000. A small number of respondents had incurred amount which is within 10000 to 20000 out of pocket expense.
8. The family members of the respondents have also availed the benefits of health insurance many times for the purposes of treatment of medical conditions, which is 53% of the respondents. About 21% of the members have utilised the services for minor surgeries, 6% of the respondents have utilised the benefits for major surgeries. Around 8% of them have utilised the services for the purpose of maternity.
9. The study reveals that, out of the total number of 34 respondents who availed the benefits for their family members, there is 56% of the members, did not pay any excess amount from their pocket. 20% of them have paid an amount which is less than 5000. 9% of them paid within the range of 5000 and 10000. 6% of them have incurred extra expense within the

range of 25000 to 30000. There is only one respondent who had paid an amount exceeding 50000 rupees.

Suggestions and strategies to overcome some of the problems.

1. In order to make the scheme available to all it's important to keep the premium at low. This can be possible by the interference of the government.

Strategies :

Government can introduce some remedial measures to overcome the problems faced by these micro insurance schemes.

a) Provide financial to the NGOs. As micro insurance schemes

b) At the same time its beneficial if government removes the service tax levied on the premiums.

c) Bring the cost of medical education under control. It's possible by reducing the fees charged by the medical institutions.

d) Bring the hospital rates under control: we can see that different hospitals charge different fee for the same treatment. There should be a rate fixed by the government for the different treatments.

2. Creating awareness among the rural poor as most of them are illiterates.

3. Suggestions to users of the scheme:

a) Reduce unnecessary admissions and diagnosis in the hospitals. As some hospitals tries to grab as much as possible from the patients, if they have an insurance.

b) Willingness to pay: its possible to run the scheme if the poor people have willingness to pay the premium. There are some cases in the rural as well as urban poor that they are not ready to pay even if they can afford to pay. but there are some poor who feel secured if they have insurance. Therefore they are ready to pay the premium even if they are not able to pay.

Conclusion:

Micro insurance business holds a lot of potentials to expand and develop in India. However, the insurers must take into account the specific needs of the clients and formulate a proper solution to meet their needs at a reasonable price to the rural population. The risk assurance or risk cover offered to the clients must be easy to understand and simple to follow without any hassles as the rural clients are generally illiterate. NGOs are the reasons for the existence of micro insurance schemes in the rural India. There should be a mechanism where government also becomes the part of micro insurance schemes.

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Paper 25**STUDENTS SATISFACTION LEVEL IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTES-A STUDY OF PUBLIC INSTITUTES IN MANGALORE CITY.****Ms. Sulfathu Nafila MK*, Ms. Shreeraksha****

II M.Com

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Abstract:

Students' satisfaction has never been considered as an issue of importance by educational authorities nor regarded as a matter of survival by higher education institutions. The measurement of student satisfaction can be useful to higher education institutions, to help them to pin point their strengths and identify areas for improvement. The study measures the students' satisfaction level in higher educational public institutes in Mangalore City. Satisfaction ratings go beyond teaching assessments, which have a narrow focus, to include broader aspects of the student learning experience. To grasp the complexity of that learning experience, it is not enough to know the degree to which students are satisfied, it is important to understand the factors that contribute to student satisfaction. The purpose of this study is to identify aspects of the educational experience that are associated with students' overall expression of satisfaction and determining which features of the student experience are most closely related to satisfaction may provide information about actions that can be taken to maintain high levels of satisfaction and improve student learning.

Keywords: Higher Education, Public Institutes, Students Satisfaction.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Education sector is expanding very rapidly all over the world in recent years. Globalization and digital revolution has created a demand for new and varied disciplines in education. The cost of providing education has gone up manifold due to better teaching methodologies and learning instruments with rising inflation worldwide. Higher education is the education at a college or university level is perceived as one of most important instruments for individual social and economic development of a nation. The primary purpose of higher education is creation of knowledge and dissemination for the development of world through innovation and creativity. Students' satisfaction as a short term attitude, resulting from an evaluation of a students' educational experiences, services and facilities. It is a positive antecedent of student loyalty and is the result and outcome of an educational system. It's a students' disposition by subjective evaluation of educational outcomes and experience. Therefore, student satisfaction can be defined as a function of relative level of experiences and perceived performance about educational service during the study period.

2. OBJECTIVE & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The objective of the study is to measure the students’ satisfaction level in higher educational public institutes in Mangalore City. This research study was done through collection of 65 respondents from Mangalore City. The research instrument used in collecting primary data was a questionnaire and survey was conducted through the means of Google form. For secondary data other sources like PDF files and internet has been used.

3. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study was restricted only to the Mangalore city.
- The study was conducted through Google form; hence it could reach technologically literate people.
- There can be chances of bias in the response given by the respondents.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Teachers Regularity.

	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied		
Satisfied		
Neutral		
Dissatisfied		7.7
Highly dissatisfied		

Table 1: depicts the students’ satisfaction regarding regularity of teachers. 38.4 percent students are highly satisfied with regularity of teachers while 40 percent students are satisfied with teacher’s regularity. 13.9 percent students are neutral and 7.7 percent students are dissatisfied with teachers’ regularity. No student is highly dissatisfied with teacher’s regularity.

2. Teacher’s Behavior in the Classroom.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	16	24.7

Satisfied	31	47.7
Neutral	10	15.3
Dissatisfied	8	12.3
Highly dissatisfied	-	-
Total	65	100

Table 2: describes the teachers' behavior towards students in the classroom. 24.7 percent students are highly satisfied and 47.7 percent students are satisfied with teachers behavior in the classroom whereas 15.3 percent students are neutral.12.3 percent students are dissatisfied with teacher behavior in the classroom and no student is highly dissatisfied with teachers' behavior in the classroom.

3. Well Equipped Labs.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	7	10.7
Satisfied	9	13.8
Neutral	27	41.5
Dissatisfied	11	17
Highly dissatisfied	11	17
Total	65	100

Table 3: shows the students satisfaction regarding labs. Only 10.7 percent students are highly satisfied and 13.8 percent students are satisfied with the labs whereas majority of the students (41.5) are neutral. 17 percent students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with labs in the institute.

4. IT Tools (projector, computer, digital board).

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	9	13.8
Satisfied	10	15.4
Neutral	18	27.7
Dissatisfied	18	27.7
Highly dissatisfied	10	15.4
Total	65	100

Table 04: describes the students' satisfaction regarding the availability of IT tools. A few students (13.8 percent) are highly satisfied and 15.4 percent students are satisfied with availability of IT tools in the public institutes. 27.7 percent students are neutral. Majority of the students (27.7 percent and 15.4 percent) are dissatisfied and highly dissatisfied regarding availability of IT tools in the institutes.

5. Parking Space.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	28	43.0
Satisfied	21	32.4
Neutral	10	15.4
Dissatisfied	3	4.6
Highly dissatisfied	3	4.6
Total	65	100

Table 05: highlighted the students' satisfaction regarding the parking space. Majority of the students (43 percent) are highly satisfied with the parking space 32.4 percent students are satisfied with the parking space whereas 15.4 percent students are neutral. A very few students (4.6 percent) are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with the availability of parking space.

6. Course Fee-Structure.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	19	29.3
Satisfied	28	43.0
Neutral	14	21.7
Dissatisfied	2	3.0
Highly dissatisfied	2	3.0
Total	65	100

Table 06: shows the students satisfaction regarding the course fee structure. 29.3 percent students are highly satisfied with the course and 43.0 percent students are satisfied with the course fee while 21.7 percent students are neutral. A very few students (3.0 percent) are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied regarding course fee structure.

7. Library Facility.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	10	15.4
Satisfied	26	40.0
Neutral	10	15.4
Dissatisfied	13	20.0
Highly dissatisfied	6	9.2
Total	65	100

Table 07: describes the students' satisfaction regarding the library. 15.4 percent students are highly satisfied and 40.0 percent students are satisfied while 15.4 percent students are neutral with the library facility provided by the institutes. Only 20.0 percent students are dissatisfied and 9.2 percent students are highly dissatisfied with library facility in the institute.

8. Placement Facility.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	7	10.8
Satisfied	10	15.4
Neutral	28	43.0
Dissatisfied	10	15.4
Highly dissatisfied	10	15.4
Total	65	100

Table 08: Shows the students satisfaction regarding the placement. Only 10.8 percent students are highly satisfied and 15.4 percent students of public institutes are satisfied with the placement provided by instituted whereas 43.0 percent students are neutral. 15.4 percent students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with the placement facilities provided by the institutes.

9. Sports and Games Facility.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	3	4.7
Satisfied	10	15.4
Neutral	17	26.1
Dissatisfied	28	43.0
Highly dissatisfied	7	10.8
Total	65	100

Table 09: describes the student's satisfaction regarding the sports facilities. Only 4.7 percent students are highly satisfied and 15.4 percent students are satisfied regarding sports facilities while 26.1 percent students are neutral. Majority of the students (43.0 percent)

are dissatisfied and 10.8 percent students are highly dissatisfied.

10. Extra-Curriculum Activity.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	4	6.1
Satisfied	18	27.7
Neutral	18	27.7
Dissatisfied	17	26.2
Highly dissatisfied	8	12.3
Total	65	100

Table 10: depicts the students’ satisfaction regarding extra curriculum activities in the institutes. 6.1 percent students are highly satisfied while 27.7 percent students are satisfied regarding extra curriculum activities in the institutes. 27.7 percent students are neutral. 26.2 percent students are dissatisfied and 12.3 percent students are highly dissatisfied regarding extra curriculum activities in the public institutes.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- From our study we found that majority of the teachers are in public institutes regular.
- We got to know that majority of the students are satisfied and highly satisfied with teachers behavior in the classroom.
- From our study we found that lab facility is not up to the mark in public institutes.
- It is found that majority of the students are not satisfied regarding availability of IT tools in public institutes.
- We also realized that there is no problem of parking space in public institutes.
- It is found that majority of the students are satisfied or highly satisfied regarding fee structure in public institutes.
- Besides, we came to know that majority of the students are satisfied with library facility in the public institutes.
- On the basis of analysis it is found that majority of the respondents in public institutes are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with placement facility.
- We could also understand that majority of the students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied from the sports facilities provided by the public institutes.
- This study also highlights that majority of the students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied regarding extra curriculum activities in the public institutes.

SUGGESTIONS

- It's suggested that public institutions have to focus more and more on extra curriculum activities to develop each and every individuals.
- It's suggested that computer labs and science labs are should be expand to get more opportunity for the students to concentrate more on their practical studies.
- The public authorities need to be provided with adequate facilities and resources for effective implementation of IT tools.
- It's suggested that public institutions have to provide proper facility for sports and games thereby students can concentrate on extra curriculum activities.
- It's suggested to organize placement programs to get job opportunity to the students.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that in public institutes students are satisfied or highly satisfied with teacher's regularity, their behavior, Parking space in the institute, Fee structure of the course and Library of public institutes. On the other hand students express their dissatisfaction regarding labs, IT tools, Placement, Sports facilities and extra curriculum activities in public institutes.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Name
2. Age
3. Gender
4. How you feel about teacher's regularity in the classroom?
 - Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
5. And about teachers behavior in the classroom?
 - Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
6. How you experienced about well equipped labs?
 - Highly satisfied

- Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
7. Satisfaction on implementation of IT tools in the classroom?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
8. Satisfaction about parking space?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
9. Satisfaction on course fee-structure?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
10. Library facility provided by the public institution?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
11. Placement facility organizes by public institutes?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
12. Facilities given by public institutes for sports and games?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied

13. Satisfaction on extra-curriculum activity?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
14. Suggestions if any.

Paper 26**ACCOUNTING STANDARDS AND FINANCIAL STATEMENTS OF MANGALORE CHEMICALS AND FERTILIZERS LTD AND KARNATAKA BANK LTD****Ms Sandhya Rani*, Caroleena Janefer****

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Abstract:

A company consists of varied number of users who contribute for the growth and prosperity of the organization. It is the duty in the part of the company to be accountable to such users. This can be achieved by summarizing the working of the organization in terms of monetary value in its financial statements. It is required to maintain these financial statements in a way which is acceptable and understandable to all the users of financial statements. This paper is based on the implication of accounting standards on the company's two different sectors, Mangalore Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd and Karnataka Bank Ltd.

Keywords: Accounting Standards, Financial Statements.**1. INTRODUCTION**

A company consists of varied number of users who contribute for the growth and prosperity of the organization. It is the duty in the part of the company to be accountable to such users. This can be achieved by summarizing the working of the organization in terms of monetary value in its financial statements. It is required to maintain these financial statements in a way which is acceptable and understandable to all the users of financial statements.

2. CONCEPT OF ACCOUNTING STANDARDS

Accounting Standards (ASs) are written policy documents issued by expert accounting body or by government or other regulatory body covering the aspects of recognition, measurement, presentation and disclosure of accounting transactions in the financial statements. The ostensible purpose of the standard setting bodies is to promote the dissemination of timely and useful financial information to investors and certain other parties having interest in the company's economic performance. Accounting Standards reduces the accounting alternatives in the preparation of the financial statements within the bounds of rationality, thereby ensuring comparability of financial statements of different enterprise.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the disclosures specified of the Accounting Standards adopted.
2. To find out the changes in the applicability Accounting Standards in past 5 years.

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Accounting standard has known is a varied concept consisting of 27 different standards applicable for different incomes and expenses. This study is based on the implication of such accounting standards on the company's two different sectors. The jurisdiction of study is in the city of Mangalore. The first is the study on 'Mangalore Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd, Mangalore' which is manufacturing company on fertilizers. The second is on 'Karnataka Bank Ltd' a banking company

1. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY OF STUDY

1. Primary data: Financial statements obtained from the annual report of the company
2. Secondary data: Files, books, journals and periodicals, manuals and text book. Which have already been passed through the statistical process are the secondary data used.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The **Author Bhattacharyya** in his **book Indian Accounting Standard** explains about different accounting standards, conceptual framework and presentation of balance sheet and also the profit and loss account. In the first chapter, the author mentions about the Accounting Standards Board (ASB) which was issued by ICAI in the year 2000. Further the author speaks about the purpose of framework issues by ASB, the concept of financial reporting and financial statements. For the preparation of the financial statements there is mainly three assumptions- accrual concept, going concern, consistency. In the second chapter, it states that the presentation of the financial statements, stipulates that a complete set of financial statements consists of balance sheet, income statement, a statement showing changes in equity, cash flow statement and accounting policies and explanatory notes.

The authors **Bruce Bennett, Michael Bradbury and Helen Prangnell** in their journal (Volume 42) place a distinction between rules based and principles based standards is not well defined and is subject to a variety of interpretations. Yet there is a commonly held view that the FASB's standards are rules based and the IASB's standards are principles based. This article identifies the basis of this distinction. For research and development, the article compares the FASB standard with two principles based standards. For each standard we identify and classify rules and judgments, and observe the level of justifications for the rules and assistance to support the judgments. The three standards have rules, are based on principles, and require the exercise of professional judgment; the less conservative standard requires more judgments and, unexpectedly, more rules. The results suggest that the rules based versus principles based distinction are not meaningful, except in relative terms. They conclude that a relatively more principles based standards regime requires professional judgment at both the transaction level (substance over form) and at the financial statement level ('true and fair view' override). Furthermore, it is suggested that any FASB and IASB convergence will require agreement on the weightings given to the qualitative characteristics.

3. FINDINGS

In case of Mangalore Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd-

1. AS1: The similar accounting policies followed by the company for five financial years are use of estimates, borrowing costs, valuation of inventories, foreign currency transactions, revenue recognition, depreciation, leases, earnings per share, intangible assets retirement benefits, taxes, intangible assets, non-financial assets, segment reporting etc.

2. AS2: Inventories are valued lower of cost and net realizable value for all the five financial years. The disclosure of inventory values in detail helps the users of the financial statements in ratio analysis in the financial statements.

3. AS3: Mangalore chemical and fertilizers Ltd follow 'indirect method' of preparation of cash flow statement for all the five years. It divides the statement into three parts that is cash flow from operating activities, cash flow from investing activities, cash flow from financial activities.

4. AS9: The company follows the same principal of revenue recognition for all the five years. Revenue in case of manufacturing company is in form of sale of goods, interest, grants or subsidies received and such other form.

5. AS10: In the statements of the company fixed assets are capitalized at cost, inclusive of financial charges on borrowed funds related to acquisition of fixed assets, depreciation (then AS-6) on fixed assets is calculated on straight line method as per the rates prescribed under Schedule XIV of the Companies Act, 1956. Written down value of insurance spares is charged off in the year of replacement of the existing part in the fixed asset.

6. AS13: The schedules of the company state that the in long term investments are valued at cost. Provision on diminution of long-term investments is deducted from such value of investments.

7. AS15: The benefits given by the company for its employees includes provident fund, gratuity, superannuation fund, pension scheme, leave encashment benefits for the five financial years.

8. AS18: The company has many related parties in their organization which includes associates, holding company, key managerial personnel.

9. AS19: The bank calculates its basic and diluted earnings per share. The EPS has decreased over the years up to the financial year 2016-17 and has increased for the financial year 2017-18.

In case of Karnataka Bank Ltd-

1. AS1: The similar accounting policies followed by the bank for five financial years are revenue recognition, investments, derivative contracts, advances, fixed assets, depreciation, foreign currency transactions, employee stock options, employee benefits, segment reporting, share issue expenses, earning per share, taxes, provisions and net profit.

2. AS2: This accounting standard is not applicable for a banking company as it is not in the line of business of production and manufacturing of goods.

Hence Karnataka Bank Ltd has no inventories in the balance sheet as they are into borrowing and lending of funds.

3. AS3: Karnataka Bank follows indirect method of preparation of cash flow statement. It divides the statement into three parts that is cash flow from operating activities, cash flow from investing activities, cash flow from financial activities.

4. AS9: The main sources of revenue are: interest on loans, interest on investments, fees income, FOREX operations etc. Income is accounted for on an accrual basis except in respect of income from non-performing assets, commission, exchange, Funded Interest Term Loan (FITL) and rent on safe deposit lockers, which are all accounted on cash basis.

5. AS10: The main two assets in the bank are premises and other fixed assets which includes furniture and fixtures. Land and building are capitalized based on conveyance or letter of allotment or physical position of the property. Software is capitalized along with computer hardware and included under Other Fixed Assets. Depreciation is charged on the basis of Written down Value as per schedule XIV. Premium paid on lease hold properties are charged off over the lease period.

6. AS13: Investments are classified under the heads 'Head to Maturity', 'Available for Sale' and 'Held for Trading' categories and valued under RBI guidelines. The value, net depreciation is shown in Balance Sheet. The investments of a banking company may be categorized into two: one investment made within India and other investments made outside India.

7. AS15: The statement states that the contribution made by the bank to Provident Fund and Contributory pension scheme is charged to profit and loss account. Contribution to the recognized Gratuity Fund, Pension fund and en-cashable leave are determined and recognized in the accounts based on actuarial valuation at Balance Sheet. Provision for short term employee benefits are accounted for on estimated basis.

8. AS18: There are no related parties as such in case of banking companies except that it contains of key management personnel. The company has no holding or a subsidiary company with whom it has trading relations.

9. AS20: The bank calculates its basic and diluted earnings per share. The EPS is increased for the year 2014-15 and gradually decreased for the next three years.

10. SUGGESTIONS

1. The company needs to mention in detail the accounting standards adopted and if not the reasons for it.

2. The form of disclosure of one year should be the same in the upcoming years.

3. It is observed that the closing balance of previous year do not be the same opening balance in the next year. The changes in such amount should be disclosed.

4. The presentation of notes to accounts differs from year to year leading in difficulty in analysis.

5. The company should note that the disclosure procedure used should be understood easily by a layman who does not have accounting knowledge.

6. It is seen in the project; the data of previous year differs when it is consolidated and written with the figures of the next year. The company should disclose the reasons for such changes.

11. CONCLUSION

After this study it can be conclude that-The accounting standards adopted are different in manufacturing sector and different in banking sector.It is compulsory for the company to follow the rules of the accounting standards given by ICAI as it helps in better presentation, analysis and comparison of data.Any change in accounting standards should be implemented by the company in its books of accounts within the time frame given by the board.Knowledge of Accounting Standard in the company helps in better presentation of the financial data.

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Paper 27

HOW DOES THE TRANSFORMATION OF AN AVATAR FACE GIVING A FAVORABLE IMPRESSION AFFECT HUMAN RECOGNITION OF THE FACE?

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Abstract:

We investigated how different appearances in the favorable impressions of 3D avatar faces affect face-recognition performances by humans. We conducted an encoding and testing experiment using synthesized facial images and artificially manipulated the strength of the perceived impressions in three different dimensions. We also subjectively assessed the favorability of the synthesized faces that were used as visual stimuli in face- recognition tests and found that facial transformation, which decreased the favorability impressions, generally deteriorates human face-recognition performance.

Keywords: Social impression of face, morphable 3D facemodel, facial impression manipulation, Thurston's paired comparison, face memory

I. INTRODUCTION

Faces play an important role in person-to- person communication as a kind of media that convey a variety of information that involves both personal identity and a person's emotional state and social impressions. This idea also applies to visual communication between humans and synthesized avatar faces based on virtual reality technologies. It remains unclear, however, how the transformation of the appearance of 3D faces actually affects people's identification of such faces. In this work, we investigated the relationship between the favorability of a face and human recognition performance.

II. OUR PREVIOUS WORK

In our previous work [1], we examined whether subjects can identify faces when their specific social impressions have been modulated between encoding and recognition phases.

Fig 1. Examples of impression-manipulated faces

The Todorov Face Database [2][3] is a set of computer-generated faces based on the morphable 3D facemodel that was implemented by Facegen Modeler [4], which is an extension of Blanz and Vetter's work [5]. It includes impression-transformed faces in three different dimensions: trustworthy, dominant, and threatening. For each dimension, impression manipulations were made at several intensity levels. Some examples of impression-manipulated faces are shown in Fig. 1. Subjective scrutiny of the perceived impressions of these stimuli has already been published [2]. Our face identification experiment consisted of encoding and recognition phases, and in both we used a set of images provided by the Todorov Face Database as target and distractor stimuli. In the encoding phase,

11 face images (including two dummy stimuli that appeared at the test phase's beginning and ending) were presented one by one for seven seconds. All of the face images were neutral and no impressions were manipulated. We asked the participants to memorize them. In the recognition phase, we conducted an old-new recognition test and made judgments on a 6-point scale: "I've definitely seen it (1)" to "I've never seen it before (6)". For this test, we presented 18 face images one by one for seven seconds each. Three of the images were the same neutral faces presented in the encoding phase, three had weakened impressions, and three had strengthened impressions. The remaining nine were distractors. We provided three sets of images that depended on one of the three dimensions assigned for impression manipulations: trustworthy, dominant, and threatening. For the analysis method, we introduced hit rates, which are indexes of the correct recognition performance achieved by humans, to represent the probability of the target face that was previously presented in the encoding phase that was correctly judged as an already "seen"

face. We identified three intensity levels of each impression manipulation (i.e., strengthened, no change, and weakened) with three semantic direction classes (i.e. positive, neutral, and negative) (Table 1).

Social impressions	Strengthened	No change	Weakened
Trustworthy	Positive	Neutral	Negative
Dominant	Negative	Neutral	Positive
Threatening	Negative	Neutral	Positive

Table 1 Positive/negative categorization of impression manipulations

Fig. 2 shows the hit rates under the manipulation of the original faces with respect to three types of social impressions in either positive/negative directions. We confirmed a significant difference in the category of negative impression manipulations. Participants generally failed to properly recognize the encoded faces as previously “seen” ones when the impression manipulation was made in a semantically negative direction (e.g., more threatening).

Fig. 2 Hit rate for operating impressions

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Our subjective assessment assigned favorability ratings to each synthesized face used in our previous work [1] as the visual stimuli of the “seen” faces. This procedure was achieved with 120 university participants with Thurston’s method of paired comparison[7] for each set composed of four synthesized faces (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Examples of impression-manipulated faces directed to paired comparison

Two faces in the set were synthesized by weakening and two others by strengthening the impression manipulation degree along each of three dimensions: trustworthy, dominant, and threatening. Each pair of facial images was presented on a 12.5-inch computer display (Fig. 4), and subjects selected relatively favorable faces.

Fig. 4 Display of two stimuli for Thurston’s method of paired comparison

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Based on the favorability rating results, we classified the face stimuli made by impression manipulation into two classes: relatively favorable and unfavorable faces. Table 2 shows the average hit rates achieved with faces that belong to each favorability class manipulated in terms of specified impression dimensions and in comparison to the average scores achieved with the original faces without impression manipulation.

When the faces were manipulated within the trustworthy dimension that generally projects a positive image to recipients, the difference in the hit rate, caused by the difference in the perceived favorability, was small. But when the faces were manipulated within the dominant and threatening dimensions that generally project negative feelings, the difference in the hit rate, caused by the difference in favorability, was large. Since unfavorable faces among those strengthened with negative impressions are less favorable than those with positive impressions, it seems difficult to recognize faces that have already been seen before.

Dimension of impressions manipulation	Favorability of synthesized faces		
	Decreased	Original	Increased
Trustworthy	58%	69%	75%
Dominant	25%		67%
Threatening	8%		75%

Table 2 Hit rates achieved in seen-unseen tests

Table 3 shows the result of a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted for the hit rate in which the three levels for the strength of impression manipulation were analyzed. The main effect of the strength of the impression manipulations was significant ($F(2, 29) = 4.238, p < .05$). Thus we found that the hit rate is affected by differences in the strength of impression manipulations.

source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Strength of the impression	0.6371528	2	0.3185764	4.238	0.0251 *
error[MC]	2.0295139	27	0.0751672		
Total	2.6666667	29			

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.005, **** p<.001

Table 3 Results of analysis of variance

V. CONCLUSION

We found that people generally failed to properly recognize encoded faces as previously “seen” ones when impression manipulation reduced their favorability. We expect that such findings will contribute to designing avatars with higher communicative competence, especially in people-search applications. Based on the results obtained by a pairwise comparison method, our future work will investigate whether gaze movements during recognition tests differ depending on the face’s favorability.

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Paper 29

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND SENSORS BASED ASSISTIVE SYSTEM FOR THE VISUALLY IMPAIRED PEOPLE

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*naktenikita@gmail.com**soumya@gmail.com**Abstract :**

The need for developing a low-cost assistive system for the visually impaired and blind people has increased with steady increase in their population worldwide. The stick system presented in the paper uses artificial intelligence along with various sensors in real time to help the visually disabled people to navigate their environment independently. Image recognition, collision detection and obstacle detection are the three tasks performed by the system. The image recognition task was performed using a smartphone application powered by artificial intelligence. The tasks of collision detection and obstacle detection utilized ultrasonic sensors to alert the user of the obstacles appearing in his route. The stick system also managed to demonstrate the important characteristics of affordability, high efficiency, mobility and ease of use.

Keywords: visually impaired; image recognition; collision detection; obstacle detection; artificial intelligence; real-time system

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the reliable estimates of WHO (World Health Organization), about 40 to 45 million people are blind from the global population of 285 million visually impaired people [1]. With the staggering number of visually disabled people around the world, providing care for such a large population results in an enormous socio- economic stress on the countries. About 90% of global visually impaired people belong to low-income households with highest numbers in developing countries like India [1, 2]. This trend will continue to grow because of widespread chronic eye diseases, population growth as well as rising ageing population around the world with developing countries bearing most of the brunt [1].

People with visual disability have a constant need of assistance in their daily lives. It can range from relying on other people for help to using various Electronic Travel Aid (ETA) assistive devices whenever needed. People also use Guide dogs and white canes but the restriction on the allowance of guide dogs in certain places and short range of white canes serve as their shortcomings. Similarly, most of the ETAs also have drawbacks of being unaffordable and inefficient. Keeping a tab on the various drawbacks of traditional and common methods of providing assistance to the blind and visually impaired people, we decided to develop and design our system with a novel approach. Past few years have seen wide scale applications of artificial intelligence ranging from national defence, scientific research, automated vehicles to space exploration. Taking advantage of the monumental

advances in artificial intelligence and helping visually impaired people was our main goal. For the features we desired and the tasks which we intended our system to perform, depending solely on artificial intelligence was not feasible. So using a microcontroller and sensors based hardware in addition to artificial intelligence was decided upon. The system thus not only makes use of artificial intelligence capabilities but also gathers precise readings from the various sensors to become a real-time assistive system. This enables the visually impaired people to navigate the world independently with confidence.

II. RELATED WORK

A significant quantity of research has been published previously for helping the visually impaired and blind people. One such work described Artificial Vision System for Blind (AVSB) [3], consisted of ultrasonic sensors and a microcontroller that anticipated the distance of the obstacles around the user and to advise him towards an alternative available route via an audio feedback. The disadvantage of this system was that it blocked the daily routine hearing of the visually impaired individuals. Tactile Vision System [4] was another published work that was studied for our paper. The system converted visual information into a tactile signal using a tractor-belt with 14 vibrators and a camera belt with two webcams. The drawback of this system was the prototype being heavy and its failure to differentiate between hanging and ground obstacles. The Navbelt system [5] used 8 ultrasonic sensors to create a map of angle and distances of objects around the user. The limitations of having a bulky prototype and use of audio feedback exclusively for functioning plagued this work.

All the work mentioned before lacked enthusiasm towards using AI in their systems along with consideration for mobility and affordability of the system. Focus on implementing obstacle detection, collision detection and image recognition together was also absent. Learning from the drawbacks and building upon the positives of these earlier works helped us design a better system. In an earlier version of our work [6] on this subject, we presented a brief explanation of our idea of developing a cost-effective assistive system for the visually impaired and blind people. The earlier system lacked the prowess of artificial intelligence and its capabilities of computer vision, machine learning and natural language processing. The implementation of image processing techniques of edge detection and texture detection for image recognition purpose often ended with error-prone results. The previous system hardware implementation also required numerous iterations of fine tuning and calibration to work seamlessly. A significant change in the use of accelerometer and improvements to the prior collision detection algorithm were also made in this work.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Two thirds of the estimated 285 million visually impaired people globally will become smartphone users in the next five years [7] with Android based smartphones having the highest user base around the world especially in developing countries [8]. The stick system was developed to leverage this estimate and consists of a 1 foot long PVC cable raceway stick and a smartphone application. The stick houses a Arduino Nano microcontroller, two ultrasonic sensors, an accelerometer and a Bluetooth module as shown in Fig. 1. The smartphone application resides on the user's Android smartphone.

Fig. 1. The stick hardware setup

After powering on the stick and opening the smartphone application, the user starts walking by holding the stick in one hand and smartphone in the other. The smartphone application and the sensors on the stick then start a continuous analysis of the environment in the user's route. In order to get some perception of his surroundings, the user captures images of his environment through his smartphone. These images are then processed by the artificial intelligence in the smartphone application leading to caption generation for each image which describes their contents. These captions are then conveyed to the user by the smartphone reading them aloud through its speakers. The ultrasonic sensor mounted on the front side of the stick detects the location of the obstacles appearing in the front of the user and an audio feedback is provided to the user so that he alters his route to avoid colliding with the obstacles. The other ultrasonic sensor mounted at the bottom of the stick along with the accelerometer detects the presence of potholes and bumps in the user's route eventually alerting the user via haptic feedback to make the user change his route. The flowchart of the proposed system is as shown below.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the system

A. System Architecture

The Arduino Nano microcontroller acts as the brain of the system, taking readings from the two ultrasonic sensors and the accelerometer to compute various the distance values. The Arduino board then sends these values to the smartphone using a Bluetooth connection. The two HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensors are tasked with identifying the recurring obstacles coming in the user's route by sending and receiving ultrasonic waves. One sensor is located at the bottom and the other on the front side of the stick.

Fig. 3. Overview of the system

The ADXL345 MEMS accelerometer provides supplementary information of the angles at which the distance between the ground and the stick were measured by the bottom ultrasonic sensor. Bluetooth HC-06 is a short range wireless communication module. This module sends all the computed distance values from the Arduino board to the user's smartphone. The smartphone application performs image recognition as one of its main tasks and makes use of the smartphone's rear camera, speakers, cellular internet connection and Bluetooth connection. It also provides audio and haptic feedback to the user.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

This system basically performs three tasks i.e. image recognition, collision detection and obstacle detection. Image recognition helps the visually impaired user to listen to a brief description of his surroundings. Collision detection focuses on instructing the user of avoiding possible collision with an obstacles upfront in his route. Obstacle detection identifies potholes and bumps on the ground in the user's route, guiding the user to avoid it. These three tasks are explained as follows:-

A. Image Recognition

Image recognition deals with extracting information from the user captured images and narrate this information back to the user. For this purpose, the user holds the smartphone in front of him and captures images via the rear camera using the volume down button on his smartphone. The images are then analyzed by the application’s artificial intelligence eventually generating captions for every user captured image. These captions describe the contents of the images which are then conveyed to the user using Google TalkBack. The smartphone application uses a cellular internet connection to perform artificial intelligence related tasks. The Computer Vision API of Microsoft Cognitive Services is what really powers the artificial intelligence in our system [10]. Whenever the need to analyze an image arises our system application code invokes a call to this API. Image analysis by the API is done using computer vision, machine learning and neural networks whereas natural language processing is used to generate the caption in a human understandable language [11]. Leveraging the power of the API, the smartphone application can analyze an image, read texts and handwritten texts from an image, identify landmarks and celebrities and also perform video analysis in near real-time [10]. For the image caption speaking feature, we decided to use Google TalkBack service since it comes preinstalled on most Android devices [9].

B. Obstacle Detection

The ultrasonic sensors generate high frequency sound waves and evaluate the echoes received back by the sensors. For the task of obstacle detection, the ultrasonic sensor mounted at the bottom of the stick sends ultrasonic waves towards the below ground and starts the timer. The timer is stopped when the waves reflected from the ground are received. Using the time required by the waves to return back to the sensor, the distance value between the stick and the ground is calculated in the Arduino board using the following formula:

Approx. speed of sound $c =$
 $331.5 + [0.6 \times (\text{air temperature in degree Celsius})]$
 at 20 degree _____
 $c = 331.5 + (0.6 \times 20) = 343.5 \text{ m/s}$
 $c = 343.5 \times 100 \text{ cm/}\mu\text{S} = 0.03435 \text{ cm/}\mu\text{S}$
 1

accessibility service [9]. Google TalkBack identifies the generated captions and speaks it to the user via the smartphone speakers or through the earphones connected to the smartphone. This allows the user to get a good perception of his surrounding environment and helps him to better navigate his route.

Fig. 4. Result of image recognition

speed of sound = $c = 29 \cdot 1$

The time interval between ultrasonic waves sent by the sensor is in μS .

distance = 2

duration

$29 \cdot 1$

The Bluetooth connection between the Arduino and the smartphone is used to transfer the computed distance value from the Arduino board. The smartphone application then processes this value and marks this reading as actual distance value (i.e. Calibrated value). Henceforth, all the incoming computed distance values and the angle values from the accelerometer are marked as the current distance values. Using all these values, the smartphone application detects the presence of bumps and potholes in the user's current route. If the current distance value is found to be less than the calibrated value then detection of a bump is inferred and the smartphone gives out a long vibration as feedback so as to caution the user. If the current distance value is found to be more than the calibrated value then the detection of a pothole is inferred with a short vibration as feedback.

C. Collision Detection

Identifying the presence of an obstacles upfront in the user's route and warning him of a possible collision with the obstacles by providing an audio feedback are the tasks performed in collision detection. The second ultrasonic sensor, mounted on the front side of the stick is utilized for this task. A distance of 4 feet has been set as the default safe distance in front of the stick wherein if any obstacle is detected inside the safe distance, the collision detection system starts warning the user. For this task, the sensor transmits ultrasonic waves towards the front direction of the user along with starting a timer to keep a track of time. Once the waves reflected from the obstacle are received by the sensor, the timer is stopped. Using the time difference between the moment the ultrasonic waves were sent from and received back by the sensor along with the distance formula used in the obstacle detection algorithm, the distance between the user and the obstacle in the user's route is calculated. These calculations are performed by the Arduino board unit. The computed distance value is then sent from the Arduino board to the user's smartphone using a Bluetooth connection in the same way as observed in the obstacle detection task. The smartphone application then processes these readings and generates a series of beeping sounds thus alerting the user and causing him to alter his current route.

Fig. 5. Result of obstacle and collision detection

All these tasks from calculating the distance of obstacles from the user to generating warning sounds happen in real time so that the user can act quickly and be safely away from a potentially dangerous situation. Fig. 5 shows the calculated values generated by the obstacle and collision detection tasks.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, design and development of a real-time artificial intelligence system for assisting visually impaired and blind people has been discussed. The system performed three main tasks of image recognition, collision detection and obstacle detection allowing the user to navigate his route independently. Using incumbent devices like a smartphone and a compact but high quality hardware, our system managed to overcome the hurdle of developing an

assistive system which was both efficient and affordable enough for the visually impaired people especially belonging to the low-income households. Future research work involves refining our system so that a more hands-free assistive system experience can be provided for the visually disabled people.

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Paper 29**LEARNING AND CAPABILITY ACQUISITION:
A CASE STUDY OF THE INDIAN AUTOMOBILE
INDUSTRY****Nithesh Shetty, Mohammed Ridwan**MBA Evening, 1st year, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, City
Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575 001.**Abstract**

This study analyzes the impact of government policy regime on the learning and capability acquisition of firms over time. Through a case study analysis of the Indian automotive industry, the study develops three hypotheses relating policy regimes with learning strategies of firms.

The study tests these hypotheses through a model of learning using a panel data for the Indian automotive industry. It finds that speed of knowledge assimilation is more important in the liberalized policy regime vis-à-vis protection when knowledge assimilation per se was a more Important economic goal.

The Indian auto industry became the 4th largest in the world with sales increasing 9.5 per cent year-on-year to 4.02 million units (excluding two wheelers) in 2017. It was the 7th largest manufacturer of commercial vehicles in 2017.

The Two Wheelers segment dominates the market in terms of volume owing to a growing middle class and a young population. Moreover, the growing interest of the companies in exploring the rural markets further aided the growth of the sector.

Keywords: Growth, Learning, Capabilities, Industrial Policy, Automobile industry, Asia, India.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well recognized in industrial organization theory and empirical literature that learning as a capability is a major factor in explaining interfirm performance differences. The success of newly industrialized countries (NICs), for example, has shown that technological progress is not merely guided by changes in relative prices, nor does competitiveness depend upon relative factor endowments. It is more than acquiring the technological blue prints and involves a learning process. This is more so in the context of late comers to industrialization, where governments have actively pursued industrial regulation and protection to allow firms to grow and learn to compete. Therefore, it is an interesting research question to ask: how does regulation impact firm

learning and growth? This paper analyzes the role played by government policies in transforming the learning abilities of the firms and the markets with reference to the Indian automobile industry.

Based on a case study analysis of automotive firms in the Indian Industry, three hypotheses are developed relating firm learning with policy regime. These hypotheses are then empirically tested using a panel data of 13 firms across a 38 year period, an interval subdivided into three different industrial policy regimes eras: protection, deregulation and liberalization.

2. INDUSTRIAL POLICY REGIMES IN INDIA AND IMPACT ON FIRM LEARNING

[1][2][3][4]

Protection: 1970-84 —Macro Economic Environment

During the protection phase, the industry's output was controlled by licensing production capacity and restricting output to single models so as to minimize the foreign exchange outflows due to the imports of components. Industrial policy did not allow capital imports or foreign direct investment (FDI). Further, complicated rules on imports made access to technology difficult and slowed down the learning process of firms.

Market Structure and Technology

The market structure was concentrated with entry barriers and restrictions to creating capacities and adding new product lines. While General Motors and Ford shut down their operations in India, business groups like the Birla and the Walchand group entered the industry. In 1960, there were three manufacturers, initially producing with licensed technology from US, UK and Italy; Premier Automobiles limited, Hindustan Motors and Standard Motors private limited, each producing very small outputs and Mahindra manufacturing jeeps. Product specific licensing policy forced companies to enter niche segments where each enjoyed a monopoly. The market structure was thus concentrated and the firms relied on licensed technology and foreign equity participation as the means to growth. In mid seventies, the commercial vehicle industry was allowed unlimited production capacity and an automatic capacity expansion of 25% every five years.

External Institutions

Supplier capabilities in India were not well developed, and TML had various training programs to develop its capabilities. Auto component manufacturing was reserved for small-scale industry but lack of volumes did not allow consolidation in the industry through a hierarchical organization of capabilities (also known as tierization) in the supplier industry. It remained highly fragmented and technologically underdeveloped during this phase.

Impact on Learning

In the presence of regulations on product lines and capacity expansions, the only means to growth was access to foreign equity which would give them superior technology. According to Narayana's study (1997), in the protection regime, in the absence of major acquisitions or diversifications, firms with foreign equity grew faster than others because of the resource advantage they possessed. Thus, in the protection phase, the firm growth was dependent on its

absorptive capacity that enables them to learn and internalize their foreign partner's technological knowledge.

Deregulation: 1984-91

Macro Environment

The industrial policy statements of 1977 and 1980 marked the beginning of deregulation by relaxing the regulations governing production licenses, foreign collaboration, asset size and the scope of industrial operations. In 1985, policy of broad banding was introduced with allowed manufacturers to make use of economies of scale and scope by manufacturing several product lines. Further, the technology imports were allowed and firms resorted to imports as a means to growth. Government entered into partnership with Suzuki in 1982 and in 1984, which led to the setting up of Maruti Udyog Limited (Maruti). The macro economic situation deteriorated in the mid 80s because of liberalized imports, rupee appreciation and drain on foreign exchange reserves. The government was forced to devalue the currency in 1991 and resort to IMF for liberalization program. Between 1984 and 1987, the Yen appreciated 200 times which hurt the Japanese joint ventures adversely.

Market Structure

Maruti manufactured 12000 vehicles challenging the market shares of the existing manufacturers and eventually becoming the market leader by 1991. Entry in the Passenger car segment was still restricted, with three players until early 1991—Maruti, Hindustan motors and Premier automobiles limited (PAL) with market shares of 60%, 13% and 23%. Standard Motors exited from the industry in the late 1980s. Thus, from this phase, the market structure changed in favor of the government joint venture-Maruti Udyog Limited and the output of automobile industry increased by nearly 400%. The commercial vehicle segment was liberalized and saw the entry of Japanese joint ventures like DCM-Toyota, Eicher-Mitsubishi Swaraj-Mazda and Allwyn-Nissan. However, most of them suffered set backs due to macro economic environment and foreign exchange appreciation.

External Institutions

The entry of Maruti also changed the supplier relations within the industry with the help of government sponsored training programs and cluster building. The presence of Japanese joint ventures in the same region created economies of industrial agglomeration. This also resulted in a widespread use of Japanese work practices that relied on cooperative agreements between suppliers and OEMs.

Impact on Learning

During the deregulation period, firms relied on technology imports and growth through spillovers from new competitors. Allowing firms to invest in several product lines resulted in firm learning as firms like Tata Motors introduced special purpose vehicles and platforms for moving towards passenger car segment. The institutional support for developing supplier capabilities led to flexible supplier relationships whereby, firms could adjust demand downwards through detailed cost negotiations. For instance, Maruti was also able to expand its capacity in

press shop from 130,000 to 180,000 without any significant capital outlays by having flexible labor practices and joint ventures

Liberalization: 1992-2008: Macro Environment

In 1993, the passenger car industry was completely delicensed followed by an entry of multinationals in this segment. This also encouraged existing firms to form joint ventures with foreign firms. From August 1991 to April 2002, the auto industry garnered 5.48% of the total foreign direct investment approved during this period (Government of India, Ministry of Commerce and Industry 2002).

Market Structure

The liberalized policies allowed firms to take advantage of low cost sourcing across the globe which in turn gave rise to modular relationships between suppliers and OEMs. For example, Sona Koyo has set up an engineering design and outsourcing company for its international clients. Rico Auto and Sundaram fasteners have laboratories with latest softwares for reverse engineering, designing and testing of parts. Such capabilities enable these firms to take up turnkey projects with low switching costs for the OEMs. At the same time, some firms did not acquire the capabilities to sustain competitiveness in the liberalized policy environment. For example, two firms exited the industry in the nineties: DCM Toyota and PAL. Both firms were taken over by multinationals, Daewoo in case of DCM and Fiat in the case of PAL. PAL exited from the industry after a failed partnership with Peugeot of France, and was taken over by Fiat.

External Institutions

With severe infrastructural and supply bottlenecks, resulting partly from past government policy of neglecting infrastructure and reserving components for the officially defined small scale industries, manufacturers were compelled to encourage partnerships among their suppliers to reduce mutual vulnerability. Supplier associations were introduced by Japanese manufacturers to enable diffusion of best practices. The Automotive component manufacturers association was an industrial lobby actively engaged in pursuing the suppliers' interests in the organized industry.

Impact on Learning

The liberalized environment exposed firms to new competition and encouraged them to undertake research and development activities, which increased during this time period. Firms introduced variety of models and the time span between new launches was also declining rapidly, indicating that firms were actively involved in new product development. For example, at Tata Motors, a new technology group was set up at engineering research center for simultaneous engineering and joint product development with suppliers. Thus, during liberalization, firms resorted to learning through innovation and spillovers resulting from inter-firm relations. Changing inter-firm relations involved setting up a new organizational form in 1995 to promote technology acquisition in the component industry. The holding company structure gives Tata Motors the flexibility to partner with multiple global majors to access cutting edge technology and also facilitates the pooling of resources, capabilities and the creation of a common infrastructure and managerial expertise.

Similarly, in the year 2004, Maruti started a “Centre for Excellence”, a joint investment between Maruti and some of its tier-I suppliers, with the OEM holding the majority stake. The Centre promoted three kinds of activities through a cluster of five to six companies: productivity improvements such as TPM, Kaizen and training for Japanese production systems; quality improvement program, where a top-down approach is adopted and emphasis is on training principles of TQM and system audits.

Year	Tata Motor	Ashok Leyland	Hindustan Motors	Maruti Udyog Ltd	Mahindra	Premier Automobile	Bajaj Tempo	Hyundai Motor India Ltd
1990	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.2	0.2	1.6	0.6	
1991	0.6	1.1	0.4	0.4	0.2	1.3	2.2	
1992	1.1	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.2	2.0	2.1	
1993	2.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	1.2	2.1	
1994	2.7	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.8	0.0	1.9	
1995	1.4	0.9	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	1.7	
1996	1.7	0.1	0.4	0.2	1.2	3.5	1.5	
1997	2.0	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.7	0.3	1.3	
1998	1.6	0.5	0.7	0.4	0.9	0.1	1.6	0.05
1999	1.2	0.7	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.4	1.0	0.02
2000	1.1	0.9	0.3	0.5	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.00
2001	1.1	0.9	0.5	0.5	1.8	0.0	2.2	0.00
2002	1.3	1.0	0.6	0.2	1.7		2.3	0.10

Source: SIAM Facts and Figures (2004), Annual reports.

Table 1: R&D Intensity (R&D expenditure as % of Sales)

Firms like Tata Motors and Maruti entered into strategic partnerships and also evolved new forms of supplier relations to promote joint product development and learning through spillovers. For example, in the liberalized regime, Tata’s technology strategy focused on acquiring strategic partnerships and import of technological know-how. It imported technology for development of fuel injected gasoline engines from AVL, Austria in 1992, body styling from IDEA, Italy, process capability for welding from HLS, Germany and engine testing from Le Moteur Moderne, France. In 1994, the machine tool division built robots for the first time, with technology imported from Nachi-Fujikashi of Japan. Tata entered the passenger car segment in 1998 and in 2000, in an effort to focus on its core business of design and development of vehicles, it hived off the machine tool division into a separate company called Tata Automation Limited (TAL).

3. DATA SOURCE

This study is based on annual production data for a sample of 13 firms in the four-wheeler automobile industry, obtained from the Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers and Automobile Component Manufacturers Association, for thirty-eight years from 1970-2008 and the time period is divided into three industrial policy regimes: protection (1970-84); deregulation

(1985-91) and liberalization (1992-2008). The thirteen firms in the four-wheeler segment can be divided into three groups: Group one is those born in the protection period (pre-1970) and group two those born in the post-regulatory period (post-1985). A third group of firms is the multinational firms which entered after 1996. The data is unbalanced with exit and entry in the liberalized regime.

The descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) of the explanatory variables are presented in table 3. Table 4 shows the compound annual average growth rates (CAGR) in different policy regimes. Growth rates of the six firms in the protection phase were higher compared to the liberalization period. In the sample of six firms, only one firm-Tata Motors did better during the liberalization as compared to the protection period. In regime III, multinational firms had the highest growth rates. To summarize, regime I was driven by growth in the commercial vehicle segment, with firms like Ashok Leyland, Tata, Mahindra and Bajaj Tempo displaying above average industry growth rates. Regime II and III were driven by growth in the passenger car segment, with the entry of Maruti in 1985 and multinational players in mid 1990s. The overall industrial growth has been the highest in regime III, the main drivers of which are the multinational firms in the passenger car sector. One can estimate the model using either the random effects or fixed effects models. The former assumes that firm-specific factors are uncorrelated with size and age, whereas, the latter allows for such a correlation. The Hausman's statistics can help to choose the method of estimation. It tests the null hypothesis of no correlation (i.e., random effect model). The Hausman's statistic supports the null hypothesis of zero correlation between firm specific factors with size. Hence, the study uses a one-way Random Effects model to estimate the coefficients.

Firms/ policy regimes	Production (Units)	Growth (Log Differences)	Lagged Output (Log)	Lagged Output (Log)- Rival Firms	Lagged Growth-Rival Firms	Sample Size
Tata Motors-Regime 1	383921	0.143	11.377	12.339	0.116	13
Regime 2	272754	0.160	8.075	8.755	0.111	7
Regime 3	343366	0.113	11.240	12.237	0.115	17
Ashok Leyl-Regime 1	10831	0.085	9.144	11.526	0.042	13
Regime 2	19875	0.074	9.805	12.534	0.125	7
Regime 3	43356	0.047	10.546	13.629	0.102	17
Hind.motors-Regime 1	23173	-0.002	10.020	11.383	0.056	13
Regime 2	26158	-0.068	10.224	12.497	0.137	7
Regime 3	22004	-0.036	9.978	13.643	0.105	17
Mahindras-Regime 1	28019	0.073	10.075	11.372	0.036	13
Regime 2	58227	0.028	10.937	12.383	0.141	7
Regime 3	138516	0.072	11.726	13.514	0.105	17
Premier Auto-Regime 1	18811	0.040	9.771	11.440	0.049	13
Regime 2	35312	0.017	10.442	12.473	0.127	7
Regime 3	14032	52.035	51.341	13.656	0.108	8
BajajTempo-Regime 1	7276	0.109	8.695	11.561	0.041	13
Regime 2	15138	0.010	9.611	12.545	0.127	7
Regime 3	19860	0.004	9.788	13.650	0.103	17
Eicher -Regime 2	3745	28.473	34.060	12.590	0.121	6
Regime 3	12524	0.088	9.089	13.664	0.101	17
Swaraj -Regime 2	3093	14.186	21.031	12.589	0.121	7
Regime 3	6290	64.016	61.606	13.671	0.101	6
DCM-Regime 2	2502	14.272	20.769	12.591	0.121	7
Regime 3	6564	0.072	8.562	13.668	0.101	17
Maruti -Regime 2	98865	0.241	11.223	12.282	0.069	7
Regime 3	415556	0.109	12.717	13.184	0.097	17
Hyundai India -Regime 3	202363	35.713	47.692	13.599	0.090	11
Ford India-Regime 3	24258	47.188	57.084	13.667	0.100	9
Toyota Kirl.-Regime 3	36477	41.397	52.030	13.661	0.099	10
Industry-Regime 1	122617	0.057	-	-	-	13
Regime 2	326894	0.085	-	-	-	7
Regime 3	1101079	0.103	-	-	-	17

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Firms	Regime 1-1970-84			Regime 2-1985-91			Regime 3-1992-2008		
	CAGR	Mean	CV	CAGR	Mean	CV	CAGR	Mean	CV
Tata Motors	6.06	5.71	2.82	11.83	11.83	0.67	11.28	11	0.57
Ashok Leyland	9.66	8.95	1.89	9.43	7.40	1.36	7.28	7	0.84
Hindmotors	0.81	4.88	7.01	-3.95	-5.33	-3.27	-6.03	-6	-0.63
MUL	0.00			56.57	16.70	1.20	10.02	11	0.28
Mahindra	7.45	10.32	2.22	5.11	3.50	3.00	5.41	7	0.46
PAL	1.98	8.38	4.39	5.16	2.82	5.96	-47.21	-81	-0.71
BT	10.78	11.16	1.53	1.49	1.12	15.00	1.61	6	1.30
Eicher				24.94	42.97	1.79	15.38	12	0.44
DCM				7.03	9.43	3.24	15.77	-10	-7.25
Swaraj				18.86	21.53	1.68	11.02	8	0.65
HMIL							31.19	33.25	0.37
TKMIL							22.22	28.48	0.75
FIL							0.21	20.00	0.71
GMIL							26.59	26.59	0.45
Industry	6.45%	7.42%	1.95	8.32%	7.51%	0.96	9.84%	11.50%	0.33

*Growth rate for PAL for Regime 3 is from 1992-2000 and for DCM it is from 1992-1999.

Table 4: Compound Average Growth Rate (%)

4. CONCLUSION

The economic success of emerging economies in the late seventies sparked off debates on several issues like the role of government versus the private sector, export oriented strategy versus import substituting industrialization and a combination of the two. In this context, this thesis undertakes a case study of the growth of the Indian automobile Industry across three policy regimes, focusing on learning and capability acquisition. The objective has been to study whether policy regime can influence firm level learning. If so, then it provides a justification to the infant industry argument from a developing country perspective as well as highlights the lessons to be learnt from successful learners. The study relies on a qualitative case study approach, complemented by quantitative techniques.

While the literature on technological capability acquisition is rich in documenting the empirical details of the process and sequence of capability acquisition, it suffers from subjective classification of capabilities and a static analysis of capabilities that are changing over time. The study has tried to integrate empirical case studies with the literature on learning by applying a dynamic model of learning to the Indian industry. The study examined the dynamic nature of learning process by looking at the time path of output across thirteen major automobile firms. The model is estimated for the Indian industry for a sample of thirteen four wheeler firms across three policy regimes, divided into twelve year, seven year and seventeen year period. The study uses random effects panel data estimation, with time trend and structural dummies as shift variables for the regime changes.

To conclude, the paper demonstrates that learning varies by the policy regime. Learning is also firm-specific, defined by the technology strategy and capabilities of the firms, which is not captured by the traditional industrial organization theory. The study rejects the hypothesis of independence between firm size and firm growth, known as Gibrat's law.

Results indicate that relation between firm size and growth differs by policy regime. The results indicate that during protection accumulation of stock of knowledge was more important, whereas during liberalization, the speed of knowledge accumulation was more important. From a policy perspective, while protection encourages acquisition of production capabilities of, it does not equip the firm with the learning capabilities necessary for survival in a competitive environment. This is shown by the fact that some of the firms that acquired learning also exited the industry in a liberalized policy regime, unable to face the competition. What is required is an ability to adapt to the changing market conditions. These conclusions also give pointers to further research to incorporate the impact of quality and coordination capabilities in the model of learning.

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Paper 31

ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYMENT GENERATION- A CASE STUDY OF RUDSET INSTITUTE IN KERALA

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Abstract:

As marching towards encompassing a high rate of growth with great potential of human resources, Indian economy struggling to utilise its man power because of lack of employment opportunity, absence of successful ventures etc. Poverty, social exclusion, inequality, and unemployment etc are still haunting Indian economy, despite a number of planned efforts made by both central and state government to mitigate them. Though, Kerala is rich with her natural endowment and high potential educated youth, still struggling to make the most out of them because of lack of successful entrepreneurship activities and absence of a favourable industrial climate. A large number of youth in rural and semi-urban Kerala could not access high professional education and employment due to financial constraint and their high orientation towards white colour jobs. The theory of development by Schumpeter highlighted the significant role played by entrepreneurs and their innovative and imperative role in the development process of the economy. Absence of credit, poor infrastructure, socio-economic backwardness due to some religious and cultural taboos and customs especially on women and marginal section etc acts as a barrier to the natural growth of entrepreneurship in India and Kerala. Both Central and State government initiated a number of programmes to foster entrepreneurial development. In 1982, an innovative initiative was taken by Sri. Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara Educational trust, Syndicate bank and Canara bank finally resulted in the setting up of a very well appreciated RUDSETI model in India to tackle unemployment issues in rural area by providing credit accessibility and skill development programmes for entrepreneurial development for the socially disadvantaged people mainly belongs to SC, ST, BPL and women. The present study is to analyse the organisational structure and functioning of RUDSETI of Kerala situated in Taliparamba and also to evaluate various Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDP) offered by the institute.

Keywords: Unemployment- Rudset- Entrepreneurship and skill development- Training- Motivation

1. INTRODUCTION

Unemployment in India is a major economic issue that impede the rate of growth of India over the years. World Employment and Social Outlook–Trends (2018) report by the International Labour Organization, released on 22 January 2018 says that “As many as 18.3 million Indians were unemployed in 2017, and this unemployment is projected to increase to 18.9 million by 2019”.According to a report first published in the Business Standard, an

Indian financial newspaper- India's jobless rate shot up to 45-year high during 2017-2018. NSSO showed unemployment rate at 6.1 percent, the highest since 1972-73- Joblessness stood at 7.8 percent in urban areas compared with 5.3 percent in the countryside.

Month/Year	India	Urban	Rural
Jan 2019	7.13	8.80	6.24
Dec 2018	7.38	7.64	7.25
Nov 2018	6.62	7.56	6.14
Oct 2018	6.91	7.27	6.72
Sep 2018	6.61	7.58	6.10
Aug 2018	6.32	6.81	6.06
Jul 2018	5.70	6.25	5.41
Jun 2018	5.81	6.77	5.30
May 2018	5.22	6.31	4.65
Apr 2018	5.64	6.31	5.29
Mar 2018	6.03	6.20	5.94
Feb 2018	5.93	6.72	5.52

Source :NSSO, 2019

The NSSO reports also highlights that, For rural male youth (aged 15-29) unemployment went from 5 percent in 2011-12 to 17.4 percent in 2017-18. For rural women in the same age group, joblessness went from 4.8 percent in 2011-12 to 13.6 percent in 2017-18. For educated rural females, the unemployment rate ranged from 9.7 per cent to 15.2 per cent during 2004-05 to 2011-12 which rose to 17.3 per cent in 2017-18. For educated rural males, the unemployment rate stands at 10.5 percent for 2017-18. The rate of joblessness for urban youths was a whopping 18.7 per cent for males and 27.2 per cent for females.

2. ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES –A TOOL TO ERADICATE UNEMPLOYMENT

Entrepreneurship has now become an important tool to eradicate unemployment and create new job opportunities for youth in both developed and developing countries. Indian government has taken a number of initiatives to eradicate unemployment. Entrepreneurial development programmes supplement the growth of micro small medium enterprises in India. MSM sector accounts for more than 95 percent of the industrial units and contributes 45 percent of the manufacturing output and 40 percent of the export (Ministry of MSME, 2014). Small enterprises play a crucial role in creating employment and helping in the industrialisation of rural and backward areas. For promoting the micro small and medium enterprises various policies, programs and schemes have been developed from time to time by state governments. In order to make Entrepreneurship the important component of state economy the government has taken various step to create awareness, entrepreneurship education, skill up gradation, knowledge dissemination, attitude modification and building consensus with national and international organizations.

3. REVIEWS OF LITERATURE

Morris et al. (2001) studied that entrepreneurship is a step-wise process affected by both exogenous and endogenous factors like presence of business friendly environment, required factor endowments, capability to acquire required resources, and implementation and management of business concept. Enormous studies highlighted the importance of entrepreneurship for eradication of unemployment issues, Drucker (1985) and Gorman et al. (1997), Alarape (2007, p. 225) Utterback and Reitberger, 1982. Watson et al. (1998) Vesper, 1985, Vesper and McMullen, 1988; Solomon and Fernald, 1991. Ronstadt, 1987; Katz, 2003; Solomon et al., 2002; Robinson and Hayes, 1991; Sexton and Upton, 1984-Kolvareid and Moen (1997). Studies made by Beck and Demirgüç, -Kunt (2006), IFC (2012) Kumar and Francisco (2005) pointed out that inadequate access to formal credit is one of the key bottlenecks for small enterprises. Entrepreneurs are majorly classified as necessity driven and opportunity driven. The necessity driven entrepreneurs are compelled by the adverse economic conditions while opportunity-driven are compelled by the new innovations and opportunities which they identify and perceive (Lehimer, 2013). The theory of economic development stages draws a direct link between entrepreneurship and innovation. Indeed, a shift in favour of opportunity entrepreneurship stimulates innovation. This result is also found in endogenous growth models such as the model of King and Levine (1993), inspired by the Schumpeterian approach. Orza (1988) discusses the major assumptions of Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDPs) and its rationale in the context of India. After a brief overview of the history of the EDP movement in India and its contribution to developing small-scale industries, he puts forward a methodology for the evaluation of EDPs. The educational background of entrepreneurs is not found to have too much bearing on their entrepreneurial pursuits whereas previous experience in the same product line was found to influence their performance. Nair et. al (1998) is by far the largest survey-based study on entrepreneurship in Kerala. Based on a field survey involving 300 rural entrepreneurs in Kerala, the study found that in the particular context of Kerala, contextual circumstances play a dominant role in facilitating entrepreneurship. The institutions created to support the growth of small-scale industries suffer from complex, cumbersome and bureaucratic practices and cause many problems for entrepreneurs. Drucker (1985) and Gorman et al. (1997) revealed that entrepreneurship education leads to the success of entrepreneurship. Alarape (2007, p. 225) described entrepreneurial learning as “the improvement of insights, knowledge, and associations between past actions, the effectiveness of those actions and future actions”. Lack of motivation and confidence hinders the entrepreneurial change; the education that leads to the creation of entrepreneurial skills and motivation (Utterback and Reitberger, 1982). Watson et al. (1998) concluded that personal background, motivation for start up and growth orientation leads to the success of any venture creation. Training in entrepreneurship has been carried out in many contexts (Vesper, 1985), but most of the training programmes focus on entrepreneurial abilities as business plan development (Vesper and McMullen, 1988; Solomon and Fernald, 1991). Recent studies have shown that entrepreneurship spirit among graduates is usually the outcome of entrepreneurship education (Ronstadt, 1987; Katz, 2003; Solomon et al., 2002; Robinson and Hayes, 1991; Sexton and Upton, 1984). Kolvareid and Moen (1997) opined that students who have taken a course or training in entrepreneurship have had shown greater interest in becoming entrepreneurs and act more entrepreneurially than other students in taking up the challenge to start a new business.

4. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Though, Kerala is rich with her natural endowment and high potential educated youth, still struggling to make the most out of them because of lack of successful entrepreneurship activities and absence of a favourable industrial climate in Kerala. A large number of youth in rural and semi-urban Kerala could not access high professional education and employment due to financial constraint and their high orientation towards white colour jobs. The theory of development presented by Schumpeter highlighted the significant role played by entrepreneurs and their innovative and imperative role in the development process of the economy. Absence of credit, poor infrastructure, socio-economic backwardness due to some religious and cultural taboos and customs especially on women and marginal's etc acts as a barrier to the natural growth of entrepreneurship in India and Kerala. Both Central and State government initiated a number of programmes to foster entrepreneurial development. The present study is about the RUDSET setup in India, an initiative undertaken in order to provide credit accessibility and skill development programmes for entrepreneurial development for the socially disadvantaged people in the rural India.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study is based on the following objectives

- 1) To understand the nature of EDP courses offered in RUDSET
- 2) To analyse the impact of EDP courses on employment creation, credit accessibility and skill development among the RUDSET trainees

6. METHODOLOGY

Present study is focused on the RUDSET institute in Kannur district. The courses offered, stake holder's details etc are explored from both primary and secondary data. The major secondary source is the statistics collected from the Directors office, RUDSET of Kerala, situated in Taliparamba, Primary data is collected with the help of a questionnaire by interviewing 100 alumni's of RUDSET, Taliparamba.

7. RUDSET

In 1982, an innovative initiative was taken by Sri. Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara Educational trust, Syndicate bank and Canara bank finally resulted in the setting up of a very well appreciated RUDSETI model to tackle unemployment issues in rural area by providing credit accessibility and skill development programmes for entrepreneurship development to the socially disadvantaged people mainly belongs to SC, ST, BPL and women. RUDSET Institute has established 27 units across 17 states in India. The success of RUDSET Institute inspired Central Government to start more than 500 institutions under RUDSETI.

RUDSET Institute, Kannur – the only RUDSET Institute in Kerala was originally established in the year 1985 at Maipady in Kasaragod district, catering to the needs of the unemployed youth in Kasaragod, Kannur, Mahe and Wayanad district. In 1994 the Institute shifted to a rented building atKannapuram. In the year 2011 the institute has shifted to own campus at Kanhirangad, Near Taliparamba.

8. EDP COURSES OFFERED IN RUDSET

Entrepreneurship training has been depicted as one of the most important step for entrepreneurship development. The basic premise of entrepreneurship development is that entrepreneurship need not necessarily be an inborn trait. It is possible to identify individuals

with 'latent entrepreneurial traits' through the application of certain behavioural tools and techniques which can be imparted through specially designed training courses known as Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDPs). The following are the major EDP courses offered in RUDSET per year. All the courses are offered with free of cost and boarding facility is provided to the participants during the course duration.

- Women's tailoring(women only)- 30 days
- Computer hardware-45 days
- Goat rearing-10 days
- Business management(REDP)-13 days
- Poultry – 10 days
- Computer DTP-45 days
- Photography and videography-30 days
- Beauty parlor management (women only)-30 days
- House wiring-30 days
- Computerized accounting -30 days
- Dairy farming and vermi composing- 10 days
- Motor Rewinding and pump set repairing-30 days
- Four wheeler driving-30 days
- Aluminum fabrication-30 days
- Honey bee keeping- 10 days
- Mobile Phone servicing-30 days
- Two wheeler mechanic-30 days
- Men's beauty Parlor (Men only)- 30 days

The following table gives the details of Programmes offered by RUDSET and the rate of growth of participants attending these courses. 71.47 percent of total course participants are now employed (4963/6944).

Source : Office of the Director, RUDSET, Kannur, January 2019

Year	No. of EDP	No. of Course Participants	Male	Female
2011	20	594	265	329
2012	29	834	453	381
2013	31	946	480	466
2014	31	948	518	430
2015	33	947	592	355
2016	33	828	428	400
2017	35	910	612	298
2018	35	937	467	470
Total	247	6944	3815	3129

There is an increasing trend in the number of courses offered by RUDSET and the number of participants over the years from 2011 to 2018. On an average 28 members are added to each year compared to the previous period. Number of male participants outnumbers their female counterpart except in the year 2011 and 2018.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROFILE OF COURSE PARTICIPANTS

The status based report of the course participants shows that from 2011 to 2018, out of the total participants majority are from OBC category(48.37) followed by religious minorities(30.73), Sc (5.79) and St's(3.04)

Year	SC	ST	OBC	Minorities	others
2011	45	18	263	198	70
2012	41	12	434	238	109
2013	61	22	571	172	120
2014	66	34	439	289	120
2015	47	31	441	331	97
2016	51	29	359	278	111
2017	46	32	402	314	116
2018	45	33	450	314	95
Total	402	211	3359	2134	838

Source : Office of the Director, RUDSET, Kannur, January 2019

Details of the RUDSET trainee's shows that among the applicants, priority shall be given to BPL, socially disadvantaged and vulnerable sections and rest of the seats are allotted to APL category.

Year	Female			Male			Total		
	BP L	APL	Differentially abled	BP L	APL	Differentially abled	BPL	APL	Differentially abled
2011	123	206	-	113	152	2	236	358	2
2012	46	335	2	84	369	3	130	704	5
2013	179	287	1	97	383	2	276	670	3
2014	104	326	2	88	430	3	192	756	5
2015	114	241	1	135	457	5	249	698	6
2016	111	289	1	90	338	1	201	627	2
2017	60	238	0	113	499	0	173	737	0
2018	187	283	2	140	327	3	327	610	5
Total	924	2205	9	860	2955	19	1784	5160	28

Source : Office of the Director, RUDSET, Kannur, January 2019

It is quite evident from the sample that many of the aspirants are from APL category, lack of proper representation from the disadvantaged groups shows the very little awareness about the courses among the general public. .

ANALYSIS OF SAMPLE SURVEY

A sample survey is collected from 100 alumni's of the RUDSET institute in order to understand the impact of EDP on employment creation and skill development and credit accessibility, and the results are as follows.

Variable	Category	No of trainees
Age	Less than 25	17
	25-35	41
	35-45	25
	45-55	17
Gender	Male	58
	Female	42
Caste	Forward Caste	17
	Other Backward Caste	53
	Other Eligible Caste	5
	Scheduled Caste	22
	Scheduled Tribe	3
Religion	Hindu	64
	Islam	25
	Christian	11
Educational attainment	Up to SSLC	50
	PDC/Plus Two	36
	Degree	14
Marital Status	Single	47
	Married	53
APL/BPL	APL	39
	BPL	61
District	Kannur	97
	Other Districts	3
Region	Urban	17
	Rural	83
Family size	Nuclear family	84
	Joint family	16

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

Majority of the alumni's are belongs to the age category 25-35, a large number of participants are from Kannur district, though there is no strict regional priority is existing in the selection of candidates, there are very few aspirants appearing the interview for the selection process. Most of the trainees are having a high school education. Regarding the awareness about the RUDSET courses is given in the following table

	Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Friend and family	50	50

Print/Electronic media	28	78
Social Networks Sites	14	92
others	8	100.0
Total	100	

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The factors that motivate a person to become an entrepreneur can be broadly classified into prime motivators, motives, compelling factor, facilitating factors and opportunity factors. A prime motivator refers to the entrepreneurs themselves and/or their friends or relatives. A question is asked to the alumni's that, from where they received the information regarding the RUDSET courses?. The answer depicts the role of friends and family and the very close network effects.

The major motives behind starting a new venture are to earn more money, to support one's family, to continue a family business or to achieve a higher social status. The factors that compel a person to start a new business can be unemployment or dissatisfaction with a particular job. Facilitating factors include the availability of idle funds at the entrepreneur's disposal, eagerness to make use of the skills the person has acquired over time, previous experience in the same line, support from friends or relatives, inherited property etc. The opportunity factors of entrepreneurship are trade information, business contacts, knowledge about sources of raw materials etc., and good education and training.

Table-6	
Motivating factors to Join RUDSET	
Factors	Frequency
To get business idea and to start a business	53
To gain knowledge and skills	25
For personal growth	8
Cost free course	11
Other reason	3
Total	100

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The major motivating factor to join the RUDSET course is to gain knowledge about business. EDP has a direct impact on development of entrepreneurial skills in terms of business knowledge, drive and determination and communication. Primary data analysis of the sample study depicts that there is significant impact on trainees in terms of their entrepreneurship skills and competencies. Also training has impact on the development of managerial and competitive skills. Out of the total sample 94 percent of them said that EDP enhanced their business knowledge and self confidence 983 percent)

Skills	Mean/ percent	Std. Deviation	N
Business knowledge	.94	.232	100
Risk taking mentality	.72	.454	100
Self confidence	.83	.378	100
Leadership Ability	.67	.478	100
Entrepreneurial skill	.72	.454	100
Creativity and Innovation	.69	.467	100
Communication Skill	.69	.467	100

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The above analysis is also checked for reliability with the help of reliability statistics Cronbach's Alpha, the value of the results shows high reliability in the statement of the trainees that it EDP helped them to improve their skills.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
.942	.931	7

The results of the study suggest that entrepreneurship By participating in entrepreneurship programs, owners/managers of small businesses learnt better managerial skills like pro-activity, creative tendency, drive and determination, and business knowledge which in turn lead to better performance of entrepreneurs and provide a unique competitive edge to the enterprises. However, the results have indicated that entrepreneurship training has great role in providing business knowledge and creation of self confidence but very least role in improving the leadership qualities and creative tendencies among the entrepreneurs. Thus a need is felt to make by the amendment in Entrepreneurship Development Training Programmes and include the leadership and creative tendency skills in the entrepreneurship course design.

9. EMPLOYMENT PROSPECTS

Out of the total 100 trainees interviewed, 53 are employed, and remaining 47 is planning to start a business in a short time span. The employment status of the respondents is given below

	Frequen cy	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Sole proprietorship	40	75.5	75.5
Partnership	11	20.8	96.3
Association	2	3.7	100.0
Total	53	100.0	

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

Sample analysis highlights that, 75.5 percent of the trainees are self employed and their major source of finance is bank loan. One of the interesting finding is that, RUDSET makes all the necessary arrangements to their credit accessibility with their tie-up institutions Syndicate bank and Canara bank.

Source of financing the business	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Own/self incurred	5	9.4	9.4
Bank loan	41	77.4	86.8
Loan from micro credit institution	4	7.6	94.4
Friends and family supported	3	5.7	100.0
Total	53	100.0	

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

9.4 percent of the alumni's raised their investment form own fund, 7.6 percent with the help of micro credit institution and the rest with the help of friends and family.

case		total investment incurred/expected	Monthly expenditure incurred/expected	Monthly returns received/expected
Course participant planning to start a business	Mean	125000.00	5705.88	17058.82
	No. of sample	47	47	47
	Std. Deviation	98425.09	7139.37	16868.87
Course participants already started a business	Mean	376315.79	22342.12	72236.84
	No. of sample	53	53	53
	Std. Deviation	350146.17	24410.87	108150.15
Total sample	Mean	257638.89	14486.11	46180.56
	No. of sample	100	100	100
	Std. Deviation	289261.34	20017.67	83221.92

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The investment expenditure incurred by the person ranges from 1 lakh to 4 lakh, with a return of Rs. 1.5 to 7 lakh. The major issue related to the courses offered in RUDSET is the lack of awareness about the courses among the general public. Few are opting the courses

without much proper objectives, though it is offered at free of cost. Wrong selection of courses is also another issue faced by the participants. Centre is at the peak of its facility to accommodate new course participants, need encouragement and support from the centre and state government. RUDEST is taking some follow –up programmes through Correspondence, Branch Level Meet, Door to Door visit, Taluk level meet, Reply through Post Card, Unit Visit by the officials of the Institute by showing much concern for its stake holders.

10. CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurship Development Programme is designed to help an individual in strengthening his entrepreneurial motive and in acquiring skills and capabilities necessary for playing his entrepreneurial role effectively and also to make him enable to get an employment and lead a better life in the society. RUDSET has to widen its entrepreneurship development programmes by giving proper awareness about their courses among the less privileged sections of the society. The centre needed immense support from the government for its venture to eradicate unemployment problem among rural youth.

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Paper 32**SMART ENERGY METERING BASED ON IOT AND POCKET PICKING USING ARDUINO AND GSM****Nisha and Nikita V Nakte**

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Abstract:

Here the idea of smart energy meter using IoT and Arduino have been introduced. In this method we are using Arduino because it is energy efficient i.e. it consume less power, it is fastest and has two UARTS. Energy meter which is already installed at our houses are not replaced, but a small modification on the already installed meters can change the existing meters into smart meters. The use of GSM module provides a feature of notification through SMS. One can easily access the meter working through web page that we designed. Current reading with cost can be seen on web page. Automatic ON & OFF of meter is possible. Threshold value setting and sending of notification is the additional task that we are performing.

Energy theft is a very common problem in countries like India where consumers of energy are increasing consistently as the population increases. Utilities in electricity system are destroying the amounts of revenue each year due to energy theft.

Keywords: Smart Energy Meter, Pocket Picking, Electric board, UARTS, IoT, GSM, Wi-Fi, webpage.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Smart Energy Metering based on IoT and Pocket Picking using Arduino and GSM” addresses the problems faced by both the consumers and the distribution companies. It deals with smart energy meter, which utilizes the features of embedded systems i.e. combination of hardware and software in order to implement desired functionality. With the use of GSM modem the consumer as well as service provider will get the used energy reading with the respective amount, Consumers will even get notification in the form text through GSM when they are about to reach their threshold value, that they have set. Also with the help of Wi-Fi modem the consumer can monitor his consumed reading and can set the threshold value through webpage.

This system enables the electricity department to read the meter readings monthly without a person visiting each house. This can be achieved by the use of Arduino unit that continuously monitor and records the energy meter reading in its permanent (non-volatile) memory location. This system continuously records the reading and the live meter reading can be displayed on webpage to the consumer on request. This system also can be used to disconnect the power supply of the house when needed.

The electric energy used by unauthorized person cause losses to utility and also pollutes the environment. Losses in electricity energy sector can come under two sets: technical and managerial. Technical losses of electrical energy are caused due to the functional tendency

of the equipment used from generating station to the distributing station. Non-Technical losses are due to lack of utility labor interference periodically.

2. ARCHITECTURAL MODEL

Figure 1: Architectural Diagram

The explanation of the above architectural model is as follows

- When the various appliances of the household consume energy the energy meter reads the reading continuously and this consumed load can be seen on meter.
 - We can see that the LED on meter continuously blinks which counts the meter reading.
 - Based on the blinking, the units are counted.
- Normally, 3200 blinks is one unit.
- In this we are trying to develop, a system in which Arduino Uno act as main controller, which continuously monitor energy meter.
 - As per the blinking of LED on energy meter the Arduino will measure the unit consumption.
 - The measured reading with the calculation of the cost will be continuously displayed on web page that we have designed.
 - Threshold value can be set on webpage with the help of Wi-Fi, as per the consumer's requirement. When the consumers reading will be near about to the set threshold value it will send a notification value to the consumer.
 - This threshold value notification will increase the awareness amongst the consumer about the energy.
 - When the consumer gets the notification he can visit the webpage and change the threshold value.
 - If the consumer is not aware with the threshold notification, then the meter will automatically get off. Then the consumer has to visit the webpage again and increment the threshold value. By the incrementation, the meter will automatically get ON.
 - Finally the overall monthly bill with cost will be sent to customer as well as service

provider in the form of text at first day of every month.

3. EASE OF USE BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 2: Block Diagram Representation

The above block diagram represents our proposed ‘SMART ENERGY METER BASED ON IOT’ system:

3.1 ENERGY METER:

Energy meter or watt-hour meter is an electrical instrument that measures the amount of electrical energy used by the consumers. Utilities is one of the electrical departments, which install these instruments at every place like homes, industries, organizations, commercial buildings to charge for the electricity consumption by loads such as lights, fans, refrigerators and other home appliances. Energy meter measures the rapid voltage and currents, calculate their product and give instantaneous power. This power is integrated over a time interval, which gives the energy utilized over that time period.

3.2 SIGNALCONDITONER(P817):

Figure 3: Signal Conditioning Circuit

Above figure shown is the simple internal working of opto-coupler P817 which we are using as signal conditioning block. As we can see on a working meter that one LED continuously blinks, it is nothing but indicates the count of power. The LED whenever blinks it produces only 0.7v which is not suitable for Arduino board to capture, so to remove this error we are using this block. When the LED blinks the diode will conduct, transistor will get active and it will give 5v at output which we are externally giving to transistor. Whenever LED will blink the 5v supply will be provided to Arduino board and it will count them. We are using signal conditioning block to increase voltage.

3.3 ARDUINO UNO(ATMEGA 328):

Arduino board is the heart of our system. Entire functioning of system depends on this board. Arduino reacts to the 5v supply given by opto-coupler and keeps on counting the supply and then calculates the power consumed and also the cost. This data, it continuously stores on webpage, so that users can visit any time and check their consumption. It even reacts accordingly as per programmed, to the situations like message sending during threshold value etc.

3.4 MAX 232:

We are using MAX 232 for serial communication with the components that are GSM module and Wi-Fi module MAX232 is used to provide TTL to the components as per the requirement. GSM needs TTL so it is connected to Arduino through MAX232. Some Wi-Fi module doesn't require TTL because it's already build in it and some may require based on its working.

3.5 GSM MODULE (SIM900):

GSM stands for Global System for Mobile communication. It is widely used mobile communication modem system in the world. GSM is an open and digital cellular technology used for transmitting mobile voice and data services operates at the 850MHZ, 900MHZ, 1800MHZ, 1900MHZ frequency bands. It has ability to carry 64kbps to 120Mbps of data rates. In our system GSM is used to send the notification of threshold reaching to consumer and for sending message of total consumption of unit with cost to the service provider and consumer

3.6 Wi-Fi MODULE (ESP8266):

Wi-Fi stands for Wireless Fidelity. We are using Wi-Fi which acts as heart for IoT. Through Wi-Fi the consumer can set changes in threshold value, he can ON and OFF the energy meter. Time to time the readings of units and cost are displayed on webpage. Consumer can accesses the Arduino board and meter with help of Wi- Fi.

3.7 WEBPAGE (HTML):

We designed webpage for operating Arduino and Energy Meter with the help of HTML. HTML stands for Hypertext Markup Language. It is a standard markup language for creating web pages and web applications with Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and JAVA scripts it forms a triad of cornerstone technologies for World Wide Web. Web browser receives HTML documents from a Web server or from local storage and render them into multimedia web pages.

HTML describes the structure of web page semantically and originally included cues for the appearance of the document. HTML elements are the building blocks of HTML pages.

3.8 DRIVER CIRCUIT (moc3071):

Figure 4: Driver Circuit

- It is a 6 pin device known as opto coupler or opto isolator.
 - In our project we are using this opto coupler to cut off the AC load.
- It is connected to the SSR to cut off the AC load

6. OVERVIEW OF INTERNET OF THINGS

Figure 6: IoT Working

Figure 5: IoT Representation

The IoT allows objects to be sensed or controlled remotely across existing network infrastructure, creating opportunities for more direct integration of the physical world into computer-based systems, and resulting in improved efficiency, accuracy and economic benefit in addition to reduced human intervention. When IoT is augmented with sensors and actuators, the technology becomes an instance of the more general class of cyber- physical system, which also encompasses technologies such as smart grids, virtual power plants, smart homes and smart cities.

IoT Working:

People also want to communicate with all non-living things through internet such as home appliances, furniture’s, stationeries, cloths etc. The people already have a lot of technologies to interact with living things but IoT enables to communicate with non-living things with comfort manner. IoT is a convergence of several technologies like ubiquitous, pervasive computing, Ambient Intelligence, Sensors, Actuators, Communications technologies, Internet Technologies, Embedded systems etc.

7. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF POCKET PICKING

The system architecture of Arduino and GSM based smart energy meter is shown in the Fig. 7. The energy consumption is being calculated using the energy meter IC and Arduino.

In order to prevent pocket picking, detection program is present in the Arduino. Arduino and GSM based smart energy meter can be divided into several parts as Energy Meter IC, LCD, Arduino, GSM modem, Relay, Opto-coupler, Lever switch, Display Unit and Power Supply Unit etc.

Fig-7: Architecture Diagram

7. RESULT

1] Current unit with cost will be displayed.

2] When threshold is about to over the following message will be sent to consumer.

4] The monthly bill with unit consumption and user Id will be sent to service provider.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Smart energy meter based on IoT is used to calculate the energy consumption of the

household, and even make the energy unit reading to be handy. Hence it reduces the wastage of energy and bring awareness among all. Even it will deduct the manual intervention. In the case of pocket picking, defaulter meter line cutting/joining labor system is reduced.

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Paper 32

INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR OF WOMEN INVESTORS IN THE STOCK MARKET: A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MANGALURU

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Introduction:

Investment means keeping some money aside so that it grows more valuable after a period of time. At the same time investing is difficult because people have to be patient and disciplined for long stretches of time. It's because all around us we see people spending and having the time of their lives while we sacrifice those pleasures. Investing involves lot of decisions - differentiating between needs and wants. Men and women differ in their approach to the investment game. Particularly stock market investment has become popular among men and women. In most of the cases the women want to earn stable income. While forming investment portfolio women are concerned about safety, liquidity and profitably but men mostly think about profitability alone. This study is an attempt to study the behavior pattern of women who invest in stock market.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The following are the objectives of the study:

- To study the investment behaviour of women in stock market in Mangaluru
- To find out the awareness level, frequency of investment and objectives behind investment.
- To find out whether the women investors are looking for long term growth or risk or return of liquidity and to analysis their long term financial goals.
- To study the various factors affecting financial behavior of women investor , to analyze how women handle financial task, risk and the influence of investment in social empowerment of women.

• **METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY**

a) Primary Data

Primary data has been used in this study. Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire by conducting personal interviews with women who invest in stock market.

b) Secondary Data For this study secondary data was collected through various sources such as magazines, articles, news papers and business journals.

Literature Review

- V.A.AVADHANI, INVESTMENT MANAGEMENT He says investment is many things to many persons. If one person advanced some money to another, it may be his loan which may be considered his investment for a return. If another person has purchased one kg of gold for the purpose of price appreciation or a consumer durable like washing machine for the flow of service it is his investment. If he purchases an insurance plan or a pension plan it is an investment. Hence there is various types of investment for different persons. Investment activity includes buying and selling or trading in the claims on money or promissory notes. An investment for one may be disinvestment of another as in the case of stock market trading or may be a fresh investment in a new issue. Saving is abstaining from present consumption for a future use. Savings are sometimes autonomous coming from households as a matter of habit. But bulk of the savings come for specific objectives like interest income, future needs, contingencies, precautionary purposes, or growth in future wealth , leading to rise in the standard of living .
- M RANGANATHAN, INVESTMENT ANALYSIS AND PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT, (2009) Investors' behavior deals with emotional reaction people experience after realizing they have made an error in judgment. It has faced with the prospect of selling a stock, investors become emotionally affected by the price at which they purchased the stock. They avoid selling it as a way to avoid the regret of having made a bad investment, as well as the embarrassment of reporting a loss JEROME BERNARD COHEM, EDWARD D ZINBERG, INVESTMENT ANALYSIS AND PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT Conducted a very detailed research in gender differences on different types of investments. His results concluded that both genders tend to choose differently in types of investments. For example, men preferred mutual bonds more than women did. H also found that almost twice men than women chose health insurance. More men also chose life insurance, stock, shares and recurring deposits. However, the only type of investments chosen by more women was fixed deposits.
- SANDEEP SHANBHAG, IN THE WONDERLAND OF INVESTMENT, (2016-2017) The study was aimed to measure financial knowledge in investment decision making, which will be helpful in this study to measure the gender gap and concluded if financial literacy is really a factor which accounts for gender gap differences. The women tend to have relatively lower level of financial knowledge. Concluded that people must be “financially knowledgeable in order to make informed investment decisions and take advantages of investment opportunities.”
- CHANDRA P, INVESTMENT ANALYSIS AND PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT(2008).Investment behavior of rural investors in their study states that the investment culture among the people of a country is an essential prerequisite for capital formation and the faster growth of an economy. Investment culture refers to the attitude, perceptions and willingness of the individuals and institutions in placing their savings in various financial assets more popularly known as securities.

- SELLAPPAN BALASWAMY AND VANITHA SOMASUNDARAM, INVESTMENT BEHAVIOR OF EQUITY INVESTOR, (2013)
In their study, “Gender difference in risk behavior in financial decision making: An experimental investment strategies as men and women are motivated by different “needs”. They put forward the idea that these difference “needs” and therefore strategies, may be that women are looking more for security whereas men are looking for returns.

Data analysis

Table showing demographic profile of the respondents

occupation	No of respondents	PERCENTAGE
Government sector Employee	7	11.7%
Private sector Employee	18	30%
Self Employed	20	33.3%
Others(home makers and students)	15	25%
Age	No of respondents	PERCENTAGE
Between 20 and 30	24	40%
Between 30 and 40	18	30%
Between 40 and 50	10	16%
Above 50	8	14%
Marital status	No of Respondents	PERCENTAGE
Married	38	63.3%
Single	22	36.7%
Annual income	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Less than Rs100000	15	25%
Between Rs100000 and Rs250000	18	30%
Between Rs250000 and 500000	17	28.3%
Above 500000	10	16.7%

Interpretation:

- It can be seen that 33.33% of the respondents are self-employed,30% are private sector employees,12% are government employees, and the remaining 25% includes home makers, students etc., Here the trend of the women becoming financially independent is highlighted.
- Most of the women investors are in the age group between 20-30 years and the least number of investors are above 50 years of age, this may be because of lack of knowledge about investment among older generation.
- It can be observed that 63.30% of the respondents are married and the remaining 36.70% of the respondents are not married. Therefore it can be said that most of the married women have the tendency to invest in much secure investments which gives benefit in the long run and the rest of the respondents are said to be more risk averse when compared to married people.
- Majority of the women are earning an income which lies between Rs.100000 and Rs.250000, 28% of the respondents earn between Rs.250000 and Rs.500000, 25% of the respondents earn less than Rs.100000 and the remaining 17% earn more than 500000. These investors plan their investments in accordance with their earnings.

Table showing investment pattern of women investor

Income invested	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Less than 10%	36	30%
10% to 20%	52	43.3%
20% to 30%	28	23.4%
More than 30%	4	3.3%
Preferred investment	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Equity shares	74	61.67%
Preference shares	24	20%
Debentures	22	18.33%
Type of investor	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Diversified investor	92	76.67%
Unvaried investor	28	23.33%

Frequency of investment	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Weekly	4	3.33%
Monthly	42	35%
Quarterly	28	23%
Half yearly	24	20%
Yearly	22	18.33%
Rate of return	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
6% to 8%	22	18.33%
8% to 10%	46	38.33%
10% to 12%	36	30%
More than 12%	16	13.4% %
Behavioral pattern	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Risk Seeker	36	30%
Risk Averse	30	25%
Risk Neutral	54	45%
Factors considered while investing	No of Respondents	PERCENTAGE
long term growth	10	8%
Risk	36	30%
Return	50	42%
Retirement Income	4	3%
Liquidity	20	17.00%

Interpretation:

- Majority of the women have invested 10% to 20% of their income making them conservative investors. 30% of them have invested less than 10% of their income,

23.40% of them have invested 20% to 30% of their income. The remaining 3.30% of the respondents have invested more than 30% of their income as they have thorough knowledge of all the investment avenues and are willing to take more risks.

- 62% of the investors invest in equity shares and gain ownership rights of that company. 20% of the investors invest in preference shares and they receive dividend payments before equity share holders. 18% of the respondents invests in debentures and are free to exchange debentures for company stocks if given the option to.
- It can be seen that majority of the investors invest in the company with higher capital gain than the company with high dividend policy this may be because high dividend yield doesn't always mean that a stock is a good choice, there are times when a high dividend yield means the company might not have future investment project.
- 77% of the investors prefer to diversify their investment in order to reduce the risk, whereas 23% of the investors prefer to invest in the same securities as they do not want to involve any change in their investment pattern.
- It shows that 3.33% of the investors invest weekly, 18.33% invest yearly, 20% invest half yearly, 23% invest quarterly and majority of the investors invest monthly which helps them to stay focused on their long-term goals.
- Majority of investors expect to achieve a return of 8 to 12% on their investment. An investor typically sets the required rate of return by adding a risk premium to the interest percentage that could be gained by investing excess funds in a risk-free investment, 30% of women expect a return of 10 to 12%, 18.33% expect a return of 6 to 8% and 13.4% expects a return more than 12% on their investment.
- Majority of 45% of the investors are risk neutral where the investor places himself in the middle of the risk spectrum, represented by risk seeking investors at one end and risk averse investors at the other end. Whereas 30% of the investors are risk seekers and 25% of the investors are risk averse.

Findings

- Majority of the women are willing to take some risk to get overall high returns, few of the women prefer investing in safer investments and very less percentage of women are not concerned about short term decrease in their investment for high, long term returns.
- Majority of investors depend upon the financial advisors while investing due to lack of confidence or lack of knowledge about investment. 23% of investor depend on the brokers, 22% of investors take decisions on their own based on their knowledge, experience and awareness level.
- Majority of investors are satisfied with the diversification of assets and dividend they receive, dissatisfied with the quick plan, highly satisfied with safety and tax benefit they get from their investments

SUGGESTIONS

- Women should be encouraged to invest in more avenues and participate in the investment avenues which involve high risks and also high returns.

- Women should increase their awareness level of the portfolio diversification to spread their risk.
- Women should recognize their financial independence and plan for the future to make it better.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that generally, women are conservative investors and they feel that safeguarding what they have as their top priority. These investors want to avoid risk particularly the risk of losing any principal that is their original investment even if that means they will have to settle for very modest returns. They prefer investing in equity shares when compared with other stock market avenues.

Paper 33

A STUDY ON E-BANKING SERVICES IN MANGALURU CITY- CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND AWARENESS

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Abstract

E banking is a method of banking in which the customer conducts transactions electronically via the Internet. Internet banking is changing the banking industry, having the major effects on banking relationships. Electronic banking has many names like e banking, virtual banking, online banking, or internet banking. It is simply the use of electronic and telecommunications network for delivering various banking products and services. Through e-banking, a customer can access his account and conduct many transactions using his computer or mobile phone. It is more helpful because there is lesser transaction costs, a reduced margin for human error, lesser paperwork, reduced fixed costs, more loyal customers. The popular services under e-banking in India are, ATMs (*Automated Teller Machines*), Telephone Banking, Electronic Clearing Cards, Smart Cards, EFT (*Electronic Funds Transfer*) System, ECS (*Electronic Clearing Services*), Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Telebanking, Door-step Banking. Tap, click and swipe-these are the new sounds of money. Modern technology is fast replacing paper with computer files, and banks too have come a long way from the old days of manually recording transactions in registers and tallying them up at the end of the day.

Keywords: e-banking, internet, advantages, service.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Since technology has penetrated virtually in all spheres of life, banking is no exception to that. The world is changing at a staggering rate and technology is considered to be the key driver for these changes around us .The adoption of technology by the banks brought more reliability , efficiency, security and privacy in it's services ever than before. Today any user with a personal computer and a browser can get connected to his bank's website to perform any of the virtual banking functions. Thus, services of the bank have become more users friendly.

E-banking provides enormous benefits to consumers in terms of ease and cost of transaction, either through internet ,telephone or other electronic delivery, besides it has become one of the most essential technological changes in the financial industry. Many activities are handled electronically due to the acceptance of information technology at home as well as at workplace .thus it made time and distance irrelevant to many transactions.

2.OBJECTIVES:

1. To know the perceptual mapping of internet banking users.
2. To find out the reasons why the customers are using internet banking services.
3. To analyse the general awareness of e-banking among the people.
4. To identify the important factor that influences the customer satisfaction towards E banking.

3.METHODOLOGY:

The research study was conducted to know the peoples’ perception towards e-banking services. This was done through the collection of data from 42 respondents from Mangalore city. The research instruments used in collecting primary data was a questionnaire. The questionnaire and survey was undertaken through the means of google forms. The questionnaire was prepared on the basis of secondary information gathered.

4.DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table -1 Age-wise classification of respondents

Percentage	No. of respondents	Age
7	3	Below 20
83	35	20 to 30
4.76	2	30 to 40
2.38	1	40 to 50
2.38	1	Above 50
100	42	TOTAL

From above diagram, it is noticed that respondents comprising of 83% belong to the age group of 20-30 years, followed by 7% customers belong to the age group of below 20 years.

Table -2 Gender -wise classification of respondents

Percentage	No. of respondents	Gender
64.3	27	Female
35.7	15	Male
100	42	Total

The above table -2 shows that 64.3% are female respondents and only 35.7% are male respondents .

TABLE- 3: Awareness of e-banking services among the people.

percentage	No. of respondents	Scale
90.5	38	Yes
2.4	1	No
7.1	3	May be
100	42	TOTAL

It is revealed from the table -3 that about 90.5% of people aware of e-banking services, provided by the banks.

TABLE -4 About the no. of users of e-banking services.

Percentage	No. of respondents	Scale
83.3	35	Yes
16.7	7	No
100	42	Total

The above diagram, shows that majority ie.83.3% people have been using e-banking services, only 16.7% of people are not using e-banking services.

TABLE: 5 The main reasons for using e-banking services

percentage	No. of respondents	Reasons
10.8	5	Better information
51.4	21	24 hours services
32.4	14	Simplification of process
5.4	2	saves time
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

With regard to the main reasons for using e-banking services above diagram -5 shows that 51.4% of the people use the facility because of the 24*7 services of the e-banking. On the other hand 32.4% of the respondents said that it is simplification in the process made them to use e-banking.

TABLE-6 The opinions with regard to the Reasons for, few people not using the online banking service

Percentage	No. of respondents	Reasons
13	5	Do not have internet at home
26.1	11	Find the process too difficult
43.5	18	Don't trust internet services for managing money
17.4	8	Not interested
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

From the above table -6 it is evident from the opinions of the 43% of respondents about the reasons some people not using e-banking that it is because they don't trust internet services for managing money ,followed by 26.1%of respondents saying it is because since they find the process too difficult.

TABLE-7 About the trusted level of the security of online banking services

Percentage	No. of respondents	scale
16.7	7	completely
61.9	26	somewhat
14.3	6	unsure
7.1	3	Not at all
100	42	TOTAL

When the respondents are asked to give their views on internet banking services on a scale with regard to the security and privacy, it is found from the table -7 that about 61.9% of the respondents somewhat trust the security level of the internet and 14.3% of respondents opined complete trust with regard to the security and privacy of the internet. Only 16.7% of them are still unsure about it, while 7.1 % of the respondents expressed disappointment with regard to it.

TABLE-8 Opinions about the convenience of manual banking with comparison to the internet banking.

Percentage	No. of respondents	scale
14.3	6	strongly agree
50	21	Agree
31	13	disagree
4.7	2	strongly disagree
100	42	TOTAL

As per the table -8 about the convenience of manual banking with comparison to internet banking, 14.3% of the people considers manual banking is more convenient than that of internet banking by strongly agreeing with it ,followed by the 50% of the respondents agreed with the same . On the other hand 31% of the people disagree saying internet banking is more convenient than that of manual banking services.

TABLE-9 About the most used e-banking service

Percentage	No. of respondents	Types
9.5	4	Checking account
21.4	9	cash management
66.7	28	Debit and credit cards
2.4	1	Business loans
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

It is revealed from the table-9 that the usage of e-banking services like debit cards and credit cards services are mostly being used by the people as 66.7% of the responded the same. Rest of the 21.4% of the people said about cash management purpose followed by 9.5% of the response pertaining to the checking account.

TABLE-10 Main disadvantage of e-banking that discourages one from using it

Percentage	No. of respondents	Disadvantages
45.2	19	Security concern
16.7	7	lack of assistance
5.1	2	impersonality services
33	14	Dependent on internet services
-	-	other
100	42	TOTAL

when the respondents are asked about the disadvantages of e-banking services majority ie.45.2% worried about the security issue .rest of the 33.3% of respondents supported the same expressing displeasure about the service dependency on internet .However, it is 16.7% considered disadvantages like lack of assistance and 5.1% of people considered impersonal services as a discouraging factors.

TABLE 11–Opinions with regard to the important factor that influences the customer satisfaction towards internet banking.

Percentage	No. of respondents	Important factors
21.4	9	service quality
-	-	web design &content
35.7	15	security and privacy
42.9	18	convenience and speed
-	-	Other
100	42	TOTAL

From the above table-11 pertaining to the questions regarding to the factors influencing the customer satisfaction towards e banking majority ie.42,9% of the respondents stressed the importance of convenience and speed in the services. and rest of the 35.7% of people said it is security and privacy gives them satisfaction with regard to the services provided .however only 21 .4% of the respondents went with the option of service quality.

TABLE-12 Rating with regard to the overall quality of the e banking services.

Percentage	No. of respondents	Ratings
14.3	6	excellent
42.9	18	very good
40.5	17	good
2.3	1	poor
100	42	TOTAL

with regard to the rating of quality of the e banking services table -12 shows 42.9% of the respondents considers 'very good' and 40.5% of the people consider 'good'. and 14.3% of the people consider e –banking services as excellent.

5. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

- The study is restricted only to Mangalore city.
- Since the survey was conducted through google form, could reach only technically literate people.
- The sample size is limited to 42 only.

6. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- With the help of our study it is found that out of 42 respondents ,majority 90.5% of people are aware of e-banking services provided by the banks.
- Our study also reveals that majority 83.3% of the people have been using e-banking services.
- Besides ,we found out the reasons like 24*7 e-banking services ,simplified process involved in the services are some of the reasons for the frequent use of e-banking services as it made the transaction convenient and easier.
- It is understood with the help of our study that most of the people are worried about the security and privacy issues of the internet as the e-banking services works through internet.
- It is revealed that internet e-banking is more convenient than traditional manual banking services as people opined the same
- It is found that the e-banking services like uses of debit card and credit card are being used by the majority of the people and playing predominant role in the e-banking industry

7. SUGGESTIONS:

- banks needs to focus more on offering standard online services to its customers by providing exceptional customer services through technologies like finger print readers ,card readers, and other new and emerging financial technologies which ensures privacy and reduce fraud concerns.
- Employ ever-evolving biometrics, such as retina scanning, to reduce customer frustrations while increasing online banking security.
- Proper training needs to be given to the bank employees pertaining to the technologies that are being used so that customers will not get any kind of confusion with regard to the uses of new e-banking service.
- The banks should conduct an effective research for making more and more awareness about E banking service.
- The banks have to do new process and strategies to create more security coverage.

8. CONCLUSION:

The paper makes an attempt to understand E banking services. The result of the study shows that convenience and speed is the most important factor that influences the customer satisfaction towards internet banking. Convenience and speed is the top reasons why peoples like online banking. People are more convenient in internet banking than manual banking. So banks have to rethink their strategies to ensure they stay relevant to modern consumers.

To create the awareness of E banking it is very important that, the Government and all the associated bodies should all offer their support in spreading E banking awareness. And it will help to increase the awareness of E banking among the people. Bank should make efforts to increase customer's awareness about internet banking facilities by conducting training programmes.

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Questionnaire on: “A study on E-Banking Services in Mangaluru city- Customer satisfaction and Awareness”

This Questionnaire aims to know the point of view of general public on “E banking services” and to collect their suggestions to alleviate it.

1. Name
2. Age
3. Gender
4. Are you aware of the E banking services provided by banks?
 - Yes
 - No
 - May be
5. Do you use E banking?
 - Yes
 - No
6. If yes, which one is the main reason for you to use E banking?
 - Better information
 - 24 hour service
 - Simplification of process
 - Limited time available
 - Other
7. Do you trust the security of online banking services?
 - Completely
 - Somewhat
 - Unsure
 - Not at all
8. Internet banking is more convenient than manual banking
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
9. Which type of e banking service mostly you use?
 - Checking account
 - Cash management
 - Debit and credit cards
 - Business loans
 - Other
10. Which is the main disadvantage of e banking that discourages you from using?
 - Security concern

- Lack of assistance
- Impersonality service
- Dependent on internet
- Other

11. In your opinion, which is one of the important factors, that influence the customer satisfaction towards internet banking?

- Service factory
- We design and content
- Security and recovery
- Convenience and speed
- Other

12. What do you feel about overall E banking service quality of your bank?

- Excellent
- Very good
- Good
- Poor

13. Suggestions (if any)

Paper 34**ACHIEVEMENTS AND OUTCOMES OF
INNOVATIONS: A CASE STUDY OF THE FOOD
PROCESSING INDUSTRY****Mohammed Ridhwan, Nithesh Shetty**MBA Evening, 1st year, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, City
Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575 001.**Abstract**

This study analyzes the role played by food processing industries in India. With the advent of planned economy from 1951 and the subsequent industrial policy followed by Government of India, both planners and Government earmarked special role for small-scale industries and medium scale industries in the Indian economy. As per the Ministry of Food Processing Industry as data source, the food processing sector is highly fragmented industry, it widely comprises of the following sub-segments: fruits and vegetables, milk and milk products, beer and alcoholic beverages, meat and poultry, marine products, grain processing, packaged or convenience food and packaged drinks. A huge number of entrepreneurs in this industry are small in terms of their production and operations, and are largely concentrated in the unorganized segment. India is the world's second largest producer of food after China but accounts for less than 1.5 per cent of international food trade. The total food production in India is likely to double in the next ten years and there is an opportunity for large investments in food and food processing technologies, skills and equipment, especially in areas of Canning, Dairy and Food Processing, Specialty Processing, Packaging and Frozen Food. India is a country of over 1.10 billion consumers, increasing urban population is also another factor for growth and there is a large untapped domestic market of consumers in the food processing sector.

Keywords: Innovations, Sales Growth, Organized Food Processing, Agriculture.**1. Introduction**

The term food processing refers to the task of value addition to the agricultural or horticultural produce which can be accomplished in different ways viz. grading, sorting and packaging of these things in a systematic manner. It helps in the preservation of food items by increasing their shelf life. It also leads to their qualitative up-gradation thereby magnifying their functional utility. It covers a diverse range of products from various sectors like agriculture, horticulture, plantation, animal husbandry and fisheries.

The Food Processing industry in India is undergoing a significant growth. Food processing industry accounts for 35% of our country's total food market and is ranked fifth in terms of production, consumption, export and expected growth. With increase in online food ordering, the food processing industry is witnessing an incredible growth. This growing demand beckons the question; is the industry equipped enough to match the supply? The food processing industry in India has a high concentration of unorganized segments, accounting for almost 75 per cent across all product categories.

2. Objectives

- To know the contribution to economy by Food processing industry
- To analyse the Benefits of Food processing industry
- To know the challenges faced by this industry

3. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY:

The proposed methodology is studies on the above said objectives are based on the secondary data. These projects consist of graphical representation obtained from secondary data.

4. Discussions:

The Food Processing industry plays prominent role in the Indian economy. Food processing has an important role to play in linking Indian farmers to consumers in the domestic and international markets. The industry engages approximately 1.77 million people in around 39,319 registered units with fixed capital of \$ 29.2 billion and aggregate output of around \$ 144.6 billion. Major industries constituting the Food processing industry are grains, sugar, edible oils, beverages and dairy products. The food processing industry is one of the largest industries in India and ranks fifth in terms of production, consumption and exports. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries (MoFPI) is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. It has approved proposals for joint ventures (JV), foreign collaborations, industrial licenses, and 100 per cent export oriented units.

5. Market Size

The Indian food and grocery market is the world's sixth largest, with retail market contributing about 70 per cent of the sales. The Indian food processing industry accounts for 32 per cent of the country's total food market, one of the largest industries in India and is ranked fifth in terms of production, consumption, export and expected growth. It contributes around 8.80 and 8.39 per cent of Gross Value Added (GVA) in Manufacturing and Agriculture respectively, 13 per cent of India's exports and six per cent of total industrial investment. The online food ordering business in India is in its nascent stage, but witnessing exponential growth. With online food delivery players like FoodPanda, Zomato, TinyOwl and Swiggy building scale through partnerships, the organised food business has a huge potential and a promising future. According to Annual Survey of Industries (ASI), the total number of registered food processing factories in the country is 37,175. Andhra accounts for 25% of the total

registered food processing units followed by Tamil Nadu (14%), Telangana (10%), Maharashtra (8%) and Punjab (7.5%).

The food industry in India has, in the last few years, seen a lot of foreign investment. The Department of Industrial Policies and Promotion (DIPP) states that India received around USD 7.54 billion FDI from April 2000 to March 2017. The CII has predicted that the food processing sector has the potential to attract around USD 33 billion FDI in the next ten years and also generate nine million person-days of employment.

To name a few giant investments in the industry:

1. Amazon, the global e-commerce giant, has plans to diversify its business by entering the Indian food retailing market and invest around USD 515 million in the next five years.
2. Parle Agro Pvt Ltd has kept its target to achieve an annual target of Rs. 5,000 crore by 2018, and to do so have launched new products like Frooti Fizz.
3. US-based Cargill Inc aims to grow its branded consumer business in India by two times by 2020.
4. Uber Technologies Inc has entered the food delivery service with its brand UberEATS.

6. Key sub-segments of the Food processing industry in India

6.1 Dairy

India is the world leader in milk production, producing around 146 million MT of milk. The Indian dairy market is amongst the largest and fastest growing markets in the world. Per capita availability of milk in India has reached 322 grams per day, higher than the world average of 293.7 grams per day. Changing lifestyle patterns, increasing disposable incomes and increasing health consciousness are the key growth drivers for milk and high value milk products in India. To tap this surging demand most dairy players have entered the processed dairy products market with introduction of value added products like ghee, flavored yogurt, butter (with variants), flavored milk, cheese etc. New value added dairy products, innovative packaging, cold chain and new technology for value added dairy product processing offer tremendous potential for technology suppliers, processors as well as service providers.

Uttar Pradesh is the highest milk producing state in India contributing around 18% to the total milk production, followed by Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat and Punjab contributing 11%, 10%, 8% and 7% respectively.

6.2 Fruits & Vegetables

India is the second largest producer of the Fruits and Vegetables in the world with a production of 256 million MT. India is the world's largest producer of bananas, papaya, mangoes & guavas and the second largest producer of potatoes, green peas, cabbage and

cauliflower. India witnesses nearly 4.6-15.9% wastage in fruits and vegetables annually, due to lack of modern harvesting practices and inadequate cold chain infrastructure. Processing levels in F&V currently stand at close to 2%. This gives immense opportunity to invest in initiatives that help reduce wastage levels including adequate infrastructure (cold chain, processing infrastructure), R&D for processed food & packaging and innovative on farm preservation systems. India's location gives it the unique advantage of connectivity to Europe, the Middle East, Japan, Singapore, Thailand, Malaysia and Korea.

Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Karnataka and Uttar Pradesh are the leading producers of fruits in India, having a combined share of around 50% in the total fruits production. For Vegetables, major producers include West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Gujarat, together accounting for over 50% of the national production.

6.3 Meat & Poultry

India has the world's largest population of livestock and produces around 5.3 million MT of meat annually. Wastages in poultry are comparatively higher at 6.7%, while in meat it is 2.7%. The current processing levels in poultry are 6%, while for meat it stands at 21%. Poultry is a highly vertically integrated industry in India and matches the efficiency levels of many western countries. India is the largest producer of buffalo meat and 2nd largest producer of goat meat. Modern abattoirs, logistics, processing and cold chain infrastructure is a huge opportunity in India, given the changing preference of Indian consumers for clean and safe meat and meat products.

6.4 Marine products

India, with a production of 9.6 million MT is the second largest fish producer in the world. India is endowed with abundant geographical resources suited for both marine and inland fisheries. The wastage levels in inland fisheries are to the tune of 5.2%, while for marine fisheries they are close to 10.5%. Processing levels of marine food in India are at 23%. Traditional independent fish retailers still dominate the distribution channel of fish and seafood in India. However, retail volume sales via modern grocery retail channels like supermarkets and hypermarkets from a smaller base have grown rapidly in recent years, particularly in major cities. Processing of fish into canned and frozen forms is carried out mostly for exports. Besides, there is an increased demand for processed and ready-to-eat marine products in the domestic and overseas market. Huge opportunity exists in India for cold chain development for marine products, value added product development for domestic as well as export market as well as innovations in packaging for increased shelf life and product differentiation.

The top five states for fisheries production in India are Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Gujarat, Kerala and Tamil Nadu with a combined share of around 60% of the total fish production.

Inland Fish Production (6 Million MT): The top five states are Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Odisha contributing close to 68% to freshwater aquaculture.

Marine Fish Production (3.5 Million MT): The top five states are Gujarat, Kerala, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu, contributing close to 74% to the total production.

7. Employment opportunities

Food processing is a branch of food science, which exists from the prehistoric times. Food processing has certain methods and techniques used to transform raw ingredients into food for the consumption of humans and animals. For job opportunities in Indian Food Processing Industry the candidates should usually have a degree in B.Sc. in Home Science/ Food Technology/ Food Science, one should have passed 10+2 examinations with Physics, Chemistry and Biology as the main subjects. For M.Sc / Management, the minimum eligibility is a B.Sc. There are opportunities like Food technologists, technicians, bio technologists and engineers which are required in this industry for the practical application of the principles of many disciplines of science in the manufacturing or production, preservation and packaging, processing and canning of various food products.

It is seen that food products industry, compared to other industries has the largest number of factories and engages largest number of employees as well. Since with respect to fixed capital the food products industry does not figure in top five, it shows that this sector is highly labour intensive per unit of capital. Thus every unit of capital invested in food products industry employs largest number of persons as compared to other industries while generating almost as high the output levels as in other industries. In 2014-15, it constituted 12.77 % of employment generated in all registered factory sector. Unregistered food processing sector supports employment to 47.9 lakh workers as per the NSSO 2010-11 and constitutes 13.72% of employment in the unregistered manufacturing sector.

8. GROWTH DRIVERS

The growth in the sector can be expected to be driven by the food and grocery market, which currently ranks sixth in the world and contributes approximately 70 % to the total retail sales. India's strong 1.2 billion consumer base provides a well-established domestic market for the food processing industry in India. As the consumers in the country are becoming more health-conscious, the demand for nutritious food is growing proportionately. In addition, rising number of working women and nuclear families is resulting in high demand for ready-to-eat and frozen food. Thus, overall India's food value chain is poised to create multiple opportunities for investment and employment in storage infrastructure, farming, retail and quality control.

India is endowed with a strong raw material base to stimulate the growth of food processing industry. The country is first in terms of milk production with production close to 155.5 million MT in FY 2015-16 and second in terms of fruits and vegetables in the world with production of 256 million MT. It is also the largest producer of spices with 6.9 million tones of spices produced in the year 2015-16. The country is third in egg production, fifth in meat production and second in fish production in the world. The steady supply of raw materials and availability of cold storage infrastructure will complement the growth in sub-segments like dairy, horticulture, plantation, animal husbandry and fisheries. India's diverse agro-climatic zones allow the country to produce a variety of crops.

Year wise Export of Processed Food Products (US \$ Million)

Year	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
Exports	31459.58	35898.06	38051.43	36171.92	29672.37	30871.47
(%)Growth		14.11%	6.00%	-4.94%	-17.97%	4.04%

Contribution of Food Processing Industry to India’s GDP through manufacturing (FY16)

9. GOVERNMENT SUPPORT

Under the Make in India initiative, the Government plans to stimulate growth in the Food Processing sector through the creation of a strong infrastructure, reduction of food wastage and promotion of Ease of Doing Business (EODB) measures. The FDI in trading and e-commerce of food products is allowed up to 100% through government approval route. Additionally, the 100% FDI policy through automatic route in the sector for manufacturing in India has resulted in inflows of USD 1.7 Billion during April 2014 to December 2016. With such an increased government support, food business giants such as Kelloggs, Ferrero and BSA International are all set to expand their footprint in India. India’s geographical proximity to food importing regions such as Singapore, Middle East, Thailand, Europe, Korea and Malaysia will further boost exports in the future.

Furthermore, the Integrated Cold Chain and Value Addition Infrastructure scheme under MoFPI aims to build strong cold storage infrastructure for dairy, fish and horticultural

industry. The Food Processing industry is critical to India's growth and the government is focused on providing adequate impetus to the sector. A well-developed Food Processing sector will help facilitate crop diversification and generate employment opportunities. The introduction of modern processing techniques for food will result in improved shelf-life of the agricultural produce and ensure steady revenue to farmers. With the correct set of policy implementations and support, the industry can grow by leaps and bounds, taking India to a new position of strength and prosperity in the global economy.

10. Strength and Opportunities

10.1 Strong demand growth

The demand for processed food is increasing due to increasing disposable income, urbanization, young population and nuclear families; leading to changing lifestyle and increasing expenditure on health and nutritional foods.

10.2 Flourishing Farm Sector

India is bestowed with a diverse agro-climatic conditions; large agriculture sector with second largest producer of fruits and and vegetables; abundant livestock with largest production of milk; and cost competitiveness.

10.3 Increasing investments

The food processing sector is a sunrise sector and government sees it as a future driver of Indian economy. Government has launched various infrastructure development schemes to increase investments in food processing infrastructure. The government is also making an amicable FDI environment in this sector.

11. Threats or Weakness of the Indian Food Processing Sector

Despite of its large size, Indian food processing industry is still at a nascent stage compared to its potential. It is one of the sunrise sectors in the country. Of the country's total agriculture and food produce, only 2 percent is processed currently in comparison to 40% in countries such as Malaysia and Thailand. There are several challenges that need to be addressed. These challenges span across the entire value chain and are as follows:

11.1 Productivity Issues

A major area of concern is food production itself. Despite being an agrarian economy and one of the largest producers of vegetables, fruits, wheat etc, it is unfortunate that the productivity of crops is quite low relative to international standards.

11.2 Availability of Skilled Resources

Human resource development needs to cover the entire gamut from basic infrastructure, education, vocational and technical guidance to qualified professionals in the sector.

11.3 Supply Chain Deterrents

Long and fragmented supply chains leading to high wastage and high costs especially due to seasonality, perishability and variability of produce.

11.4 Deadlocks in Infrastructure

Indian export- related infrastructure for agri-produce is grossly inadequate, especially at sea ports and airports. More than 30 percent of the produce is lost due to poor post-harvesting facilities and lack of cold chain infrastructure.

11.5 Low Adherence to Quality Standards

Lack of basic standard and infrastructure for adhering to quality standards. Given the size of the industry, there is a huge gap in the availability of laboratories, trained manpower, and certification agencies.

11.6 Low level of Linkages between Industries

Low level of interaction between industry and research institutes are one of the major problems. In order to improve farm productivity, continuous introduction and implementation of innovative technologies calls for existence of a strong R& D network. While investments are being made in this regard, the efforts have not been as rewarding.

12. Conclusion

As an extended arm of the agriculture, the food processing sector has immense nutritional and food security benefits for a vastly populated country like India plagued with problems like hunger and malnutrition. The sector has immense employment generation capacity. India is one of the major exporters of processed food products and so the FPI earns significant export revenue for the country. In this competitive environment, India has a leading edge on account of cultivation of a wide variety of fruits and vegetables supported by India's climatic and geographic diversity. India is also blessed with a reasonable supply of cereals, grains, livestock, fish etc. India needs to go for technology up-gradation as well as innovation and diminish the adverse role of intermediaries and strengthen supply chain for the robust growth of this sector. A vibrant FPI sector marked by a supportive ecosystem can alleviate India's concerns on inter-linked issues of food security, malnutrition and food inflation. And this must be a core priority for the government in the larger national interest.

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Paper 35

**A STUDY ON RURAL INFRASTRUCTURE FUNDING
– A CASE STUDY ON PAVOOR GRAM PANCHAYAT****Mr Shakin Raj*, Mr Arjun Prakash****

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*Mail: shakinraj03@gmail.com**Mail: arjunetu@gmail.com**Abstract:**

In a country, infrastructure plays an important role in supporting nation's economic growth. Rural infrastructure assumes great importance in India because of the country's predominantly rural nature and the crucial linkages of rural infrastructure to economic growth, poverty alleviation and human development as a whole in the country. In fact, as per Census 2011, there are 6.4 lakh villages in India, which shelter more than two-third of the country's population. In such a scenario, the role and importance of rural infrastructure in India cannot be neglected. The study on operational and financial operations of the Pavoore Gram Panchayat helps to know the various sources of funds received and amount of funds actually utilized towards rural infrastructure development.

Keywords: infrastructure, rural infrastructure**1. INTRODUCTION**

In a country, infrastructure plays an important role in supporting nation's economic growth. Rural infrastructure assumes great importance in India because of the country's predominantly rural nature and the crucial linkages of rural infrastructure to economic growth, poverty alleviation and human development as a whole in the country. In fact, as per Census 2011, there are 6.4 lakh villages in India, which shelter more than two-third of the country's population. In such a scenario, the role and importance of rural infrastructure in India cannot be neglected. The study on operational and financial operations of the Pavoore Gram Panchayat helps to know the various sources of funds received and amount of funds actually utilized towards rural infrastructure development.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To study the grants sanctioned by the union and state government towards the development of Gram Panchayat infrastructure.
- To study the allocation of funds to Gram Panchayat through fourteenth finance of union budget.

3. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

PRIMARY DATA: The primary data was gathered from personal interviews with the Gram Panchayat employees and higher officials. The entire survey was conducted in Pavoore Gram Panchayat, which consisted of the information on understanding the different sources of funding received by the Gram Panchayat from government and other alternative sources. The

data was collected through interviews from the month of November 2018. Information was drawn from employees, higher officials and files maintained by the Gram Panchayat.

SECONDARY DATA The secondary data was collected from various sources like newspapers, articles, books and files maintained by the Gram Panchayat.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Soumya Manjunath & Elumalai Kannan (2017)

The present study analyzed the effect of rural infrastructure on agricultural development in the southern Indian state of Karnataka. The study used district-level data for 30 years period and employed infrastructure availability and utilization framework to examine the relationship between the rural infrastructure and agricultural development. The analysis showed that infrastructure availability and infrastructure utilization had positive and significant effect on agricultural productivity growth. The effect of infrastructure utilization on productivity growth seemed to be higher than that of infrastructure availability. Further, the combined effect of availability and utilization of infrastructure had larger effect on agricultural productivity. The analysis of spatial convergence of agricultural productivity growth showed that districts converge in land productivity over time.

Amar Kumar Mohanty & Narayan Chandra Nayak & Bani Chatterjee (2016)

In pursuit of achieving and maintaining high human development, infrastructure is said to play a critical role. The present paper examines the spatial differences in infrastructural facilities and human development across 30 districts of Odisha, and consequently, tries to find out the impact of infrastructure on human development in the state. The study records significant regional differences in the level of human development as well as infrastructural development in Odisha. It applies a data model to examine the effects of composite infrastructure and its individual components on human development and its three dimensions. The study establishes close linkage between infrastructure and human development. Telecommunication, postal services, village electricity, banking, school and drinking water facilities play significant roles in the process of attaining high level of human development. In order to achieve high and sustained human development, the state needs to prioritize its efforts towards infrastructure creation for these regions.

Ramakrishna Nallathiga (2015)

Infrastructure is vital for economic growth and development of any nation. Although national infrastructure plays an important role, the development of infrastructure and its growth, however, may depend upon the peculiar priorities and performance of state governments in a federal structure such as that of India. India has been growing extensively in the terms of infrastructure but the states may show differential performance in terms of infrastructure development due to various reasons. It is in this context that this article reports the findings from a study to assess the performance of Indian states on a constructible infrastructure using levels and growth data.

5. FINDINGS

1. There is a gradual decrease in the funds allocated by the government in the year 2014-15 and 2015-16 by 5.28% and 6.3%. The amount sanctioned in 2016-17 is almost 3 times and in 2017-18 is almost 5 times the amount sanctioned in the base year.
2. The funds raised by the issue of business license in 2014-15 is double the amount raised in the base year. There is almost 70-80% increase in the amount raised in 2015-16 and 2016-17

when compared with the base year. The increase in the funds raised is more in 2017-18 as compared to earlier years.

3. There is a considerable decrease in the funds raised by issue of building license when compared with 2013-14. The amount raised in 2014-15 and 2015-16 has decreased by 47.66% and 32.49% respectively. 54% of base year amount is raised in the last two years.

4. The amount raised through Panchayat building rent has continuously increased up to 2015-16 though in different proportions i.e. 42-51%. The amount raised in 2016-17 though greater than base year, has decreased by almost 21-22% than 2015-16. There is a further hike in the amount raised in 2017-18 by 54.19% than the base year.

5. The amount raised through house tax has continuously increased from 2013-14 to 2015-16, i.e. 100-162.42%. There is a downfall in the amount raised in 2016-17 and 2017-18 when compared to 2015-16 by 5.88% and 10.37%.

6. The amount raised through Library tax has continuously increased from 2013-14 to 2015-16, i.e. 100-162.41%. There is a downfall in the amount raised in 2016-17 and 2017-18 when compared to 2015-16 by 5.87% and 10.37%.

7. The amount raised through education tax has continuously increased up to 2015-16 though in different proportions i.e. 132-164%. There is a downfall in the amount raised in 2016-17 and 2017-18 when compared to 2015-16 by 5.87% and 10.37%.

8. There is a considerable increase in all the above years from 2013 to 2018. The percentage in 2014-15 is 107.79% as compared to 100 in 2013-14. The funds raised through issue of water connection bills increase at a pace of 25.31% in 2015-16, 42.46% in 2016-17 and 78.61% in 2017-18 over the base year 2013-14.

9. The amount sanctioned through MGNRE Act exhibits a continuous increasing trend over the period. The percentage in 2014-15 is 128.05% as compared to 100 in 2013-14. The increase in the funds raised is more in 2017-18 as compared to earlier years. The funds sanctioned through MGNRE Act increase at a pace of 167.87% in 2015-16, 310.85% in 2016-17 and 365.54% in 2017-18.

10. There is a decline in trend as there is no State allocations towards housing plans under Basava Vasathi Yojana for the year 2014-15 and 2015-16. A sharp increase of 53.49% is noticed in 2016-17 and there is a dip in 2018-19 to 9.19%.

11. There is a decline in trend as there is no State allocations towards housing plans under Ambedkar Vasathi Yojana for the year 2014-15. There is a sudden increase in trend to 164.8% in 2015-16 and again oscillating between 0 to 43.65% in 2016-17 and 2017-18. There is an overall decrease of 56.35% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

12. There is a decline in trend as there is no State allocations through Pradhan Mantri Awaaz Yojana for the year 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2016-17. A sharp increase of 31.25% is noticed in 2017-18. The chart shows overall decrease of 68.75% over the five year period.

13. There is a considerable decrease in the amount sanctioned for irrigation activities when compared with 2013-14. There is a drop in trend to 71.92% in 2014-15. A slight increase to 80.7% and 83.95% is noticed in the year 2015-16 and 2016-17. 24.69% of base year amount is raised in the last year.

14. The chart shows a slight decrease of 11.48% in 2014-15 in sanctioned towards maintenance and construction of Underground Drainages. A sign of improvement is seen in 2015-16 to 128.73% and sliding down to 32.17% in 2016-17. There is a rebound in trend with the increase to 125.79% in 2017-18. The chart shows a positive trend as there is 25.79% increase over the base year.

15. There is a considerable decrease to 2.88% in the funds sanctioned for construction and maintenance of roads in 2014-15 when compared with 2013-14. The amount sanctioned in 2015-16 and 2017-18 has decreased by 95.38% and 58.5% respectively. 94.04% of base year amount is raised in the last year.

16. The amount sanctioned for setting up street lights and maintenance of Community has increased in 2014-15 to 704.23%. There is a downfall in the amount sanctioned in 2015-16 as no amount is sanctioned for setting up street lights and maintenance of Community. There is a rebound in trend with the increase to 1408.45% in 2016-17 and to 2464.79% in 2017-18. The chart shows a positive trend as there is 2364.79% increase over the base year.

17. The closing balance of fund available with the Gram Panchayat has increased by 41.31% in 2014-15. A slight fall in trend is seen in 2015-16 by 62.93% when compared to 2014-15. There is a sudden increase in trend to 539.63% in 2016-17 and again oscillating to 515.78% in 2017-18. It shows a positive trend as there is an overall increase of 415.78% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

18. There is a considerable decrease of 8.02% in the treasury of the Gram Panchayat in 2014-15 when compared with 2013-14. There is a sudden increase in trend to 160.45% in 2015-16. A further rise to 217% in trend is seen in 2016-17. There is a drastic drop in trend from 217% to 90.21% in 2017-18. There is an overall decrease of 9.79% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

19. As 46.45% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of roads. As it forms the major part of the total amount sanctioned, it states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of roads in 2013-14.

The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on other activities such as setting up of street lights and maintenance of community halls as only 0.38% of total amount sanctioned is allotted towards this area in 2013-14.

20. As 57.62% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of underground drainages. As it forms the major part of the total amount sanctioned, it states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of underground drainages in 2014-15. The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on housing activities, and on construction and maintenance of roads as only 3.61% of total amount sanctioned is allotted towards this area in 2014-15.

21. As 48.56% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of underground drainages. It states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of underground drainages in 2015-16.

The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on other activities such as setting up of street lights and maintenance of community halls as no fund allotment is made towards this area in 2015-16.

22. The Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on housing activities in 2016-17. The Gram Panchayat has concentrated least on other activities such as setting up of street lights and maintenance of community halls as only 5.5% of total amount sanctioned is allotted towards this area in 2016-17.

23. As 40.68% of the total amount is sanctioned towards construction and maintenance of roads. It states that the Gram Panchayat has mainly concentrated on development of roads in 2017-18.

24. The amount allotted towards payment of the employee's salary has increased from 100-165.77% in 2014-15. The amount raised in 2015-16 though greater than base year by 51.17%,

has decreased by almost 14.6% than 2015-16. There is a further hike in the amount paid in 2016-17 by 67.73% than the base year.

There is a further decline in trend in the year 2017-18 as the trend has dropped to 21.05%. From the information depicted in this chart it shows a negative trend as there is an overall decrease of 78.95% over the five year period with base 2013-14.

6. SUGGESTIONS

- To encourage local initiatives to fund existing infrastructure problems for small network development.
- Implementation of new technologies, which are cost effective even at low volumes. For example, a watershed can be developed only for one or two villages. Small hydel plants can be built to utilize the flow of small mountainous streams and generate power. These technologies can be used in remote and sparsely populated areas.
- Gram Panchayat should allow private providers to pool their funds in Roads and power projects by encouraging private providers by validating their claims, through incentives for limited ownership of the created assets, and by providing them with opportunities to recover costs through user fees.
- Gram Panchayat should invite proposals from various service providers as maximum fund is allocated to irrigation activity i.e. installation of water pump towards only one service provider.
- The online portal should be open to the public.
- Government should implement a rule compelling the Gram Panchayat to maintain accounting journals and ledgers.
- The educational qualification for the post of the President of the Gram Panchayat should be set by the government, as it indirectly affects the efficiency of the management.

7. CONCLUSION

The study of Rural Infrastructure Funding has focused mainly on the funds allotted by the Government to the Gram Panchayat and funds raised through various sources of funds. The underlying objective of the study was to assess the current status of rural infrastructure in the Pavor Village by focusing on the funding done towards the five sectors i.e. Roads, drainage system, drinking water supply, setting up of street lights along with maintaining of community buildings and sanitation. According to the study findings, the rural populations is not covered by basic infrastructure facilities like telecom, power, and roads .As far as drinking water is concerned, while most rural inhabitants have access to some sort of water source, the quality and maintenance of these sources leave a lot to be desired. The dismal state of rural infrastructure has hardly improved. This implies that five decades of development planning in India has been unable to ensure a decent living for a large number of people residing in rural areas. Despite many large-scale rural development schemes, the absolute number of people in poverty has not decline .

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5. d substantially; abject poverty still remains pervasive in rural region

Paper 36

STUDY OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES

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Abstract:

The process which deals with obtaining, processing, storing, disseminating and applying of information and knowledge within an organization to support and enhance its business performance and employee satisfaction is referred to as Knowledge Management (KM). The main aim of this study is to measure the importance of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in software industries. In this study, a sample of 140 respondents was selected randomly from different software companies.

The result clearly shows that components of KM policies and knowledge sharing have positive relation with the organizational performance measured in terms of employee satisfaction.

Keywords: software industries, knowledge management policies, knowledge sharing, Employee Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Knowledge & Knowledge Management Knowledge is defined by the Oxford English Dictionary as (i) expertise, and skills acquired by a person through experience or education; (ii) the theoretical or practical understanding of a subject, (iii) what is known in a particular field and (iv) awareness or familiarity gained by experience of a fact or situation.

Knowledge Management helps to improve the overall organizational performance. Active and dynamic implementation and management of knowledge are the two critical ways of enabling organizational performance enhancements, problem solving and decision making (Liebowitz, 1999).

Knowledge is often defined as a “justified personal belief.” There are much taxonomy that specify various kinds of knowledge. The most fundamental distinction is between “tacit” and “explicit” knowledge. (King, 2009)

The Knowledge Management Policy sets the standard for Knowledge Management within an organisation. It ensures that everyone knows what is expected of them in terms of Knowledge Management, and why this is important to the organisation.

Knowledge sharing is a process through which knowledge is exchanged among people and members of an organization.

Employee Satisfaction refers to the attitude of an employee towards his work and organizational environment. Each employee has a different level of satisfaction in accordance with the system of values prevailing itself, because each employee has a wide range of perceptions of job satisfaction itself. Employee satisfaction concerns with a person's attitude

This study is an attempt to find the importance of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in knowledge management.

2. Literature Review:

Hurley, et. al. (2005) in their paper offers many suggestions to Non-governmental organizations NGOs for more effectively managing their knowledge. Leavitt's model of organization change is reviewed and suggested as a framework for NGOs to consider in their development and implementation of a "within" KM program. This model suggests that in order to affect change, a coordinated effort of adjustment and balance between technology, people, task, and structure is required. More specifically, the model suggests that the addition of technology alone is not sufficient. Instead, all four of the subsystems require balance in order for a KM culture to be successfully established.

Aurum et.al., (2007) in their study, using both quantitative and qualitative methods, investigates current practice of Knowledge Management (KM) in Software Engineering (SE) processes in two Australian companies on the basis that they both claimed to apply KM practices in their software development work. It also describes the KM activities and KM process used in SE practice, and examines the enablers of KM process for SE in terms of leadership, technology, culture, process and measurement.

Technol. *et. al.* (2013), in the article states that for Knowledge Management to be efficient and effective, some principles should be considered (Davenport and Prusak, 2003): a) Knowledge originates and resides in people's heads; b) Knowledge-sharing requires trust; c) Technology enables new behaviors related to knowledge; d) Knowledge sharing should be encouraged and rewarded; e) Support of the leadership and resources are essential factors; f) Initiatives related to knowledge should begin with a pilot program; g) Quantitative and qualitative measurements are necessary to evaluate the initiative; h) Knowledge is creative and should be encouraged to develop in unexpected ways.

Howell and Annansingh (2013) investigated whether there was any path-dependency in association

with cultural expectations of knowledge generation and sharing in knowledge intensive firms.

They

concluded that certain universities display critical junctures and cultural transformation in terms of

knowledge generation, dissemination and sharing.

Jiacheng et al. (2010) reported that intrinsic motivation operated through affective commitment: internalization, identification and conformity; rewards had little direct impacts on final intentions. They explored individual cognitive mechanisms of knowledge-sharing (KS) motivation to provide effective measures of individual inclinations towards KS.

Alhawari et al. (2012) presented a knowledge-based risk management framework for information technology project. They explored the field of risk management associated with KM and attempted to present a conceptual framework, called Knowledge-Based Risk Management (KBRM), which employed KM processes to improve its effectiveness and to increase the likelihood of success in

innovative Information Technology (IT) projects.

3. Objectives of the Research

The aim of this research is to study the effectiveness of knowledge management in software industries by analysing the influences of different dimensions of knowledge management policies and organisational effectiveness. To accomplish this aim, following objectives have been developed.

1. Identify the dimensions which constitute the knowledge sharing and employee satisfaction as relevant to effectiveness of knowledge management in the organization.
2. Develop a metric to measure above mentioned research constructs and validate it.
3. Obtain the empirical evidence for the inter-relationships between the dimensions of the research constructs.

Draw implications and make suggestions to the organizations to enhance the organizational performance by implementing knowledge management effectively and efficiently.

4. Methodology

The questionnaire on the two dimensions namely Knowledge Management policies and knowledge sharing of knowledge management (having 7 and 9 questions respectively) is prepared and distributed in Google Forms to the employees of different software companies. 141 employees from different software industries responded to the questionnaire. The questionnaire had 13 a priori items on a Likert 5-point scale (5-strongly agree and 1-Strongly disagree).

Likert Scale is a psychometric scale, which is one of the most widely used question types in a survey. In a Likert Scale Survey respondents has specific choices based on "agreeing" or "disagreeing" on a certain question in the survey rather than simply choosing between "yes/no"

Likert scale survey questions are useful in measuring respondent's opinion or attitude towards a given subject. Likert Scale is typically a five, seven, or nine point agreement scale used to measure respondents' agreement with a variety of statements. In this study a five point scale is used for measuring respondent's response.

This study tests only one main hypothesis (the role of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in effectiveness of knowledge management).

Total responses for each category is tabulated, analyzed and graph is prepared to show the importance of each of the factors in the knowledge management

5. Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant effect of knowledge management policies on employee satisfaction of software industries.

H1: There a significant effect of knowledge management policies on employee satisfaction of software industries.

H0: There is no significant effect of knowledge sharing on employee satisfaction of software industries.

H1: There a significant effect of knowledge sharing on employee satisfaction of software industries.

Results and Analysis

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES							
	KMP1	KMP2	KMP3	KMP4	KMP5	KMP6	KMP7
Strongly disagree	3	1	2	1	2	2	2
Disagree	3	10	8	7	10	4	8
Neutral	22	24	26	34	25	17	19
Agree	76	77	77	71	79	90	71
Strongly agree	37	29	28	28	25	28	41

Table 1.1: Total responses in 5 point scale to different items related to Knowledge Management policies

- KMP1 - There is a Knowledge Management methodology or set of plans in our Organization for acquiring and sharing Knowledge.
- KMP2 - There is an advisory board and internal meetings are held by our organization to exchange Knowledge.
- KMP3 - Our Organization encourages systematic neighbour training and interdisciplinary training groups in order to get holistic overview of a given task.
- KMP4 - Knowledge sharing is prompted most effectively and it is incorporated in the Organization's strategic activities.
- KMP5 - There is support and trust for Knowledge Management policy formulation in our Organization.
- KMP6 - Employees accept the activities designed to acquire and share knowledge as part of their job.
- KMP7 - Meetings are also used as a means of transferring Knowledge in our Organization.

	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)
KMP1	2%	2%	16%	54%	26%
KMP2	1%	7%	17%	55%	21%
KMP3	1%	6%	18%	55%	20%
KMP4	1%	5%	24%	50%	20%
KMP5	1%	7%	18%	56%	18%
KMP6	1%	3%	12%	64%	20%
KMP7	1%	6%	13%	50%	29%

Table 1.2 : Average responses to different items used to measure Knowledge Management Policies with 5 point scale.

Figure 1.1: Graphical representation of responses for each items related to Knowledge Management Policies with 5 point scale.

Out of 141 responses 77% (55% Agree and 22% Strongly Agree) of the employees have accepted that they have effective Knowledge Management policies in their organizations, only 6% (1% Strongly disagree and 5% Disagree) have denied that they have effective knowledge management policies, 17% neither agree or disagree for the fact by being neutral.

KNOWLEDGE SHARING									
	KSH1	KSH2	KSH3	KSH4	KSH5	KSH6	KSH7	KSH8	KSH9
Strongly disagree	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	2	3
Disagree	8	14	6	13	13	10	11	15	11
Neutral	28	20	17	31	26	33	26	29	22
Agree	72	77	83	67	80	75	83	74	82
Strongly agree	32	29	34	27	21	21	19	20	22

Table 1.3: Shows the total responses in 5 point scale to different items related to Knowledge Sharing

- KSH1 - Senior officials and staff share their experiences and advice through Knowledge Management practices.
- KSH2 - New employees are encouraged to use knowledge portal and knowledge bank to learn how things are done.
- KSH3 - Sharing best practices help employees to provide useful feedback that helps to increase learning.
- KSH4 - It is easy to browse Knowledge bank in this organization.
- KSH5 - Knowledge Management portals are used to coordinate with other teams to meet organizational objectives.
- KSH6 - Knowledge Gaps are systematically identified and well-defined processes are used to bridge the knowledge gaps.
- KSH7 - The organization has formalized the process of transferring best practices, including documentation and lessons learned to other departments.

- KSH8 - Tacit knowledge (what employees know how to do, but cannot express) is valued and transferred across the organization.
- KSH9 - Knowledge bank is regularly used to figure out ways to improve the work processes

	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree(%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)
KSH1	0%	6%	20%	51%	23%
KSH2	0%	10%	14%	55%	21%
KSH3	0%	4%	12%	59%	24%
KSH4	1%	9%	22%	48%	19%
KSH5	0%	9%	19%	57%	15%
KSH6	1%	7%	24%	54%	15%
KSH7	0%	8%	19%	59%	14%
KSH8	1%	11%	21%	53%	14%
KSH9	2%	8%	16%	59%	16%

Table 1.4: Average responses to different items used to measure Knowledge Sharing with 5 point scale.

Figure 1.2: Graphical representation of responses for each items related to Knowledge Sharing with 5 point scale.

Out of 141 responses 73% (55% Agree and 18% Strongly Agree) of the employees have accepted that they have effectiveness in their organizations, only 9% (1% Strongly disagree and 8% Disagree) have denied that they have effective knowledge Sharing , 18% neither agree or disagree for the fact by being neutral.

EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION					
	EMS1	EMS2	EMS3	EMS4	EMS5
Strongly disagree	2	7	7	5	4
Disagree	6	12	14	9	7
Neutral	28	26	27	34	41
Agree	77	73	73	69	65
Strongly agree	27	22	19	23	23

Table 1.5: Shows the total responses in 5 point scale to different items related to Employee Satisfaction.

- EMS1 - Our organization improves working conditions in order to recognize the quality improvement efforts of employees
- EMS2 - Our organization has an incentive scheme for encouraging employee participation in quality improvement.
- EMS3 - The organization offers incentives to its employees relative to their performance.
- EMS4 - Employees' reward and penalties are clear to all.
- EMS5 - Compensation and reward in the organization is in par with others in the business.

	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree(%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)
EMS1	1%	4%	20%	55%	19%
EMS2	5%	9%	19%	52%	16%
EMS3	5%	10%	19%	52%	14%
EMS4	4%	6%	24%	48%	16%
EMS5	3%	5%	29%	46%	16%

Table 1.6: Average responses to different items used to measure Employee Satisfaction with 5 point scale.

Figure 1.3: Graphical representation of responses for each items related to Employee Satisfaction with 5 point scale.

Out of 141 responses 62% (46% Agree and 16% Strongly Agree) of the employees have accepted that they have effectiveness in their organizations, only 8% (3% Strongly disagree

and 5% Disagree) have denied that they have effective employee satisfaction in Knowledge Management, 29% neither agree or disagree for the fact by being neutral.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

Total of 141 responses were collected from different employees by distribution of questionnaire.

Out of 141 responses 77% of the employees have accepted that they have Knowledge Management policies (KMP) in their organizations and 74% accepted that they have knowledge sharing (KSH) methods in their organizations.

	KMP	KSH	EMS
Strongly disagree (%)	1%	1%	4%
Disagree (%)	5%	6%	7%
Neutral (%)	17%	19%	23%
Agree (%)	55%	56%	49%
Strongly agree (%)	22%	18%	17%

6. Conclusion

The result shows that more than 75% of employees agreed that they have Knowledge Management Policies and Knowledge Sharing is the two important concepts adopted in their organizations. So this proves that these two concepts of knowledge management are very effective tools and this is true with regard to the alternative hypothesis. Good implementation of Knowledge Management Policies and Knowledge Sharing shows the high rate of employee satisfaction.

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Paper 37

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS E-BANKING SERVICES, A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS IN UJIRE***Vignesh Pai B. H., **Padmini Y. S., ***Vijetha Pai B. H.***2nd M.COM, SDM College (Autonomous) UjireEmail: bhvigneshpai@gmail.com**2nd M.COM, SDM College (Autonomous) UjireEmail: Raniprishabharadhwaj@gmail.com***2nd M.SC, SDM College (Autonomous), UjireEmail: Vijetha.paibh@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Bank industry is most favoured industry for the development of the country. From the past few years banks have taken revolutionary steps to satisfy its valuable customers. The technology has strengthened the banking sector, the services provided by them have been updated and also uplifted the citizens of the world. The time has emerged for each and every bank to go electronically. This paper studies the role of e-banking towards the customers. The paper has made an attempt to investigate the satisfaction level of customers towards e-banking services provided by various public sector banks in Ujire. The study utilises the research paper and structured questionnaire is developed and distributed to collect the primary responses based on convenience sampling method. Results and findings are generalised through table and graph.

Keywords: Bank, Services, Technology, e-banking, customers.

1. Introduction

E-banking or electronic banking is a major innovation in the field of banking earlier banking was conducted in a very traditional manner there were no such innovation Electronic banking makes banking convenient on your schedule. Many people are now able to avoid the rush to get to the bank before it closes, as they can bank from a home computer or via automatic teller machine (ATM). Although the two systems are different, ATMs and online banking are the two types of electronic banking systems in use today. Electronic banking (E-banking) is a generic term encompassing internet banking, telephone banking, mobile banking etc. e-banking is a process of delivery of banking services and products through electronic channels such as telephone, internet, cell phone etc. Several initiatives taken by the RBI have facilitated the development of E-banking in India. The RBI has made considerable progress in consolidating the existing payment and settlement systems, and in upgrading technology with a view to establishing an efficient, integrated and secure system functioning in a real-time environment, which further helped the development of E-banking in India. E-banking has experienced strong and sustained growth. With rigid controls giving way to deregulation, banks are gearing up their communications infrastructure to obtain a competitive edge from E-banking. Thus it is fast becoming a reality in India. E-banking is fast becoming a strategic necessity for most commercial banks, as competition

increases from private banks. Though de-regulation may have had an impact on the banking industry in general. There is a better price discovery process as more and more markets gain integrated real-time and improved access to these trading and data-dissemination platforms. At the same time, however, many changes are still required in technology, access infrastructure and banking regulation. Virtually all banks use banking software at their head. A quarter of local banks, provide Credit card and point of sale services major cities, ATM and internet banking are expanding rapidly. However, E-Banking is the product of different generations of electronic transactions. Since its inception, electronic banking or online banking has gone through different transitions. Automated teller machines (ATMs) were the first well-known machines to provide electronic access to customers.

2. Literature review

1. Mr. Lakshmi Narayana.K, Mr. Sri Hari.V, Dr.P. Paramashivaiah (April 2013)

The study focused on investigating the major factors that influence online customers' satisfaction with the overall service quality of their banks. The study going to help the bank management not only in improving the level of satisfaction but also strengthening the bond between the banks and their customers. The results have also shown that pricing and bank charges related factors, namely Interest Policy and Bank Charging, are not significant. The researcher believes that customers' identification with the considered factors do not have a significant influence on their overall satisfaction. This research study revealed that Banking Needs, followed by Core Services, Problem Resolution, Cost Saved, Convenience and Risk and Privacy Concerns were the major factors that strongly affect the overall satisfaction of online consumers.

2. Md. Abdul Bashir, Mass Hareeza Ali, Md.Reaz (December 2015)

The study made an attempt to analyse the Customer's Satisfaction towards E-banking in Bangladesh. The research work made an attempt to find out the status of e-banking by customer satisfaction and importance level on different dimension of e-products like ATM, Credit Card, Internet/Online, Tele banking, and SMS Banking. The study revealed that Technological development is essential for making e-banking product and services familiar to customers. Banks should give concentration to its promotional activities to attract customers to involve e-banking services rather than conventional branch-based banking. The study also says that All Banks in Bangladesh should require ATM booths all over the country and should start to deposit money by ATM.

3. Reeta. Manju Asht (January 2016)

The study endeavors to explore the online customer services provided by the banking industry in India and additionally discussed the magnification rate and future prospects of the e-banking services provided by the Indian banks . The study found that there is lack of preparedness on the part of both Banks and customers in the adoption of incipient technological changes. There is lack of congruous infrastructure for the installation of e-delivery channels. Indian banks are making sincere efforts for the adoption of advanced technology and for installation of e-delivery channels, but it should be still improved. The study also states that Government should magnify investments for the construction of well-furnished building and infrastructure.

4. Shilpa Vyas

The study made an attempt to study the Impact of E-Banking on Traditional Banking Services. The study found that E-banking transactions are much cheaper than branch or even phone transactions. The start-up costs of an e-bank are high. Establishing a trusted

brand is very costly as it requires significant advertising expenditure in addition to the purchase of expensive technology.

5. Dr. M. Vasani (December 2017)

The research was focussed on customers satisfaction towards Internet banking of ICICI bank in erode city. The study has been conducted in order to meticulously evaluate and examine the level of satisfaction towards internet banking services. The study also had the objective to observe and analyse the purpose of using internet banking. The study revealed that the banker should configure security systems and firewalls to the highest security consistent with the level of protection according to customer requirements. The banker should reduce the cumbersome formalities for getting internet banking facility and should reduce the processing charges for NEFT and RTGS. The study suggests that banks should arrange demonstration programs for the customers, so that customers can understand the process of e-banking properly and can enjoy all the services provided by bank.

3. Objective

- To know customers satisfaction level towards e-banking service.
- To understand the concept of e-banking in rural area.
- To study customers awareness and satisfaction level about e-banking in ujire

4. Research methodology

The study is based mainly on primary data and supported by the secondary data. The primary data is collected from the customers with the help of questionnaire to evaluate the customer's prospective. For this purpose a structured questionnaire is prepared for the research. Secondary data are obtained from the existing research articles on the research topic. Data gathered through secondary used to formulate conceptual framework for the study and used as source for the development of primary data collection instruments.

Primary data: Self report questionnaire.

Sample size: 100

Sampling method: convenient sampling method

Analysis: data collected through questionnaire present in table and graph for the future analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table no 1: Gender

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	54	54
Female	46	46
Total	100	100

Figure no 1

Source: Primary Data

The above chart reveals that out 100 respondents 54% of the respondents are male and 46% of the respondents are female.

Table no 2: Respondents awareness towards e-banking

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Highly aware	62	62
Aware	22	22
Neutral	8	8
Unaware	8	8
Highly unaware	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 2

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that out of 100 respondents 62% respondents highly aware towards e-banking ,22% of the respondents aware of e-banking ,8% of the respondents are neutral and remaining 8% of the respondents unaware towards e-banking service.

Table no 3: Internet banking service is less costly than other banking services

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	54	54
Agree	16	16
Neither agree nor Disagree	22	22
Disagree	4	4
Strongly disagree	4	4
Total	100	100

Figure no 3

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 54% of the respondents strongly agree that internet banking service is less costly compare to other banking service, 16% of the respondents agree that internet banking service is less costly when compared toto other banking service. 22% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, ,4% of the respondents disagree above statement and remaining 4% strongly disagrees because of lack of awareness about e-banking service.

Table no 4: Internet banking transaction procedures are simple and straightforward.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	36	36
Agree	26	26
Neither agree nor Disagree	22	22
Disagree	12	12
Strongly disagree	6	6
Total	100	100

Figure no 4:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart depicts that 34% of the respondents strongly agree internet banking is simple and straight forward process, 26% of the respondents agree above statement, 22% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree the internet banking process simple and straight forward, 12% of the respondents disagrees above statement and remaining 6% of the respondents strongly disagree that internet banking transaction procedure are simple and straight forward.

Table no 5: Using the e-banking is an easy task

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	30	30
Agree	32	32
Neither agree nor Disagree	28	28
Disagree	8	8
Strongly disagree	2	2
Total	100	100

Figure no 5:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 32% of the respondents agree the e-banking using is an easy, 30% Of the respondents strongly agree the using of e-banking is an easy task, 28% of the respondents neither agree nor disagrees the above statement ,8% of the respondents disagree e-banking using and remaining 2% strongly disagree that using of an e-banking is not easy.

Table no 6: Respondents satisfaction level with e-banking because they do not have to go to bank.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	27	27
Agree	31	31
Neither agree nor Disagree	25	25
Disagree	13	13
Strongly disagree	4	4
Total	100	100

Figure no 6:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 31% of the respondents agree the satisfaction level of e-banking, 27% of the respondents strongly agree the satisfaction level of e-banking, 25% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 13% of the respondents disagree above statement and remaining 4% of the respondents strongly disagree above statement.

Table no 7: Banks are providing timely information about e-banking to the customers.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	28	28
Agree	18	18
Neither agree nor Disagree	24	24
Disagree	18	18
Strongly disagree	12	12
Total	100	100

Figure no 7:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 28% of the respondents strongly agree that banks are providing timely information about e-banking to customers. 18% of the respondents agree the banks are providing timely information 24% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with the above statement, 18% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 12% of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement saying banks are not providing timely information to customers.

Table no 8: Respondents knowledge about the e-banking transactions

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	21	21
Agree	27	27
Neither agree nor Disagree	33	33
Disagree	16	16
Strongly disagree	3	3
Total	100	100

Figure no 8:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 21% of the respondents strongly agree that they have proper knowledge about e-banking. 27% of the respondents agrees the proper knowledge about e-banking transaction, 33% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 16% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 3% of the respondents strongly disagree that they do not have proper knowledge about e-banking transactions.

Table no 9: Personal data of customers under e-banking is protected

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	17	17
Agree	21	21
Neither agree nor Disagree	32	32
Disagree	16	16
Strongly disagree	14	14
Total	100	100

Figure no 9:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 17% of the respondents strongly agree that Personal data of customers under e-banking is protected by bank authority, 21% of the respondents agree with the statement, 32% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 16% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 14% of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement saying that bank authority do not protect customers personal information.

Table no 10: Internet banking is more effective than branch banking about time saving.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	34	34
Agree	31	31
Neither agree nor Disagree	21	21
Disagree	9	9
Strongly disagree	5	5
Total	100	100

Figure no 10:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 34% of the respondents strongly agree internet banking more effective than branch banking, 31% of the respondents agrees the internet bank saving time. 21% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 9% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 5% of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement saying that internet banking is not much effective than branch banking.

Table no 11: Websites which offer e-banking services are safe

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	16	16
Agree	20	20
Neither agree nor Disagree	29	29
Disagree	19	19
Strongly disagree	16	16
Total	100	100

Figure no 11:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 16% of the respondents strongly agree websites which offer e-banking services are safer, 20% of the respondents agree that websites offer e-banking service are safe, 29% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with above statement, 19% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 16% of the respondents strongly disagree with the above statement saying websites which offer e-banking services are not safer.

Table no 12: e-banking is convenient because it eliminates the risk of carrying cash.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	41	41
Agree	36	36
Neither agree nor Disagree	18	18
Disagree	5	5
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 12:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 41% of the respondents strongly agree that e-banking service is convenient, 36% of the respondents agrees the above statement saying e-banking service is convenient, 18% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree above statement, 5% of the respondents disagree with the above statement. None of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement.

Table no 13: If respondents face any problem about e-banking service, Banks authorities solve it

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	21	21
Agree	25	25
Neither agree nor Disagree	24	24
Disagree	18	18
Strongly disagree	12	12
Total	100	100

Figure no 13:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 21% of the respondents strongly agree that if respondents face any problem from e-banking bank authorities solve it in a right way, 25% of the respondents agree the above statement, 24% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree the above statement, 18% of the respondents disagree the above statement and remaining 12% of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement saying banking authorities do not solve e-banking problem faced by customers.

Table no 14: Respondents suggest others to use e-banking services

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	31	31
Agree	37	37
Neither agree nor Disagree	27	27
Disagree	5	5
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 14:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart indicates that 31% of the respondents strongly agree, 37% of the respondents agree the above statement saying that they suggest others to use e-banking services. 36% of the respondents agrees the above statement, 27% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with the statement, 5% of the respondents disagree that they do not suggest others to use e-banking service. None of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement.

Table no 15: Respondents Willingness to continue e-banking

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
Strongly Agree	33	33
Agree	35	35
Neither agree nor Disagree	21	21
Disagree	11	11
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	100	100

Figure no 15:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 33% of the respondents strongly agree, 35% of the respondents agree the above statement saying they are willing to continue e-banking service offered by bank. 21% respondents neither agree nor disagree with the above statement, 11% of respondents disagreed that they not willing to continue e-banking service offered by the bank. None of the respondents strongly disagree the above statement.

Table no 16: Respondents overall rating towards e-banking service

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage %
5	24	24
4	32	32
3	22	22
2	14	14
1	8	8
Total	100	100

Figure no 16:

Source: Primary Data

The above table and chart reveals that 24% of the respondents rated as 5 for the e-banking service, 32% of the respondents given the rating as 4 out of 5 saying e-banking services has satisfied them, 22% of the respondents rated 3, 14% of the respondents rated as 2 and remaining 8% of the respondents rated as 1 out of 5 saying e-banking services has to be improved to reach all customers.

Findings

- Majority (84%) of the respondents are aware about e-banking service.
- Majority (70%) of the respondents agree that internet banking service is less costly than other banking services.
- Internet banking transaction procedures are simple and straightforward, Majority (62%) of the respondents agree that internet banking transactions are simple.
- The study found that majority (62%) agree that using e-banking is an easy task.
- Majority (51%) of the respondents agreed that e-banking services is being beneficiary for them and is saving their valuable time.
- Most (46%) of the respondents agree that banks are providing timely information about e-banking to the customers.
- Most (48%) of the respondents have proper knowledge about the e-banking transactions.
- Most (38%) of the respondents agreed that Personal data of customers under e-banking is protected.
- Majority (65%) of the respondents agreed that internet banking is more effective than branch banking.
- Majority (65%) of the respondents agreed that websites which offer e-banking services are safe.
- E-banking is convenient because it eliminates the risk of carrying cash, Majority (77%) of the respondents agreed that e-banking is convenient and also it eliminates risk of carrying cash.
- Most (46%) of the respondents agreed that bank authorities solve e-banking problem faced by the customers.

- Majority (68%) of the respondents agree that they like to suggest others to use internet banking.
- The study found that Majority (68%) of the respondents agreed to continue e-banking services, indicates that they are satisfied with e-banking services.
- Respondents overall rating towards e-banking service, Most (32%) of the respondents have rated as 4 out of 5.

Suggestion

- Electronic channel mostly used by both male and female and people living in urban area. It is suggested that the bankers should take measures for creating awareness and educate all kinds of people about electronic channels.
- The young generations are more aware about E-Banking system than older generation. The older generation having less confidence in using E-Banking.
- Due to the complexity and operating methodology. It is suggested that the bankers should take measures for developing confidence about E-Banking operations among older generations.
- The high income groups of customers are having more awareness about E-Banking services than other income group customers. Therefore, the bankers should take necessary steps to create awareness to other income group of customers by way of conducting seminars, exhibition, customer meet, advertisements etc., Among all the E-Banking channels ATM and mobile banking services most familiar among the users.
- The research suggest that the bankers should take much efforts to inculcate knowledge and awareness about other E-Banking channels to the customers. Availability cash in ATM centre is always problematic aspect among the customers. Therefore, it is suggested that the bankers should took care of the availability of cash in ATM centers particularly in remote ATM locations.
- Internet security is the one of the prominent set back of E-Banking operations in many times. The study suggests that the bankers should take initiative and measures for a perfect E-Banking security system.
- The working of e-banking should be updated and also should be made convenient for each and every users. So that customers who are using it and new users can easily make transaction through e-banking services.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, it can be concluded that technology has greatly influenced the bank customers encouraging them to conduct banking in an innovative manner. They have good awareness regarding ATMs and credit card whereas it is low in internet and mobile banking. Variability of adoption of internet banking is high among the different age groups leading. It is further found that internet banking is dependent on education level also where highly educated have high rate of adoption. e-banking service is one of the best tool for both public sectors and private sector banks to reach their valuable customers. In this technological world e-banking is the best example to educate people about banking services which are provided through internet. e-banking services has a great chance to eliminate various barriers which exists in the banking sector. If all the government and banking measures adopted in a right way then e-banking services can rule Indian economy and can also convert Indian banking sector into digital banking sector.

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Paper 38

**NECESSITY OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT
IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS*****Vinutha, **Vranda**

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Abstract

India is the richest human capital country in the world. However enrolment in higher education is lower as compared to developed countries. It is a setback to take Indian economy on rapid economic growth path. Thus, in recent year's government of India paid highest attention to enhance enrolment ratio in higher education under NITHI AYOGA. The major difficulty is how to develop employability among graduates particularly in rural India. Keeping this in mind various levels of government introduced skill development training to improve the qualities of graduate of rural area. In this context this paper makes an attempt to highlight the necessity of various kinds of occasional training and skill development schemes within the framework of higher education institution. The paper suggests the government to integrate soft skill and job skill training with course curriculum of graduation and post graduation. The integration of training and development with course curriculum will improve the employability amongst rural people thereby channelize human resource to economic growth.

Keywords: Development, Higher education, Necessities, Training, Soft skill

1. INTRODUCTION

India is a country which has abundant human resource. Hence, the central and state government has a commitment of transferring this man power as human capital. The process of transformation human resource into human capital involves training and development. Training is a short-term and reactive activity which focuses on changing or improving the knowledge, skills and above all attitude of individuals to perform a particular job or task. From the two decades, training and development closely link human resource management, talent management, human resource development, institutional design, and knowledge management. The process of development in relation to insights, attitudes, adoptability, leadership and human relationship are most essential to enhance emotional quotient.

Unfortunately, the efforts of government towards training and development in higher education institutions are negligible and consequently, 5% of labour has occasional training in India. It is very low as compared to developed country like USA, China and Mexico. The adverse consequence of it is on productivity, health, safety and personal development of employee. Thus, the training on cross-cultural and new organisation development which relates to employment is very essential to make access population more productive.

In this context, various committee reports suggested government of India to undertake training and development activities within the course curriculum of higher education. The integration of training within higher education framework will enhance intelligent and emotional quotient of the students. An improvement in emotional quotient makes people of our nation more productive and sustainable. Therefore, this proposed study aims to evaluate a necessity of training and development activities in higher education institutions particularly in rural India.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

K.Ashwatappa (2008) - Training and Development improves performance of employee by changing his attitude

Rajendran Karuppanan (2012) - It reveals that training is necessary any to inculcate positive changes in knowledge skills and attitudes.

Vo and Hannif (2012) - Lack of vocational training in higher education cause to increase cost burden of employer for training.

Lorette (2018) - The training and development remains to nourish the skills of employees which help to accomplish the organisational goals.

The study relates to necessity of training and development in higher education institutes is very limited in Indian context. Hence this study is unique.

3. STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM:

Soon after the globalisation, Indian higher education institutes gave emphasis to job oriented course curriculum. However, the changing pattern of food, culture and skills has adverse consequences on health and competence level of youth. Therefore leakages of human resource have been increasing in recent years. In this context integration of soft skills training within higher education frame work is very much essential to reduce leakages in human resource. The proposed study aims to evaluate necessity of training and development in higher education institutions.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- 1) To high light necessity of training and development in higher education.
- 2) To identify the challenges for integrating training and development programs within the frame work of higher education institution.

5. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Sources of data:-As study deals with training and development in higher education particularly in rural area, the data's are collected from primary source of information.

Sample size: - Study covers 50 respondents of sample unit.

6. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES:

The study uses pie square and ratio analysis techniques to analyse data.

TRAINING ATTENDED (%)

Author’s calculation:

In the given chart 42% of respondent participated in personality development (soft skill and life skill training).22% respondent took occasional training .16% of respondent got job skill training. 20% of respondent have undergone corporate training. Therefore the finding of the study reveals that the awareness of occasional training and some job oriented training is very limited in rural area.

METHOD OF GETTING JOB TRAINING (%)

Author’s calculation:

In the analysis, 16% of respondent willing to attend on the job training, 22% like to take off the job training and 62% suggested on the job and off the job training.

NUMBER OF TRAINING SESSION ATTENDED (%)

Author’s calculation:

In the survey, 44% of students have attended maximum 2 training sessions. 28% of students attended 3 training sessions. 14% of students attended 4 training sessions and 14% of students participated in more than 5 training sessions. This finding suggests education institutions to create awareness on the relevance of soft skill and job skill training in cultivating employability among graduates of rural areas.

PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS ON TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

DESCRIPTION	PERCENTAGE OF STUDENTS	
	YES	NO
Necessity of training on employability	88	12
Regularity of training process in college	54	46
Training enhances confidence level	86	14
Positive influence of training on personality	70	30

Author

’s calculation:

In the given data analysis 88% students highlighted the necessity of training in education institutions to develop competency amongst graduates in rural areas. In the survey 54% of students have undergone capacity enhancement programmes on a regular basis training process. 86% of trainings have developed their self-confidence through soft skill education. In the total number of trainings 70% of them find positive effects of training in their personality development.

7. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The main focus of the study is to empower rural people through training and development. The integration of training and development in the course curriculum of higher education will increase the productivity of education institutions. Also, the performance of employees will be increased. The ultimate impact of inclusion of training and development in higher education is the minimisation of leakage of human resources. Therefore, this study throws light on how training and development in higher education will influence human resource development and economic growth.

8. LIMITATIONS:

As training and development in higher education newly introduced concept, the awareness on it is very limited among students of rural area. Hence, the collection of data in relation to training and development is problematic task.

9. CONCLUSION:

In the rural area, most of the students are first generation graduates. Hence they are not aware of contribution of training programmes in personality development. Thus, this paper suggests government to formulate policy on soft skill and job skill training in the course curriculum of higher education.

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Paper 39

**WATER LEVEL MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT
OF DAMS USING IOT****Akhila, Mekhala R.**

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Akhiju19@gmail.com Mekhalarao96@gmail.com**Abstract:**

The history, culture, current and future socioeconomic status and environmental sustainability of India and its people are intricately linked to the water resources which are available from dams. These water resources available through dams are one of the main sources available for the usage to industries, livestock, irrigation etc. and there is a critical need to ensure the safety of the water level at these dams against any natural or anthropogenic threats and to develop an effective Water Level Management system using IoT. This paper gives an outline for the development of an information system based on the existing systems with the utilization of some sensors and IoT. This paper also proposes a novel idea of collecting and sharing real-time information about water levels to an authorized central command center through far field communication. The authorized central command center then takes a call whether to release the water by opening dam gates or keep them closed. By doing so, the operation of dams all over the country is centralized and automatized.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dams are the major sources of water supply to cities, they also play a vital role in flood control and can assist river navigation. Most of the dams are built to serve more than one purpose and their benefits are manifold. It is necessary to implement some sort of communication between the metering systems and computer models to provide support in managing the complex systems of the hydro power plants. Generally, the dams are monitored through traditional surveillance techniques and the water management except the monitoring of level of water in some of the dams which is automatized. Management of water resources through dams becomes complex as the number of users depending on dams is huge and these users may have conflicting interests. This situation gets much complex with the fact that the available resources are limited with high possibilities of droughts and floods. This affects the densely populated areas. Dam monitoring is a tedious and long term process which has to be improved step by step. A new system for dam water monitoring and management should be established which can provide water level in real time and can allow us to come to quick conclusions regarding the safety operations of the dams. Internet of Things (IoT) can be defined as a network of devices which are interconnected. It comprises a set of sensors, communication network as well as software enabled electronic devices that enables end users to acquire accurate data from time to time through the communication channel and allows for data interchange between users and the connected devices.

This system can be used to automatize the control of dams without human interference. This can also be used to gather information on the level of water throughout the country and can be used to route water based on the requirements. We can get information on the water

availability in a particular region and route the water to that area if there's scarcity. This helps a lot in irrigation. Keeping a check on the safety of dam from time to time is one of the important measure to ensure the safety of dams. Use of Wireless sensors network with software for dam safety management helps in improving the functionality of dams. All the sensors in the cluster of dam such as Water Level Sensor ,Vibration Sensor and Pressure Sensor can be used to sense Water level ,Vibrations on the wall of dam and Pressure exerted on the wall of dam from the dam into the main pipeline in Litres per minute respectively[1].Differential Pressure sensors are fitted at equal spaces along the main pipeline which can sense the pressure difference because of the breaking or leakage of the pipeline and will immediately be communicated to the observer. In case of floods the routing of flood water can be done more efficiently considering the level of water across different dams. Surveillance of areas near the dams can be done using cameras which transmit live footage to the base station and will be helpful in identifying the presence of people near the dams and can help in ensuring safety while releasing water during flash floods. Internet of Things technology focusses on making the ecosystem of sensors more and more intelligent by establishing a connection to the internet. Collecting the data regarding the failed sensors enables us to generate more reliable equipment which in turn improves the reliability of the dams. Integration of Internet of Things with big data, cloud computing and WSN will enhance the operation capability to dams to a greater extent [2]. The entire processing of data will be done on the cloud which will ensure that the data retrieval and issuing of commands can be made faster with more reliability.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Level controlling of water or liquid is a very active field where many papers have addressed the fuzzy or neural networks control in the water level control system. It requires measurement and control of the water-level.

One of the easiest way to measure water level is using submersible pressure transducers (wet sensors) which are easy to install and require very little maintenance. For the very reason, they are often used for temporary installations and installations in remote locations. They are supposed to be installed in a fixed position and should remain fully submersed at all times. It works on the concept of application of hydrostatic pressure to a strain gauge, which converts mechanical movement into an electrical signal which is in turn measured by the station data logger and converted into pressure, level and discharge.

As we see, now a days the safety control of large dams depends mainly on the measurement of some important quantities like absolute and relative displacements, strains and stresses in the concrete, discharges through the foundation, etc. and on visual inspections of the dam structures. In certain dams, the analysis of the measured data is compared with results of mathematical or physical models and is helpful in the structural safety assessment.

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) provide a quick and flexible means of creating models for river flow prediction, and have been shown to perform well in comparison with conventional methods. These networks can be used for characterising the normal structural behaviour of the dams by taking into account the actions to which the structure is subject to in the past. An artificial neural network is nothing but an interconnected group of nodes, similar to the vast network of neurons in a brain. Each circular node of this network represents an artificial network and an arrow represents flow from the output of one node to the input of another.

A dam in its lifetime, can be exposed to significant water level variations and seasonal environmental temperature changes. The most important factor in water supplying is to

supply the required water quantity while maintaining a water head above a minimum limit. It is required to deliver the necessary quantity of water with the adequate pressure to the final consumers. The overhead storage tanks are built so that the water level could be kept at a constant value to maintain that pressure. The demand of the consumers is changing throughout the day and that leads to change the output flow rate of the tank. If water is supplied at a constant rate either over flow of water or pressure drops at end user may happen. This leads to the necessity of water level management.

One such project was done on river Nile by establishing national geo referential databases and spatial layers along with hydro-meteorological parameters, water usage information, land use, extent of land cover and soil types. Present day monitoring technologies such as automatized weather stations and acoustic based Doppler current profilers were introduced. This sort of equipment is coherent for water flow measurement. In majority of the rivers the Doppler current profiler is mounted on a boat and operated from there. This scraps the need for the construction of an expensive cableway. This project also constitutes two buoys to measure the extent of water evaporation on Lake Nasser in Egypt, serving as a means to check the ground truth for the satellite based evaporation computations. Most of the basin countries have adopted this data structure, which was designed in an interactive process with the respective water resource agencies. This generated data structure ensures seamless and rapid data exchange once it has set up proper mechanisms for data sharing. A common structure is also necessary for developing basin-wide assessment instruments like the Nile DST [3].

However, the South-East river trust employed a method called weir for water level control in river Teise .A weir is basically a barrier built across a river to alter the flow characteristics. In most cases weirs are constructed in the form of a horizontal barrier across the width of a river that pools water behind it whilst still allowing it to flow steadily over the top. Weirs are often used to prevent flooding and measure discharge.

Another monitoring system was developed for measurement of water levels, and it is composed of ultrasonic sensor, PIC micro-controller, and GSM module. The ultrasonic sensor measures the distance from the sensor to the liquid surface. This system proposes the development of water level monitoring system by integrating the GSM module to alert the person-in-charge through Short Message Service (SMS) when the water has reached the critical level and it will automatically turn OFF the pump. It is possible to monitor the level of water whenever required [4].

In China, computing techniques are deployed to curb wastage of water and generate better financial gains. It also ensures the conservation of environment and water cycle so that we can pass on the water resources to our future generations. They used systems constituting Arduino for the automation of pumping of water into the tanks with the help of sensors which can sense the level of water in the tank. The pump system will function automatically based on the level of water and a LED screen is used to keep the user informed regarding the status. This system can also be extended to automate the extraction of water from sump tank. The same strategy for measuring the level of water using sensors in the sump can be used nut here if the system senses that the water level is low it prevents the motor from running to ensure safety from dry running. An alert sound can be initiated in that case to alert the user regarding the issue [5].

The current dam control technology is manual wherein the handler operates the gate on command. This gives room for irregular water sharing between two properties, human error which can result in floods or unnecessary wastage of water. Our proposed system removes

these possibilities incorporating automated dam control system. The entire system is also partially self-powered. The design involves energy harvesting thereby making the system self sustained.

III. BASIC SCHEMATIC

The basic idea of this project is to fully automate the water level management near all the dams through a central server. This can be achieved by the use of IoT linked cloud services applications. At first each dam is considered as a single node. Many such nodes are linked to a central command centre which can oversee the working of each and every node.

Figure 1. Schematic of each node

At first the setup near the primary node i.e, (dam) consists of ultrasonic sensors on the either side of the dam gate. These ultrasonic sensors are useful to get the real time level of water on both the sides of the gate. Every dam has a local base station from which the data on level of water can be transmitted to the central server.

The ultrasonic sensor has to be interfaced with a micro controller through which information is relayed to the local base station. For this we need to use far-field communication methods as the minimum distance between the transmitter (near the sensor) and receiver (near the base station) will be at least 1 km. In this way the data from both the water level sensor reaches the local base station.

After gathering the information from both the water sensors, the base station sends the data to the central command centre via cloud. The data from each base station is uploaded to the cloud and the central command center can check the real time water level using this data and can decide whether the dam gates have to be kept open or closed.

All the dams will have base stations like these which gather data and transmit data to the cloud. So the command center has the real time data of all the dams across the country.

Figure 2. Schematic of the collection of nodes

After getting the data from each primary node the work of command center is decide whether the dam gates have to be opened or kept closed or vice versa. For this a pre-defined water levels have to be formulated i.e, below a certain threshold water level the gates of the dam have to be closed and above a threshold water level the dam gates have to be lifted. These defined water levels vary from node to node depending on the amount of water that dam can hold or the requirement of water at that particular area.

Now after the decision to open or close the gate has

been taken, this has to be sent as a command to the base station. So the command centre transmits the command to the base station and the base station in turn transmits the data to the gate control which opens or closes the gate based on the command. The flowchart depicting this entire process is being attached.

Figure 3. Flowchart of the implementation

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Determining the Level of Water

In the first stage we plan on getting the data on the level of water using ultrasonic sensors. The ultrasonic sensors are interfaced with a micro controller which transfers the data to a local base station using far field/near field communication. [6] Components required: Ultrasonic sensors, Arduino.

B. Short Range Communication

In this stage we deal with transferring the data at shorter distances i.e., at a local base station. The distance might range from few hundred meters to one or two kilometres. The short data transfer modules like Bluetooth or XBee are interfaced with the Arduino and used to transfer the data. Components required: Bluetooth module / XBee module.

C. Long Range Communication

In this stage we work on transferring the data to long distances of order of several hundred kilometres. These helps us in gathering the data from all the nodes to a central base station which in turn reads the data and send the commands based on it. The technologies required to achieve this are yet to be finalized. Some types of communication which can be used for such purposes are LoRa , NB-IoT.

- LoRaWAN is a Low Power Wide Area Network

(LPWAN) intended to provide long range connectivity for wireless battery operated Things in a regional, national or global network. LoRaWAN meets the key requirements of Internet of Things such as secure bidirectional communication, mobility and localization services.

- Narrow Band IoT (NB-IoT) is a category of Low Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN) technology standard developed to enable a connection using cellular LTE bands between wide range of devices and services. NB-IoT is a narrowband radio technology designed specifically for the Internet of Things (IoT) applications. NB-IoT focuses primarily on indoor coverage, low cost, long battery life, and enabling a large number of connected devices.

V. PROGRESS

A prototype of the proposed idea has been implemented using short range communication (Bluetooth modules), Ultrasonic sensors and Arduino micro controller. The first stage of the implementation which involves determining the level of water using water level sensors. The water level sensor is mounted on the top of a water container which determines the distance between the top of the container and the surface of the water. If the distance goes below a certain point it indicates that the water level in the container has exceeded optimum level. The pictorial representation of the setup is shown below.

Figure 4. Setup of water level sensor

The water level data is transmitted to the second Arduino board through Bluetooth module. The readings received by the micro controller are shown in Fig. 6. Two nodes send data simultaneously to the central command centre. The level of water from both the stations are received one after the other at the central station. If the volume is increasing, then the level of water is increasing and when it is about to reach the max capacity of the container a signal is sent to the servo motor. The second micro controller which operates the servo motor interprets the input data and when the level of water is more, it switches on

Figure 5. Setup of the Servo motor controlling gate mechanism

the servo motor which will be connected to the gate mechanism. As soon as the level of water decreases the second micro controller will not send any command to operate the servo motor hence the gate mechanism is closed.

VI. APPLICATIONS & USES

The above mentioned method will ease the process of water level management on a large scale. We can solve many water related issues by this method. By installing a central command center we are decreasing the manpower required at each and every dam. Since this

is a fully automated project, any kind of human intervention has been avoided. So the possibility of faults has also decreased.

In cases of emergency, the override capability will be given to an authorized personnel who can change the command if required. In places where there are issues of water distribution between two areas, this method helps in maintaining neutrality as the command is with the central command center and neither of the areas involved in the fight can give the command.

During times of natural disasters like floods, this method will be very helpful as we don't need to have any human to control near the actual site of the dam. Any command required for the gate opening or gate closing can be given from remote center. This also reduces the response time as the water level data near command center is real time and the decisions are taken almost instantaneously

Since the data of water levels near all the dams throughout the country are at the same place, a quick decision on the routing of flood water can also be taken. This helps in decreasing the losses due to floods to a significant extent.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Water is one of the primary resource for human survival. But unfortunately a mammoth amount of water is being squandered by uncontrolled use. There are certain automated water level monitoring systems in practice but they are used for various applications and have some shortness in practice. We tried to suggest ways to tackle this problem and implement an efficient water level monitoring and management system. The main motto of this research work is to establish a flexible, economical and easy configurable system which can solve our water distribution problem between two regions and safeguard the low lying areas from floods etc. among many other issues. We have been using a micro controller to manage the data and to reduce the cost. We have been successfully conducting the experiments in lab and therefore proposed a cloud based water level monitoring and management network whose flexibility would offer us to control the system from any place via access to cloud data with different type of devices. This type of system is more helpful in situations like floods where the automated gate lifting system will check the water levels and react according the situation. This could have a substantial benefit to the research work related to the efficient management of water at dams by reducing the manual work.

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Paper 40**THE STUDY OF SOLAR CHARGE CONTROLLER
USING PWM TECHNIQUE AND A MODEL TO
IMPROVE ITS PERFORMANCE****P. Sridhar Acharya * P. S. Aithal ****

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E-mail: sridharaacharya@gmail.com* psaithal@gmail.com****Abstract**

The performance efficiency of solar energy is identified to be around 20%. The major portion of the solar energy produced will be lost due to several reasons like photon incident, impurities in the photovoltaic cell, the guiding media which is the copper wire offering resistance to the flow of current, the performance of the charge controller and the voltage level of the battery bank. Its really difficult to improve the efficiency of the solar energy due to the above reasons. The performance of solar charge controller is very essential to improve the efficiency of solar energy. The solar charge controller also plays a very important role in improving the life of the storage device. There are various types of solar charge controller available. Recently the solar energy system started using the PWM based charge controller technique to improve the performance of the solar energy system as well as to increase the life span of the battery backup. This paper contains the performance of solar charge controller using PWM technique. The variation in the charging depends on the pulse width. This paper proposes the new model in addition to the PWM charge controller to divert the solar energy to the load during short pulse width. This improves the performance efficiency of the solar energy.

1. Introduction

The most popular alternate renewable energy used in India is the solar energy. [1] This form of energy has a lot of advantages. The energy from solar PV panel is eco-friendly by contributing zero to the pollution [2] The Solar energy system is becoming more and more popular because this system can be used for a small power requirements to light a single bulb inside the small shop or street light to any power requirements for industries, commercial power requirements etc.[3] The installation of solar plants is easy and can be done in a bare land or roof top. The only requirement for the installation is the sufficient availability of sun light for a longer period in a day time. [4] The solar energy thus generated from the solar panel can be directly given to the load along with the available commercial electricity supply. [5]

In the same way the solar energy can be stored and then utilised using a hybrid technology. [6] Thus the solar energy can be considered as an alternate energy to the existing commercial energy system. This energy can be used along with the conventional commercial energy. This enables the consumer to go for any amount of power generation from the solar energy system.

The most challenging factor of the solar energy system is the efficiency of the same. [7] The total efficiency of the solar energy system is found to be 18% to 20%. There are various factors contributing to the low efficiency of the solar energy like[8]

- Performance of the photovoltaic cell due to impurities in the cell.
- Dust particle deposited on the surface of the solar panel.
- Incident of sunlight to the solar panel.
- Resistance offered by the conducting element which carries the solar energy to the storage device.
- Performance of the solar charge controller.

The major factor for the photovoltaic cell impurities is the minor charge carriers in the diode. [9]The improved technology using nano technology increases the efficiency by decreasing the impurities. But this increases the cost of the solar panel. [10] Due to the high production cost of the solar panel using nano technology, the panel is not affordable in the market.

Another factor which influences the efficiency of the solar panel is the deposition of the dust particles on the protective glass surface of the solar panel. The dust particle deposited on the glass surface will decrease the current in Amps when the sun light falls on the solar panel. [11] This reduces the efficiency of the solar energy system. This problem can be solved by regularly cleaning the panel.

One more factor which effects the performance of the solar energy is the varying incident of the sunlight throughout a day. [12] The maximum power output can be expected when the solar cell is placed perpendicular to the sunlight incident. [13] But in practice this is possible only for a few seconds. The variation in the sunlight incident changes the amount of current produced in Amps. For example if a panel is able to produce a current of say 7 Amps, the current of 7Amps can be produced only when the sun light is perpendicular to the solar panel. In reality the current varies from 0Amp to max 7 Amps and back to 0Amp in a day time from morning till evening.

The performance efficiency of the solar energy system is affected by the resistance offered by the conducting medium which carries the energy generated to the battery backup.[14] Normally the solar panels are mounted at the roof top where there is a sufficient amount of sunlight available. The solution to this loss is to minimise the distance between the solar panel and the battery backup. But the arrangement of the solar panel and battery backup depends on the building or geographical conditions.

The efficiency of the solar panel depends even on the charge controller which is used to charge a battery bank.[15] There are different technologies used for charging the battery bank in the solar energy system like transistor series and shunt switching circuit, PWM charge controller and MPPT based charge controller. The performance of these charge controllers differ from one another because of their performance characteristics. This results in the efficiency of the solar energy system.[16]

2. Objective

The objective of this paper is to study the performance of the solar charge controller using PWM technique and to propose a conceptual model which can improve the performance efficiency of the PWM solar charge controller.

3. Methodology

- The working principle of the PWM solar charge controller is explained.
- The conceptual model is introduced
- Working of the model
- The performance is analysed.

3.1 Working of PWM solar charge controller

The PWM solar charge controller uses a variable pulse generator. This variation in the pulse is due to the stored energy level in the battery bank. If the battery bank is having less energy stored then the pulse width will be more so that the energy from the solar panel can directly be stored in the battery backup. As the battery is getting charged the pulse width reduces and the charging rate also decreases. This technique improves the battery life. The conceptual diagram is shown in figure 1 and figure 2.

Figure 1. Performance of the PWM charge controller when battery backup is low

Figure 2. Performance of the PWM charge controller when battery backup is getting full

From the above two figures it is clear that when the battery backup is not full the solar energy is directly stored inside the battery backup. The charging pulse width goes on reducing when the battery backup is getting filled. This protects the battery backup from overcharging. Once the battery is fully charged the controller sends small pulse to sense the battery backup. If the battery is full then the charge controller will not charge the battery. Whereas if the battery backup needs charging then the pulse width will increase to charge the battery. To vary the pulse width the charge controller takes the battery voltage as a reference voltage.

The main drawback of this technology is the solar energy produced during the sunlight when the battery is fully charged. The charge controller will not charge the battery when the battery is full. During this period the solar energy produced will be wasted either in the form of heat or the panel may be damaged due to non-utilization of the solar energy.

3.2 The conceptual Model

The drawback of the PWM based solar charge controller is taken as an opportunity to develop a conceptual model. The idea behind the conceptual model is to divert the solar energy to the load when the battery is fully charged and divert to the battery backup when the charge in the battery is not full. The proposed model is shown in the figure 3.

Figure 3. The proposed New conceptual model.

3.3 Working of the model

The proposed model works like the regular PWM charge controller when the pulse width is more. This charges the battery at the rapid rate. When the battery is getting fully charged the pulse width decreases. This decrease in the pulse width reduces the charging rate. Once the battery is fully charged the pulse becomes a spike to sense the battery voltage.

The model has another load controller which sends the solar energy to the inverter. The inverter is connected to the load. The load controller gets the solar energy when the battery backup is either getting full or full. The input solar energy is given to the load though the inverter. The inverter is not just an ordinary inverter instead it is a smart inverter which will take the input energy from solar and in case required the additional energy is taken from the battery backup.

4. Analysis

The proposed model is utilising the solar energy to the maximum extent. Whenever the battery backup requires the energy to be stored the controller diverts the solar energy into the battery bank for charging whereas when the battery bank is getting full the solar energy is taken by the load controller which converts the energy into alternative energy and the load. Thus whatever energy produced by the solar PV system is utilised to the maximum extent.

5. Conclusion

The model is used efficiently by switching from charging mode to the connecting to the load mode. Whatever energy produced from the solar PV system is utilised to the maximum extent. This improves the overall efficiency of the model.

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Paper 41

**CHANGES IN BASEL NORMS AND ITS IMPACT ON
INDIAN BANKS****Mr. Amith Donald Menezes**Assistant Professor, Dept.of Mgt. & Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar , Mangalore
& Research Scholar at VTUE-mail- amith.menezes@yahoo.co.in**Abstract:**

Basel III norms are guidelines framed by a committee of central banks that is based in Basel, Switzerland. The Reserve Bank of India is also a member of this committee. The norms aim to toughen up the banking system in every country to withstand financial shock. They focus on the risks that banks are vulnerable to, particularly after the crisis in the banking sector, which was triggered by the problem in the US sub-prime mortgage market. Basel III aims to plug the gaps in the existing Basel II guidelines. The new norms will be made effective in a phased manner from January 1, 2013 and implemented fully from March 31, 2019. The guidelines will ensure that banks are well capitalized to manage all kinds of risks. The existing norms stipulate that banks should maintain Tier-I capital, or core capital, and Tier-II capital that comprise instruments with debt-like features. The proposed Basel III norms are going to have a significant impact on the Indian financial sector. While it is in a comfortable position to meet some of the proposed Basel III norms, the implementation of some of the other norms will be a challenge.

This paper tries to find out the impact of Basel III norms on the Indian banking industry.

Keywords: Banking, Basel-III, Equity, Buffers, Capital-Adequacy-Ratio, Tier-I, Tier-II**1. INTRODUCTION**

The breakdown of the Bretton Woods system of managed exchange rates in 1973 soon led to casualties. On 26 June 1974, West Germany's Federal Banking Supervisory Office withdrew Bankhaus Herstatt's banking license after finding that the bank's foreign exchange exposures amounted to three times its capital. Banks outside Germany took heavy losses on their unsettled trades with Herstatt, adding an international dimension to the debacle.

In October the same year, the Franklin National Bank of New York also closed its doors after racking up huge foreign exchange losses. Three months later, in response to these and other disruptions in the international financial markets, the central bank governors of the G10 countries established a Committee on Banking Regulations and Supervisory Practices.

Later renamed as the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, the Committee was designed as a forum for regular cooperation between its member countries on banking supervisory matters. Its aim was and is to enhance financial stability by improving supervisory knowhow and the quality of banking supervision worldwide.

The Committee seeks to achieve its aims by setting minimum supervisory standards; by improving the effectiveness of techniques for supervising international banking business; and by exchanging information on national supervisory arrangements. And, to engage with the

challenges presented by diversified financial conglomerates, the Committee also works with other standard-setting bodies, including those of the securities and insurance industries.

Since the first meeting in February 1975, meetings have been held regularly three or four times a year. After starting life as a G10 body, the Committee expanded its membership in 2009 and now includes 27 jurisdictions. The Committee now reports to an oversight body, the Group of Central Bank Governors and Heads of Supervision (GHOS), which comprises central bank governors and (non-central bank) heads of supervision from member countries. This committee has taken various measures to strengthen the banking structure, to enable the banks to face the financial crisis, and to survive in the period of stress. Namely, this committee has given following three accords:

1. BASEL I
2. BASEL II
3. BASEL III

The first concrete evidence of global coordination in banking regulation were felt towards the end of 1974, when the G-10 countries (now its G-20 group of nations) took the initiative to form the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) under the auspices of Bank for International Settlements (BIS) comprising of central bank governors of participating countries.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To understand the Basel Accords and more particularly Basel-III in detail.
- To know/understand the need of Basel Accords.
- To understand the RBI guidelines regarding Basel-III.
- To estimate the additional capital requirements of PSB's and Pvt. Sector.
- To examine the impact of Latest Basel Accord on Indian banking.

3. METHODOLOGY:

To fulfil the objectives of the study, we have taken both primary & secondary data into consideration.

Primary data: Primary data has been collected through personal interview by direct contact method. Personal interview and discussion was made with the manager and other personnel in the organization for this purpose.

Secondary data:

The secondary data is collected from the Magazines, Annual reports, Internet and Text books.

Basel I Accord:

The Accord called for a minimum capital ratio of capital to risk-weighted assets of 8% to be implemented by the end of 1992. Ultimately, this framework was introduced not only in member countries but also in virtually all other countries with active international banks. In September 1993, a statement was issued confirming that all the banks in the G10 countries with material international banking business were meeting the minimum requirements set out in the 1988 Accord.

Limitations of Basel I

However, Basel I comprised of some rigidities, as it did not discriminate between different levels of risks. As a result, a loan to an established corporate borrower was considered as

risky as a loan to a new business. .So all loans given to corporate borrowers were subject to the same capital requirements, without taking into account the ability of the counterparties to repay. It also did not take cognizance of the credit rating, credit history and corporate governance structure of all corporate borrowers

Basel II Accord: Banking has changed dramatically since the Basel I document of 1988. Advances in risk management and the increasing complexity of financial activities / instruments (like options, hybrid securities etc.) prompted international supervisors to review the appropriateness of regulatory capital standards under Basel I. To meet this requirement, the Basel I accord was amended and refined, which came out as the Basel II accord.

The new proposal is based on three mutually reinforcing pillars that allow banks and supervisors to evaluate properly the various risks that banks face and realign regulatory capital more closely with underlying risks.

Figure 1 : Basel II framework

LIMITATIONS OF BASEL II:

1. Lack of sufficient public knowledge
2. Lack of precise knowledge
3. Lack of consistency

BASEL III

A strong and resilient banking system is the foundation for sustainable economic growth, as banks are at the centre of the credit intermediation process between savers and investors. And provide critical services to consumers, small and medium-sized Business, large corporate firms and governments who rely on them to conduct their daily business, both at a domestic and international level. One of the main reasons the economic and financial crisis of 2007 became so severe was that the banking sectors of many countries had built up excessive on and off-balance sheet leverage.

The approach to capital regulation – based on so-called “Basel I” and “Basel II” – was identified by many regulators and commentators as one of the key factors contributing to the financial crisis. Moreover, Basel I and II focused on capital only, with no internationally agreed quantitative standards for liquidity. This is often perceived to have been a serious shortcoming when the financial crisis unfolded in 2007 and liquidity evaporated in the key funding markets used by many banks and bank-sponsored vehicles.

To address the market failures revealed by the crisis, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) introduced Basel III as fundamental reforms to the international regulatory framework. The reforms strengthen bank-level, or micro prudential, regulation, which will help raise the resilience of individual banking institutions to periods of stress.

Under Basel III, the quality and composition of capital are expected to be increased in a phased manner spanning up to year 2019. While Tier-1 capital has to be increased from 4.5% in 2013 to 6% by 2019, the overall capital, including capital conservation buffers and counter-cyclical buffers, is required to be increased from 8% in 2013 to 10.5% in 2019. Liquidity ratios are envisaged to be initiated in a phased manner beginning with an observation period that commenced in 2011. The introduction of minimum standards for liquidity ratios are expected to be between 2014 and 2018. The most discussed leverage ratio is monitored from 2011. Below table captures the key elements of Basel-III framework and the timeline for their full compliance as per BCBS.

Features of the Basel III

- 1.) Enhanced Capital Requirement:
- 2.) Tier 1 Capital requirements
- 3.) Introduction of a Capital Conservation Buffer
- 4.) Introduction of Countercyclical Buffer
- 5.) Leverage Ratio (Ratio of Tier 1 Capital to Total Assets)
- 6.) Liquidity Risk Measurement

BASEL III OBJECTIVES

According to the BCBS, the Basel III proposals has two main objectives:

- 1.) To strengthen global capital and liquidity regulation with the goal of promoting a more resilient banking sector.
- 2.) To improve the banking sector’s ability to absorb shocks arising from financial and economic stress, which, in turn, would reduce the risk of a spillover from the financial sector to the real economy.

Figure 2 Comparison of Basel II to Basel III

Table. 1. Comparison of capital requirements under Basel II and Basel III

Requirements	Under Basel II	Under Basel III
Minimum Ratio of Total capital to RWAs	8%	10.5%
Minimum Ratio of common Equity to RWAs	2%	4.5% to 7%
Tier 1 capital to RWAs	4%	6%
Core Tier 1 capital to RWAs	2%	5%
capital conservation Buffers to RWAs	None	2.5%
Leverage Ratio	None	3%
Countercyclical Buffer	None	0% to 2.5%
Minimum liquidity coverage Ratio	None	From 2015
Minimum Net stable Funding Ratio	None	From 2018
Systemically important Financial Institutions Charge	None	From 2011

Significance of Basel III for Indian banking:

Basel III guidelines attempt to enhance the ability of banks to withstand periods of economic and financial stress by prescribing more stringent capital and liquidity requirements for them. The new Basel III capital requirement would be a positive impact for banks as it raises the minimum core capital stipulation, introduces counter-cyclical measures, and enhance banks' ability to conserve core capital in the event of stress through a conservation capital buffer. The prescribed liquidity requirements, on the other hand, would bring in uniformity in the liquidity standards followed by the banks globally. This liquidity standard requirement, would benefit the Indian banks manage pressure on liquidity in a stress scenario more effectively.

Although implementing Basel III will only be an evolutionary step, the impact of Basel III on banking sector cannot be underestimated, as it will drive significant challenges that need to be understood and addressed. Working out the most cost-effective model for implementation of Basel III will be a critical issue for Indian banking.

1. Impact on the financial system:

Basel III framework implementation would lead to reduced risk of systematic banking crisis as the enhanced capital and liquidity buffers together lead to better management of probable risks emanating due to counterparty defaults and or liquidity stress circumstances.

2. Higher Capital Requirement

Presently, in India, most banks' common equity ratio falls in the range of about 6-10 per cent. Hence, in my opinion, banks may able to comply with the higher capital requirement as per Basel III norms at least till 2014/15. This, without infusing any fresh equity, even while taking into account the marginal increase in capital requirement.

3. Pressure on Return on Equity:

To meet the new norms, apart from government support a significant number of banks have to raise capital from the market. This will push the interest rate up, and in turn, cost of capital will rise while return on equity (RoE) will come down.

4. Pressure on Yield on Assets:

On account of higher deployment of funds in liquid assets that give comparatively lower returns, banks' yield on assets, and thereby their profit margins, may be under pressure.

5. On weaker banks:

Further, there would be a drastic impact on the weaker banks leading to their crowding out. As is well established, as conditions deteriorate and the regulatory position gets even more intensive, the weaker banks would definitely find it very challenging to raise the required capital and funding.

6. Increased supervisory vigil:

Banking operations might experience a reduced pace as there would be an increased supervisory vigil on the activities of the banks in terms of ensuring the capital standards, liquidity ratios-LCR and NSFR and others.

7. Reorganization of institutions:

The increased focus of the regulatory authorities on the organizational structure and capital structure ability of the financial firms (mainly banks) would lead the banks to reorganize their legal identity by resorting to mergers and disposals of portfolios, entities, or parts of entities wherever possible.

8. International Arbitrage:

In case of inconsistent implementation of Basel III framework among different countries would lead to international arbitrage thereby resulting in disruption of global financial stability.

Action Required from Banks

In this regard the following strategies need to be adopted:

1. Change in Business Mix:

Since retail banking has a comparatively lower risk weight compared to corporate banking (except in the case of clients who are A rated and above), the impact on higher allocation of capital will be less on retail banking

2. Change in Customer Mix:

Banks need to review their capital allocation to each client segment and price it in line with the profile to ensure that capital is allocated to segments that generate higher risk-adjusted returns.

3. Low-Cost Funding:

One of the most important factors to meet the new regulations is to have a stable low-cost deposit base. For this, banks need to focus more on having business correspondents/facilitators to reach customers as adding branches will increase costs and have an impact on the profit margin.

4. Improvement in systems and procedures:

Refining the rating model/data cleaning/ modernization of systems and procedures may help banks economize their risk-weighted assets, which will help reduce capital requirements to some extent.

5. Additional capital:

In order to fully compliment with the Basel III capital requirements banks require additional capital, banks need to frame out the proper strategy regarding procurement of needed funds.

Are Indian banks ready to implement Basel III?

Most of the private sector and foreign banks are in a comfortable position since they have a core capital in excess of 9% whereas this is not the case with the public sector banks. According to an ICRA report, public and private sector banks would require an additional capital of 600000 crore, assuming a 20% growth in risk-weighted assets, which is “achievable so long as banks can find investors for the riskier additional tier I capital,” says ICRA.

Out of the total requirement 75-80% will be required by the public sector banks. Thus the burden will fall on the cash-stripped government which will need to infuse massive amount of capital to maintain its shareholding of 58%. This looks difficult to achieve seeing the current state of the government financials with high fiscal deficit of 5.9% in 2011-12 and massive subsidy burden. The government is not in a position to provide the capital nor will it allow other investors to do so because it would reduce the government’s grip on public sector banks.

The leverage ratio of 3% will not affect the Indian banks much because this is meant for banks with large trading book and exposure to off balance sheet derivatives and Indian banks don’t have much exposure to the derivatives market. Liquidity coverage Ratio (LCR) requires banks to hold enough liquid assets to cover cash outflows during a 30 day stress period. Indian banks are fairly comfortable on this front as well as they hold 24% in government securities in form of SLR(Statutory Liquidity Ratio) and 4.75% in cash in form of CRR(Cash Reserve Ratio) with the RBI.

However the ultimate LCR burden would depend on how much CRR and SLR can be offset against LCR. Basel III will also force banks to put a large part of their profit back in the balance sheet as retained earnings rather than distributing dividends. Although there is no significant improvement in capital requirement under Basel3 as compared to Basel 2 but the problem is change in way that some of the capital market instruments will be treated. Perpetual debt which is now treated as Tier 1 capital will be excluded under Basel3, putting more pressure in the requirement of core capital.

Findings

The new capital requirements under Basel III would have a positive impact for banks as they raise the minimum core capital, introduces counter-cyclical measures, and enhance bank’s ability to conserve core capital in the event of stress through a conservation capital buffer. The liquidity standards requirements would benefit the Indian banks in managing the pressures on liquidity in a stress scenario more effectively. However, in case of inconsistent implementation of a new framework among different countries would lead to international arbitrage thereby resulting in disruption of global financial stability.

Basel III framework’s impact on the financial system would be significant, as its implementation would lead to reduced risk of systemic banking crises as the enhanced capital and liquidity buffers together lead to an improved management of probable risk emanating due to counter party defaults and or liquidity stress circumstances. The stricter norms on inter-bank liability limits would reduce the interdependence of the banks and the reduced

interconnectivity among the banks would save the banks from contagion risk during the times of crisis.

There would be a strong impact on the weaker banks leading to their crowding out. As the conditions deteriorate and the regulatory position gets even more intensive, the weaker banks would definitely find it very challenging to raise the required capital and funding. Further, this would affect their business models apart from titling the banking business in favour of large financial institutions and thereby titling the competition in the light of increased regulatory oversight on the organisational structure and capital structure of the financial firms (mainly banks), there would be scenarios where the banks may look towards reorganizing their legal identity by resorting to mergers and acquisitions and disposal of portfolios, entities, or parts of entities wherever possible.

Summary of Basel III implications

1) **Increased quality of capital**

Basel III contains various measures aimed at improving the quality of capital, with the ultimate aim to improve loss-absorption capacity in both going concern and liquidation scenarios.

2) **Increased quantity of capital**

Basel III contains various measures aimed at increasing the level of capital held by institutions, as well as providing counter-cyclical mechanisms

3) **Reduced leverage**

Leverage ratio acts as non-risk sensitive backstop measure to reduce the risk of build up of excessive leverage in the institution and in the financial system as a whole.

4) **Increase short term liquidity coverage**

The regulatory response to the financial crisis has seen a long overdue rebalancing towards the importance of the liquidity risk management and to complement its “principles for sound liquidity risk management and supervision”, the Basel committee has further strengthened its liquidity frameworks by developing two minimum standards for funding liquidity: have a negative impact on probability.

5) **Increased stable long term balance sheet funding**

The Net Stable Funding Ratios (NSFR) is designed to encourage and incentivize the banks to use stable source to fund their activities to reduce the dependency on short-term funding.

6) **Strengthen risk capture, notably counterparty risk**

The BCBs seek to ensure full coverage of risks in the Pillar 1 framework increasing the capital requirements against risks not adequately captured in the Basel II framework.

4. RECOMENDATIONS :

Actions to consider in respect of capital management

- Carry out appropriate scenario planning and impact assessments to ensure the development of a successful capital strategy.
- Identify which businesses have most attractive fundamentals under Basel III and which businesses in the firm’s portfolio should be considered for exiting, growing, or diverting.
- Ensure managers have adequate incentive to optimize use of capital.
- Apply consistent, quantified capital objectives throughout the group.

- Identify the changes needed to fine-tune/lower capital consumption.
- Ensure the firm is geared up to deliver measurement and management and requirements on a sufficiently timely basis.
- Consider how to address the pricing implications arising from changes in the capital requirements for certain products.
- Review whether the same business models can continue under a different structure, minimizing capital penalties (e.g. branch versus subsidiary).
- Prepare to be able to meet accelerated implementation time scales if required.

Actions to consider in respect of liquidity Management

- Ensure an understanding of current liquidity position in sufficient detail and possession of knowledge of where the stress points are.
- Ensure management has adequate incentive to optimize use of capital.
- Consider the impact of new liquidity rules on profitability and whether it has been factored into key business process and pricing.
- Check that liquidity planning, governance, and modelling are in line with leading industry practice.
- Determine an appropriate series of liquidity stress test and how these will change overtime.
- Gain awareness of the likely implementation timetable for different elements of the global and national framework being proposed.
- Assess the firm's strategy in light of the existing legal and regulatory structure of the organization and identity whether the system, data, and management reporting are adequate to meet the requirements.

Actions to consider in respect of general capital planning:

- Ensure that business is correctly charged for the capital costs of the business that they are doing.
- Ensure that Basel III capital implications are taken into account for new business and consider how existing long-dated business can be revisited.
- Consider the introduction of external capital into specialist structure models to mitigate the capital impacts arising.
- Focus on Basel III implementation as well as Basel III given that Basel III amplifies any increase in RWAs arising from Basel II.
- Examine the performance of existing assessment methodologies (e.g. IRB Models)
- Review existing data quality—Are the benefits from collateral information or improved re-rating of obligors due to inappropriate process missing?

5. CONCLUSION

It needs to be clearly understood that Basel III is an evolution rather than a revolution for many banks. It is an improvement over the existing Basel II framework. The most significant differences for banks are the introduction of liquidity and leverage ratios and enhanced minimum capital requirements. Basel III provides for a timeline of implementation which is quite acceptable in the case of Indian context, as it is observed that Indian banks are relatively well positioned for smoother implementation of the new standards.

While the effective implementation of Basel III will demonstrate to the stakeholders that the bank is quite well positioned, a speedy implementation would contribute to bank's competitiveness by delivering better management insight into the business, enabling it to take strategic advantage of future opportunities.

One of the main significant challenges posed by Basel III apart from the increased capital standards is that of creating a new risk management culture with a greater rigor and accountability. In effect, Basel III is changing the way the banks look at their risk management functions and might imply them to go for a robust risk management framework to ensure a true enterprise risk management. From the regulator's angle, it requires RBI to be proactive and stricter in terms of regulatory supervision surveillance.

The major challenge the Indian banks face is the deteriorating quality of assets and reduced profitability. Dr. D. Subha Rao, Former Governor of R.B.I. has rightly opined that effective implementation of Basel –III is going to make Indian banks stronger, more stable and sound so that they could deliver value to the real sectors of the economy. By far, the most important reform is that there should be a radical change in banks approach to risk management. Banks in India are currently operating on the standardized approaches of Basel – II. Since Basel III is a Universal compulsion, Indian Banks have no choice but to prepare themselves for achieving this herculean task of capital augmentation. The large scale banks need to migrate to the advanced approaches, especially as they expand their overseas presence. The adoption of advanced approaches to risk management would enable banks to manage their capital more efficiently and improve their profitability.

As Basel III aims at providing a solid foundation for financially sound banking, it is both a challenge and an opportunity for Indian banks. The opportunity comes in the form of acquiring new quality capital, selection of technology architecture and redesigning of the risk management as well as risk reporting. The challenge is for the bank management and the regulator in successfully implementing the new standards as per the suggested timeline and win over the stakeholders.

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Paper 46

A CRITICAL STUDY ON APPLICATIONS OF MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN BUSINESS ANALYTICS

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Abstract:

The advancement of Information and Communication Computing Technology (ICCT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) made a revolution in Computer Science and its applications areas like Business Intelligence (BI). Artificial Intelligence, Business Intelligence, and Machine Learning work together in order to predict and analyze some complex business analytics and thereby assisting the top managers to take some better decisions at higher levels. With the aid of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning can able to provide the ability to machines or systems automatically learn, and take decisions like human beings without programming explicitly based on experience. Machine Learning concepts have applications in diverse fields like day-to-day or daily business transactions to complex business analytics like Marketing Analytics, Pricing Analytics, Social Media Analytics, Customer Analytics, Supply Chain Analytics, and many more. Business Analytics is analyzing the business in 3600 angle which covers historical perspective or Descriptive, future perspective or Predictive and combinations of both or Perspective in order to make better and highly valuable decisions. Machine learning algorithms include supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and Meta-learning. The Machine learning algorithms include different techniques like Nearest Neighbour, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Classification Rule, Regression Analysis, Regression Trees, Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, and many others. Unsupervised learning includes Clustering, Anomaly Detection, Association Rule, and a few others. Meta-learning algorithm covers Bagging, Boosting, Random Forest and a few others. This paper covers applications of machine learning algorithms in different areas of business analytics which includes Marketing Analytics, Pricing Analytics, Social Media Analytics, Customer Analytics, Supply Chain Analytics, Healthcare Analytics, and Portfolio analytics. This paper also tries to distinguish between supervised learning and unsupervised learning. This paper tries to find upcoming areas where machine learning algorithms can best fit in order to make some complex decision or to solve complex business problems.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Neural Network, Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Business Analytics, Meta-Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Data is the centered around all types of business analytics which acts as raw input and are generated every now and then from various sources. Human beings are centered around this data and can generate data through different activities like mobile usage and computing,

health care, professional, entertainment, pricing, financial, social media, sports, retail and many more [1]. Not only human beings but also machine generates data like robotics systems, satellite system, computers, and an other types of machine which are used by human beings for various purposes all over the world. Data are usually classified as structured, semi structured, quasi-structured and un-structured data and spread over the globe [2]. The structured data are usually stored in well defined format and are easily recorded, where as unstructured data are not having any order and schema which are generating using various click streams at the time of browsing and internet usage [3-4]. Larger and unstructured or schema less data are accessible at our fingertips through internet. The machine learning is the special field where heterogeneous data are processed into information using well defined set of algorithms and these informations are used for business intelligent decision making purpose. The machine learning field is closely related with statistics, mathematical techniques, and computer science or computing power [5]. Due to mobile wireless technology, satellite, internet of things, and many more advanced technology created data explosions and which necessitated need of extra or more computing power and that led to the development of more statistical methods to discover and analyze the huge datasets.

A closely related branch of machine learning, data mining, deals with the generation of new knowledge from large databases [6]. As the name implies, data extraction involves a systematic search for a piece of actionable intelligence. While there is some disagreement about the extent to which machine learning and data extraction overlap, a possible point of distinction is that machine learning focuses on teaching computers how to use data to solve a problem, while Data extraction focuses on teaching computers to identify patterns that humans then use to solve a problem. Practically all data extraction involves the use of machine learning, but not all machine learning involves data extraction [7-9]. For example, you can apply machine learning to car traffic data from the data mine for patterns related to accident rates; On the other hand, if the computer is learning to drive the car itself, this is purely machine learning without data mining. Machines are not good at asking questions, or even knowing what questions to ask. They are much better at answering them, provided the question is stated in a way the computer can comprehend. Present-day machine learning algorithms partner with people much like a bloodhound partners with its trainer; the dog's sense of smell may be many times stronger than its master's, but without being carefully directed, the hound may end up chasing its tail [10].

This paper is divided into five sections. Section1 describes brief introduction to machine learning, data explosion, and machine learning and data mining. Section 2 describes types of data and learning. Section 3 describes business analytics types. Section 4 describes machine learning applications. Section 5 concludes the paper. This paper also tries to distinguish between supervised learning and unsupervised learning. This paper tries to find upcoming areas where machine learning algorithms can best fit in order to make some complex decision or to solve complex business problems.

2. TYPES OF DATA AND LEARNING

Digital data can be broadly classified into structured, semi-structured and unstructured data [11-13].

Unstructured data: data that does not fit a data model or is not in a form that can be easily used by a computer program. About 80-90% of the data of an organization is in this format; For example, notes, chat rooms, PowerPoint presentations, images, videos, letters, research, technical documents, the body of an email, etc [14]. Unstructured data does not fit any

predefined data model. In fact, to explain things a bit more, let's take a closer look at the different types of text available and the possible structure associated with it. In general, the structure or framework of unstructured data is quite unpredictable. In Figure 1.8 we look at the other sources of unstructured data. Essentially everything that has not been specifically structured is considered unstructured. The list of truly unstructured data includes free text, such as documents produced in your company, images and videos, audio files and some types of social networks. If the object to be stored does not carry labels (metadata about the data) and does not have an established scheme, ontology, glossary or consistent organization, it is not structured. However, in the same category as unstructured data, there are many types of data that have at least one organization. Some more examples of unstructured data are Twitter messages, Facebook posts, log files and email. Nowadays, unstructured data constitutes approximately 80% of the data that is generated in any company. The balance is clearly changing in favor of unstructured data. It is such a large percentage that it can not be ignored. *Semi-structured data*: data that does not fit a data model but has some structure. However, it is not in a form that can be easily used by a computer program; for example, emails, XML, markup languages such as HTML, etc. The metadata for this data is available but not sufficient. Semi-structured data is also known as a self-description structure. It has the following characteristics:

1. It does not conform to the data models that one usually associates with relational databases or any other form of data tables.
2. Use labels to segregate semantic elements.
3. Labels are also used to impose hierarchies of records and fields within the data.
4. There is no separation between the data and the scheme. The amount of structure used is dictated by the purpose in question.
5. In semi-structured data, entities belonging to the same class and also grouped do not necessarily have to have the same set of attributes. And, in any case, they have the same set of attributes, the order of the attributes may not be similar and, for all practical purposes, it is not important either.

Structured data: are the data that are organized (for example, in rows and columns) and that a computer program can easily use. Relationships exist between data entities, such as classes and their objects. The data stored in databases is an example of structured data. The majority of the structured data is maintained in RDBMS. An RDBMS conforms to the relational data model in which the data is stored in rows / columns. The number of rows / records / tuples in a relationship is called the cardinality of a relation and the number of columns is known as the degree of a relation. The current data store contains structured data and only structured data. It is structured because when it was placed in its relational database system a structure was imposed, so we know where it is, what it means and how it relates to other data there. It can be text (the name of a person) or numeric (its age) but we know that the value of age goes with a specific person, therefore structured. If your data is highly structured, you can look at it using any of the available RDBMS. It is normally used to maintain transaction / transaction data generated and collected by daily business activities. In other words, data from Online Transaction Processing (OLTP) systems are generally quite structured.

The learning can be classified into two types as supervised learning and unsupervised learning.

Supervised Learning: A predictive model is used for tasks that involve, as the name implies, the prediction of a value using other values in the data set. The learning algorithm attempts to discover and model the relationship between the objective characteristic (the characteristic that is predicted) and the other characteristics. Despite the common use of the word "prediction" to imply forecasting, predictive models do not necessarily need to predict events in the future. For example, a predictive model could be used to predict past events, such as the date of conception of a baby using the mother's current hormonal levels. Predictive models can also be used in real time to control the traffic lights during peak hours. Because predictive models receive clear instructions about what they need to learn and how they should learn it, the process of training a predictive model is known as supervised learning. Supervision does not refer to human participation, but to the fact that objective values provide a way for the student to know how well he has learned the desired task. Stated more formally, given a data set, a supervised learning algorithm attempts to optimize a function (the model) to find the combination of characteristic values that result in the objective result. In the classification, the destination characteristic to be predicted is a categorical characteristic known as the class, and it is divided into categories called levels. A class can have two or more levels, and the levels may or may not be ordinal. Because classification is used so much in machine learning, there are many types of classification algorithms, with appropriate strengths and weaknesses for different types of input data.

Supervised trainees can also be used to predict numerical data such as income, laboratory values, test scores or item counts. To predict such numerical values, a common form of numerical prediction adjusts the linear regression models to the input data. Although regression models are not the only type of numerical models, they are by far the most used. Regression methods are widely used for forecasting, since they quantify in exact terms the association between the inputs and the objective, including both, the magnitude and uncertainty of the relationship.

Unsupervised Learning: A single feature is more important than any other. In fact, because there is no objective to be learned, the process of training a descriptive model is called unsupervised learning. Although it may be more difficult to think of applications for descriptive models, after all, the good thing is that a student, who is not learning anything in particular, is used quite frequently for data extraction.

For example, the descriptive modeling task called pattern discovery is used to identify useful associations within the data. Pattern discovery is often used to analyze the market basket in the transactional purchase data of retailers. Here, the goal is to identify items that are often bought together, so that the information learned can be used to refine marketing tactics. For example, if a retailer finds out that swim trunks are commonly purchased at the same time as sunglasses, the retailer may reposition items more closely at the store or perform a promotion to "sell" to customers with associated articles.

The descriptive modeling task of dividing a data set into homogeneous groups is called clustering. This is sometimes used for segmentation analysis that identifies groups of individuals with similar behavior or demographic information, so that ad campaigns could be tailored to particular audiences. Although the machine is capable of identifying groups, human intervention is required to interpret them. For example, given five different groups of buyers in a grocery store, the marketing team should understand the differences between the groups to create the promotion that best suits each group.

Finally, a class of machine learning algorithms known as meta-apprentices is not tied to a specific learning task, but focuses on learning to learn more effectively. A meta-learning algorithm uses the results of some learning to inform the additional learning. This can be beneficial for very difficult problems or when the performance of a predictive algorithm should be as accurate as possible.

3. BUSINESS ANALYTICS TYPES

The different types of business analytics are Marketing Analytics, Pricing Analytics, Social Media Analytics, Customer Analytics, Supply Chain Analytics, and many more. Business Analytics is analyzing the business in 360° angle which covers historical perspective or Descriptive, future perspective or Predictive and combinations of both or Perspective in order to make better and highly valuable decisions [15].

Descriptive Analytics: Descriptive analyzes are performed to answer questions about events that have already occurred. This form of analysis contextualizes the data to generate information. Sample questions may include:

- What was the volume of sales in the last 12 months?
- What is the number of support calls received according to the category of severity and geographic location?
- What is the monthly commission that each sales agent earns?

It is estimated that 80% of the analytical results generated are descriptive in nature. In terms of value, descriptive analyzes provide the least value and require a relatively basic set of skills. Descriptive analytics is often done through ad-hoc reports or control panels. Reports are generally static in nature and show historical data that is presented in the form of data grids or graphs. Queries are executed in operational data stores from a company, for example, a customer relationship management system (CRM) or an enterprise resource planning system (ERP).

As an example, the descriptive analysis includes consulting the policy administration system to determine the number of policies sold each day, consulting the claims management system to find out how many claims are sent daily, and checking the billing system to find out how many customers are behind your premium payments.

Marketing Analytics: Marketing analysis includes the processes and technologies that allow marketers to evaluate the success of their marketing initiatives. This is achieved by measuring performance (for example, blogs versus social networks versus channel communications). Marketing analysis uses important business metrics, such as ROI, marketing attribution and marketing effectiveness in general. In other words, it tells you how your marketing programs are really working. Marketing analysis collects data from all marketing channels and consolidates them into a common marketing vision. From this common point of view, you can extract analytical results that can provide invaluable assistance to boost your marketing efforts.

Over the years, as companies expanded into new marketing categories, new technologies were adopted to support them. Because each new technology was usually implemented in isolation, the result was a mix of disconnected data environments. Consequently, marketing professionals often make decisions based on data from individual channels (for example, website metrics), regardless of the overall marketing image. The information of social networks alone is not enough. Web analytics data alone is not enough. And the tools that watch only one snapshot in time for a single channel are terribly inadequate.

Predictive Analytics: Predictive analysis is the use of data, statistical algorithms and machine learning techniques to identify the probability of future results based on historical data. The goal is to go beyond knowing what has happened to provide a better assessment of what will happen in the future. Although predictive analysis has existed for decades, it is a technology whose time has come. More and more organizations are turning to predictive analytics to increase their profitability and competitive advantage. Because right now?

- Growing volumes and types of data, and more interest in using data to produce valuable information.
- Faster and cheaper computers.
- Software easier to use.
- Tougher economic conditions and a need for competitive differentiation

As interactive and easy-to-use software is becoming more frequent, predictive analytics is no longer just the domain of mathematicians and statisticians. Business analysts and online business experts are also using these technologies.

Pricing Analytics: In marketing, price analysis refers to the analysis of consumer response to theoretical prices in survey research. In general, price analysis is the process of examining and evaluating a proposed price without evaluating its separate cost elements and the proposed profit / rate. The price analysis can also refer to the breakdown of a price into a unit figure. In general, per unit of price analysis, per square meter, square foot of accommodation, per hectare or even square meter of land. The price with the appropriate adjustment for several differences is applied to the valuation problem.

Financial Analytics: financial analysis is the creation of an ad hoc analysis to answer specific business questions and forecast possible future financial scenarios. The financial analysis software can accelerate the creation of reports and present the data in an executive panel, a graphical presentation that is easier to read and interpret than a series of spreadsheets with dynamic tables.

Social Media Analytics: The analysis of social networks is the practice of collecting data from social network websites and analyzing them using social network analysis tools to make business decisions. The most common use of social media analysis is to undermine customer confidence to support marketing and customer service activities.

Sports Analytics: Sports analytics are a broad spectrum that basically covers production in the field and outside of it, and how to obtain an advantage. It helps coaches by measuring opponents' tendencies, and helps GMs get a complete study of a player on and off the field, as well as how they fit in with other players on the team. It also helps in the creation of the playbook, in judging the strengths and weaknesses of a player, and how it can be correlated with better production.

4. MACHINE LEARNING APPLICATIONS

Although it is impossible to list all the use cases of machine learning, a survey of recent success stories includes several outstanding applications:

- Identification of unwanted spam messages in the email.
- Segmentation of customer behavior for targeted advertising.
- Predictions of climatic behavior and long-term climate changes.
- Reduction of fraudulent transactions with a credit card.
- Estimates Actuarial estimates of financial damages from storms and natural disasters.
- Prediction of popular electoral results.

- Development of algorithms for automatic piloting drones and automatic driving cars.
- Optimization of energy use in homes and office buildings.
- Projection of areas where criminal activity is most likely.
- Discovery of genetic sequences linked to diseases.

The ability of machines to understand the language has improved enough since 1994, so that Google, Apple and Microsoft have enough confidence to offer virtual concierge services operated through voice recognition. Even so, even these services routinely struggle to answer relatively simple questions. Furthermore, online translation services sometimes misinterpret phrases that a young child would easily understand. The predictive text function on many devices has also led to a series of sites with self-correcting errors with humor that illustrate the computer's ability to understand basic language but completely misinterpret the context.

5. CONCLUSION

The avalanche of data has led some to say that we have entered an era of Big Data, but this may be a bit inappropriate. Humans have always been surrounded by large amounts of data. What makes the current era unique is that we have large amounts of recorded data, many of which can be accessed directly from computers. The largest and most interesting data sets are increasingly accessible at the tip of our fingers, just a web search. This large amount of information has the potential to inform action, given a systematic way to make sense of all this. This paper divided into five sections. Section 1 described brief introduction to machine learning, data explosion, and machine learning and data mining. Section 2 described types of data and learning. Section 3 described business analytics types. Section 4 described machine learning applications. Section 5 concluded the paper. This paper also tries to distinguish between supervised learning and unsupervised learning.

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